

Jyrki Miettinen, Ville-Valtteri Visuri & Timo Fabritius

Chromium-, copper-, molybdenum-,
and nickel-containing thermodynamic
descriptions of the
Fe–Al–Cr–Cu–Mn–Mo–Ni–Si system
for modeling the solidification of steels

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Abstract

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PO Box 4300, FI-90014 University of Oulu, Finland

Abstract

The Thermodynamic Iron Alloy Database (IAD) has been developed since 2000 to provide consistent thermodynamic data for modeling solidification of steels. This work presents the chromium, copper, molybdenum and nickel containing thermodynamic descriptions of the Fe–Al–Cr–Cu–Mn–Mo–Ni–Si system, extending the earlier published Fe–Al–Mn–Si–C description of that database. The results suggest a good agreement of the thermodynamic descriptions with the measured data.

Keywords: steels, solidification, thermodynamics, Fe–Al–Cr–Cu–Mn–Mo–Ni–Si system.

Tiivistelmä

Miettinen, Jyrki; Visuri, Ville-Valtteri; Fabritius, Timo; Kromia, kuparia, molybdeeniä ja nikkeliä sisältävät termodynaamiset kuvaukset Fe–Al–Cr–Cu–Mn–Mo–Ni–Si –systeemille teräksien jähmettymisen mallintamiseen.

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Tiivistelmä

Vuodesta 2000 lähtien on kehitetty rautapohjaisten seosten termodynaamista datakanta, IAD, jonka tarkoituksena on tuottaa yksinkertaista ja konsistenttia termodynaamista dataa terästen jähmettymisen mallintamiseen. Tämä työ esittelee systeemin Fe–Al–Cr–Cu–Mn–Mo–Ni–Si alikuvaukset kromin, kuparin, molybdeenin ja nikkelin osalta. Kuvaukset laajentavat aiemmassa tutkimuksessa esitetystä Fe–Al–Mn–Si–C –systeemin kuvauksesta luotua IAD-datakanta. Tulokset osoittavat termodynaamisten kuvausten vastaavan hyvin mitattua aineistoa.

Asiasanat: teräs, jähmettyminen, termodynamiikka, Fe–Al–Cr–Cu–Mn–Mo–Ni–Si –systeemi.

In memory of Jukka Laine

Acknowledgements

This study represents a continuation of long-term research into modeling solidification of steels, which started with the development of the interdendritic solidification (IDS) model at the former Helsinki University of Technology (the present-day Aalto University) in 1984. The research work has continued until the present day, and at the University of Oulu since 2018.

The creation of this book was executed within the framework of the Genome of Steel profiling project. The authors would like to acknowledge the Academy of Finland (project 311934) for funding this work.

April 22, 2020

J. Miettinen, V.-V. Visuri & T. Fabritius

Nomenclature

Abbreviations

IAD	Iron Alloy Database
RK	Redlich–Kister excess model
RKM	Redlich–Kister–Muggianu excess model
SER	Standard element reference: 298.15 K (25 °C) and 1 bar
SGTE	Scientific Group Thermodata Europe

Symbols

a_i	Activity of component i
E	Ternary eutectic reaction
f_i	Activity coefficient of component i related to the 1 wt-% standard state
G	Gibbs free energy [J/mol]
H	Enthalpy [J/mol]
L	Interaction parameter [J/mol]
P	Ternary peritectic reaction
R	Gas constant [J/(mol·K)]
T	Temperature [K]
U	Ternary quasi-peritectic reaction
w_i	Weight fraction of component i
x_i	Mole fraction of component i
y_i	Site fraction of component i (atoms) in a sublattice of a phase
γ_i	Redlich–Kister excess model

Subscripts

bcc	Body-centered cubic crystal structure (ferrite)
cub	Cubic crystal structure
dia	Diamond
E	Excess
fcc	Face-centered cubic crystal structure (austenite)
gra	Graphite
hcp	Hexagonal close-packed crystal structure

L Liquid
 ϕ Phase

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Tiivistelmä

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1 Introduction

In a previous study by the authors [1], a thermodynamic description was presented for the Fe–Al–Mn–Si–C system. That description is a part of the unpublished Iron Alloy Database (IAD). The purpose of the IAD is to provide simple-format thermodynamic data for the IDS thermodynamic-kinetic software [2, 3] to simulate the solidification and austenite decomposition of steels.

In this study, the Fe–Al–Mn–Si part of the Fe–Al–Mn–Si–C description of Mieltinen *et al.* [1] is expanded with four new elements: chromium (Cr), copper (Cu), molybdenum (Mo), and nickel (Ni). In the resulting Fe–Al–Cr–Cu–Mn–Mo–Ni–Si description, only Cr-, Cu-, Mo-, and Ni-containing sub-descriptions are presented. For the other descriptions, the reader is guided to an earlier study [1]. Table 1 shows the Cr-, Cu-, Mo-, and Ni-containing sub-systems assessed in the literature and according to the IAD.

The benefit of the new IAD descriptions is their easy and rapid handling in the IDS solidification model in regard to the literature descriptions, which may be either complex or incompatible with each other. The new descriptions are based on some practical simplifications made for the thermodynamic solution models. For the present description of the Fe–Al–Cr–Cu–Mn–Mo–Ni–Si system, the most essential simplification is to apply simple compound descriptions whenever possible. This treatment enables an easy extension of these compounds by using new components. Another simplification facilitating the IDS calculations is that the IAD ignores the B2-ordering of the bcc phase in alloys when the Al and Si contents are high. In fact, such high Al and Si contents are not found in typical steels, but in spite of this, the energetic contribution due to the ordering effect was added to the disordered part of the bcc phase. With this treatment, it was possible to fit the calculated bcc-containing phase equilibria in the IAD with the measurements in the literature.

The calculations were carried out by applying a conventional substitutional solution model for the main solution phases (*i.e.* liquid, bcc, and fcc) and the sublattice model [94] for the intermetallic compounds. These models have been described in [1], though the model description by Sundman and Ågren [94] has been opened only for a semistoichiometric compound of $(A,B)_dC_c$. For more complex compounds such as

Table 1. Cr-, Cu-, Mo-, and Ni-containing thermodynamic descriptions of the Fe–Al–Cr–Cu–Mn–Mo–Ni–Si system.

System	Literature assessment	IAD	This work
Binary subsystems			Chapter 3
Fe–Cr	[4, 5]	[5]	Section 3.1
Fe–Cu	[6–11]	[9]	Section 3.2
Fe–Mo	[12, 13]	X	Section 3.3
Fe–Ni	[5, 14, 15]	[5]	Section 3.4
Al–Cr	[16–19]	X	Section 3.5
Al–Cu	[20–23]	X	Section 3.6
Al–Mo	[20, 24, 25]	X	Section 3.7
Al–Ni	[26, 27]	X	Section 3.8
Cr–Cu	[28, 29]	X	Section 3.9
Cr–Mn	[30]	[30]	Section 3.10
Cr–Mo	[31, 32]	X	Section 3.11
Cr–Ni	[33, 34]	[34]	Section 3.12
Cr–Si	[35–39]	X	Section 3.13
Cu–Mn	[40–43]	[43]	Section 3.14
Cu–Mo	[44]	[44]	Section 3.15
Cu–Ni	[45–47]	[45]	Section 3.16
Cu–Si	[36, 48–50]	[50]	Section 3.17
Mn–Mo	[51]	X	Section 3.18
Mn–Ni	[52, 53]	[52]	Section 3.19
Mo–Ni	[54–59]	X	Section 3.20
Mo–Si	[60, 61]	X	Section 3.21
Ni–Si	[62–65]	X	Section 3.22

Notes: X = assessed in this work; NA = not available (no direct evidence of the assessment status); F = only the fcc phase is assessed. The Fe–Al–Mn–Si-based descriptions are available in [1].

Sigma, Mu and R, each owning a three-sublattice structure, the reader is guided to the works by Andersson [32] and Hillert and Qiu [75].

The following sections introduce the models applied in the present study and the sub-descriptions of the Fe–Al–Cr–Cu–Mn–Mo–Ni–Si system assessed for the IAD. Additionally, their validation is shown with the available experimental data, and a comparison with some earlier calculation, if available. All calculations are made using the ThermoCalc software [95] with the IAD as its user database. The unary thermodynamic data of the pure components are identical to those of the Scientific Group Thermodata Europe (SGTE) [96].

Table 1 (continued)

System	Literature assessment	IAD	This work
Ternary subsystems			Chapter 4
Fe–Al–Cr	[66]	X	Section 4.1
Fe–Al–Cu	[?, 67–69]	X	Section 4.2
Fe–Al–Mo	[70]	X	Section 4.3
Fe–Al–Ni	[71]	X	Section 4.4
Fe–Cr–Cu	[67, 72, 73]	X	Section 4.2
Fe–Cr–Mn	[30]	X	Section 4.6
Fe–Cr–Mo	[32, 74]	X	Section 4.7
Fe–Cr–Ni	[5, 75–77]	X	Section 4.8
Fe–Cr–Si	[78]	X	Section 4.9
Fe–Cu–Mn	[42, 67, 79, 80]	X	Section 4.10
Fe–Cu–Mo	[44]	X	Section 4.11
Fe–Cu–Ni	[45, 67, 81, 82]	X	Section 4.12
Fe–Cu–Si	[67, 72, 83–85]	X	Section 4.13
Fe–Mn–Mo	NA	X	Section 4.14
Fe–Mn–Ni	[86, 87]	X	Section 4.15
Fe–Mo–Ni	[88]	X	Section 4.16
Fe–Mo–Si	NA	X	Section 4.17
Fe–Ni–Si	NA	X	Section 4.18
Al–Cr–Ni	[89–91]	X	Section 4.19
Cr–Mo–Ni	[92]	X	Section 4.20
Cr–Ni–Si	[93]	X	Section 4.21
Quaternary subsystems			Chapter 5
Fe–Al–Cr–Ni	NA	X	Section 5.1
Fe–Cr–Mo–Ni	NA	X	Section 5.2
Fe–Cr–Mn–Ni–Si	NA	X, F	Chapter 6

Notes: X = assessed in this work; NA = not available (no direct evidence of the assessment status);
F = only the fcc phase is assessed.

2 Phases and their modeling

The phases modeled for the Fe–Al–Cr–Cu–Mn–Mo–Ni–Si system and their formulations are given in Table 2. The phases are classified in six phase groups according to their modeling. The first (1) group of phases are modeled with the classical substitutional solution model, the second (2) and third (3) group phases are treated as stoichiometric phases, the fourth (4) and fifth (5) group phases are modeled with the two-sublattice model and the sixth (6) group phases are modeled with the three-sublattice model. The thermodynamic models have been introduced in several literature studies in Table 1 and more generally by Saunders and Miodownik [97]. In fact, the compounds of groups (2), (3) and (4) belong to the sublattice phases (groups 5 and 6), but the simplest possible means for their presentation is preferred in this study.

In Table 2, worth noting is the treating of many binary and ternary compounds as stoichiometric phases in regard to some literature assessments giving them a more extensive homogeneity range in composition. This simplification mainly concerns the binary compounds of the iron-free binary systems which only marginally affect the phase equilibria in iron-rich alloys. A similar marginal effect is also due to the simple semi-stoichiometric or sublattice treatments of some Fe–Al and Fe–Si compounds, as they do not take part in the phase equilibria of the iron-rich alloys. Particularly, note the simple formulation of the Delta phase (in group 4) extended from the MoNi description of the Mo–Ni system, whereas its more general formulation in the Fe–Mo–Ni system is $(\text{Fe},\text{Ni})_{24}(\text{Fe},\text{Mo},\text{Ni})_{20}\text{Mo}_{12}$ [88]. Nevertheless, there are also compounds whose descriptions could not be simplified. Such compounds are the three-sublattice phases in Table 2, which were assessed using the SGTE recommended formulation for these phases.

Table 2. Phases and their formulation in the Fe–Al–Cr–Cu–Mn–Mo–Ni–Si description.

Phase group	Phase	Formulation	
(1) Substitutional solution phases	liquid ¹⁾	(Al,Cr,Cu,Fe,Mn,Mo,Ni,Si)	
	fcc_A1 ¹⁾	(Al,Cr,Cu,Fe,Mn,Mo,Ni,Si)	
	bcc_A2 ¹⁾	(Al,Cr,Cu,Fe,Mn,Mo,Ni,Si)	
	hcp_A3 ²⁾	(Al,Cr,Cu,Fe,Mn,Mo,Ni,Si)	
	cbcc_A12 ³⁾	(Al,Cr,Cu,Fe,Mn,Mo,Ni,Si)	
	cub_A13 ³⁾	(Al,Cr,Cu,Fe,Mn,Mo,Ni,Si)	
	dia_A4 ⁴⁾	(Al,Si)	
	Al ₅ Fe ₄ ⁵⁾	(Al,Cr,Fe,Mo)	
	τ -AlFeMo ⁶⁾	(Al,Fe,Mo)	
	(2) Binary stoichiometric compounds	Al ₇ Cr	(Al) ₇ (Cr)
		Al ₁₁ Cr ₂	(Al) ₁₁ (Cr) ₂
AlCr ₂		(Al)(Cr) ₂	
AlCu- ξ		(Al) ₉ (Cu) ₁₁	
AlCu- δ		(Al) ₂ (Cu) ₃	
Al ₁₁ Mn ₄		(Al) ₁₁ (Mn) ₄	
Al ₄ Mn		(Al) ₄ (Mn)	
Al ₆ Mn		(Al) ₆ (Mn)	
Al ₁₂ Mn		(Al) ₁₂ (Mn)	
Al ₁₂ Mo		(Al) ₁₂ (Mo)	
Al ₅ Mo		(Al) ₅ (Mo)	
Al ₆₃ Mo ₃₇		(Al) ₆₃ (Mo) ₃₇	
Al ₈ Mo ₃		(Al) ₈ (Mo) ₃	
AlMo		(Al) _{48.5} (Mo) _{51.5}	
Al ₃ Ni		(Al) ₃ (Ni)	
Al ₃ Ni ₂		(Al) ₃ (Ni) ₂	
Al ₃ Ni ₅		(Al) ₃ (Ni) ₅	
Cr ₃ Mn ₅		(Cr) ₃ (Mn) ₅	
CrSi ₂		(Cr)(Si) ₂	
Cu ₅₆ Si ₁₁		(Cu) ₅₆ (Si) ₁₁	
Cu ₃₃ Si ₇		(Cu) ₃₃ (Si) ₇	
Cu ₁₅ Si ₄		(Cu) ₁₅ (Si) ₄	
Cu ₁₉ Si ₆		(Cu) ₁₉ (Si) ₆	
Mn ₅ Mo ₄		(Mn) _{55.55} (Mo) _{44.45}	
Mn ₁₆ Mo ₉		(Mn) ₁₆ (Mo) ₉	
MnNi		(Mn)(Ni)	
Mn ₂ Ni		(Mn) ₂ (Ni)	
MnNi ₂	(Mn)(Ni) ₂		

Notes: 1) stable in all Fe-containing ternary systems; 2) stable in the Cu–Si and Fe–Cu–Si systems and the later published N-containing systems; 3) stable in the Mn-containing systems; 4) stable in the Si-containing systems; 5) stable in the binary Fe–Al system and its higher-order extensions; 6) stable in the ternary Fe–Al–Mo system.

Table 2 (continued)

Phase group	Phase	Formulation	
(2) Binary stoichiometric compounds (cont.)	Mn ₆ Si	(Mn) ₆ (Si)	
	Mn ₉ Si ₂	(Mn) ₉ (Si) ₂	
	Mn ₁₁ Si ₁₉	(Mn) ₁₁ (Si) ₁₉	
	MoNi ₃	(Mo)(Ni) ₃	
	MoNi ₄	(Mo)(Ni) ₄	
	Mo ₃ Si	(Mo) ₃ (Si)	
	MoSi ₂	(Mo)(Si) ₂	
	Ni ₃ Si-β ₁	(Ni) ₁₉ (Si) ₆	
	Ni ₃ Si-β ₂	(Ni) ₃ (Si)	
	Ni ₃ Si-θ ₃	(Ni) ₃ (Si)	
	Ni ₂ Si-θ	(Ni) ₂ (Si)	
	(3) Ternary stoichiometric compounds	Al ₉ FeMo ₃	(Al) ₉ (Fe)(Mo) ₃
		τ ₃ -AlFeSi	(Al) ₁₁ (Fe) ₅ (Si) ₄
τ ₅ -AlFeSi		(Al) ₇₁ (Fe) ₁₉ (Si) ₁₀	
τ ₆ -AlFeSi		(Al) ₉ (Fe) ₂ (Si) ₂	
τ ₁₀ -AlFeSi		(Al) ₁₂ (Fe) ₅ (Si) ₃	
τ ₁₁ -AlFeSi		(Al) ₁₇ (Fe) ₆ (Si) ₃	
τ ₁₂ -AlFeSi		(Al) ₁₂ (Fe) ₉ (Si) ₄	
Fe ₂ MoSi ₂		(Fe) _{39.24} (Mo) _{18.54} (Si) _{42.22}	
Cr ₃ Ni ₅ Si ₂		(Cr) ₃ (Ni) ₅ (Si) ₂	
τ ₁ -CrNiSi		(Cr) ₅ (Ni) ₅ (Si) ₃	
(4) Semi-stoichiometric compounds		Al ₄ Cr	(Al,Fe) ₄ (Cr)
	Al ₈ Cr ₅ -H	(Al) ₃ (Cr,Fe) ₂	
	Al ₈ Cr ₅ -L	(Al) ₃ (Cr,Fe) ₂	
	AlCu-θ	(Al) ₂ (Al,Cu)	
	AlCu-η	(Al,Cu)(Cu)	
	AlCu-ε	(Al,Cu)(Cu)	
	Al ₁₃ Fe ₄	(Al,Si) _{7.52} (Fe) _{2.48}	
	Al ₄ Mo	(Al) ₄ (Fe,Mo)	
	AlMo ₃	(Al,Fe)(Mo) ₃	
	AlNi ₃	(Al) ₆ (Cr,Fe,Ni) ₁₉	
	Cr ₃ Si	(Cr,Fe,Ni) ₃ (Si)	
	Cr ₅ Si ₃	(Cr,Fe) ₅ (Si) ₃	
	Fe ₂ Mo	(Al,Cr,Cu,Fe,Mn,Ni,Si) ₂ (Mo)	
	Fe ₂ Si	(Fe,Ni) ₂ (Si)	
	Fe ₅ Si ₃	(Cr,Fe,Mn) ₅ (Si) ₃	
	FeSi ₂ -L	(Fe)(Al,Si) ₂	
	Mn ₃ Si	(Fe,Mn) ₃ (Si)	
	Mo ₅ Si ₃	(Fe,Mo) ₅ (Si) ₃	
	Ni ₅ Si ₂	(Cr,Fe,Ni) ₅ (Si) ₂	
	Ni ₂ Si-δ	(Cr,Fe,Ni) ₂ (Si)	
	Ni ₃ Si ₂	(Fe,Ni) ₃ (Si) ₂	

Table 2 (continued)

Phase group	Phase	Formulation	
(4) Semi-stoichiometric compounds (cont.)	NiSi	(Fe,Ni)(Si)	
	NiSi ₂	(Fe,Ni)(Si) ₂	
	τ ₁ -AlFeSi	(Al,Si) ₅ (Fe) ₃	
	τ ₂ -AlFeSi	(Al,Si) ₇ (Fe) ₂	
	τ ₄ -AlFeSi	(Al,Si) ₅ (Fe)	
	τ ₇ -AlFeSi	(Al,Si) ₃ (Fe)	
	τ ₈ -AlFeSi	(Al,Si) ₂ (Fe)	
	τ-FeNiSi	(Fe,Ni) ₄ (Si)	
	τ ₂ -CrNiSi	(Cr,Ni) ₄ (Si) ₃	
	Delta	(Mo)(Cr,Fe,Ni)	
	(5) Two- sublattice phases	Al ₂ Fe	(Al,Si) ₂ (Cr,Fe)
		Al ₅ Fe ₂	(Al,Si) ₅ (Cr,Fe,Mo) ₂
FeSi		(Cr,Fe,Mn,Mo,Ni)(Al,Si)	
FeSi ₂ -H		(Fe,Ni) ₃ (Al,Si) ₇	
(6) Three-sublattice phases	AlCu-γH	(Al) ₄ (Al,Cu)(Cu) ₈	
	AlCu-γD83	(Al) ₄ (Al,Cu)(Cu) ₈	
	Al ₈ Mn ₅ -D810	(Al) ₁₂ (Mn) ₄ (Al,Mn) ₁₀	
	Chi	(Cr,Fe) ₂₄ (Cr,Mo) ₁₀ (Cr,Fe,Mo) ₂₄	
	Sigma	(Fe,Mn) ₈ (Cr) ₄ (Fe,Cr,Mn) ₁₈	
	Sigma-H	(Fe,Mn) ₈ (Cr) ₄ (Fe,Cr,Mn) ₁₈	
	P	(Cr,Fe,Ni) ₂₄ (Cr,Fe,Mo,Ni) ₂₀ (Mo) ₁₂	
	R	(Cr,Fe) ₂₇ (Mo) ₁₄ (Cr,Fe,Mo) ₁₂	
	Mu	(Al,Cr,Fe,Ni) ₇ (Mo) ₂ (Cr,Fe,Mo,Ni) ₄	

The molar Gibbs energy of a substitutional solution phase (belonging to group 1 of Table 2) is expressed as

$$G^\phi = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^\phi G_i^{\circ,\phi} + RT \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^\phi \ln x_i^\phi + G^{E,\phi}. \quad (1)$$

The first and the second summations represent the mechanical mixture of pure components and the contribution of mixing entropy, respectively. The third term ($G^{E,\phi}$) is the Gibbs excess energy expressed as

$$G^{E,\phi} = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^n x_i^\phi x_j^\phi L_{ij}^\phi + \sum_{i=1}^{n-2} \sum_{j=i+1}^{n-1} \sum_{k=j+1}^n x_i^\phi x_j^\phi x_k^\phi L_{ijk}^\phi + \sum_{i=1}^{n-3} \sum_{j=i+1}^{n-2} \sum_{k=j+1}^{n-1} \sum_{l=k+1}^n x_i^\phi x_j^\phi x_k^\phi x_l^\phi L_{ijkl}^\phi, \quad (2)$$

In Eqs. 1 and 2, x_i^ϕ is the mole fraction of component i in phase ϕ , $G^{\circ,\phi}$ is the Gibbs energy of a pure component in phase ϕ expressed relative to its enthalpy in the SER state [96], R is the gas constant, and T is the temperature. Parameters L^ϕ describe the interactions between the components indicated by the proper subscripts. Binary parameters L_{ij}^ϕ and ternary parameters L_{ijk}^ϕ can have the following composition dependencies [98,99]:

$$L_{ij}^\phi = \sum_{m=0}^{m_{\max}} m L_{ij}^{\phi,m} (x_i^\phi - x_j^\phi)^m, \quad (3)$$

$$L_{ijk}^\phi = v_i^\phi L_{iijk}^\phi + v_j^\phi L_{ijjk}^\phi + v_k^\phi L_{ijkk}^\phi, \quad (4)$$

where m is the degree of the binary parameter (m_{\max} = maximum degree) and v_s are composition variables defined as $v_i = x_i + (1 - x_i - x_j - x_k)/3$. Note that for the bcc and fcc phases of iron alloys, a contribution due to magnetic ordering must be added to Eq. 1. This contribution is expressed as

$$G_m^{\text{mo},\phi} = RT \ln(\beta^\phi + 1) \cdot f(\tau), \quad (5)$$

where β^ϕ is a composition-dependent parameter related to the total magnetic entropy and τ is defined as $\tau = T/T_c^\phi$ where T_c^ϕ is the critical temperature of magnetic ordering. Function $f(\tau)$ in Eq. 5 takes the polynomial form proposed by Hillert and Jarl [100]. The magnetic contribution can be calculated also for other solid solution phases but this is not made in the present study due their negligible effect on the Gibbs energy. Most compounds of the present Fe–Al–Cr–Cu–Mn–Mo–Ni–Si description have a simple formulation and are stoichiometric or semi-stoichiometric. For the binary and ternary stoichiometric compounds, A_aB_b and $A_aB_bC_c$ (groups 2 and 3 of Table 2), the Gibbs energy is expressed as

$$G_{A_aB_b}^{\circ,\theta} = aG^{\circ,\phi_1} + bG^{\circ,\phi_2} + A + BT + CT \ln T + DT^2, \quad (6)$$

$$G_{A_aB_bC_c}^{\circ,\theta} = aG^{\circ,\phi_1} + bG^{\circ,\phi_2} + cG^{\circ,\phi_3} + A + BT + CT \ln T + DT^2, \quad (7)$$

where $G_i^{\circ,\theta}$ is the Gibbs energy of pure component i in its stable phase (θ) at 25 °C (298.15 K) [96], and terms A to D are optimized coefficients. For the multicomponent semi-stoichiometric compound, $(A_1 \dots A_n)_aC_c$ (group 4 of Table 2), the Gibbs energy is expressed as

$$G_m^\theta = \sum_{i=1}^m y_{A_i}^\theta G_{A_i:C}^{\circ,\theta} + aRT \sum_{i=1}^m y_{A_i}^\theta \ln y_{A_i}^\theta + \sum_{i=1}^{m-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^m y_{A_i}^\theta y_{A_j}^\theta L_{A_i,A_j:C}^\theta, \quad (8)$$

where m is the number of the binary stoichiometric compounds, A_iC_c , $G_{A_i:C}^{\circ,\theta}$ is the Gibbs energy of pure A_iC_c , $y_{A_i}^\theta$ is the site fraction of A_i atoms occupying the first sublattice, and $L_{A_i,A_j:C}^\theta$ is a parameter describing the interaction between A_i and A_j atoms in that sublattice. For the Gibbs energy expression of more complex compounds, i.e. the compounds of groups 5 and 6 of Table 2, the reader is guided to the work by Saunders and Miodownik [97]. Note however that if the two-sublattice phases of group 5 contain either Al or Si but not both of them, Eq. 8 can be applied also for those phases. The same holds for these phases if they contain both Al and Si in one sublattice and only Fe in another one.

3 Binary systems

3.1 The Fe–Cr system

The Fe–Cr system has been assessed by Andersson and Sundman [4]. Their liquid phase description was later modified by Lee [5] to get a better agreement between the experimental and calculated phase equilibria in the ternary Fe–Cr–Ni system. The Fe–Cr description by Lee [5] was adapted for the IAD, due to its use in many higher-order SGTE assessments. The present work reviews this description and presents its experimental verification.

3.1.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 3 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 4 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 5.

Table 3. Phases and their modeling in the Fe–Cr description by Lee [5].

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Cr,Fe), substitutional, RK
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Cr,Fe), substitutional, RK
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Cr,Fe), substitutional, RK
sigma (\approx σ)	(Fe) ₈ (Cr) ₄ (Cr,Fe) ₁₈ , sublattice, RK

Note: RK = Redlich–Kister excess model.

Table 4. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Fe–Cr [5].

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Phase equilibria of the phase diagram	[101–111]
Enthalpy of mixing in liquid alloys at 1600 °C	[112, 113]
Chemical potentials in liquid alloys at 1600 °C	[114–117]
Activity of Cr in solid alloys from 1277 °C to 1400 °C	[108, 114, 118–122]

Table 5. The thermodynamic description of the Fe–Cr system [5].

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Fe)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Fe}^L = (-17737 + 7.997T) + (-1331)(x_{Cr} - x_{Fe})$	[5]
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Fe)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Fe}^{bcc} = (+20500 - 9.68T)$	[4]
$T_c^{bcc} = 1043x_{Fe} - 311x_{Cr} + x_{Fe}x_{Cr}(1650 - 550(x_{Fe} - x_{Cr}))$	[4]
$\beta^{bcc} = 2.22x_{Fe} - 0.008x_{Cr} - 0.85x_{Fe}x_{Cr}$	[4]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Fe)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Fe}^{fcc} = (+10833 - 7.477T) + (+1410)(x_{Cr} - x_{Fe})$	[4]
$T_c^{fcc} = -201x_{Fe} - 1109x_{Cr}$	[96]
$\beta^{fcc} = -2.1x_{Fe} - 2.46x_{Cr}$	[96]
<i>sigma (σ) (3 sublattices, sites: 8:4:18, constituents: Fe:Cr:Cr,Fe)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Cr:Cr}^{\sigma} = 8G_{Fe}^{\sigma,fcc} + 22G_{Cr}^{\sigma,bcc} + (+92300 - 95.96T)$	[4]
$G_{Fe:Cr:Fe}^{\sigma} = 8G_{Fe}^{\sigma,fcc} + 4G_{Cr}^{\sigma,bcc} + 18G_{Fe}^{\sigma,bcc} + (+117300 - 95.96T)$	[4]

Note: the thermodynamic data for the pure components is given by [96] unless not shown in the table.

3.1.2 Results

The results of the calculations [5] together with the experimental data (Table 4) are presented in Figures 1–4. The agreement is reasonably good.

Fig. 1. A calculated [5] Fe–Cr phase diagram, together with the experimental data points (31Adc [101], 51Put [102], 56Pom [103], 57Hel [104], 61Bae [105], 66Nis [106], 75Nis [107], 76Nor [108], 77Sch [109], 82Her [110], and 84Kun [111]).

Fig. 2. The calculated [5] enthalpy of mixing in liquid Fe–Cr alloys at 1600 °C, together with the experimental data points (82lgu [112] and 84Bat [113]). The reference states used are pure liquid Fe and Cr.

Fig. 3. The calculated [5] chemical potentials of Fe and Cr in liquid Fe–Cr alloys at 1600 °C, together with the experimental data points (68Ree [114], 69Fru [115], 69Gil [116], and 80Mar [117]). The reference states used are pure liquid Fe and Cr.

Fig. 4. The calculated [5] activity of Cr in bcc Fe–Cr alloys at 1277 °C and 1400 °C, together with the experimental data points (58McC [118], 60Kub [119], 63Jea [120], 68Ree [114], 69Lid [121], 76Nor [108], and 78Vre [122]). The reference state used is pure bcc Cr.

3.2 The Fe–Cu system

The Fe–Cu system has been assessed in [6–11]. The simple assessment by Chen and Jin [9] was preferred to the more recent assessments by Turchanin *et al.* [10] and Shubhank and Kang [11] and was adapted for the IAD. The present work reviews the Fe–Cu description by Chen and Jin [9] and presents its experimental verification.

3.2.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 6 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 7 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 8.

Table 6. Phases and their modeling in the Fe–Cu description of Chen and Jin [9].

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Cu,Fe), substitutional, RK
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Cu,Fe), substitutional, RK
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Cu,Fe), substitutional, RK

Note: RK = Redlich–Kister excess model.

Table 7. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Fe–Cu system [9].

Experimental data	Reference
Phase equilibria of the phase diagram	[104, 123–135]
Enthalpy of mixing for liquid alloys at 1600 °C	[128, 136–140]
Partial enthalpies in liquid alloys at 1600 °C and 1550 °C	[141, 142]
Chemical potentials in liquid alloys at 1600 °C	[117, 140, 143, 144]
$G_{\text{Cu}}^E/(1-x_{\text{Cu}})^2$ in liquid alloys at 1600 °C	[117, 143–145]
Enthalpy of mixing for fcc alloys at 1050 °C	[146]
Activity of Cu in fcc alloys at 1050 °C to 1310 °C	[147]
Metastable bcc–L equilibrium	[135]
Metastable liquid miscibility gap	[126, 135, 148, 149]

Table 8. The thermodynamic description of the Fe–Cu system [9].

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Fe)</i>	
$L_{\text{Cu,Fe}}^L = (+35626 - 2.19T) + (-1530 + 1.153T)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Fe}})$ $+ (+12714 - 5.186T)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Fe}})^2 + (+1177)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Fe}})^3$	[9]
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Fe)</i>	
$L_{\text{Cu,Fe}}^{\text{bcc}} = (+39676 - 4.732T)$	[9]
$T_c^{\text{bcc}} = 1043x_{\text{Fe}} - 41.4x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Cu}}$	[9]
$\beta^{\text{bcc}} = 2.22x_{\text{Fe}}$	[9]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Fe)</i>	
$L_{\text{Cu,Fe}}^{\text{fcc}} = (+43320 - 6.944T) + (+6069 - 2.837T)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Fe}}) + (+3629)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Fe}})^2$	[9]
$T_c^{\text{fcc}} = -201x_{\text{Fe}}$	[9]
$\beta^{\text{fcc}} = -2.1x_{\text{Fe}}$	[9]

Note: the thermodynamic data for the pure components is given by [96].

3.2.2 Results

The results of the calculations [6, 9] together with the experimental data (Table 7) are presented in Figures 5–15 and Table 9. The agreement is reasonably good in both calculations but slightly better in [9].

Table 9. The calculated and experimental invariant points of the Fe–Cu system.

$\phi_1 - \phi_2 - \phi_3$	T [°C]	$x_{\text{Cu}}^{\phi_1}$	$x_{\text{Cu}}^{\phi_2}$	$x_{\text{Cu}}^{\phi_3}$	Type	Ref.
bcc + L = fcc ₁	1485±10	0.067	0.115	0.072	Exp.	[8]
	1491	0.064	0.116	0.076	Exp.	[150]
	1478	0.066	0.127	0.080	Exp.	[151]
	1482	0.061	0.100	0.066	Exp.	[128]
	1486	0.063	0.108	0.073	Calc.	[9]
	1487	0.069	0.104	0.058	Calc.	[10]
	1489	0.069	0.117	0.075	Calc.	[6]
fcc ₁ + L = fcc ₂	1096±5	0.073	0.965	0.954	Exp.	[8]
	1098	0.076	0.965	0.952	Exp.	[150]
	1094	0.058	0.961	0.952	Exp.	[151]
	1096	0.071	0.956	0.955	Exp.	[128]
	1096	0.075	0.968	0.955	Calc.	[9]
	1095	0.076	0.965	0.950	Calc.	[10]
	1096	0.068	0.963	0.953	Calc.	[6]
fcc ₁ = bcc + fcc ₂	850±5	0.027	0.019	0.987	Exp.	[8]
	845	0.028	0.021	0.987	Exp.	[150]
	850	0.027	0.018	0.988	Exp.	[151]
	851	0.018	0.012	0.985	Exp.	[128]
	849	0.026	0.017	0.987	Calc.	[9]
	847	0.025	0.016	0.990	Calc.	[10]
	847	0.025	0.017	0.989	Calc.	[6]

Fig. 5. A calculated Fe–Cu phase diagram, together with the experimental data points [104, 123–134]. The solid lines refer to the calculations by Chevalier *et al.* [9] and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [6].

Fig. 6. A calculated Fe–Cu phase diagram, together with the recent experimental data points (99Ama [135]). The solid lines refer to the calculations by Chevalier *et al.* [9] and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [6].

Fig. 7. The calculated enthalpy of mixing for liquid Fe–Cu alloys at 1600 °C, together with the experimental data points (61Oel [128], 61Pod [136], 66EIK [137], 67Woo [138], 73Toz [139], and 80Bat [140]). The solid line refers to the calculations by Chevalier *et al.* [9] and the dotted line refers to those by Jansson [6]. The reference states used are pure liquid Fe and Cu.

Fig. 8. The calculated partial enthalpies in liquid Fe–Cu alloys at 1600 °C, together with experimental data points [142]. The solid lines refer to the calculations by Chevalier *et al.* [9] and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [6]. The reference states used are pure liquid Fe and Cu.

Fig. 9. The calculated partial enthalpies in liquid Fe–Cu alloys at 1550 °C, together with the experimental data points [141]. The solid lines refer to the calculations by Chevalier *et al.* [9] and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [6]. The reference states used are pure liquid Fe and Cu.

Fig. 10. The calculated chemical potentials of Fe and Cu in liquid Fe–Cu alloys at 1600 °C, together with the experimental data points (56Mor [143], 80Bat [140], 80Mar [117], and 81Tim [144]). The solid lines refer to the calculations by Chevalier *et al.* [9] and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [6]. The reference states used are pure liquid Fe and Cu.

Fig. 11. The calculated function $G_{Cu}^E / (1-x_{Cu})^2$ in liquid Fe–Cu alloys at 1600 °C, together with the experimental data points (56Kor [145], 56Mor [143], 80Mar [117], and 81Tim [144]). The solid line refers to the calculations by Chevalier *et al.* [9] and the dotted line refers to those by Jansson [6]. The reference state used is pure fcc Cu.

Fig. 12. The calculated enthalpy of mixing for fcc Fe–Cu alloys at 1050 °C, together with the experimental data points (79Kub [146]). The solid line refers to the calculations by Chevalier *et al.* [9] and the dotted line refers to those by Jansson [6]. The reference states used are pure fcc Fe and Cu.

Fig. 13. The calculated activity of Cu in fcc Fe–Cu alloys at 1310 °C to 1050 °C, together with the experimental data points (81Ari [147]). The solid line refers to the calculations by Chevalier *et al.* [9] and the dotted line refers to those by Jansson [6]. The reference state used is pure fcc Cu.

Fig. 14. The calculated metastable (MS) bcc–L region in the Fe–Cu system, together with the experimental data points (99Ama [135]). The solid lines refer to the calculations by Chevalier *et al.* [9] and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [6].

Fig. 15. The calculated metastable (MS) liquid miscibility gap of the Fe–Cu system, together with the experimental data points (58Nak [126], 89Eld [148], 97Wil [149], and 99Ama [135]). The solid lines refer to the calculations by Chevalier *et al.* [9] and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [6].

3.3 The Fe–Mo system

The Fe–Mo system has been assessed by Fernández Guillermet [12] and Andersson [13]. The latter description was later modified for the IAD optimizing a new description for the liquid phase. This resulted in better agreement with the experimental bcc+liquid region. The present work reviews this description and presents its experimental verification.

3.3.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 10 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 11 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 12.

Table 10. Phases and their modeling in the Fe–Mo description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Fe,Mo), substitutional, RK
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Fe,Mo), substitutional, RK
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Fe,Mo), substitutional, RK
μ (\approx μ)	(Fe) ₇ (Mo) ₂ (Fe,Mo) ₄ , sublattice, RK
R	(Fe) ₂₇ (Mo) ₁₄ (Fe,Mo) ₁₂ , sublattice, RK
sigma (\approx σ)	(Fe) ₈ (Mo) ₄ (Fe,Mo) ₁₈ , sublattice, RK
Fe ₂ Mo (\approx λ)	(Fe) ₂ (Mo), stoichiometric

Note: RK = Redlich–Kister excess model.

Table 11. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Fe–Mo according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Phase equilibria of the phase diagram	[152–160]
Enthalpy of mixing in liquid alloys at 1575 °C	[112]
Activity of Fe in liquid and solid alloys at 1550 °C	[159]

Table 12. The thermodynamic description of the Fe–Mo system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe,Mo)</i>	
$L_{\text{Fe,Mo}}^{\text{L}} = (-6900 - 0.23T) + (-9000 + 3.85T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Mo}})$	IAD
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe,Mo)</i>	
$L_{\text{Fe,Mo}}^{\text{bcc}} = (+36818 - 9.141T) + (-362 - 5.724T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Mo}})$	[13]
$T_{\text{c}}^{\text{bcc}} = 1043x_{\text{Fe}} + x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Mo}}(335 + 526(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Mo}}))$	[13]
$\beta^{\text{bcc}} = 2.22x_{\text{Fe}}$	[96]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe,Mo)</i>	
$L_{\text{Fe,Mo}}^{\text{fcc}} = (+28347 - 17.691T)$	[13]
$T_{\text{c}}^{\text{fcc}} = -201x_{\text{Fe}}$	[96]
$\beta^{\text{fcc}} = -2.1x_{\text{Fe}}$	[96]
<i>μ (μ) (3 sublattices, sites: 7:2:4, constituents: Fe:Mo:Fe,Mo)</i>	
$G_{\text{Fe:Mo:Fe}}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 2G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + 4G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + (+39475 - 6.032T)$	[13]
$G_{\text{Fe:Mo:Mo}}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 6G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + (-46663 - 5.891T)$	[13]
<i>R (3 sublattices, sites: 27:14:12, constituents: Fe:Mo:Fe,Mo)</i>	
$G_{\text{Fe:Mo:Fe}}^{\circ,\text{R}} = 27G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 14G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + 12G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + (-77487 - 50.486T)$	[13]
$G_{\text{Fe:Mo:Mo}}^{\circ,\text{R}} = 27G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 26G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + (+313474 - 289.472T)$	[13]

Note: the thermodynamic data for the pure components is given by [96].

Table 12 (continued)

Equation	Reference
<i>sigma</i> (σ) (3 sublattices, sites: 8:4:18, constituents: Fe:Mo:Fe,Mo)	
$G_{\text{Fe:Mo:Fe}}^{\sigma} = 8G_{\text{Fe}}^{\text{fcc}} + 4G_{\text{Mo}}^{\text{bcc}} + 18G_{\text{Fe}}^{\text{bcc}} + (-1813 - 27.272T)$	[13]
$G_{\text{Fe:Mo:Mo}}^{\sigma} = 8G_{\text{Fe}}^{\text{fcc}} + 22G_{\text{Mo}}^{\text{bcc}} + (+83326 - 69.618T)$	[13]
$L_{\text{Fe:Mo:Fe,Mo}}^{\sigma} = (+222909)$	[13]
<i>Fe₂Mo</i> (λ) (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents: Fe:Mo)	
$G_{\text{Fe:Mo}}^{\lambda} = 2G_{\text{Fe}}^{\text{fcc}} + G_{\text{Mo}}^{\text{bcc}} + (-10798 - 0.132T)$	[161]

Note: the thermodynamic data for the pure components is given by [96].

3.3.2 Results

The results of the calculations using the IAD and by Andersson [13] together with the experimental data (Table 11) are presented in Figures 16–19. The agreement is reasonably good in both calculations. Note the improved position of the L+bcc region using the IAD (Figure 17).

Fig. 16. A calculated Fe–Mo phase diagram, together with the experimental data points (51Ham [152], 61Gib [153], 68Raw [154], 73Kir [155], 74Hei [156], 75Alb [157], 79Ues [158], 80Ich [159], and 81Tak [160]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines show those by Andersson [13].

Fig. 17. The Fe-rich portion of the calculated Fe–Mo phase diagram, together with the experimental data points (61Gib [153] and 80lch [159]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines show those by Andersson [13].

Fig. 18. The enthalpy of mixing for liquid Fe–Mo alloys at 1575 °C, together with the experimental data points (82lch [112]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines show those by Andersson [13]. The reference states used are pure liquid Fe and Mo.

Fig. 19. The activity of Fe in Fe–Mo alloys at 1550 °C, together with the experimental data points (80lch [159]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines show those by Andersson [13]. The reference state used is pure bcc Fe.

3.4 The Fe–Ni system

The Fe–Ni system has been assessed by Xin *et al.* [14], Swartzendruber *et al.* [15], and Lee [5]. The description by Xin *et al.* [14], not presented in the open literature, was applied by Jansson [45] in his ternary Cu–Fe–Ni description. Later, Lee [5] modified the liquid phase description by Jansson [45] to get better agreement with the experimental phase equilibria in the ternary Fe–Cr–Ni system. The Fe–Ni description of Lee [5] was adapted for use in the IAD, due to its use in many higher-order SGTE assessments. The present work reviews this description and presents its experimental verification.

3.4.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 13 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 14 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 15.

Table 13. Phases and their modeling in the Fe–Ni description by Lee [5].

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Fe,Ni), substitutional, RK
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Fe,Ni), substitutional, RK
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Fe,Ni), substitutional, RK
hcp_A3 (\approx hcp, metastable)	(Fe,Ni), substitutional, RK
fcc-L12 phase (ordered, stable below 517 °C)	(Fe,Ni) _{0.75} (Fe,Ni) _{0.25} , sublattice

Note: RK = Redlich–Kister excess model.

Table 14. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Fe–Ni [5].

Experimental data	Reference(s)
High-temperature phase equilibria of the phase diagram	[104, 109, 162–165]
Low-temperature phase equilibria of the phase diagram	[166–171]
Mixing enthalpy of liquid alloys at 1600 °C	[172–175]
Mixing enthalpy of fcc alloys at 1400 °C	[176–179]
Chemical potentials in liquid alloys at 1600 °C (from activity coefficient measurements)	[180–187]
Chemical potentials in fcc alloys at 1200 °C and 1000 °C (from activity coefficient measurements)	[185, 187–192]

Table 15. The thermodynamic description of the Fe–Ni system [5] excluding the fcc-L12 phase described in [45]

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe,Ni)</i> $L_{\text{Fe,Ni}}^{\text{L}} = (-16911 + 5.162T) + (+10180 - 4.147T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})$	[5]
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe,Ni)</i> $L_{\text{Fe,Ni}}^{\text{bcc}} = (-957 - 1.287T) + (+1789 - 1.929T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})$	[45]
$T^{\text{cbcc}} = 1043x_{\text{Fe}} + 575x_{\text{Ni}}$	[96]
$\beta^{\text{bcc}} = 2.22x_{\text{Fe}} + 0.85x_{\text{Ni}}$	[96]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe,Ni)</i> $L_{\text{Fe,Ni}}^{\text{fcc}} = (-12054 + 3.274T) + (+11082 - 4.45T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}}) + (-726)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})^2$	[45]
$T_{\text{c}}^{\text{fcc}} = -201x_{\text{Fe}} + 633x_{\text{Ni}} + x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Ni}}(2133 - 682(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}}))$	[45]
$\beta^{\text{fcc}} = -2.1x_{\text{Fe}} + 0.52x_{\text{Ni}} + x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Ni}}(9.55 + 7.23(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}}) + 5.93(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})^2 + 6.18(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})^3)$	[45]
<i>hcp^(m) (1 sublattices, sites: 1:1, constituents: Fe,Ni)</i> $L_{\text{Fe,Ni}}^{\text{hcp}} = L_{\text{Fe,Ni}}^{\text{fcc}}$	[45]

Notes: (m) = metastable phase; the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

3.4.2 Results

The results of the calculations [5] together with the experimental data (Table 14) are presented in Figures 20–26. The agreement is reasonably good.

Fig. 20. The calculated [5] high-temperature portion of the Fe–Ni phase diagram, together with the experimental data points (23Han [162], 25Kas [163], 57Hel [104], 76Cho [164], 77Sch [109], and 84Kun [165]).

Fig. 21. The calculated [5] low-temperature portion of the Fe–Ni phase diagram, together with the experimental data points (36Jet [166], 49Jon [167], 49Owe [168], 63Heu [169], 65Gol [170], and 80Rom [171]).

Fig. 22. The calculated [5] enthalpy of mixing in liquid Fe–Ni alloys at 1600 °C, together with the experimental data points (70Pre [172], 74Bat [173], 81Igu [174], and 98Thi [175]). The reference states used are pure liquid Fe and Ni.

Fig. 23. The calculated [5] enthalpy of mixing in fcc Fe–Ni alloys at 1400 °C, together with the experimental data points (61Ste [176], 63Den [177], 67Kub [178], and 71Spe [179]). The reference states used are pure fcc Fe and Ni.

Fig. 24. The calculated [5] chemical potentials of Fe and Ni in liquid Fe–Ni alloys at 1600 °C, together with the experimental data points [180–187]. The reference states used are pure liquid Fe and Ni.

Fig. 25. The calculated [5] chemical potentials of Fe and Ni in fcc Fe-Ni alloys at 1200 °C, together with the experimental data points [185, 187–192]. The reference states used are pure fcc Fe and Ni.

Fig. 26. The calculated [5] chemical potentials of Fe and Ni in fcc Fe-Ni alloys at 1000 °C, together with the experimental data points [189, 190, 192]. The reference states used are pure fcc Fe and Ni.

3.5 The Al–Cr system

The Al–Cr system has been assessed by Saunders and Rivlin [16], Murray [17], Saunders [18], and Liang *et al.* [19]. The assessment by Liang *et al.* [19] was later modified in the IAD by optimizing new descriptions for the liquid and fcc phases and treating all non-stoichiometric compounds of the system as stoichiometric. The purpose was to make the binary description and the following Fe–Al–Cr description as simple as possible, for practical calculations for solidification modeling of steels. The present work reviews the Al–Cr description according to the IAD and presents its experimental verification.

3.5.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 16 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 17 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 18. Note the simple treatment of all compounds, in regard to those by Liang *et al.* [19], and the modeling of Al_8Cr_5 phases as $(\text{Al})_3(\text{Cr})_2$ emphasizing their Cr-rich boundary.

Table 16. Phases and their modeling in the Al–Cr description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Al,Cr), substitutional, RK
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Al,Cr), substitutional, RK
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Al,Cr), substitutional, RK
Al_7Cr	$(\text{Al})_7(\text{Cr})$, stoichiometric
$\text{Al}_{11}\text{Cr}_2$	$(\text{Al})_{11}(\text{Cr})_2$, stoichiometric
Al_4Cr	$(\text{Al})_4(\text{Cr})$, stoichiometric
$\text{Al}_8\text{Cr}_5\text{-H}$	$(\text{Al})_3(\text{Cr})_2$, stoichiometric
$\text{Al}_8\text{Cr}_5\text{-L}$	$(\text{Al})_3(\text{Cr})_2$, stoichiometric
AlCr_2	$(\text{Al})(\text{Cr})_2$, stoichiometric

Note: RK = Redlich–Kister excess model.

Table 17. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Al–Cr according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Phase equilibria of the phase diagram	[193–203]
Chemical potential of Al in bcc alloys at 1000 °C	[199]
Activity of Cr in solid alloys at 1000 °C and 1150 °C	[141, 204]
Enthalpy of formation for solid alloys at 1010 °C and 25 °C	[119, 202, 205], [206] (predicted)

Table 18. The thermodynamic description of the Al–Cr system according to the IAD

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Cr)</i> $L_{Al,Cr}^L = (-33500) + (-10000 + 4T)(x_{Al} - x_{Cr})$	IAD
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Cr)</i> $L_{Al,Cr}^{bcc} = (-58258 + 8.441T)$ $T_c^{bcc} = -311x_{Cr}$ $\beta^{bcc} = -0.008x_{Cr}$	[19] [96] [96]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Cr)</i> $L_{Al,Cr}^{fcc} = (-47000 + 7T)$ $T_c^{fcc} = -1109x_{Cr}$ $\beta^{fcc} = -2.46x_{Cr}$	IAD [96] [96]
<i>Al₇Cr (2 sublattices, sites: 7:1, constituents: Al:Cr)</i> $G_{Al:Cr}^{o,Al_7Cr} = 7G_{Al}^{o,fcc} + G_{Cr}^{o,bcc} + (-89000 + 14T)$	IAD
<i>Al₁₁Cr₂ (2 sublattices, sites: 11:2, constituents: Al:Cr)</i> $G_{Al:Cr}^{o,Al_{11}Cr_2} = 11G_{Al}^{o,fcc} + 2G_{Cr}^{o,bcc} + (-137000 - 6T)$	IAD
<i>Al₄Cr (2 sublattices, sites: 4:1, constituents: Al:Cr)</i> $G_{Al:Cr}^{o,Al_4Cr} = 4G_{Al}^{o,fcc} + G_{Cr}^{o,bcc} + (-82000 + 13T)$	IAD
<i>Al₈Cr₅-H (2 sublattices, sites: 3:2, constituents: Al:Cr)</i> $G_{Al:Cr}^{o,Al_8Cr_5-H} = 3G_{Al}^{o,fcc} + 2G_{Cr}^{o,bcc} + (-83200 - 8T)$	IAD
<i>Al₈Cr₅-L (2 sublattices, sites: 3:2, constituents: Al:Cr)</i> $G_{Al:Cr}^{o,Al_8Cr_5-L} = 3G_{Al}^{o,fcc} + 2G_{Cr}^{o,bcc} + (-94500)$	IAD
<i>AlCr₂ (2 sublattices, sites: 1:2, constituents: Al:Cr)</i> $G_{Al:Cr}^{o,AlCr_2} = G_{Al}^{o,fcc} + 2G_{Cr}^{o,bcc} + (-45400 - 1T)$	IAD

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

3.5.2 Results

The results of the calculations according to the IAD and Liang *et al.* [19] together with the experimental data (Table 17) are presented in Figures 27–32. The agreement is reasonably good in both calculations. Note the simplified (stoichiometric) description of all compounds (Figure 27) and the slightly better agreement for the fcc region (Figure 28) according to the IAD.

Fig. 27. A calculated Al–Cr phase diagram, together with the experimental data points (45Kor [195], 63Kös [198], 68Joh [199], 80Ere [200], 00Mah [202], and 05Gru [203]). The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Liang *et al.* [19].

Fig. 28. The calculated Al-rich portion of the Al–Cr phase diagram, together with the experimental data points (33Fin [193], 38Koc [194], 45Ray [196], 60Zol [197], 80Ere [200], and 83Kuz [201]). The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Liang *et al.* [19].

Fig. 29. The calculated (IAD) chemical potential of Al in bcc Al–Cr alloys at 1000 °C, together with the experimental data points (68Joh [199]). The calculations are practically identical to those by Liang *et al.* [19]. The reference state used is pure bcc Al.

Fig. 30. The calculated activity of Cr in solid Al–Cr alloys at 1150 °C and 1000 °C, together with the experimental data points (86Ofo [204] and 73Hul [141]). The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted line refers to those by Liang *et al.* [19]. The reference state used is pure bcc Cr.

Fig. 31. The calculated enthalpy of formation for solid Al–Cr alloys at 1000 °C, together with the experimental data points [202]. The solid line refers to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted line refers to those by Liang *et al.* [19]. The reference states used are pure liquid Al and pure bcc Cr.

Fig. 32. The calculated enthalpy of formation for solid Al–Cr alloys, at 25 °C, together with the experimental (60Kub [119] and 95Bar [205]) and predicted (83Nie [206]) data points. The solid line refers to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted line refers to those by Liang *et al.* [19]. The reference states used are pure fcc Al and pure bcc Cr.

3.6 The Al–Cu system

The Al–Cu system has been assessed by Kaufman and Nesor [20], Murray [21], Saunders [22], and Miettinen [23]. The latest assessment by Miettinen [23] was focused on Cu-rich alloys and correlated well with the experimental data. However, as it stabilized the bcc phase too much at higher Al contents ($x_{\text{Al}} > 0.35$), it was reasonable to rely on the earlier but complete assessment of Saunders [22]. On the other hand, as the copper-rich bcc+fcc equilibrium was not as well assessed by Saunders [22], slight modifications were made for the IAD for the bcc, fcc, and γ D83 phase data by Saunders [22]. The present work reviews the Al–Cu description of the IAD and presents its experimental verification. It should be remembered that this work is still heavily based on the essential work by Saunders [22].

3.6.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 19 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 20 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 21.

Table 19. Phases and their modeling in the Al–Cu description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Al,Cu), substitutional, RK
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Al,Cu), substitutional, RK
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Al,Cu), substitutional, RK
AlCu- θ (\approx θ)	(Al) ₂ (Al,Cu), sublattice, RK
AlCu- η (\approx η)	(Al,Cu)(Cu), sublattice, RK
AlCu- ε (\approx ε)	(Al,Cu)(Cu), sublattice, RK
AlCu- γ H (\approx γ H)	(Al) ₄ (Al,Cu)(Cu) ₈ , sublattice, RK
AlCu- γ D83 (\approx γ D83)	(Al) ₄ (Al,Cu)(Cu) ₈ , sublattice, RK
AlCu- ξ (\approx ξ)	(Al) ₉ (Cu) ₁₁ , stoichiometric
AlCu- δ (\approx δ)	(Al) ₂ (Cu) ₃ , stoichiometric

Note: RK = Redlich–Kister excess model.

Table 20. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Al–Cu according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Phase equilibria of the phase diagram	[207–228]
Enthalpy of mixing for liquid alloys at 1427–1100 °C	[229–232]
Chemical potential of Al in liquid alloys at 1100 °C	[233, 234]
Enthalpy of formation for solid alloys at 500 ° and 25 °C	[230, 235, 236]
Chemical potential of Al in solid alloys at 707 °C and 500 °C	[236, 237]

Table 21. The thermodynamic description of the Al–Cu system according to the IAD

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Cu)</i>	
$L_{Al,Cu}^L = (-66622 + 8.1T) + (+46800 - 90.8T + 10T \ln T)(x_{Al} - x_{Cu}) + (-2812)(x_{Al} - x_{Cu})^2$	[22]
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Cu)</i>	
$L_{Al,Cu}^{bcc} = (-76700 + 7T) + (+46000 - 5.5T)(x_{Al} - x_{Cu}) + (+2200)(x_{Al} - x_{Cu})^2$	IAD
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Cu)</i>	
$L_{Al,Cu}^{fcc} = (-53500 + 2T) + (+38600 - 2T)(x_{Al} - x_{Cu}) + (+1.4T)(x_{Al} - x_{Cu})^2$	IAD
<i>AlCu-θ (θ) (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents (Al)(Al,Cu)₂)</i>	
$G_{Al:Al}^{\circ,\theta} = 3G_{Al}^{\circ,bcc}$	[22]
$G_{Al:Cu}^{\circ,\theta} = 2G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + G_{Cu}^{\circ,fcc} + (-47406 + 6.75T)$	[22]
$L_{Al:Al,Cu}^{\theta} = (+2221)$	[22]
<i>AlCu-η (η) (2 sublattices, sites: 1:1, constituents (Al,Cu)(Cu))</i>	
$G_{Al:Cu}^{\circ,\eta} = 2G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + G_{Cu}^{\circ,fcc} + (-40560 + 3.14T)$	[22]
$G_{Cu:Cu}^{\circ,\eta} = 2G_{Cu}^{\circ,bcc}$	[22]
$L_{Al,Cu:Cu}^{\eta} = (-25740 - 20T)$	[22]
<i>AlCu-ε (ε) (2 sublattices, sites: 1:1, constituents (Al,Cu)(Cu))</i>	
$G_{Al:Cu}^{\circ,\epsilon} = 2G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + G_{Cu}^{\circ,fcc} + (-36976 + 1.2T)$	[22]
$G_{Cu:Cu}^{\circ,\epsilon} = 2G_{Cu}^{\circ,bcc}$	[22]
$L_{Al,Cu:Cu}^{\epsilon} = (+7600 - 24T) + (-72000)(y_{Al} - y_{Cu})$	[22]
<i>AlCu-γH (γH) (3 sublattices, sites: 4:1:8, constituents (Al)₄(Al,Cu)(Cu)₈)</i>	
$G_{Al:Al:Cu}^{\circ,\gamma H} = 5G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 8G_{Cu}^{\circ,fcc} + (-219258 - 45.5T)$	[22]
$G_{Al:Cu:Cu}^{\circ,\gamma H} = 4G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 9G_{Cu}^{\circ,fcc} + (-200460 - 58.5T)$	[22]
<i>AlCu-γD83 (γD83) (3 sublattices, sites: 4:1:8, constituents (Al)₄(Al,Cu)(Cu)₈)</i>	
$G_{Al:Al:Cu}^{\circ,\gamma D83} = 5G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 8G_{Cu}^{\circ,fcc} + (-300716 + 390T - 52T \ln T)$	[22]
$G_{Al:Cu:Cu}^{\circ,\gamma D83} = 4G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 9G_{Cu}^{\circ,fcc} + (-277700 + 377T - 52T \ln T)$	IAD
<i>AlCu-ξ (ξ) (2 sublattices, sites: 9:11, constituents (Al)₉(Cu)₁₁)</i>	
$G_{Al:Cu}^{\circ,\xi} = 9G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 11G_{Cu}^{\circ,fcc} + (-420000 + 18T)$	[22]
<i>AlCu-δ (δ) (2 sublattices, sites: 2:3, constituents (Al)₂(Cu)₃)</i>	
$G_{Al:Cu}^{\circ,\delta} = 2G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 3G_{Cu}^{\circ,fcc} + (-106700 + 3T)$	[22]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

3.6.2 Results

The results of the calculations using the IAD and those by Saunders [22] together with the experimental data (Table 20) are presented in Figures 33–41. The agreement is reasonably good in both calculations. Note the slightly better agreement according to the IAD for the Cu-rich bcc+fcc and fcc+liq equilibria in Figure 36.

Fig. 33. A calculated Al–Cu phase diagram, together with points of invariant phase equilibria assessed by Murray [21] (94Mur). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Saunders [22].

Fig. 34. The calculated Al-rich portion of the Al-Cu phase diagram at 0 to 3 at-% Cu, together with the experimental data points (26Dix [211], 33Phi [214], 33Sto [215], 34Mat [217], 36Aue [218], 38Zak [220], 41Bro, [222], 43Bor [223], and 48EII [224]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Saunders [22].

Fig. 35. The calculated (IAD) Al-rich portion of the Al-Cu phase diagram, at 0 to 35 at-% Cu, together with the experimental data points (08Gwy [207], 22Sto [208], 25Taz [210], 27Nis [212], 33Sto [215], 34His [216], 76Tas [227], and 77Sch [228]). The calculations are practically identical to those by Saunders [22].

Fig. 36. The calculated Cu-rich portion of the Al-Cu phase diagram at 60 to 95 at-%Cu, together with the experimental data points (22Sto [208], 24Sto [209], 33Obi [213], 34His [216], 37Dow [219], 40Hum [221], 58Vig [225], and 72Lin [226]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Saunders [22].

Fig. 37. The calculated (IAD) enthalpy of mixing for liquid Al-Cu alloys at 1150 °C, together with the experimental data points (30Kaw [229], 37Oel [230], 75Ita [231], and 93Sto [232]). The calculations are identical to those by Saunders [22]. The reference states used are pure liquid Cu and Al.

Fig. 38. The calculated (IAD) chemical potential of Al in liquid Al–Cu alloys at 1100 °C, together with the experimental data points (65Wil [233] and 76Lay [234]). The calculations are identical to those by Saunders [22]. The reference state used is pure liquid Al.

Fig. 39. The calculated enthalpy of formation for solid Al–Cu alloys at 500 ° and 25 °C, together with the experimental data points (37Oel [230], 67Sin [235], and 73Hai [236]). The solid line refers to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted line refers to those by Saunders [22]. The reference states used are pure fcc Cu and Al.

Fig. 40. The calculated (IAD) chemical potential of Al in Al–Cu alloys at 707 °C, together with the experimental data points (72Al [237]). The calculations are practically identical to those by Saunders [22]. The reference state used is pure liquid Al.

Fig. 41. The calculated chemical potential of Al in Al–Cu alloys at 500 °C, together with the experimental data points (73Hai [236]). The solid line refers to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted line refers to those by Saunders [22]. The reference state used is pure fcc Al.

3.7 The Al–Mo system

The Al–Mo system has been assessed by Kaufman and Nesor [20], and Saunders [24, 25]. The assessment by Saunders [25] was later modified for use in the IAD introducing a new description for the fcc phase and treating the non-stoichiometric AlMo phase as stoichiometric. The purpose was to make the binary description and the following Fe–Al–Mo description as simple as possible for practical calculations to be used in solidification modeling of steels. The present work reviews the Al–Mo description according to the IAD and presents its experimental verification.

3.7.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 22 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 23 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 24. Note that the stoichiometric AlMo phase, which is formulated as $(Al)_{48.5}(Mo)_{51.5}$ in the IAD, refers to the non-stoichiometric AlMo phase by Saunders [25] formulated as $(Al,Mo)(Al,Mo)$.

Table 22. Phases and their modeling in the Al–Mo description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Al,Mo), substitutional, RK
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Al,Mo), substitutional, RK
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Al,Mo), substitutional, RK
hcp_A3 (\approx hcp, metastable)	(Al,Mo), substitutional, RK
Al ₁₂ Mo	(Al) ₁₂ (Mo), stoichiometric
Al ₅ Mo	(Al) ₅ (Mo), stoichiometric
Al ₄ Mo	(Al) ₄ (Mo), stoichiometric
Al ₈ Mo ₃	(Al) ₈ (Mo) ₃ , stoichiometric
Al ₆₃ Mo ₃₇	(Al) ₆₃ (Mo) ₃₇ , stoichiometric
AlMo	(Al) _{48.5} (Mo) _{51.5} , stoichiometric
AlMo ₃	(Al)(Mo) ₃ , stoichiometric

Note: RK = Redlich–Kister excess model.

Table 23. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Al–Mo according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Phase equilibria of the phase diagram	[152, 238–243]
Enthalpy of mixing for liquid alloys at 1427 °C	[244]
Enthalpy of formation for solid alloys at 25 °C	[243]

Table 24. The thermodynamic description of the Al–Mo system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Mo)</i>	
$L_{Al,Mo}^L = (-100000 + 35T) + (-15000 + 6.3T)(x_{Al} - x_{Mo})$	[25]
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Mo)</i>	
$L_{Al,Mo}^{bcc} = (-75000 + 25T)$	[25]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Mo)</i>	
$L_{Al,Mo}^{fcc} = (-120000 + 50T)$	IAD
<i>hcp^(m) (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Mo)</i>	
$L_{Al,Mo}^{hcp} = (-85570 + 25T)$	[25]
<i>Al₁₂Mo (2 sublattices, sites: 12:1, constituents: Al,Mo)</i>	
$G_{Al,Mo}^{o,Al_{12}Mo} = 12G_{Al}^{o,fcc} + G_{Mo}^{o,bcc} + (-139100 + 26.975T)$	[25]
<i>Al₅Mo (2 sublattices, sites: 5:1, constituents: Al,Mo)</i>	
$G_{Al,Mo}^{o,Al_5Mo} = 5G_{Al}^{o,fcc} + G_{Mo}^{o,bcc} + (-139104 + 30.156T)$	[25]
<i>Al₄Mo (2 sublattices, sites: 4:1, constituents: Al,Mo)</i>	
$G_{Al,Mo}^{o,Al_4Mo} = 4G_{Al}^{o,fcc} + oGb_{cc}Mo + (-137570 + 29.69T)$	[25]
<i>Al₈Mo₃ (2 sublattices, sites: 8:3 constituents: Al,Mo)</i>	
$G_{Al,Mo}^{o,Al_8Mo_3} = 8G_{Al}^{o,fcc} + 3G_{Mo}^{o,bcc} + (-412500 + 105.05T)$	[25]
<i>Al₆₃Mo₃₇ (2 sublattices, sites: 63:37, constituents: Al,Mo)</i>	
$G_{Al,Mo}^{o,Al_{63}Mo_{37}} = 63G_{Al}^{o,fcc} + 37G_{Mo}^{o,bcc} + (-2268100 + 167.2T)$	[25]
<i>AlMo (2 sublattices, sites: 48.5:51.5 constituents: Al,Mo)</i>	
$G_{Al,Mo}^{o,AlMo} = 4.85G_{Al}^{o,fcc} + 5.15G_{Mo}^{o,bcc} + (-141800 - 23.5T)$	IAD
<i>AlMo₃ (2 sublattices, sites: 1:3 constituents: Al,Mo)</i>	
$G_{Al,Mo}^{o,AlMo_3} = G_{Al}^{o,fcc} + 3G_{Mo}^{o,bcc} + (-89000 + 20T - 0.003T^2)$	[25]

Notes: (m) = metastable phase; the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

3.7.2 Results

The results of the calculations using the IAD as well as by Saunders [25] together with the experimental data (Table 23) are presented in Figures 42–45. The agreement is reasonably good in both calculations. Note the simplified (stoichiometric) description of the AlMo phase (Figure 42) and the slightly better agreement for the fcc region (Figure 43) according to the IAD.

Fig. 42. A calculated Al–Mo phase diagram, together with the experimental data points (51Ham [152], 71Rex [240], 80Mal [242], and 82Shi [243]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dashed lines refer to those by Saunders [25].

Fig. 43. The calculated Al-rich portion of the Al–Mo phase diagram, together with the experimental data points (40Yam [238], 60Vig [239], 76Yer [241], and 80Mal [242]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Saunders [25].

Fig. 44. The calculated (IAD) enthalpy of mixing for liquid Al–Mo alloys at 1427 °C, together with the experimental data points (85Sud [244]). The calculations are identical to those by Saunders [25]. The reference states used are pure liquid Al and Mo.

Fig. 45. The calculated (IAD) enthalpy of formation for solid Al–Mo alloys at 25 °C, together with the experimental data points (82Shi [243]). The calculations are practically identical to those by Saunders [25]. The reference states used are pure fcc Al.

3.8 The Al–Ni system

The Al–Ni system has been assessed by Ansara *et al.* [26] and Huang and Chang [27]. The ordered bcc and AlNi₃ (fcc-L12) phases, and the not-stoichiometric Al₃Ni₂ phase were treated with a sublattice model. The description by Ansara *et al.* [26] was later simplified by Miettinen [65], treating bcc as a substitutional solution phase, and AlNi₃ and Al₃Ni₂ as stoichiometric phases. The B2-ordering of the bcc phase was thus ignored but its effect was included in the disordered bcc phase. The scope of that study was to achieve a simple description of the ternary Cu–Al–Ni system. More recently, the Al–Ni description by Miettinen [65] was modified for the IAD introducing a simpler liquid phase description for the system. The purpose was to make the binary description and the following Fe–Al–Ni description as simple as possible, for practical calculations for the solidification modeling of steels. The present work reviews the Al–Ni description according to the IAD and presents its experimental verification.

3.8.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 25 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 26 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 27. Note that the substitutional solution bcc phase according to the IAD and [65] refers to the ordered bcc phase by [26, 27] formulated as (Al,Ni)(Ni,Va), the stoichiometric AlNi₃ (γ') phase according to the IAD and [65] refers to the ordered fcc-L12 phase by [26,27] formulated as (Al,Ni)₃(Al,Ni), and the stoichiometric Al₃Ni₂ (γ_2) phase according to the IAD and [65] refers to the not-stoichiometric γ_2 phase of [26, 27], formulated as Al₃(Al,Ni)₂(Ni,Va).

Table 25. Phases and their modeling in the Al–Ni description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Al,Ni), substitutional, RK
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Al,Ni), substitutional, RK
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Al,Ni), substitutional, RK
Al ₃ Ni (\approx γ_1)	(Al) ₃ (Ni), stoichiometric
Al ₃ Ni ₂ (\approx γ_2)	(Al) ₃ (Ni) ₂ , stoichiometric
Al ₃ Ni ₅ (\approx γ_3)	(Al) ₃ (Ni) ₅ , stoichiometric
AlNi ₃ (\approx γ')	(Al) ₆ (Ni) ₁₉ , stoichiometric

Note: RK = Redlich–Kister excess model.

Table 26. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Al–Ni according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Phase equilibria of the phase diagram	[245–252]
Enthalpy of mixing for liquid alloys at 1650–1413 °C	[232, 253–257]
Chemical potentials in liquid alloys at 1727–1455 °C	[258–261]
Chemical potentials in solid alloys at 1327 °C	[249]
Chemical potentials in alloys at 1150–1000 °C	[204, 262, 263]
Enthalpy of formation for solid alloys at 827–25 °C	[141, 230, 264–267]
Enthalpy of formation for AlNi ₃	[268]
Gibbs energy of formation for AlNi ₃ and bcc	[269]

Table 27. The thermodynamic description of the Al–Ni system according to the IAD

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Ni)</i>	
$L_{Al,Ni}^L = (-206257 + 40.826T) + (-6759 + 3.932T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})$ $+ (+69168 - 24.759T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})^2 + (-4181 + 2.314T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})^3$	IAD
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Ni)</i>	
$L_{Al,Ni}^{bcc} = (-264500 - 119T + 23T \ln T) + (-107000 + 559T - 67T \ln T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})$ $+ (414000 - 800T + 95T \ln T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})^2$ $+ (-118000 + 970T - 99T \ln T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})^3$	[65]
$T_c^{bcc} = 575x_{Ni}$	[96]
$\beta^{bcc} = 0.85x_{Ni}$	[96]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Ni)</i>	
$L_{Al,Ni}^{fcc} = (-162408 + 16.213T) + (73418 - 34.914T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})$ $+ (33471 - 9.837T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})^2 + (-30758 + 10.253T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})^3$	[26]
$T_c^{fcc} = 633x_{Ni}$	[96]
$\beta^{fcc} = 0.52x_{Ni}$	[96]
<i>Al₃Ni (γ₁) (2 sublattices, sites: 3:1 constituents: Al:Ni)</i>	
$G_{Al:Ni}^{\circ,\gamma_1} = 3G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + (-193936 + 49.196T)$	[26]
<i>Al₃Ni₂ (γ₂) (2 sublattices, sites: 3:2, constituents: Al:Ni)</i>	
$G_{Al:Ni}^{\circ,\gamma_2} = 3G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 2G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + (-296500 - 72.675T + 15T \ln T)$	[65]
<i>Al₃Ni₅ (γ₃) (2 sublattices, sites: 3:5, constituents: Al:Ni)</i>	
$G_{Al:Ni}^{\circ,\gamma_3} = 3G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 5G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + (-444064 + 52.304T)$	[65]
<i>AlNi₃ (γ') (2 sublattices, sites: 6:19, constituents: Al:Ni)</i>	
$G_{Al:Ni}^{\circ,\gamma'} = 6G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 19G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + (-1073000 + 525T - 50T \ln T)$	[65]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

3.8.2 Results

The results of the calculations using the IAD and those by Ansara *et al.* [26] together with the experimental data (Table 26) are presented in Figures 46 through 55 and Table 28. The agreement is reasonably good in both calculations. Note, however, the slightly worse agreement using the IAD due to the simple treatment of the bcc, γ_2 , and γ' phases. Additional experimental phase equilibrium data are available from [270–276], which agree reasonably well with the calculations.

Fig. 46. A calculated Al–Ni phase diagram together with the experimental data points (37Ale [245], 52Tay [246], 69Ras [247], 72Tay [248], 87Hil [249], 88Bre [250], 90Jia [251], and 93Cot [252]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dashed lines refer to those by Ansara *et al.* [26].

Table 28. The calculated and experimental invariant points of the Al–Ni system.

$\phi_1 - \phi_2 - \phi_3$	T (°C)	$x_{\text{Ni}}^{\phi_1}$	$x_{\text{Ni}}^{\phi_2}$	$x_{\text{Ni}}^{\phi_3}$	Type	Reference
L = fcc + Al ₃ Ni	640	0.029	–	0.250	Exp	[277]
	644	0.027	0.002	0.250	Cal	[26]
	645	0.027	0.002	0.250	Cal	IAD
L + Al ₃ Ni ₂ = Al ₃ Ni	854	0.153	0.370	0.250	Exp	[277]
	851	0.172	0.359	0.250	Cal	[26]
	851	0.174	0.400	0.250	Cal	IAD
L + bcc = Al ₃ Ni ₂	1133	0.270	0.420	0.385	Exp	[277]
	1137	0.258	0.411	0.401	Cal	[26]
	1134	0.253	0.415	0.400	Cal	IAD
L = bcc + AlNi ₃ (γ')	1360	0.737	0.700	0.750	Exp	[277]
	1369	0.752	–	–	Exp	[249]
	1362	0.757	–	–	Exp	[250]
	1380	0.755	–	0.765	Exp	[275]
	1369	0.746	0.707	0.750	Cal	[26]
	1364	0.738	0.652	0.760	Cal	IAD
L + fcc = AlNi ₃ (γ')	1362	0.742	0.776	0.751	Exp	[277]
	1372	–	–	0.762	Exp	[249]
	1365	–	–	0.770	Exp	[250]
	1383	0.760	0.790	0.770	Exp	[275]
	1370	0.756	0.788	0.760	Cal	[26]
	1370	0.755	0.788	0.760	Cal	IAD
bcc + AlNi ₃ (γ') = Al ₃ Ni ₅	700	0.605	0.720	0.660	Exp	[277]
	700	0.601	0.728	0.625	Cal	[26]
	700	0.606	0.760	0.625	Cal	IAD
L = bcc	1638	0.500	0.500	–	Exp	[277]
	1680	0.500	0.500	–	Exp	[252]
	1676	0.500	0.500	–	Cal	[26]
	1642	0.508	0.508	–	Cal	IAD

Fig. 47. The calculated enthalpy of mixing for liquid Al–Ni alloys at 1650 °C, together with the experimental data points (71San [253], 72Dyu [254], 83Giz [255], 90Hay [256], 90Sud [257], and 93Sto [232]). The solid line refers to the calculations using the IAD and the dashed line refers to those by Ansara *et al.* [26]. The reference states used are pure liquid Ni and Al.

Fig. 48. The calculated chemical potentials of Al and Ni in liquid Al–Ni alloys at 1600 °C, together with the experimental data points (65Vac [258], 79Sch [259], 80Joh [260], and 90Hil [261]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dashed lines refer to those by Ansara *et al.* [26]. The reference states used are pure liquid Ni and Al.

Fig. 49. The calculated chemical potentials of Al and Ni in solid Al–Ni alloys at 1327 °C, together with the experimental data points (87Hil [249]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dashed lines refer to those by Ansara *et al.* [26]. The reference states used are pure fcc Ni and pure liquid Al.

Fig. 50. The calculated chemical potentials of Al and Ni in Al–Ni alloys at 1150 °C, together with the experimental data points (86Ofo [204]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dashed lines refer to those by Ansara *et al.* [26]. The reference states used are pure fcc Ni and pure liquid Al.

Fig. 51. The calculated chemical potentials of Al and Ni in Al–Ni alloys at 1000 °C, together with the experimental data points (64Ste [262] and 69Han [263]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dashed lines refer to those by Ansara *et al.* [26]. The reference states used are pure fcc Ni and pure liquid Al.

Fig. 52. The calculated enthalpy of the formation for solid Al–Ni alloys at 827 °C, together with the experimental data points (74Esk [264], 75Hen [265], 02Wan [266], and 04Chr [267]). The solid line refers to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted line refers to those by Ansara *et al.* [26]. The reference states used are pure fcc Ni and pure liquid Al.

Fig. 53. The calculated enthalpy of formation for solid Al–Ni alloys at 25 °C, together with the experimental data points (37Oel [230] and 73Hul [141]). The solid line refers to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted line refers to those by Ansara *et al.* [26]. The reference states used are pure fcc Ni and Al.

Fig. 54. The calculated enthalpy of the formation for AlNi_3 (γ'), together with the experimental data points (96Rzy [268]). The solid line refers to the calculations using the IAD for $(\text{Al})_6(\text{Ni})_{19}$ and the dotted line refers to those by Ansara *et al.* [26] for $(\text{Al})(\text{Ni})_3$. The reference states used are pure fcc Ni and Al.

Fig. 55. The calculated Gibbs energy of formation for the AlNi_3 (γ') and bcc phases, together with the points of experimental functions (80Tur [269]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines show those by Ansara *et al.* [26]. Al_3Ni refers to $(\text{Al})_6(\text{Ni})_{19}$ in the IAD and $(\text{Al})(\text{Ni})_3$ in [26]. The reference states used are pure fcc Ni and pure liquid Al.

3.9 The Cr–Cu system

The Cr–Cu system has been assessed by Hämäläinen *et al.* [28], and Zeng and Hämäläinen [29]. It was later reassessed for the IAD to improve the agreement with some experimental phase equilibrium data and to prevent the overly strong stabilization of the fcc phase in the following Fe–Cr–Cu description. The present work reviews the Cr–Cu description using the IAD and presents its experimental verification.

3.9.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 29 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 30 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 31.

Table 29. Phases and their modeling in the Cr–Cu description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Cr,Cu), substitutional, RK
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Cr,Cu), substitutional, RK
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Cr,Cu), substitutional, RK

Note: RK = Redlich–Kister excess model.

Table 30. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Cr–Cu according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Phase equilibria of the phase diagram	[278–287]
Activity of Cr in liquid alloys at 1150 to 1550 °C	[284, 285, 288]

Table 31. The thermodynamic description of the Cr–Cu system according to the IAD

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Cu)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Cu}^L = (+35500 - 3T) + (-1000)(x_{Cr} - x_{Cu}) + (+5500)(x_{Cr} - x_{Cu})^2$	IAD
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Cu)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Cu}^{bcc} = (+70700 + 5T)$	IAD
$T_c^{bcc} = -311x_{Cr}$	[96]
$\beta^{bcc} = -0.008x_{Cr}$	[96]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Cu)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Cu}^{fcc} = (+74700 - 20T)$	IAD
$T_c^{fcc} = -1109x_{Cr}$	[96]
$\beta^{fcc} = -2.46x_{Cr}$	[96]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

3.9.2 Results

The results of the calculations using the IAD as well as those by Zeng and Hämäläinen [29] together with the experimental data (Table 30) are presented in Figures 56–61. The agreement is reasonably good in both calculations but slightly better according to the IAD.

Fig. 56. A calculated Cr-Cu phase diagram, together with the experimental data points (57Doi [280], 77Kuz [283], 82Tim [284], 84Ono [285], and 00Li [287]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zeng and Hämmäläinen [29].

Fig. 57. The calculated Cr-rich portion of the Cr-Cu phase diagram, together with the experimental data points (77Kuz [283] and 86Leo [286]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zeng and Hämmäläinen [29].

Fig. 58. The calculated Cu-rich portion of the Cr–Cu phase diagram, together with the experimental data points (39Ale [278], 48Hib [279], 57Doi [280], 67Zak [281], and 75Dri [282]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zeng and Hämmäläinen [29].

Fig. 59. The calculated activity of Cr in liquid Cu-rich Cr–Cu alloys at 1150 °C and 1250 °C, together with the experimental data points (91Ono [288]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zeng and Hämmäläinen [29]. The reference state used is pure bcc Cr.

Fig. 60. The calculated activity of Cr in liquid Cu-rich Cr–Cu alloys at 1200 °C and 1300 °C, together with the experimental data points (84Ono [285] and 91Ono [288]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zeng and Härmäläinen [29]. The reference state used is pure bcc Cr.

Fig. 61. The calculated (IAD) activity of Cr in the bcc+liquid and liquid regions of the Cr–Cu system at 1550 °C, together with the experimental data points (82Tim [284]). The calculations are practically identical to those by Zeng and Härmäläinen [29]. The reference state used is pure bcc Cr.

3.10 The Cr–Mn system

The Cr–Mn system has been assessed by Lee [30]. This description was later modified for the IAD, simplifying its complex magnetic ordering functions of the bcc phase. The new description, however, is still considered to be that by Lee [30]. The present work reviews the Cr–Mn description by Lee [30] and presents its experimental verification.

3.10.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 32 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 33 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 34.

Table 32. Phases and their modeling in the Cr–Mn description by Lee [30].

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Cr,Mn), substitutional, RK
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Cr,Mn), substitutional, RK
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Cr,Mn), substitutional, RK
cbcc_A12 (\approx cbcc)	(Cr,Mn), substitutional, RK
cub_A13 (\approx cub)	(Cr,Mn), substitutional, RK
Sigma (\approx σ)	(Mn) ₈ (Cr) ₄ (Cr,Mn) ₁₈ , sublattice, RK
Sigma-H (\approx σ H, high-temperature sigma)	(Mn) ₈ (Cr) ₄ (Cr,Mn) ₁₈ , sublattice, RK
Cr ₃ Mn ₅ (\approx α)	(Cr) ₃ (Mn) ₅ , stoichiometric

Note: RK = Redlich–Kister excess model.

Table 33. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Cr–Mn [30].

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Phase equilibria of the phase diagram	[104, 289–293]
Activity of Mn in solid alloys at 900 °C and 1000 °C	[294]
Activity of Mn in solid alloys at $x_{\text{Mn}} = 0.588$ and $x_{\text{Mn}} = 0.725$	[294]
Neel temperature of bcc alloys	[293, 295–297]

Table 34. The thermodynamic description of the Cr–Mn system according to the IAD and [30].

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Mn)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Mn}^L = (-15009 + 13.659T) + (+504 + 0.948T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Mn})$	[30]
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Mn)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Mn}^{bcc} = (-20328 + 18.734T) + (-9162 + 4.418T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Mn})$	[30]
$T_c^{bcc} = -311x_{Cr} - 580x_{Mn} + x_{Cr}x_{Mn}(-1350 - 1350(x_{Cr} - x_{Mn})^2 - 2400(x_{Cr} - x_{Mn})^3)$	IAD
$\beta^{bcc} = -0.008x_{Cr} - 0.27x_{Mn} + x_{Cr}x_{Mn}(0.5 - 1.9(x_{Cr} - x_{Mn})^2)$	IAD
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Mn)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Mn}^{fcc} = (-19088 + 17.542T)$	[30]
$T_c^{fcc} = -1109x_{Cr} - 1620x_{Mn}$	[30]
$\beta^{fcc} = -2.46x_{Cr} - 1.86x_{Mn}$	[30]
<i>cbcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Mn)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Mn}^{cbcc} = (-38349 + 22.693T)$	[30]
<i>cub (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Mn)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Mn}^{cub} = (-31260 + 16.492T)$	[30]
<i>Sigma (σ) (3 sublattices, sites: 8:4:18, constituents: Mn:Cr:Cr,Mn)</i>	
$G_{Mn:Cr:Mn}^{\sigma,\sigma} = 8G_{Mn}^{\sigma,fcc} + 4G_{Cr}^{\sigma,bcc} + 18G_{Mn}^{\sigma,bcc} + (+172946 + 69.0245T)$	[30]
$G_{Mn:Cr:Cr}^{\sigma,\sigma} = 8G_{Mn}^{\sigma,fcc} + 22G_{Cr}^{\sigma,bcc} + (+65859.5)$	[30]
$L_{Mn:Cr:Cr,Mn}^{\sigma} = (-1095771 + 862.0312T)$	[30]
<i>Sigma-High (σ^H) (3 sublattices, sites: 8:4:18, constituents: Mn:Cr:Cr,Mn)</i>	
$G_{Mn:Cr:Mn}^{\sigma,\sigma^H} = 8G_{Mn}^{\sigma,fcc} + 4G_{Cr}^{\sigma,bcc} + 18G_{Mn}^{\sigma,bcc} + (-74263 - 10.7082T)$	[30]
$G_{Mn:Cr:Cr}^{\sigma,\sigma^H} = 8G_{Mn}^{\sigma,fcc} + 22G_{Cr}^{\sigma,bcc} + (-192369 + 152.4742T)$	[30]
$L_{Mn:Cr:Cr,Mn}^{\sigma^H} = (+90000)$	[30]
<i>Cr₃Mn₅ (α') (2 sublattices, sites: 3:5, constituents: Cr:Mn)</i>	
$G_{Cr:Mn}^{\sigma,\alpha'} = 3G_{Cr}^{\sigma,bcc} + 5G_{Mn}^{\sigma,cbcc} + (-72550 + 21.1732T)$	[30]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

3.10.2 Results

The results of the calculations using the IAD and those by Lee [30] together with the experimental data (Table 33) are presented in Figures 62–67. The agreement is reasonably good in both calculations. Concerning Figure 64, note that additional Mn activity data are available from Jacob [298] and Ranganathan and Hajra [299, 300]. These data disagree with each other showing negative [298] and positive [299, 300] deviations from ideality, whereas the measurements by Zaitsev *et al.* [294] lie between these two extremes.

In Figure 66, note the slightly worse agreement obtained using the IAD when introducing a much simpler composition function for parameter T_c^{bcc} , in regard to that by Lee [30] containing composition terms up to $(x_{Cr} - x_{Mn})^8$. Additionally, the com-

position function of parameter β^{bcc} was simplified. This caused only slightly different values for β^{bcc} , as shown in Figure 67.

Fig. 62. A calculated (IAD) Cr-Mn phase diagram, together with the experimental data points (49Car [289], 51Gre [290], 51Zwi [291], 52Pea [292], 57Hel [104], and 64Wac [293]). The calculations are practically identical to those by Lee [30].

Fig. 63. The calculated (IAD) Mn-rich portion of the Cr–Mn phase diagram, together with the experimental data points (49Car [289], 51Zwi [291], 52Pea [292], and 64Wac [293]). The calculations are practically identical to those by Lee [30].

Fig. 64. The calculated (IAD) activity of Mn in solid Cr–Mn alloys at 900 °C and 1000 °C, together with the experimental data points (90Zai [294]). The calculations are identical to those by Lee [30]. The reference state used is pure cub Mn.

Fig. 65. The calculated (IAD) activity of Mn in solid Cr-Mn alloys at $x_{Mn} = 0.588$ and $x_{Mn} = 0.725$, together with the experimental data points (90Zai [294]). The calculations are identical to those by Lee [30]. The reference state used is pure cub Mn.

Fig. 66. The calculated Neel temperature of bcc Cr-Mn alloys, together with the experimental data points (64Ham [295], 64Wac [293], 68Pep [296], and 87Alb [297]). The solid line refers to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted line refers to those by Lee [30].

Fig. 67. The calculated magnetic moment per atom of the bcc phase. The solid line refers to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted line refers to those by Lee [30].

3.11 The Cr–Mo system

The Cr–Mo system has been assessed by Frisk [31]. This assessment is not available in the open literature, but its thermodynamic data were presented in the Fe–Cr–Mo assessment by Andersson and Lange [32]. The Cr–Mo description by Frisk [31] was later modified for the IAD optimizing a new description for the liquid phase. The purpose was to improve the state of the liquid phase stability for the following Fe–Cr–Mo description. The present work reviews the Cr–Mo description according to the IAD and presents its experimental verification.

3.11.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 35 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 36 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 37. Note the metastable fcc phase description by Qiu [301].

Table 35. Phases and their modeling in the Cr–Mo description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Cr,Mo), substitutional, RK
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Cr,Mo), substitutional, RK
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc, metastable)	(Cr,Mo), substitutional, RK

Note: RK = Redlich–Kister excess model.

Table 36. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Cr–Mo according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Phase equilibria of the phase diagram	[102, 302–306]
Enthalpy of mixing for bcc alloys at 1400 °C	[304]
Entropy of mixing for bcc alloys at 1198 °C	[304]
Activity of Cr in bcc alloys at 1198 °C	[304, 307]

Table 37. The thermodynamic description of the Cr–Mo system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid</i> (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Mo)	
$L_{Cr,Mo}^L = (+15810 - 6.714T) + (-9220)(x_{Cr} - x_{Mo})$	IAD
<i>bcc</i> (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Mo)	
$L_{Cr,Mo}^{bcc} = (+28890 - 7.962T) + (+5974 - 2.428T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Mo})$	[32]
$T_e^{bcc} = -311x_{Cr}$	[96]
$\beta^{bcc} = -0.008x_{Cr}$	[96]
<i>fcc</i> ^(m) (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Mo)	
$L_{Cr,Mo}^{fcc} = L_{Cr,Mo}^{bcc}$	[301]
$T_e^{fcc} = -1109x_{Cr}$	[96]
$\beta^{fcc} = -2.46x_{Cr}$	[96]

Notes: (m) = metastable phase; the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

3.11.2 Results

The results of the calculations using the IAD and those by Frisk [31] together with the experimental data (Table 36) are presented in Figures 68–71. The agreement is reasonably good in both calculations. Note the higher stability of the liquid phase using the IAD which agrees better with the experimental data (Figure 68). Note also that according to [308], the bcc miscibility gap extends to 1500 °C, but their results were not accepted by Venkatraman and Neumann [309].

Fig. 68. The calculated high-temperature portion of the Cr-Mo phase diagram, together with the experimental data points (51Put [102], 54Blo [302], 64Sve [303], 69Rud [305], and 79Koc [306]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Frisk [31].

Fig. 69. The calculated (IAD) low-temperature portion of the Cr-Mo phase diagram, together with the experimental data points [304]. The calculations using the IAD are identical to those by Frisk [31].

Fig. 70. The calculated (IAD) enthalpy and entropy for mixing of bcc Cr-Mo alloys, together with the experimental data points (65Kub [304]). The calculations using the IAD are identical to those by Frisk [31]. The reference states used are pure bcc Cr and Mo.

Fig. 71. The calculated (IAD) activity of Cr in bcc Cr-Mo alloys at 1198 °C, together with the experimental data points (61Laf [307] and 65Kub [304]). The calculations according to the IAD are identical to those by Frisk [31]. The reference states used are pure bcc Cr and Mo.

3.12 The Cr–Ni system

The Cr–Ni system has been assessed by Chart [33]. This description, not presented in open literature, was later reviewed by Lee [34]. It was also adapted for the IAD, due to its use in many higher-order SGTE assessments. The present work reviews the Cr–Ni description by Lee [34] and presents its experimental verification.

3.12.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 38 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 39 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 40.

Table 38. Phases and their modeling in the Cr–Ni description by Lee [34].

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Cr,Ni), substitutional, RK
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Cr,Ni), substitutional, RK
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Cr,Ni), substitutional, RK

Note: RK = Redlich–Kister excess model.

Table 39. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Cr–Ni [34].

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Phase equilibria of the phase diagram	[310–320]
Activity of Cr in liquid alloys at 1600 °C	[116, 321]
Activity of Cr in solid alloys at 1300 °C to 1000 °C	[322]
Enthalpy of formation for solid alloys at 1310 °C and 1265 °C	[177, 323]

Table 40. The thermodynamic description of the Cr–Ni system [34].

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Ni)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Ni}^L = (+318 - 7.332T) + (+16941 - 6.37T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Ni})$	[34]
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Ni)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Ni}^{bcc} = (+17170 - 11.82T) + (+34418 - 11.858T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Ni})$	[34]
$T_c^{bcc} = -311x_{Cr} + 575x_{Ni} + x_{Cr}x_{Ni}(2376 + 617(x_{Cr} - x_{Ni}))$	[34]
$\beta^{bcc} = -0.008x_{Cr} + 0.85x_{Ni} + 4x_{Cr}x_{Ni}$	[34]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Ni)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Ni}^{fcc} = (+8030 - 12.88T) + (+33080 - 16.036T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Ni})$	[34]
$T_c^{fcc} = -1109x_{Cr} + 633x_{Ni} - 3605x_{Cr}x_{Ni}$	[34]
$\beta^{fcc} = -2.46x_{Cr} + 0.52x_{Ni} - 1.91x_{Cr}x_{Ni}$	[34]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

3.12.2 Results

The results of the calculations [34] together with the experimental data (Table 39) are presented in Figures 72–75. The agreement is reasonably good.

Fig. 72. A calculated [34] Cr–Ni phase diagram, together with the experimental data points (34Jet [310], 37Jen [311], 51Tay [312], 58Bae [313], 61Bec [314], 62Sve [315], 71Chi [316], 82Kar [317], and 85Kik [318–320]).

Fig. 73. The calculated [34] activity of Cr in liquid Cr–Ni alloys at 1600 °C, together with the experimental data points (68Fru [321] and 69Gil [116]). The reference state used is pure liquid Cr.

Fig. 74. The calculated [34] activity of Cr in solid Cr–Ni alloys at 1000 °C to 1300 °C, together with the experimental data points (73Mat [322]). The reference state used is pure bcc Cr.

Fig. 75. The calculated [34] enthalpy of formation for solid Cr–Ni alloys at 1300 °C, together with the experimental data points (63Den [177] and 87Wat [323]). The reference states used are pure bcc Cr and pure fcc Ni.

3.13 The Cr–Si system

The Cr–Si binary system has been assessed by Riegert *et al.* [35], Kaufman [36], Coughanowr and Ansara [37], Chen *et al.* [38], and Cui and Jung [39]. Coughanowr and Ansara [37] presented a simple description treating all silicides as stoichiometric phases and a more complicated description treating Cr_3Si and CrSi_2 with the Wagner–Schottky model. The former, simple description by Coughanowr and Ansara [37] was later modified for the IAD introducing simpler temperature functions for the Gibbs energies of formation of silicides. The purpose was to simplify the Cr–Si description and the following Fe–Cr–Si description for practical calculations to be used in the solidification modeling of steels. The present work reviews the Cr–Si according to the IAD and presents its experimental verification.

3.13.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 41 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 42 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the

system is presented in Table 43. Note the metastable fcc phase description according to the IAD.

Table 41. Phases and their modeling in the Cr–Si description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Cr,Si), substitutional, RK
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Cr,Si), substitutional, RK
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc, metastable)	(Cr,Si), substitutional, RK
Cr ₃ Si	(Cr) ₃ (Si), stoichiometric
Cr ₅ Si ₃	(Cr) ₅ (Si) ₃ , stoichiometric
CrSi	(Cr)(Si), stoichiometric
CrSi ₂	(Cr)(Si) ₂ , stoichiometric
dia_A4 (\approx dia)	pure Si

Note: RK = Redlich–Kister excess model.

Table 42. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Cr–Si according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Phase equilibria of the phase diagram	[324–330]
Enthalpy of mixing for liquid alloys at 1700 °C	[331]
Chemical potentials of Cr and Si	[35]
Cr chemical potential – temperature diagram	[35, 332–335]
Si chemical potential – temperature diagram	[335, 336]
Enthalpy of formation for solid alloys at 25 °C	[337, 338]
Heat content of Cr ₅ Si ₃ and CrSi ₂	[339]
Heat capacity of CrSi	[340]

Table 43. The thermodynamic description of the Cr–Si system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Si)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Si}^L = (-119811 + 16.602T) + (-49125 + 14.11T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Si})$	[37]
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Si)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Si}^{bcc} = (-102085 + 9.543T) + (-49125 + 14.110T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Si})$	[37]
$T_c^{bcc} = -311x_{Cr}$	[96]
$\beta^{bcc} = -0.008x_{Cr}$	[96]
<i>fcc^(m) (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Si)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Si}^{fcc} = L_{Cr,Si}^{bcc}$	IAD
$T_c^{fcc} = -1109x_{Cr}$	[96]
$\beta^{fcc} = -2.46x_{Cr}$	[96]
<i>Cr₃Si (2 sublattices, sites: 3:1, constituents: Cr:Si)</i>	
$G_{Cr,Si}^{o, Cr_3Si} = 3G_{Cr}^{o, bcc} + G_{Si}^{o, dia} + (-127685 + 5.106T)$	[37]
<i>Cr₅Si₃ (2 sublattices, sites: 5:3, constituents: Cr:Si)</i>	
$G_{Cr,Si}^{o, Cr_5Si_3} = 5G_{Cr}^{o, bcc} + 3G_{Si}^{o, dia} + (-268968 + 138.0708T - 20.4422T \ln T + 0.007841T^2)$	[37] ^(#)
<i>CrSi (2 sublattices, sites: 1:1, constituents: Cr:Si)</i>	
$G_{Cr,Si}^{o, CrSi} = G_{Cr}^{o, bcc} + G_{Si}^{o, dia} + (-63665 + 59.411T - 8.7776T \ln T + 0.0039T^2)$	[37] ^(#)
<i>CrSi₂ (2 sublattices, sites: 1:2, constituents: Cr:Si)</i>	
$G_{Cr,Si}^{o, CrSi_2} = G_{Cr}^{o, bcc} + 2G_{Si}^{o, dia} + (-76539 - 30.0488T + 4.4806T \ln T - 0.003426T^2)$	[37] ^(#)

Notes: (m) = metastable function; (#) = simplified function; the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96]. The reference states of Cr and Si different from SER.

3.13.2 Results

The results of the calculations using IAD and those by Coughanowr and Ansara [37] together with the experimental data (Table 42) are presented in Figures 76–84. The agreement is reasonably good in both calculations. Note the simplified (stoichiometric) description of the Cr₅Si₃ and CrSi₂ phases (Figure 76) and the slightly worse agreement for the heat capacity of CrSi (Figure 84) according to the IAD. The latter is due to the simplified temperature function applied by IAD for the Gibbs energy of formation of CrSi. Figure 85 shows a comparison for the Gibbs energies of formation of the silicides obtained using the IAD and by Coughanowr and Ansara [37]. Slight differences are due to the simpler parameter expressions for the silicides in the IAD but also due to the slightly different set of parameters applied by Coughanowr and Ansara [37] for the silicides when using the Wagner–Schottky model.

Fig. 76. A calculated Cr-Si phase diagram, together with the experimental data points (61Gol [337], 62Dud [325], 63Dub [326], 64Sve [327], 68Cha [328], 68Vor [329], and 71Pya [330]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Coughanowr and Ansara [37] treating Cr_3Si and CrSi_2 with the Wagner-Schottky model.

Fig. 77. The calculated enthalpy of mixing for liquid Cr-Si alloys at 1700 °C, together with the experimental data points (76Esi [331]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Coughanowr and Ansara [37] treating Cr_3Si and CrSi_2 with the Wagner-Schottky model. The reference states used are pure liquid Cr and Si.

Fig. 78. The calculated chemical potential of Cr in Cr–Si alloys at 1627 °C, together with the experimental data points (73Rie [35]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Coughanowr and Ansara [37] treating Cr_3Si and CrSi_2 with the Wagner–Schottky model.

Fig. 79. The calculated chemical potential–temperature diagram for Cr, together with the experimental data points (71Ere [332], 72Ere [333], 73Rie [35], 86Luk [334], and 86Mye [335]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Coughanowr and Ansara [37] treating Cr_3Si and CrSi_2 with the Wagner–Schottky model. The reference state used is pure bcc Cr.

Fig. 80. The calculated chemical potential–temperature diagram for Si, together with the experimental data points (75Cha [336] and 86Mye [335]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Coughanowr and Ansara [37] treating Cr_3Si and CrSi_2 with the Wagner–Schottky model. The reference state used is pure diamond Si.

Fig. 81. The calculated (IAD) enthalpy of formation for solid Cr–Si alloys at 25 °C, together with the experimental data points (61Gol2 [337] and 87Top [338]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Coughanowr and Ansara [37] treating Cr_3Si and CrSi_2 with the Wagner–Schottky model. The reference states used are pure SER of pure Cr and Si.

Fig. 82. The calculated (IAD) heat content of Cr_5Si_3 , together with the experimental data points (66Kal [339]). The calculations are practically identical to those by Coughanowr and Ansara [37].

Fig. 83. The calculated heat content of CrSi_2 , together with the experimental data points (66Kal [339]). The calculations are practically identical to those by Coughanowr and Ansara [37].

Fig. 84. The calculated heat capacity of CrSi, together with the experimental data points (68KAl [340]). The solid line refers to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted line refers to those by Coughanowr and Ansara [37]. The reference states used are pure bcc Cr and pure diamond Si.

Fig. 85. The calculated Gibbs energies of formation for Cr_3Si , Cr_5Si_3 , CrSi, and CrSi_2 . The solid lines refer to the calculations using IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Coughanowr and Ansara [37] treating Cr_3Si and CrSi_2 with the Wagner–Schottky model. The reference states used are pure bcc Cr and pure diamond Si.

3.14 The Cu–Mn system

The Cu–Mn system has been assessed by Vrešt'ál *et al.* [40], Miettinen [41], Wang *et al.* [42], and He *et al.* [43]. The most recent description by He *et al.* [43] was adapted for the IAD. The present work reviews this description and presents its experimental verification.

3.14.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 44 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 45 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 46.

Table 44. Phases and their modeling in the Cu–Mn description oby He *et al.* [43].

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Cu,Mn), substitutional, RK
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Cu,Mn), substitutional, RK
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Cu,Mn), substitutional, RK
cbcc_A12 (\approx cbcc)	(Cu,Mn), substitutional, RK
cub_A13 (\approx cub)	(Cu,Mn), substitutional, RK

Note: RK = Redlich–Kister excess model.

Table 45. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Cu–Mn [43].

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Phase equilibria of the phase diagram	[104, 341–344]
Enthalpy of mixing for liquid alloys at 1097 °C to 1300 °C	[40, 345–347]
Activity of Mn in liquid alloys at 1097 °C	[40]
Gibbs energy of mixing for liquid alloys at 780 °C and 802 °C	[348]
Activity of Mn in solid alloys at 820 °C, 797 °C, and 707 °C	[349, 350]

Table 46. The thermodynamic description of the Cu–Mn system [43].

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Mn)</i>	
$L_{\text{Cu,Mn}}^{\text{L}} = (+1119 - 5.623T) + (-10915)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Mn}})$	[43]
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Mn)</i>	
$L_{\text{Cu,Mn}}^{\text{bcc}} = (+18366 - 16.221T) + (-12668)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Mn}})$	[43]
$T_{\text{c}}^{\text{bcc}} = -580x_{\text{Mn}}$	[96]
$\beta^{\text{bcc}} = -0.27x_{\text{Mn}}$	[96]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Mn)</i>	
$L_{\text{Cu,Mn}}^{\text{fcc}} = (+20236 - 13.244T) + (-12155 + 2.94T)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Mn}}) + (+1038)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Mn}})^2$	[43]
$T_{\text{c}}^{\text{fcc}} = -1620x_{\text{Mn}}$	[96]
$\beta^{\text{fcc}} = -1.86x_{\text{Mn}}$	[96]
<i>cbcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Mn)</i>	
$G_{\text{Cu}}^{\text{o,cbcc}} = G_{\text{Cu}}^{\text{o,fcc}} + (+3556)$	[43]
$L_{\text{Cu,Mn}}^{\text{cbcc}} = (+36627 - 12.209T)$	[43]
<i>cub (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Mn)</i>	
$G_{\text{Cu}}^{\text{o,cub}} = G_{\text{Cu}}^{\text{o,fcc}} + (+2092)$	[43]
$L_{\text{Cu,Mn}}^{\text{cub}} = (+42493 - 14.164T)$	[43]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

3.14.2 Results

The results of the calculations by [42, 43] together with the experimental data (Table 45) are presented in Figures 86–90 and Table 47. The agreement is reasonably good in both calculations but slightly better in the calculations by [43]. In Table 47, note the reaction $\text{cub} + \text{fcc} = \text{cbcc}$ by [43] instead of $\text{cub} = \text{fcc} + \text{cbcc}$ by other researchers. In Figure 87, note the poor agreement between the mixing enthalpy measurements by [345] and [40, 346, 347]. Due to this inconsistency, the liquid state activity data provided by [345] was not considered in [43]. These data were modeled in a reasonable way by [42] but at the same time, the agreement between the calculated and experimental mixing enthalpies of the liquid became very poor (Figure 87).

Table 47. The calculated and experimental invariant points of the Cu–Mn system.

$\phi_1 - \phi_2 - \phi_3$	T (°C)	$x_{Mn}^{\phi_1}$	$x_{Mn}^{\phi_2}$	$x_{Mn}^{\phi_3}$	Type	Reference
bcc = L + fcc	1100	0.875	0.762	0.885	Exp	[351]
	1098	0.875	0.760	0.882	Exp	[104]
	1110	0.880	0.780	0.890	Exp	[342]
	1100	0.849	0.740	0.862	Cal	[42]
	1095	0.876	0.750	0.888	Cal	[43]
L = fcc	873	0.380	0.380	–	Exp	[351]
	868	0.380	0.380	–	Exp	[342]
	874	0.390	0.390	–	Cal	[42]
	871	0.381	0.381	–	Cal	[43]
cub = fcc + cbcc	725	0.996	0.780	0.997	Exp	[351]
	725	–	–	–	Exp	[43]
	705	1	0.670	1	Exp	[343]
	704	0.992	0.800	0.993	Cal	[42]
cub + fcc = cbcc	720	0.989	0.750	0.985	Cal	[43]

Fig. 86. A calculated Cu–Mn phase diagram, together with the experimental data points (30Smi [341], 39Gru [342], 45Dea [343], 57Hel [104], 71Sch [344]). The solid lines refer to the calculations by He *et al.* [43] and the dotted lines refer to those by Wang *et al.* [42].

Fig. 87. The calculated enthalpy of mixing for liquid Cu–Mn alloys at 1300 °C, together with the experimental data points (68Spe [345], 79Sat [346], 96Vre [40], and 97Tur [347]). The solid line refers to the calculations by He *et al.* [43] and the dotted line refers to those by Wang *et al.* [42]. The reference states used are pure liquid Cu and Mn.

Fig. 88. The calculated activity of Mn in liquid Cu–Mn alloys at 1097 °C, together with the experimental data points (96Vre [40]). The solid line refers to the calculations by He *et al.* [43] and the dotted line refers to those by Wang *et al.* [42]. The reference state used is pure fcc Mn.

Fig. 89. The calculated Gibbs energy of mixing for liquid Cu–Mn alloys at 780 °C and 802 °C, together with the experimental data points (69Kre [348]). The solid line refers to the calculations by He *et al.* [43] and the dotted line refers to those by Wang *et al.* [42]. The reference states used are pure fcc Cu and pure cub Mn.

Fig. 90. The calculated activity of Mn in solid Cu–Mn alloys at 820 °C, 797 °C, and 707 °C, together with the experimental data points (63Pet [349] and 79Haj [350]). The solid line refers to the calculations by He *et al.* [43] and the dotted line refers to those by Wang *et al.* [42]. The reference state used is pure cub Mn.

3.15 The Cu–Mo system

The Cu–Mo system has been assessed tentatively by Wang *et al.* [44]. This description was adapted for the IAD. The present work reviews the Cu–Mo description by Wang *et al.* [44] and presents its experimental verification.

3.15.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 48 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 49 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 50.

Table 48. Phases and their modeling in the Cu–Mo description by Wang *et al.* [44].

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Cu,Mo), substitutional, RK
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Cu,Mo), substitutional, RK
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Cu,Mo), substitutional, RK

Note: RK = Redlich–Kister excess model.

Table 49. Experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Cu–Mo [44].

Experimental data	Reference
Phase equilibria of the phase diagram	[352] (suggested)

Table 50. The thermodynamic description of the Cu–Mo system [44].

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Mo)</i> $L_{\text{Cu,Mo}}^{\text{l}} = (+57285 + 2T) + (-1200)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Mo}})$	[44]
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Mo)</i> $L_{\text{Cu,Mo}}^{\text{bcc}} = (+82313)$	[44]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Mo)</i> $L_{\text{Cu,Mo}}^{\text{fcc}} = (+83144)$	[44]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

3.15.2 Results

The results of the calculations [44] together with the experimental data (Table 49) are presented in Figure 91. The agreement is reasonably good.

Fig. 91. The calculated [44] Cu–Mo phase diagram, together with the suggested experimental data points (94Sub [352]).

3.16 The Cu–Ni system

The Cu–Ni system has been assessed by Jansson [45], an Mey [46], and Chakrabarti *et al.* [47]. The earliest description by Jansson [45] was adapted for the IAD due to its use in many higher-order SGTE assessments. The present work reviews this description and presents its experimental verification.

3.16.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 51 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 52 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 53.

Table 51. Phases and their modeling in the Cu–Ni description by Jansson [45].

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Cu,Ni), substitutional, RK
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc, metastable)	(Cu,Ni), substitutional, RK
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Cu,Ni), substitutional, RK
hcp_A3 (\approx hcp, metastable)	(Cu,Ni), substitutional, RK

Note: RK = Redlich–Kister excess model.

Table 52. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Cu–Ni [45].

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Phase equilibria of the phase diagram	[344, 353–355]
Enthalpy of mixing for liquid alloys at 1200–1480 °C	[355–357]
Activity of Cu in liquid alloys at 1550 °C	[358]
Activity of Ni in liquid alloys at 1400 °C	[359]
Enthalpy of mixing for fcc alloys at 0–1000 °C	[360–363]
Activity of Ni in fcc alloys at 700 °C and 1000 °C	[364–366]

Table 53. The thermodynamic description of the Cu–Ni system [45].

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Ni)</i>	
$L_{Cu,Ni}^L = (11760 + 1.084T) + (-1672)(x_{Cu} - x_{Ni})$	[45]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Ni)</i>	
$L_{Cu,Ni}^{fcc} = (8366 + 2.802T) + (-4360 + 1.812T)(x_{Cu} - x_{Ni})$	[45]
$T_c^{fcc} = 633x_{Ni} + x_{Cu}x_{Ni}(-935.5 - 549.9(x_{Cu} - x_{Ni}))$	[96]
$\beta^{fcc} = 0.52x_{Ni} + x_{Cu}x_{Ni}(-0.732 - 0.317(x_{Cu} - x_{Ni}))$	[96]
<i>bcc^(m) (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Ni)</i>	
$L_{Cu,Ni}^{bcc} = (+8366 + 2.802T)$	[45]
$T_c^{bcc} = 575x_{Ni}$	[96]
$\beta^{bcc} = 0.85x_{Ni}$	[96]
<i>hcp^(m) (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Ni)</i>	
$L_{Cu,Ni}^{hcp} = (+8366 + 2.802T)$	[45]

Notes: (m) = metastable phase; the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

3.16.2 Results

The results of the calculations [45, 46] together with the experimental data (Table 52) are presented in Figures 92–97. The agreement is reasonably good in both calculations.

Fig. 92. The calculated Cu–Ni phase diagram, together with the experimental data points (71Bas [353], 71Fee [354], 71Pre [355], 71Sch [344]). The solid lines refer to the calculations by Jansson [45] and the dotted lines refer to those by an Mey [46].

Fig. 93. The calculated enthalpy of mixing for liquid Cu–Ni alloys at 1477 °C, together with the experimental data points (64Ben [356], 71Pre [355], and 83Tom [357]). The solid line refers to the calculations by Jansson [45] and the dotted line refers to those by an Mey [46]. The reference states used are pure liquid Cu and Ni.

Fig. 94. The calculated activity of Cu in liquid Cu–Ni alloys at 1550 °C, together with the experimental data points (64Sch [358]). The solid line refers to the calculations by Jansson [45] and the dotted line refers to those by an Mey [46]. The reference state used is pure liquid Cu.

Fig. 95. The calculated activity of Ni in liquid Cu–Ni alloys at 1400 °C, together with the experimental data points (73Kul [359]). The solid line refers to the calculations by Jansson [45] and the dotted line refers to those by an Mey [46]. The reference state used is pure liquid Ni.

Fig. 96. The calculated enthalpy of mixing for fcc Cu–Ni alloys at 1000 °C, together with experimental data points (59Lea [360], 60Ori [361], 69Elf [362], and 73Kat [363]). The solid line refers to the calculations by Jansson [45] and the dotted line refers to those by an Mey [46]. The reference states used are pure fcc Cu and Ni.

Fig. 97. The calculated activity of Ni in fcc Cu–Ni alloys at 700 °C and 1000 °C, together with the experimental data points (62Rap [364], 78Kon [365], and 85Spe [366]). The solid lines refer to the calculations by Jansson [45] and the dotted lines refer to those by an Mey [46]. The reference state used is pure fcc Ni.

3.17 The Cu–Si system

The Cu–Si system has been assessed by Kaufman [36], Lüdecke [48], Bühler [49], and Yan and Chang [50]. The latest description by Yan and Chang [50], reviewed by Okamoto [367], was adapted for the IAD. The present work reviews that description and presents its experimental verification.

3.17.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 54 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 55 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 56.

Table 54. Phases and their modeling in the Cu–Si description by Yan and Chang [50].

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Cu,Si), substitutional, RK
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Cu,Si), substitutional, RK
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Cu,Si), substitutional, RK
hcp_A3 (\approx hcp)	(Cu,Si), substitutional, RK
Cu ₅₆ Si ₁₁ (\approx γ)	(Cu) ₅₆ (Si) ₁₁ , stoichiometric
Cu ₃₃ Si ₇ (\approx δ)	(Cu) ₃₃ (Si) ₇ , stoichiometric
Cu ₁₅ Si ₄ (\approx ϵ)	(Cu) ₁₅ (Si) ₄ , stoichiometric
Cu ₁₉ Si ₆ (\approx η)	(Cu) ₁₉ (Si) ₆ , stoichiometric
A4 (\approx dia)	pure Si

Note: RK = Redlich–Kister excess model.

Table 55. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Cu–Si [50].

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Phase equilibria of the phase diagram	[368–373]
Enthalpy of mixing for liquid alloys at 1097–1627 °C	[374–377]
Partial enthalpies of mixing for liquid alloys at 1627 °C	[377]
Chemical potential of Si in liquid alloys at 1400–1560 °C	[376, 378–381]

Table 56. The thermodynamic description of the Cu–Si system [50].

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Si)</i> $L_{\text{Cu,Si}}^{\text{L}} = (-38764 + 12T) + (-52431 + 27.457T)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Si}}) + (-29427 + 14.775T)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Si}})^2$	[50]
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Si)</i> $L_{\text{Cu,Si}}^{\text{bcc}} = (-26447 + 10.216T) + (-47275 - 8.517T)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Si}})$	[50]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Si)</i> $L_{\text{Cu,Si}}^{\text{fcc}} = (-42204 + 13.891T) + (-1102 - 18.178T)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Si}})$	[50]
<i>hcp (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Si)</i> $L_{\text{Cu,Si}}^{\text{hcp}} = (-26799 - 0.732T) + (-28065 - 0.029T)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Si}})$	[50]
<i>Cu₅₆Si₁₁ (γ) (2 sublattices, sites: 56:11, constituents: Cu:Si)</i> $G_{\text{Cu,Si}}^{\circ,\gamma} = 56G_{\text{Cu}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 11G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ,\text{dia}} + (+70116 - 393.605T)$	[50]
<i>Cu₃₃Si₇ (δ) (2 sublattices, sites: 33:7, constituents: Cu:Si)</i> $G_{\text{Cu,Si}}^{\circ,\delta} = 33G_{\text{Cu}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 7G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ,\text{dia}} + (+78896 - 278.656T)$	[50]
<i>Cu₁₅Si₄ (ε) (2 sublattices, sites: 15:4, constituents: Cu:Si)</i> $G_{\text{Cu,Si}}^{\circ,\epsilon} = 15G_{\text{Cu}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 4G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ,\text{dia}} + (+23579 - 127.663T)$	[50]
<i>Cu₁₉Si₆ (η) (2 sublattices, sites: 19:6, constituents: Cu:Si)</i> $G_{\text{Cu,Si}}^{\circ,\eta} = 19G_{\text{Cu}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 6G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ,\text{dia}} + (+34193 - 179.94T)$	[50]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

3.17.2 Results

The results of the calculations [50] together with the experimental data (Table 55) are presented in Figures 98–102 and Table 57. The agreement is reasonably good. In Table 57 note the slightly better agreement obtained by [50] for the invariant phase equilibria than by [49].

Table 57. The experimental and calculated invariant phase equilibria of the Cu–Si system.

$\phi_1 - \phi_2 - \phi_3$	T (°C)	$x_{Si}^{\phi_1}$	$x_{Si}^{\phi_2}$	$x_{Si}^{\phi_3}$	Type	Reference
hcp = fcc + γ	552	0.111	0.0995	0.1715	Exp	[373]
	552	0.115	0.097	0.164	Cal	[50]
	552	0.105	0.093	0.164	Cal	[49]
$\delta = \varepsilon + \gamma$	710	0.182	0.212	0.176	Exp	[370]
	711	0.175	0.210	0.164	Cal	[50]
	683	0.175	0.200	0.164	Cal	[49]
$\delta + \text{hcp} = \gamma$	729	0.177	0.145	0.171	Exp	[373]
	729	0.175	0.139	0.164	Cal	[50]
	735	0.175	0.121	0.164	Cal	[49]
bcc = δ hcp	785	0.160	0.176	0.143	Exp	[373]
	787	0.157	0.175	0.142	Cal	[50]
	786	0.154	0.175	0.125	Cal	[49]
$\eta + \delta = \varepsilon$	800	0.235	0.194	0.212	Exp	[371]
	800	0.240	0.175	0.211	Cal	[50]
	805	0.240	0.175	0.200	Cal	[49]
L = dia + η	802	0.301	1	0.249	Exp	[370]
	802	0.307	1	0.240	Cal	[50]
	801	0.306	1	0.240	Cal	[49]
L = $\eta + \delta$	820	0.199	0.234	0.196	Exp	[370]
	820	0.192	0.240	0.175	Cal	[50]
	816	0.191	0.240	0.175	Cal	[49]
L + bcc = δ	824	0.181	0.172	0.176	Exp	[373]
	824	0.187	0.167	0.175	Cal	[50]
	820	0.186	0.169	0.175	Cal	[49]
bcc + fcc = hcp	842	0.144	0.1125	0.1245	Exp	[373]
	842	0.147	0.112	0.130	Cal	[50]
	846	0.147	0.113	0.118	Cal	[49]
L + fcc = bcc	852	0.160	0.1115	0.142	Exp	[373]
	853	0.157	0.111	0.146	Cal	[50]
	852	0.154	0.112	0.146	Cal	[49]
L = η	859	0.24	0.24		Cal	[50]
	859	0.24	0.24		Cal	[49]

Fig. 98. A calculated [50] Cu-Si phase diagram, together with the experimental data points (07Rud [368], 28Smi [369], 29Smi [370], 31lok [371], 40And [372], and 40Smi [373]).

Fig. 99. The calculated [50] Cu-rich portion of the Cu-Si phase diagram, together with the experimental data points (07Rud [368], 28Smi [369], 29Smi [370], 31lok [371], 40And [372], and 40Smi [373]).

Fig. 100. The calculated [50] enthalpy of mixing for liquid Cu–Si alloys at 1500 °C, together with the experimental data points (79Cas [374], 81Arp [375], 82Bat [376], and 97Wit [377]). The reference states used are pure liquid Cu and Si.

Fig. 101. The calculated [50] partial enthalpies of mixing in liquid Cu–Si alloys at 1627 °C, together with the experimental data points [377]. The reference states used are pure liquid Cu and Si.

Fig. 102. The calculated [50] chemical potential of Si in liquid Cu–Si alloys at 1470 °C, together with the experimental data points (56San [378], 62Nik [379], 64Bow [380], 82Bat [376], and 86Ber [381]). The reference state used is pure liquid Si.

3.18 The Mn–Mo system

The Mn–Mo system has been assessed by Lee [51] but not shown in the open literature. This assessment was later modified for the IAD using the Gibbs energy and enthalpy data b Lee [51] as tabulated by Franke and Neuschütz [382] and by treating the Mu and Sigma phases as simple stoichiometric phases, Mn_5Mo_4 and $Mn_{16}Mo_9$. Note that due to the low stabilities of Mu and Sigma in the Mn–Mo system, their contribution to the iron-rich modifications of the phases would remain small. The purpose was to simplify the binary description and the following Fe–Mn–Mo description for practical calculations for solidification modeling of steels. The present work reviews the Mn–Mo description for the IAD and presents its experimental verification.

3.18.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 58 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 59 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 60.

Table 58. Phases and their modeling in the Mn–Mo description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Mn,Mo), substitutional, RK
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Mn,Mo), substitutional, RK
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Mn,Mo), substitutional, RK
cbcc_A12 (\approx cbcc)	(Mn,Mo), substitutional, RK
cub_A13 (\approx cub)	(Mn,Mo), substitutional, RK
Mn ₅ Mo ₄	(Mn) ₅ (Mo) ₄ , stoichiometric
Mn ₁₆ Mo ₉	(Mn) ₁₆ (Mo) ₉ , stoichiometric

Note: RK = Redlich–Kister excess model.

Table 59. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Mn–Mo according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Phase equilibria of the phase diagram	[383, 384] (assessed)
Gibbs energy and enthalpy data	[382] (assessed)

Table 60. The thermodynamic description of the Mn–Mo system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Mn,Mo)</i> $L_{Mn,Mo}^L = (-22500 + 13.83T) + (+23600 - 10.82T)(x_{Mn} - x_{Mo})$	IAD
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Mn,Mo)</i> $L_{Mn,Mo}^{bcc} = (+49900 - 14.30T) + (-7150)(x_{Mn} - x_{Mo})$ $T_c^{bcc} = -580x_{Mn}$ $\beta^{bcc} = -0.27x_{Mn}$	IAD [96] [96]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Mn,Mo)</i> $L_{Mn,Mo}^{fcc} = (+8500)$ $T_c^{fcc} = -1620x_{Mn}$ $\beta^{fcc} = -1.86x_{Mn}$	IAD [96] [96]
<i>cbcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Mn,Mo)</i> $G_{Mo}^{o,cbcc} = G_{Mo}^{o,bcc} + (+11550)$ $L_{Mn,Mo}^{cbcc} = (+4700)$	IAD (*) IAD
<i>cub (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Mn,Mo)</i> $G_{Mo}^{o,cub} = G_{Mo}^{o,bcc} + (+11550)$ $L_{Mn,Mo}^{cub} = (+11500)$	IAD (**) IAD
<i>Mn₅Mo₄ (2 sublattices, sites: 5:4, constituents: Mn:Mo)</i> $G_{Mn:Mo}^{o,Mn_5Mo_4} = 5G_{Mn}^{o,cbcc} + 4G_{Mo}^{o,bcc} + (+18000 - 39.6T)$	IAD
<i>Mn₁₆Mo₉ (2 sublattices, sites: 16:9, constituents: Mn:Mo)</i> $G_{Mn:Mo}^{o,Mn_{16}Mo_9} = 16G_{Mn}^{o,cbcc} + 9G_{Mo}^{o,bcc} + (+118950 - 152.5T)$	IAD

Notes: (*) $G_{Mo}^{o,cbcc}$ assumed to be identical to $G_{Mo}^{o,hcp}$ of [96]; (**) $G_{Mo}^{o,cub}$ assumed to be identical to $G_{Mo}^{o,hcp}$ of [96]; the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

3.18.2 Results

The results of the calculations using the IAD, together with the experimental data (Table 59), are presented in Figures 103 and 104. The agreement is reasonable and very close to that by Lee [51], excluding the σ phase owing some compositional variation by [51] with respect to Mn_5Mo_4 according to the IAD.

Fig. 103. A calculated (IAD) Mn–Mo phase diagram, together with the experimental (59Hel [383]) and assessed (04Gup [384]) data points.

Fig. 104. The Mn-rich portion of the calculated (IAD) Mn–Mo phase diagram, together with the experimental (59HeI [383]) and assessed (04Gup [384]) data points.

3.19 The Mn–Ni system

The Mn–Ni system has been assessed by Miettinen [52], and Guo and Du [53]. The more complex assessment by Guo and Du [53] describes the complex phase equilibria of the system [385] quite well. The simpler description by Miettinen [52], however, was adapted for the IAD, as it is accurate enough for practical calculations for solidification modeling. The present work reviews the Mn–Ni description by Miettinen [52] and presents its experimental verification.

3.19.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 61 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 62 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 63. Note that three temperature forms of MnNi and two temperature forms of MnNi₂ have been reported [386]. However, due to the lack of experimental data, only one MnNi and MnNi₂ phase were considered. Besides, at low temperatures, Mn₃Ni becomes stable instead of Mn₂Ni but due to the lack of thermodynamic data, Mn₃Ni was not considered.

Table 61. Phases and their modeling in the Mn–Ni description by Miettinen [52].

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Mn,Ni), substitutional, RK
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Mn,Ni), substitutional, RK
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Mn,Ni), substitutional, RK
cbcc_A12 (\approx cbcc)	(Mn,Ni), substitutional, RK
cub_A13 (\approx cub)	(Mn,Ni), substitutional, RK
MnNi ($\approx \lambda_1$)	(Mn)(Ni), stoichiometric
Mn ₂ Ni ($\approx \lambda_2$)	(Mn) ₂ (Ni), stoichiometric
MnNi ₂ ($\approx \lambda_3$)	(Mn)(Ni) ₂ , stoichiometric

Note: RK = Redlich–Kister excess model.

Table 62. The experimental information applied in the assessment verification for Mn–Ni [52].

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Phase equilibria of the phase diagram	[104, 387, 388]
Enthalpy of mixing in liquid alloys at 1300 °C	[389]
Activity coefficient of Mn in liquid alloys at 1470 °C	[389–393]
Activity of Mn in fcc alloys at 959 °C	[394]
Chemical potential of Mn and Ni in solid alloys at 927 °C and 777 °C	[395] (assessed)

Table 63. The thermodynamic description of the Mn–Ni system [52].

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Mn,Ni)</i> $L_{\text{Mn,Ni}}^{\text{L}} = (-85853 + 22.715T) + (-1620 + 4.902T)(x_{\text{Mn}} - x_{\text{Ni}})$	[52]
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Mn,Ni)</i> $L_{\text{Mn,Ni}}^{\text{bcc}} = (-51785 + 3.5T) + (6670)(x_{\text{Mn}} - x_{\text{Ni}})$ $T_{\text{c}}^{\text{bcc}} = -580x_{\text{Mn}} + 575x_{\text{Ni}}$ $\beta^{\text{bcc}} = -0.27x_{\text{Mn}} + 0.85x_{\text{Ni}}$	[52] [96] [96]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Mn,Ni)</i> $L_{\text{Mn,Ni}}^{\text{fcc}} = (-58173 + 10.5T) + (6300)(x_{\text{Mn}} - x_{\text{Ni}})$ $T_{\text{c}}^{\text{fcc}} = -1620x_{\text{Mn}} + 633x_{\text{Ni}}$ $\beta^{\text{fcc}} = -1.86x_{\text{Mn}} + 0.52x_{\text{Ni}}$	[52] [96] [96]
<i>cbcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Mn,Ni)</i> $L_{\text{Mn,Ni}}^{\text{cbcc}} = (-53000 + 30T) + (-58000 + 30T)(x_{\text{Mn}} - x_{\text{Ni}})$	[52]
<i>cub (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Mn,Ni)</i> $L_{\text{Mn,Ni}}^{\text{cub}} = (-63000 + 29T) + (-15000)(x_{\text{Mn}} - x_{\text{Ni}})$	[52]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

Table 63 (continued)

Equation	Reference
$MnNi (\lambda_1)$ (2 sublattices, sites: 1:1, constituents: Mn:Ni)	
$G_{Mn:Ni}^{\circ, \lambda_1} = G_{Mn}^{\circ, cbcc} + G_{Ni}^{\circ, fcc} + (-36300)$	[52]
$Mn_2Ni (\lambda_2)$ (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents: Mn:Ni)	
$G_{Mn:Ni}^{\circ, \lambda_2} = 2G_{Mn}^{\circ, cbcc} + G_{Ni}^{\circ, fcc} + (-43900)$	[52]
$MnNi_2 (\lambda_3)$ (2 sublattices, sites: 1:2, constituents: Mn:Ni)	
$G_{Mn:Ni}^{\circ, \lambda_3} = G_{Mn}^{\circ, cbcc} + 2G_{Ni}^{\circ, fcc} + (-48100)$	[52]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

3.19.2 Results

The results of the calculations [52] together with the experimental data (Table 62) are presented in Figures 105–109. The agreement is reasonably good.

Fig. 105. A calculated [52] phase diagram of the Mn–Ni system, together with the experimental data points (51Col [387], 57Hel [104], and 69Tsi [388]).

Fig. 106. The calculated [52] Gibbs energy of mixing in liquid Mn–Ni alloys at 1300 °C, together with the experimental data points (81Bat [389]). The reference states used are pure liquid Mn and Ni.

Fig. 107. The calculated [52] activity coefficient of Mn in liquid Mn–Ni alloys at 1470 °C, together with the experimental data points (75Pra [390], 81Bat [389], 82Jac [391], 82Muc [392], and 85Ale [393]). The reference state of Mn is pure liquid Mn.

Fig. 108. The calculated [52] activity of Mn in fcc Mn–Ni alloys at 959 °C, together with the experimental data points (64Smi [394]). The reference state of Mn is pure fcc Mn.

Fig. 109. The calculated [52] chemical potential of Mn and Ni in solid Mn–Ni alloys at 927 °C, together with data points converted from the experimental partial Gibbs excess energy data [395]. The reference states used are pure bcc Mn and pure fcc Ni.

Fig. 110. The calculated [52] chemical potential of Mn and Ni in solid Mn–Ni alloys at 777 °C, together with data points converted from the experimental partial Gibbs excess energy data [395]. The reference states used are pure cbcc Mn.

3.20 The Mo–Ni system

The Mo–Ni system has been assessed by Brewer *et al.* [54], Frisk [55], Cui *et al.* [56], Morishita *et al.* [57], Zhou *et al.* [58], and Yaqoob *et al.* [59]. The assessment by Frisk [55] was modified for the IAD optimizing new descriptions for MoNi, MoNi₃, and MoNi₄ phases. The purpose was to simplify the Mo–Ni description and the following Fe–Mo–Ni description for practical calculations for modeling the solidification of steels. The present work reviews the Mo–Ni description according to the IAD and presents its experimental verification.

3.20.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 64 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 65 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 66.

Table 64. Phases and their modeling in the Mo–Ni description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Mo,Ni), substitutional, RK
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Mo,Ni), substitutional, RK
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Mo,Ni), substitutional, RK
MoNi (\approx δ)	(Mo)(Ni), stoichiometric
MoNi ₃	(Mo)(Ni) ₃ , stoichiometric
MoNi ₄	(Mo)(Ni) ₄ , stoichiometric

Note: RK = Redlich–Kister excess model.

Table 65. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Mo–Ni according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Phase equilibria of the phase diagram	[59, 302, 396–400]
Activity of Mo in solid alloys at 1100 °C to 950 °C	[363, 401–404]
Enthalpy of formation for phases	[59, 405–408]
Heat capacity of MoNi	[405]

Table 66. The thermodynamic description of the Mo–Ni system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Mo,Ni)</i> $L_{\text{Mo,Ni}}^{\text{L}} = (-46540 + 19.53T) + (+2915)(x_{\text{Mo}} - x_{\text{Ni}})$	[55]
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Mo,Ni)</i> $L_{\text{Mo,Ni}}^{\text{bcc}} = (+46422)$ $T_{\text{c}}^{\text{bcc}} = 575x_{\text{Ni}}$ $\beta^{\text{bcc}} = 0.85x_{\text{Ni}}$	[55] [55] [55]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Mo,Ni)</i> $L_{\text{Mo,Ni}}^{\text{fcc}} = (+4804 - 5.96T) + (+10880)(x_{\text{Mo}} - x_{\text{Ni}})$ $T_{\text{c}}^{\text{fcc}} = 633x_{\text{Ni}}$ $\beta^{\text{fcc}} = 0.52x_{\text{Ni}}$	[55] [55] [55]
<i>MoNi (δ) (2 sublattices, sites: 1:1, constituents: Mo:Ni)</i> $G_{\text{Mo:Ni}}^{\circ, \delta} = G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + (-6000 + 32.5T - 4.6T \ln T)$	IAD
<i>MoNi₃ (2 sublattices, sites: 3:1, constituents: Mo:Ni)</i> $G_{\text{Mo:Ni}_3}^{\circ, \text{MoNi}_3} = 3G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + (-4300 - 7T)$	IAD
<i>MoNi₄ (2 sublattices, sites: 4:1, constituents: Mo:Ni)</i> $G_{\text{Mo:Ni}_4}^{\circ, \text{MoNi}_4} = 4G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + (-4600 - 9T)$	IAD

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

3.20.2 Results

The results of the calculations by IAD and Frisk [55] together with the experimental data (Table 65) are presented in Figures 111–116. The agreement is reasonably good in both calculations. In Figure 111, note the simplified (stoichiometric) description of the MoNi phase according to the IAD. Note also the negative entropy terms of functions $G_{\text{Mo:Ni}}^{\circ, \text{MoNi}_3}$ and $G_{\text{Mo:Ni}}^{\circ, \text{MoNi}_4}$, in Table 66, which are comparable to those by Frisk [55]. These functions give much less negative values for the enthalpy of formation than obtained by the DFT calculations [58].

Fig. 111. A calculated phase diagram of the Mo–Ni system, together with the experimental data points (42EII [397], 64Cas [398], and 18Yaq [59]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Frisk [55].

Fig. 112. An enlargement of the Mo–Ni phase diagram between 1600 °C and 700 °C, together with the experimental data points (38Gru [396], 54Blo [302], 64Cas [398], 73Hej [399], 84Kan [400], and 18Yaq [59]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Frisk [55].

Fig. 113. The calculated activity of Mo in solid Mo–Ni alloys at 1000 °C, together with the experimental data points (73Kat [363], 75Mes [401], 83Tsa [402], 85Pej [403], and 89Koy [404]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Frisk [55]. The reference state used is pure bcc Mo.

Fig. 114. The calculated (IAD) enthalpy of formation for liquid, bcc and fcc phases at 25 °C, together with the experimental (93Chi [407] and 99Sud [408]) and calculated (DFT) [59] data points. The calculations are identical to those by Frisk [55]. The reference states used are pure bcc Mo and pure fcc Ni.

Fig. 115. The calculated enthalpy of formation for MoNi, together with the experimental data points (75Spe [405] and 83Kub [406]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Frisk [55]. The reference states used are pure bcc Mo and pure fcc Ni.

Fig. 116. The calculated heat capacity of MoNi phase, together with the experimental data points (75Spe [405]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Frisk [55]. The reference states used are pure bcc Mo and pure fcc Ni.

3.21 The Mo–Si system

The Mo–Si system has been assessed by Vahlas *et al.* [60] and Liu *et al.* [61]. The latter description was later modified for the IAD assuming the Mo_5Si_3 phase to be stoichiometric. The purpose was to allow a simple extension of that phase to $(\text{Mo,Fe})_5\text{Si}_3$ in the following Fe–Mo–Si assessment. The present work reviews the Mo–Si description according to the IAD and presents its experimental verification.

3.21.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 67 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 68 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 69. Note the metastable fcc phase description according to the IAD.

Table 67. Phases and their modeling in the Mo–Si description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Mo,Si), substitutional, RK
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Mo,Si), substitutional, RK
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc, metastable)	(Mo,Si), substitutional, RK
Mo ₃ Si	(Mo) ₃ (Si), stoichiometric
Mo ₅ Si ₃	(Mo) ₅ (Si) ₃ , stoichiometric
MoSi ₂	(Mo)(Si) ₂ , stoichiometric
dia_A4 (\approx dia)	pure Si

Note: RK = Redlich–Kister excess model.

Table 68. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Mo–Si according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Phase equilibria of the phase diagram	[152, 385, 409]
Enthalpy of mixing in liquid alloys at 2814 °C	[410]
Enthalpy of formation for solid alloys at 25 °C	[411, 412]
Entropy of formation for solid alloys at 25 °C	[412]

Table 69. The thermodynamic description of the Mo–Si system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Mo,Si)</i> $L_{\text{Mo,Si}}^L = (-146000 + 16.5T) + (+7100 - 3T)(x_{\text{Mo}} - x_{\text{Si}}) + (+8000 + 12T)(x_{\text{Mo}} - x_{\text{Si}})^2$	[61]
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Mo,Si)</i> $L_{\text{Mo,Si}}^{\text{bcc}} = (-60000 + 5T)$	[61]
<i>fcc^(m) (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Mo,Si)</i> $L_{\text{Mo,Si}}^{\text{fcc}} = L_{\text{Mo,Si}}^{\text{bcc}}$	IAD
<i>Mo₃Si (2 sublattices, sites: 3:1, constituents: Mo:Si)</i> $G_{\text{Mo:Si}}^{\circ, \text{Mo}_3\text{Si}} = 3G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-111600 - 1.12T)$	[61]
<i>Mo₅Si₃ (2 sublattices, sites: 5:3, constituents: Mo:Si)</i> $G_{\text{Mo:Si}}^{\circ, \text{Mo}_5\text{Si}_3} = 5G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + 3G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-311840 - 10.792T)$	IAD
<i>MoSi₂ (2 sublattices, sites: 1:2, constituents: Mo:Si)</i> $G_{\text{Mo:Si}}^{\circ, \text{MoSi}_2} = G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + 2G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-135468 + 0.669T)$	[61]

Notes: (m) = metastable phase; the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

3.21.2 Results

The results of the calculations using the IAD and those by Liu *et al.* [61] together with the experimental data (Table 68) are presented in Figures 117–120. The agreement is reasonably good in both calculations. In Figure 117, note the simplified (stoichiometric) description of the Mo_5Si_3 phase according to the IAD.

Fig. 117. The calculated Mo–Si phase diagram, together with the experimental data points (51Ham [152], 71Sve [409], and 91Gok [385]). The solid lines refer to the calculations using the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Liu *et al.* [61].

Fig. 118. The calculated (IAD) enthalpy of mixing for liquid Mo–Si alloys at 2814 °C, together with the experimental data points (85Arp [410]). The calculations are identical to those by Liu *et al.* [61]. The reference states used are pure liquid Mo and Si.

Fig. 119. The calculated (IAD) enthalpy of formation for solid Mo–Si alloys at 25 °C, together with the experimental data points (74Cha [411] and 89Bar [412]). The calculations are practically identical to those by Liu *et al.* [61]. The reference states used are pure bcc Mo and pure diamond Si.

Fig. 120. The calculated (IAD) entropy of formation for solid Mo–Si alloys at 25 °C, together with the experimental data points (89Bar [412]). The calculations are practically identical to those by Liu *et al.* [61]. The reference states used are pure bcc Mo and pure diamond Si.

3.22 The Ni–Si system

The Ni–Si system has been assessed by Lindholm and Sundman [62], Du and Schuster [63], and Tokunaga *et al.* [64]. In each study, the fcc phase was shown to dissolve the Ni₃Si phase too much in regard to the experimental measurements. A new description was made by Miettinen [65] to reduce the solubility. More recently, the bcc, Ni₂Si- θ and Ni₃Si₂- ϵ phase descriptions by [65] were modified for the IAD to make bcc metastable (otherwise, a tiny bcc region was formed in the middle of the Ni–Si diagram) and to achieve a simpler description for Ni₂Si- θ . The purpose was to simplify the Ni–Si description and the following Fe–Ni–Si description for practical calculations for modeling the solidification of steels. The present work reviews the Ni–Si description according to the IAD and presents its experimental verification.

3.22.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 70 shows the phases and their modeling, while Table 71 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the Ni–Si system is presented in Table 72. Note the metastable bcc phase description

according to the IAD. The stoichiometric Ni₃Si-β₁ phase according to the IAD and [65] refers to the ordered fcc-L12 phase according to [62–64] and the stoichiometric Ni₂Si-θ phase according to the IAD refers to the (Ni)(Ni,Va)(Si) phase according to [62–65].

Table 70. Phases and their modeling in the Ni–Si description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (≈ L)	(Ni,Si), substitutional, RK
bcc_A2 (≈ bcc, metastable)	(Ni,Si), substitutional, RK
fcc_A1 (≈ fcc)	(Ni,Si), substitutional, RK
Ni ₃ Si-β ₁	(Ni) ₃ (Si), stoichiometric
Ni ₃ Si-β ₂	(Ni) ₃ (Si), stoichiometric
Ni ₃ Si-β ₃	(Ni) ₃ (Si), stoichiometric
Ni ₅ Si ₂ -γ	(Ni) ₅ (Si) ₂ , stoichiometric
Ni ₂ Si-δ	(Ni) ₂ (Si), stoichiometric
Ni ₂ Si-θ	(Ni) ₂ (Si), stoichiometric
Ni ₃ Si ₂ -ε	(Ni) ₃ (Si) ₂ , stoichiometric
NiSi	(Ni)(Si), stoichiometric
NiSi ₂ -α	(Ni)(Si) ₂ , stoichiometric
dia_A4 (≈ dia)	pure Si

Note: RK = Redlich–Kister excess model.

Table 71. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Ni–Si according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Phase equilibria of the phase diagram	[413–418]
Enthalpy of mixing for liquid alloys at 1580 °C	[137, 419, 420]
Activity of Si in liquid alloys at 1580 °C and 1480 °C	[421, 422]
Enthalpy of formation for solid alloys at 25 °C	[423–425]

Table 72. The thermodynamic description of the Ni–Si system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid</i> (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Ni,Si) $L_{\text{Ni,Si}}^{\text{L}} = (-205000 + 33T) + (-102700 + 27T)(x_{\text{Ni}} - x_{\text{Si}}) + (+25000)(x_{\text{Ni}} - x_{\text{Si}})^2 + (+117000 - 55T)(x_{\text{Ni}} - x_{\text{Si}})^3$	[65]
<i>bcc^(m)</i> (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Ni,Si) $L_{\text{Ni,Si}}^{\text{bcc}} = (-185000 + 30T)$	IAD
$T_{\text{c}}^{\text{bcc}} = 575x_{\text{Ni}}$	[65]
$\beta^{\text{bcc}} = 0.85x_{\text{Ni}}$	[65]
<i>fcc</i> (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Ni,Si) $L_{\text{Ni,Si}}^{\text{fcc}} = (-205000 + 30T) + (-52000 + 20T)(x_{\text{Ni}} - x_{\text{Si}})$	[65]
$T_{\text{c}}^{\text{fcc}} = 633x_{\text{Ni}}$	[65]
$\beta^{\text{fcc}} = 0.52x_{\text{Ni}}$	[65]
<i>Ni₃Si-β₁</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 19:6, constituents: Ni:Si) $G_{\text{Ni:Si}}^{\circ,\beta_1} = 19G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 6G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ,\text{dia}} + (-1040800 + 120T)$	[65]
<i>Ni₃Si-β₂</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 3:1, constituents: Ni:Si) $G_{\text{Ni:Si}}^{\circ,\beta_2} = 3G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ,\text{dia}} + (-161860 + 12T)$	[65]
<i>Ni₃Si-β₃</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 3:1, constituents: Ni:Si) $G_{\text{Ni:Si}}^{\circ,\beta_3} = 3G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ,\text{dia}} + (-132440 - 9.2T)$	[65]
<i>Ni₅Si₂-γ</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 5:2, constituents: Ni:Si) $G_{\text{Ni:Si}}^{\circ,\gamma} = 5G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 2G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ,\text{dia}} + (-302190 + 14T)$	[65]
<i>Ni₂Si-δ</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents: Ni:Si) $G_{\text{Ni:Si}}^{\circ,\delta} = 2G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ,\text{dia}} + (-149000 + 166T - 21T \ln T)$	IAD
<i>Ni₂Si-θ</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents: Ni:Si) $G_{\text{Ni:Si}}^{\circ,\theta} = 2G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ,\text{dia}} + (-115333 - 10T)$	IAD
<i>Ni₃Si₂-ε</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 3:2, constituents: Ni:Si) $G_{\text{Ni:Si}}^{\circ,\epsilon} = 3G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 2G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ,\text{dia}} + (-218700 + 10T)$	IAD
<i>NiSi</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 1:1, constituents: Ni:Si) $G_{\text{Ni:Si}}^{\circ} = G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ,\text{dia}} + (-80600 + 1.2T)$	[65]
<i>NiSi₂-α</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 1:2, constituents: Ni:Si) $G_{\text{Ni:Si}}^{\circ,\alpha} = G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 2G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ,\text{dia}} + (-106800 + 18T)$	[65]

Notes: (m) = metastable phase; the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

3.22.2 Results

The results of the calculations according to the IAD, and Lindholm and Sundman [62] together with the experimental data (Table 71) are presented in Figures 121–124 and Table 73. The agreement is reasonably good in both calculations. In Figure 121, note the better agreement for the fcc region according to the IAD and the better agreement for the L+dia region, between 1000 °C and 1150 °C, by Lindholm and Sundman [62]. Note also the simple, stoichiometric presentation for the Ni₂Si-θ phase according to

the IAD, in regard to a more realistic presentation by Lindholm and Sundman [62] and Miettinen [65] allowing a wider composition range for that phase. In Figure 123, note the slightly better agreement with low Si contents and the slightly worse agreement with high Si contents according to the IAD.

Table 73. The calculated and experimental invariant points in the Ni-rich portion of the Ni–Si system.

$\phi_1 - \phi_2 - \phi_3$	T [°C]	$x_{\text{Si}}^{\phi_1}$	$x_{\text{Si}}^{\phi_2}$	$x_{\text{Si}}^{\phi_3}$	Type	Ref.
L = fcc + β_3	1151	–	–	–	Exp.	[414]
	1143	0.214	0.158	0.249	Exp.	[416]
	1158	0.207	0.161	0.248	Exp.	[417]
	1143	0.210	0.170	0.250	Calc.	[62]
	1144	0.211	0.158	0.250	Calc.	IAD
L + $\gamma = \beta_3$	1163	0.222	–	–	Exp.	[414]
	1170	0.225	0.280	0.250	Exp.	[416]
	1189	0.221	0.282	0.250	Exp.	[417]
	1173	0.232	0.286	0.250	Calc.	[62]
	1170	0.225	0.286	0.250	Calc.	IAD
L = $\gamma + \delta$	1214	0.306	–	–	Exp.	[414]
	1215	0.305	–	–	Exp.	[416]
	1231	0.314	0.289	–	Exp.	[417]
	1244	0.296	0.289	0.333	Calc.	[62]
	1242	0.292	0.289	0.333	Calc.	IAD
L = γ	1242	0.281	0.281	–	Exp.	[416]
	1256	0.285	0.285	–	Exp.	[417]
	1246	0.286	0.286	–	Calc.	[62]
	1243	0.286	0.286	–	Calc.	IAD
L = θ	1306	0.333	0.333	–	Exp.	[426]
	1285	0.333	0.333	–	Exp.	[414]
	1288	0.333	0.333	–	Calc.	[62]
	1290	0.333	0.333	–	Calc.	IAD
L + $\theta = \delta$	1255	0.303	0.333	–	Exp.	[426]
	1257	0.296	0.333	–	Calc.	[62]
	1254	0.334	0.333	–	Calc.	IAD

Table 73 (continued)

$\phi_1 - \phi_2 - \phi_3$	T [°C]	$x_{\text{Si}}^{\phi_1}$	$x_{\text{Si}}^{\phi_2}$	$x_{\text{Si}}^{\phi_3}$	Type	Ref.
$\beta_3 = \beta_2$	1115	–	–	–	Exp.	[416]
	1120	–	–	–	Exp.	[417]
	1117	0.250	0.250	–	Calc.	[62]
	1115	0.250	0.250	–	Calc.	IAD
fcc + $\beta_2 = \beta_1$	1040	–	0.250	–	Exp.	[414]
	1035	0.148	0.249	0.239	Exp.	[416]
	1010	0.150	0.248	0.239	Exp.	[417]
	1036	0.160	0.250	0.232	Calc.	[62]
	1035	0.149	0.250	0.240	Calc.	IAD
$\beta_2 = \beta_1 + \gamma$	990	0.252	0.246	0.280	Exp.	[416]
	1001	0.250	0.242	0.282	Exp.	[417]
	989	0.250	0.245	0.286	Calc.	[62]
	993	0.250	0.240	0.286	Calc.	IAD

Fig. 121. A calculated Ni–Si phase diagram, together with the experimental data points (32Dah [413], 36lwa [414], 71Ras [415], 83Oya [416], 84Leb [417], and 05Him [418]). The solid lines refer to the the calculations using the IAD and the dashed lines refer to those by Lindholm and Sundman [62].

Fig. 122. The calculated enthalpy of mixing for liquid Ni-Si alloys at 1580 °C, together with the experimental data points (66EIK [137], 73Cha [419], and 79Stu [420]). The solid lines refer to the the calculations using the IAD and the dashed lines refer to those by Lindholm and Sundman [62]. The reference states used are pure liquid Ni and pure liquid Si.

Fig. 123. The calculated activity of Si in liquid Ni-Si alloys at 1580 °C and 1480 °C, together with the experimental data points (65Sch [421] and 68Mar [422]). The solid lines refer to the the calculations using the IAD and the dashed lines refer to those by Lindholm and Sundman [62]. The reference state for Si is pure liquid Si.

Fig. 124. The calculated enthalpy of formation for solid Ni-Si alloys at 25 °C, together with the experimental data points (36Oel [423], 68Rez [424], and 91Kek [425]). The solid lines refer to the the calculations using the IAD and the dashed lines refer to those by Lindholm and Sundman [62]. The reference states used are pure fcc Ni and pure diamond Si.

4 Ternary systems

4.1 The Fe–Al–Cr system

Experimental studies on the Fe–Al–Cr system have been reviewed by Raynor and Rivlin [427] and Raghavan [428, 429], and a thermodynamic assessment has been given by Jacobs *et al.* [66]. The system was later reassessed for the IAD as its binary Al–Cr and Fe–Al data differs from that of Jacobs *et al.* [66]. The present work reviews the Fe–Al–Cr description according to the IAD and presents its experimental verification.

4.1.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 74 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 75 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 76.

Table 74. Phases and their modeling in the Fe–Al–Cr description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Al,Cr,Fe), substitutional, RKM
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Al,Cr,Fe), substitutional, RKM
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Al,Cr,Fe), substitutional, RKM
Al ₅ Fe ₄	(Al,Cr,Fe), substitutional, RKM
Sigma (\approx σ)	(Fe) ₈ (Cr) ₄ (Cr,Fe) ₁₈ , sublattice, RKM
Al ₂ Fe (dissolving Cr)	(Al) ₂ (Cr,Fe), sublattice, RKM
Al ₅ Fe ₂ (dissolving Cr)	(Al) ₅ (Cr,Fe) ₂ , sublattice, RKM
Al ₄ Cr (dissolving Fe)	(Al,Fe) ₄ (Cr), sublattice, RKM
Al ₈ Cr ₅ -H (dissolving Fe)	(Al) ₃ (Cr,Fe) ₂ , sublattice, RKM
Al ₈ Cr ₅ -L (dissolving Fe)	(Al) ₃ (Cr,Fe) ₂ , sublattice, RKM
Al ₁₃ Fe ₄	(Al) _{7.52} (Fe) _{2.48} , stoichiometric
Al ₇ Cr	(Al) ₇ (Cr), stoichiometric
Al ₁₁ Cr ₂	(Al) ₁₁ (Cr) ₂ , stoichiometric
AlCr ₂	(Al)(Cr) ₂ , stoichiometric

Note: RKM = Redlich–Kister–Muggianu excess model.

Table 75. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Fe–Al–Cr according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
2 isothermal sections at 1150 °C and 1000 °C	[195, 430]
3 vertical sections $w_{Fe}:w_{Cr} = 85:15$, $w_{Fe}:w_{Cr} = 75:25$ and $w_{Fe}:w_{Cr} = 50:50$, and at 15 and 25 wt-% Al	[195, 431]
Activity coefficient γ_{Al}^{Cr} in liquid alloys at 1600 °C	[432, 433]
Activity of Al, Cr, and Fe in 2 bcc alloys as a function of temperature	[66]

Table 76. The thermodynamic description of the Fe–Al–Cr system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Cr,Fe)</i>	
$L_{Al,Cr}^L = (-33500) + (-10000 + 4T)(x_{Al} - x_{Cr})$	IAD
$L_{Al,Fe}^L = (-80800 + 15T) + (-5000 + 3T)(x_{Al} - x_{Fe}) + (+4500 - 4T)(x_{Al} - x_{Fe})^2$	IAD
$L_{Cr,Fe}^L = (-17737 + 7.997T) + (-1331)(x_{Cr} - x_{Fe})$	[5]
$L_{Al,Cr,Fe}^L = (+0)x_{Al} + (+30000)x_{Cr} + (+75000 - 15T)x_{Fe}$	IAD
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Cr,Fe)</i>	
$L_{Al,Cr}^{bcc} = (-58258 + 8.441T)$	[19]
$L_{Al,Fe}^{bcc} = (-128300 + 35T) + (-13600 + 10T)(x_{Al} - x_{Fe})$	IAD
$L_{Cr,Fe}^{bcc} = (+20500 - 9.68T)$	[4]
$L_{Al,Cr,Fe}^{bcc} = (-10000)x_{Al} + (+30000)x_{Cr} + (+30000 + 10T)x_{Fe}$	IAD
$T_c^{bcc} = 1043x_{Fe} - 311x_{Cr} + x_{Al}x_{Fe}(-1100(x_{Al} - x_{Fe})) + x_{Fe}x_{Cr}(1650 - 550(x_{Fe} - x_{Cr}))$	IAD
$\beta^{bcc} = 2.22x_{Fe} - 0.008x_{Cr} - 0.85x_{Fe}x_{Cr}$	[4]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Cr,Fe)</i>	
$L_{Al,Cr}^{fcc} = (-47000 + 7T)$	IAD
$L_{Al,Fe}^{fcc} = (-84100 + 17T) + (+22000)(x_{Al} - x_{Fe}) + (+10000)(x_{Al} - x_{Fe})^2$	IAD
$L_{Cr,Fe}^{fcc} = (+10833 - 7.477T) + (+1410)(x_{Cr} - x_{Fe})$	[4]
$L_{Al,Cr,Fe}^{fcc} = (-10000)$	IAD
$T_c^{fcc} = -201x_{Fe} - 1109x_{Cr}$	[4]
$\beta^{fcc} = -2.1x_{Fe} - 2.46x_{Cr}$	[4]
<i>Al₅Fe₄ (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Cr,Fe)</i>	
$G_{Al}^{\circ, Al_5Fe_4} = G_{Al}^{\circ, fcc} + (+12179 - 4.813T)$	[434]
$G_{Cr}^{\circ, Al_5Fe_4} = G_{Cr}^{\circ, bcc} + (+5000)$	IAD
$G_{Fe}^{\circ, Al_5Fe_4} = G_{Fe}^{\circ, bcc} + (+5009)$	[434]
$L_{Al,Cr}^{Al_5Fe_4} = (-74000 + 12T)$	IAD
$L_{Al,Fe}^{Al_5Fe_4} = (-131500 + 29T) + (-16000)(x_{Al} - x_{Fe})$	IAD
$L_{Cr,Fe}^{Al_5Fe_4} = (+10000)$	IAD
<i>Sigma (σ) (3 sublattices, sites: 8:4:18, constituents: Fe:Cr:Cr,Fe)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Cr:Cr}^{\circ, \sigma} = 8G_{Fe}^{\circ, fcc} + 22G_{Cr}^{\circ, bcc} + (+92300 - 95.96T)$	[4]
$G_{Fe:Cr:Fe}^{\circ, \sigma} = 8G_{Fe}^{\circ, fcc} + 4G_{Cr}^{\circ, bcc} + 18G_{Fe}^{\circ, bcc} + (+117300 - 95.96T)$	[4]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

Table 76 (continued)

Equation	Reference
<i>Al₂Fe</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents: Al:Cr,Fe)	
$G_{\text{Al:Cr}}^{\circ, \text{Al}_2\text{Fe}} = 2G_{\text{Al}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + G_{\text{Cr}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}}$	IAD
$G_{\text{Al:Fe}}^{\circ, \text{Al}_2\text{Fe}} = 2G_{\text{Al}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + (-98097 + 18.750T)$	[434]
$L_{\text{Al:Cr,Fe}}^{\text{Al}_2\text{Fe}} = (-50000)$	IAD
<i>Al₅Fe₂</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 5:2, constituents: Al:Cr,Fe)	
$G_{\text{Al:Cr}}^{\circ, \text{Al}_5\text{Fe}_2} = 5G_{\text{Al}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + 2G_{\text{Cr}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}}$	IAD
$G_{\text{Al:Fe}}^{\circ, \text{Al}_5\text{Fe}_2} = 5G_{\text{Al}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + 2G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + (-228576 + 48.995T)$	[434]
$L_{\text{Al:Cr,Fe}}^{\text{Al}_5\text{Fe}_2} = (-137000)$	IAD
<i>Al₄Cr</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 4:1, constituents: Al,Fe:Cr)	
$G_{\text{Al:Cr}}^{\circ, \text{Al}_4\text{Cr}} = 4G_{\text{Al}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + G_{\text{Cr}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + (-82000 + 13T)$	IAD
$G_{\text{Fe:Cr}}^{\circ, \text{Al}_4\text{Cr}} = 4G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + G_{\text{Cr}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}}$	IAD
$L_{\text{Al,Fe:Cr}}^{\text{Al}_4\text{Cr}} = (-120000) + (-120000)(y_{\text{Al}} - y_{\text{Fe}})$	IAD
<i>Al₈Cr₅-H</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 3:2, constituents: Al:Cr,Fe)	
$G_{\text{Al:Cr}}^{\circ, \text{Al}_8\text{Cr}_5\text{-H}} = 3G_{\text{Al}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + 2G_{\text{Cr}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + (-83200 - 8T)$	IAD
$G_{\text{Al:Fe}}^{\circ, \text{Al}_8\text{Cr}_5\text{-H}} = 3G_{\text{Al}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + 2G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + (-122000)$	IAD
$L_{\text{Al:Cr,Fe}}^{\text{Al}_8\text{Cr}_5\text{-H}} = (-15500)$	IAD
<i>Al₈Cr₅-L</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 3:2, constituents: Al:Cr,Fe)	
$G_{\text{Al:Cr}}^{\circ, \text{Al}_8\text{Cr}_5\text{-L}} = 3G_{\text{Al}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + 2G_{\text{Cr}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + (-94500)$	IAD
$G_{\text{Al:Fe}}^{\circ, \text{Al}_8\text{Cr}_5\text{-L}} = 3G_{\text{Al}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + 2G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + (-122000)$	IAD
$L_{\text{Al:Cr,Fe}}^{\text{Al}_8\text{Cr}_5\text{-L}} = (-15000)$	IAD
<i>Al₁₃Fe₄</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 7.52:2.48, constituents: Al:Fe)	
$G_{\text{Al:Fe}}^{\circ, \text{Al}_{13}\text{Fe}_4} = 7.52G_{\text{Al}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + 2.48G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + (-320004 + 74.7T)$	IAD
<i>Al₇Cr</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 7:1, constituents: Al:Cr)	
$G_{\text{Al:Cr}}^{\circ, \text{Al}_7\text{Cr}} = 7G_{\text{Al}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + G_{\text{Cr}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + (-89000 + 14T)$	IAD
<i>Al₁₁Cr₂</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 11:2, constituents: Al:Cr)	
$G_{\text{Al:Cr}}^{\circ, \text{Al}_{11}\text{Cr}_2} = 11G_{\text{Al}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + 2G_{\text{Cr}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + (-137000 - 6T)$	IAD
<i>AlCr₂</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 1:2, constituents: Al:Cr)	
$G_{\text{Al:Cr}}^{\circ, \text{AlCr}_2} = G_{\text{Al}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + 2G_{\text{Cr}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + (-45400 - 1T)$	IAD

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

4.1.2 Results

The results of the calculations according to the IAD together with the experimental data (Table 75) are presented in Figures 125–134 and Table 77. The agreement is reasonably good. In Figure 127, note the wide experimental composition region of the Al₈Cr₅-H phase in regard to that of the calculated line compound, Al₈Cr₅-H. Additional measurements, for the isothermal sections of 1647 °C, 1547 °C, and 1527 °C, are available from Kozheurov *et al.* [431]. These data were rejected from the optimization, to keep the liquidus temperature values in the iron-rich corner reasonably low, as measured recently

by [435] for commercial Fe+20 wt-%Cr–Al alloys containing slight amounts of C, Si, and Mn. The overly high liquidus temperatures by Kozheurov *et al.* [431] can be seen in Figures 128 and 129.

Table 77. The calculated (IAD) invariant points of the Fe–Cr–Al system.

Reaction	Code	Temp. [°C]	Cr in Liq [at-%]	N in Liq [at-%]
$L + \text{bcc} + \text{Al}_8\text{Cr}_5\text{-H} = \text{Al}_5\text{Fe}_4$	P	1271	14.78	55.24
$L + \text{Al}_8\text{Cr}_5\text{-H} = \text{Al}_5\text{Fe}_4 + \text{Al}_5\text{Fe}_2$	U ₁	1163	2.57	68.09
$L + \text{Al}_8\text{Cr}_5\text{-H} = \text{Al}_5\text{Fe}_2 + \text{Al}_8\text{Cr}_5\text{-L}$	U ₂	1114	8.84	77.86
$L + \text{Al}_8\text{Cr}_5\text{-L} = \text{Al}_5\text{Fe}_2 + \text{Al}_4\text{Cr}$	U ₃	1014	9.45	83.66
$L + \text{Al}_5\text{Fe}_2 + \text{Al}_{13}\text{Fe}_4 + \text{Al}_4\text{Cr}$	U ₄	951	5.62	88.67

Fig. 125. The calculated (IAD) liquidus projection in the Fe–Al–Cr system. Also shown are the calculated liquidus isotherms between 1800 °C and 900 °C, by the dotted lines.

Fig. 126. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1150 °C in the Fe–Al–Cr system, together with the experimental data points [195].

Fig. 127. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1000 °C in the Fe–Al–Cr system, together with the experimental data points (70Koz [431] and 97Pal [430]).

Fig. 128. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of $w_{Fe}:w_{Cr} = 85:15$ in the Fe-Al-Cr system, together with the experimental data points (45Kor [195] and 70Koz [431]).

Fig. 129. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of $w_{Fe}:w_{Cr} = 75:25$ in the Fe-Al-Cr system, together with the experimental data points (45Kor [195] and 70Koz [431]).

Fig. 130. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of $w_{Fe}:w_{Cr} = 1$ in the Fe-Al-Cr system, together with the experimental data points [195].

Fig. 131. The calculated (IAD) liquidus vertical sections of 15 wt-% Al and 25 wt-% Al in the Fe-Al-Cr system, together with the experimental data points (45Kor [195]).

Fig. 132. The calculated activity coefficient $\gamma_{\text{Al}}^{\text{Cr}}$ in liquid Fe–Al–Cr alloys at 1600 °C, together with the experimental data points (78Wad [432] and 80Leo [433]).

Fig. 133. The calculated (IAD) activities of Al, Cr, and Fe in bcc Fe–16.7 at-% Cr–38.6 at-% Al alloy, together with the experimental data points [66].

Fig. 134. The calculated (IAD) activities of Al, Cr, and Fe in bcc Fe–30.4 at-% Cr–19.7 at-% Al alloy, together with the experimental data points [66].

4.2 The Fe–Al–Cu system

Experimental studies on the Fe–Al–Cu system have been reviewed in [436–440] and a thermodynamic assessment has been given in [?, 67–69]. The studies by Ohtani *et al.* [67], Wang *et al.* [68], and Miettinen [69] focused on the Fe–Cu side while Chen *et al.* [?] described the whole system, with an emphasis on the Al-corner.

The ternary system was later reassessed for the IAD as its binary Al–Fe and Al–Cu data differs from those by [?, 67–69]. This description is valid on the Fe–Cu side of the system up to 70 wt-% Al on the Fe–Al side and to up to 40 wt-% Al on the Cu–Al side. Thus, there was no need to assess the complex phase equilibria of the Al-rich corner [?, 436] similarly to Chen *et al.* [?]. The present work reviews the Fe–Al–Cu description according to the IAD and presents its experimental verification.

4.2.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 78 shows the phases and their modeling. Note the simplified treatment for the bcc phase according to the IAD ignoring the B2-ordering but including its effect on the

disordered bcc phase. Table 79 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification.

Note that there is disagreement between the results of two early studies [441, 442] concerning the liquidus surfaces, and between the present and the earlier [441, 442] binary phase diagrams. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 80. Note that this does not contain data for the ternary compounds of the Al-rich corner. For the calculations for that region, the Fe–Al–Cu description of Chen *et al.* [?] is recommended.

Table 78. Phases and their modeling in the Fe–Al–Cu description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Al,Cu,Fe), substitutional, RKM
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Al,Cu,Fe), substitutional, RKM
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Al,Cu,Fe), substitutional, RKM
Al ₅ Fe ₄	(Al,Fe), substitutional, RKM
Al ₂ Fe	(Al) ₂ (Fe), stoichiometric
Al ₅ Fe ₂	(Al) ₅ (Fe) ₂ , stoichiometric
Al ₁₃ Fe ₄	(Al) _{7.52} (Fe) _{2.48} , stoichiometric
AlCu- γ H (\approx γ H)	(Al) ₄ (Al,Cu)(Cu) ₈ , sublattice, RKM
AlCu- γ D83 (\approx γ D83)	(Al) ₄ (Al,Cu)(Cu) ₈ , sublattice, RKM
AlCu- δ (\approx δ)	(Al) ₂ (Cu) ₃ , stoichiometric
AlCu- ϵ (\approx ϵ)	(Al,Cu)(Cu), sublattice, RKM
AlCu- ξ (\approx ξ)	(Al) ₉ (Cu) ₁₁ , stoichiometric
AlCu- η (\approx η)	(Al,Cu)(Cu), sublattice, RKM
AlCu- θ (\approx θ)	(Al) ₂ (Al,Cu), sublattice, RKM

Note: RKM = Redlich–Kister–Muggianu excess model.

Table 79. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Fe–Al–Cu according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
6 isothermal sections at 1300 °C, 1200 °C, 1100 °C, 1000 °C, 900 °C, and 800 °C	[8, 67, 68, 442]
3 isothermal sections of Cu-corner, at 1000 °C, 800 °C, and 600 °C	[442]
6 vertical sections at 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 wt-% Al, and at 2 wt-% Fe	[441, 442]

Table 80. The thermodynamic description of the Fe–Cu side Fe–Al–Cu system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Cu,Fe)</i>	
$L_{Al,Cu}^L = (-66622 + 8.1T) + (+46800 - 90.8T + 10T \ln T)(x_{Al} - x_{Cu}) + (-2812)(x_{Al} - x_{Cu})^2$	[22]
$L_{Al,Fe}^L = (-80800 + 15T) + (-5000 + 3T)(x_{Al} - x_{Fe}) + (+4500 - 4T)(x_{Al} - x_{Fe})^2$	IAD
$L_{Cu,Fe}^L = (+35626 - 2.19T) + (-1530 + 1.153T)(x_{Cu} - x_{Fe}) + (+12714 - 5.186T)(x_{Cu} - x_{Fe})^2 + (+1177)(x_{Cu} - x_{Fe})^3$	[9]
$L_{Al,Cu,Fe}^L = (-70000)x_{Al} + (+10000)x_{Cu} + (-20000)x_{Fe}$	IAD
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Cu,Fe)</i>	
$L_{Al,Cu}^{bcc} = (-76700 + 7T) + (+46000 - 5.5T)(x_{Al} - x_{Cu}) + (+2200)(x_{Al} - x_{Cu})^2$	IAD
$L_{Al,Fe}^{bcc} = (-128300 + 35T) + (-13600 + 10T)(x_{Al} - x_{Fe})$	IAD
$L_{Cu,Fe}^{bcc} = (+39676 - 4.732T)$	[9]
$L_{Al,Cu,Fe}^{bcc} = (-300000 + 70T)x_{Al} + (-30000 + 70T)x_{Cu} + (-100000 + 70T)x_{Fe}$	IAD
$T_c^{bcc} = 1043x_{Fe} + x_{Al}x_{Fe}(-1100(x_{Al} - x_{Fe})) - 41.4x_{Fe}x_{Cu}$	IAD
$\beta^{bcc} = 2.22x_{Fe}$	[96]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Cu,Fe)</i>	
$L_{Al,Cu}^{fcc} = (-53500 + 2T) + (+38600 - 2T)(x_{Al} - x_{Cu}) + (+1.4T)(x_{Al} - x_{Cu})^2$	IAD
$L_{Al,Fe}^{fcc} = (-84100 + 17T) + (+22000)(x_{Al} - x_{Fe}) + (+10000)(x_{Al} - x_{Fe})^2$	IAD
$L_{Cu,Fe}^{fcc} = (+43320 - 6.944T) + (+6069 - 2.837T)(x_{Cu} - x_{Fe}) + (+3629)(x_{Cu} - x_{Fe})^2$	[9]
$L_{Al,Cu,Fe}^{fcc} = (-170000 + 120T)$	IAD
$T_c^{fcc} = -201x_{Fe}$	[96]
$\beta^{fcc} = -2.1x_{Fe}$	[96]
<i>Al₅Fe₄ (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Fe)</i>	
$G_{Al}^{\circ,Al_5Fe_4} = G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + (+12179 - 4.813T)$	[443]
$G_{Fe}^{\circ,Al_5Fe_4} = G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (+5009)$	[443]
$L_{Al,Fe}^{Al_5Fe_4} = (-131500 + 29T) + (-16000)(x_{Al} - x_{Fe})$	IAD
<i>Al₂Fe (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents: Al:Fe)</i>	
$G_{Al:Fe}^{\circ,Al_2Fe} = 2G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (-98097 + 18.750T)$	[443]
<i>Al₅Fe₂ (2 sublattices, sites: 5:2, constituents: Al:Fe)</i>	
$G_{Al:Fe}^{\circ,Al_5Fe_2} = 5G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 2G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (-228576 + 48.995T)$	[443]
<i>Al₁₃Fe₄ (2 sublattices, sites: 7.52:2.48, constituents: Al:Fe)</i>	
$G_{Al:Fe}^{\circ,Al_{13}Fe_4} = 7.52G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 2.48G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (-320004 + 74.7T)$	IAD
<i>AlCu-γH (γH) (3 sublattices, sites: 4:1:8, constituents (Al)₄(Al,Cu)(Cu)₈)</i>	
$G_{Al:Al:Cu}^{\circ,\gamma H} = 5G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 8G_{Cu}^{\circ,fcc} + (-219258 - 45.5T)$	[22]
$G_{Al:Cu:Cu}^{\circ,\gamma H} = 4G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 9G_{Cu}^{\circ,fcc} + (-200460 - 58.5T)$	[22]
<i>AlCu-γD83 (γD83) (3 sublattices, sites: 4:1:8, constituents (Al)₄(Al,Cu)(Cu)₈)</i>	
$G_{Al:Al:Cu}^{\circ,\gamma D83} = 5G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 8G_{Cu}^{\circ,fcc} + (-300716 + 390T - 52T \ln T)$	[22]
$G_{Al:Cu:Cu}^{\circ,\gamma D83} = 4G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 9G_{Cu}^{\circ,fcc} + (-277700 + 377T - 52T \ln T)$	IAD

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

Table 80 (continued)

Equation	Reference
<i>AlCu-δ</i> (δ) (2 sublattices, sites: 2:3, constituents $(Al)_2(Cu)_3$) $G_{Al:Cu}^{\circ,\delta} = 2G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 3G_{Cu}^{\circ,fcc} + (-106700 + 3T)$	[22]
<i>AlCu-ε</i> (ϵ) (2 sublattices, sites: 1:1, constituents $(Al,Cu)(Cu)$) $G_{Al:Cu}^{\circ,\epsilon} = 2G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + G_{Cu}^{\circ,fcc} + (-36976 + 1.2T)$	[22]
$G_{Cu:Cu}^{\circ,\epsilon} = 2G_{Cu}^{\circ,bcc}$	[22]
$L_{Al,Cu:Cu}^{\epsilon} = (+7600 - 24T) + (-72000)(y_{Al} - y_{Cu})$	[22]
<i>AlCu-ξ</i> (ξ) (2 sublattices, sites: 9:11, constituents $(Al)_9(Cu)_{11}$) $G_{Al:Cu}^{\circ,\xi} = 9G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 11G_{Cu}^{\circ,fcc} + (-420000 + 18T)$	[22]
<i>AlCu-η</i> (η) (2 sublattices, sites: 1:1, constituents $(Al,Cu)(Cu)$) $G_{Al:Cu}^{\circ,\eta} = 2G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + G_{Cu}^{\circ,fcc} + (-40560 + 3.14T)$	[22]
$G_{Cu:Cu}^{\circ,\eta} = 2G_{Cu}^{\circ,bcc}$	[22]
$L_{Al,Cu:Cu}^{\eta} = (-25740 - 20T)$	[22]
<i>AlCu-θ</i> (θ) (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents $(Al)(Al,Cu)_2$) $G_{Al:Al}^{\circ,\theta} = 3G_{Al}^{\circ,bcc}$	[22]
$G_{Al:Cu}^{\circ,\theta} = 2G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + G_{Cu}^{\circ,fcc} + (-47406 + 6.75T)$	[22]
$L_{Al:Al,Cu}^{\theta} = (+2221)$	[22]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

4.2.2 Results

The results of the calculations according to the IAD together with the experimental data (Table 79) are presented in Figures 135–151 and Table 81. The agreement is reasonably good. As shown by the liquidus projection in Figure 135, the bcc phase is the dominating primary surface of the system. In the Cu-rich part of that projection (Figure 136), note the cease of the bcc miscibility gap at point C. In Figure 137, some deviation can be seen in the calculated and experimentally determined [442] liquid phase boundary with high Al contents. This disagreement is understandable because of the clear differences between the earlier [442] and the present Cu–Al and Cu–Fe phase diagrams.

Additional experimental phase equilibrium data are available from [444,445]. They agree reasonably with the calculations, though the experimental fcc stability at 700 °C by Turkin and Bakhvalova [444] is too strong and the experimental bcc1 stability at 672 °C by Haworth and Hume-Rothery [445] is too weak with respect to the calculations and the experimental data by Yutaka [442]. Experimental data were also available for the solid-state phase equilibria [441,442], but for the most part, the data are inconsistent with each other and with the presently accepted binary phase diagrams.

Table 81. The calculated and experimental invariant points of the Fe–Al–Cu system.

Reaction	Code	Figure	Temp. [°C]	Cu in Liq [wt-%]	Al in Liq [wt-%]	Type	Ref.
$L + Al_5Fe_4 = bcc + Al_2Fe$	U ₁	135	1143	4.39	48.89	Calc.	IAD
$L + Al_2Fe = bcc + Al_5Fe_2$	U ₂	135	1125	8.48	49.45	Calc.	IAD
$L + Al_5Fe_2 = bcc + Al_{13}Fe_4$	U ₃	135	1014	37.41	45.62	Calc.	IAD
$L + bcc = Al_{13}Fe_4 + \epsilon$	U ₄	136	779	65.52	33.94	Calc.	IAD
$L + fcc_1 = bcc_1 + fcc_2$	U ₅	136	1092	95.02	2.15	Calc.	IAD
			1072	92.2	5.5	Exp.	[442]
$L + bcc_1 = fcc_2 + bcc_2$	U ₆	136	1048	89.72	7.64	Calc.	IAD
			1048	89.1	8.5	Exp.	[442]

Fig. 135. The calculated (IAD) liquidus projection of the Fe–Al–Cu system. Also shown are the calculated liquidus isotherms between 1500 °C and 950 °C (dotted lines).

Fig. 136. The calculated (IAD) Cu-rich liquidus projection of the Fe-Al-Cu system. Also shown are the calculated liquidus isotherms between 1300 °C and 700 °C (dotted lines).

Fig. 137. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1300 °C in the Fe-Al-Cu system, together with the experimental data points (41Yut [442], 94Swa [8], and 97Oht [67]). L-bnd denotes the liquid phase boundary.

Fig. 138. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1200 °C in the Fe–Al–Cu system, together with the experimental data points (41Yut [442], 94Swa [8], and 97Oht [67]). L-bnd denotes the liquid phase boundary.

Fig. 139. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1100 °C in the Fe–Al–Cu system, together with the experimental data points (41Yut [442], 94Swa [8], and 97Oht [67]). L-bnd denotes the liquid phase boundary.

Fig. 140. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1000 °C in the Fe–Al–Cu system, together with the experimental data points (94Swa [8] and 98Wan [68]).

Fig. 141. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 900 °C in the Fe–Al–Cu system, together with the experimental data points (94Swa [8] and 98Wan [68]).

Fig. 142. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 800 °C in the Fe–Al–Cu system, together with the experimental data points (94Swa [8] and 98Wan [68]).

Fig. 143. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1000 °C in the Cu-corner of the Fe–Al–Cu system, together with the experimental data points [442].

Fig. 144. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 800 °C in the Cu-corner of the Fe–Al–Cu system, together with the experimental data points [442].

Fig. 145. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 600 °C in the Cu-corner of the Fe–Al–Cu system, together with the experimental data points [442].

Fig. 146. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 2 wt-% Al in the Fe-Al-Cu system, together with the experimental data points (38Nis [441] and 41Yut [442]).

Fig. 147. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 4 wt-% Al in the Fe-Al-Cu system, together with the experimental data points (38Nis [441] and 41Yut [442]).

Fig. 148. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 6 wt-% Al in the Fe–Al–Cu system, together with the experimental data points (38Nis [441] and 41Yut [442]).

Fig. 149. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 8 wt-% Al in the Fe–Al–Cu system, together with the experimental data points (38Nis [441] and 41Yut [442]).

Fig. 150. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 10 wt-% Al in the Fe–Al–Cu system, together with the experimental data points (38NiS [441] and [442]).

Fig. 151. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 2 wt-% Fe in the Cu-corner of the Fe–Al–Cu system, together with the experimental data points (38NiS [441] and 41Yut [442]).

4.3 The Fe–Al–Mo system

Experimental studies on the Fe–Al–Mo system have been reviewed by Raghavan [439, 446,447] and a thermodynamic assessment has been given by Du *et al.* [70]. The system was later reassessed for the IAD as its binary data differs from that of Du *et al.* [70].

A simple sublattice treatment was chosen for most compounds of the system, instead of the more complex sublattice treatments applied by Du *et al.* [70]. The purpose was to simplify the Fe–Al–Mo description for practical calculations for modeling the solidification of steels. The present work reviews the Fe–Al–Mo description according to the IAD and presents its experimental verification.

4.3.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 82 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 83 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 84.

Table 82. Phases and their modeling in the Fe–Al–Mo description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid ($\approx L$)	(Al,Mo,Fe), substitutional, RKM
bcc_A2 ($\approx bcc$)	(Al,Mo,Fe), substitutional, RKM
fcc_A1 ($\approx fcc$)	(Al,Mo,Fe), substitutional, RKM
Mu ($\approx \mu$)	(Al,Fe) ₇ (Mo) ₂ (Fe,Mo) ₄ , sublattice, RKM
R	(Fe) ₂₇ (Mo) ₁₄ (Fe,Mo) ₁₂ , sublattice, RKM
Sigma ($\approx \sigma$)	(Fe) ₈ (Mo) ₄ (Fe,Mo) ₁₈ , sublattice, RKM
Fe ₂ Mo ($\approx \lambda$)	(Al,Fe) ₂ (Mo), sublattice, RKM
Al ₅ Fe ₄	(Al,Fe,Mo), substitutional, RKM
Al ₂ Fe	(Al) ₂ (Fe), stoichiometric
Al ₅ Fe ₂	(Al) ₅ (Fe,Mo) ₂ , sublattice, RKM
Al ₁₃ Fe ₄	(Al) _{7.52} (Fe) _{2.48} , stoichiometric
Al ₁₂ Mo	(Al) ₁₂ (Mo), stoichiometric
Al ₅ Mo	(Al) ₅ (Mo), stoichiometric
Al ₄ Mo	(Al) ₄ (Fe,Mo), sublattice, RKM
Al ₈ Mo ₃	(Al) ₈ (Mo) ₃ , stoichiometric
Al ₆₃ Mo ₃₇	(Al) ₆₃ (Mo) ₃₇ , stoichiometric
AlMo	(Al) _{0.485} (Mo) _{0.515} , stoichiometric
AlMo ₃	(Al,Fe)(Mo) ₃ , sublattice, RKM
Al ₉ FeMo ₃ ($\approx \pi$)	(Al) ₉ (Fe)(Mo) ₃ , stoichiometric
τ -AlFeMo ($\approx \tau$)	(Al,Fe,Mo), substitutional, RKM

Note: RKM = Redlich–Kister–Muggianu excess model.

Table 83. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Fe–Al–Mo according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
3 isotherms at 1150 °C, 1000 °C, and 800 °C	[448, 449]

Table 84. The thermodynamic description of the Fe–Al–Mo system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference(s)
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Mo,Fe)</i>	
$L_{Al,Fe}^L = (-80800 + 15T) + (-5000 + 3T)(x_{Al} - x_{Fe}) + (+4500 - 4T)(x_{Al} - x_{Fe})^2$	IAD
$L_{Al,Mo}^L = (-100000 + 35T) + (-15000 + 6.3T)(x_{Al} - x_{Mo})$	[25]
$L_{Fe,Mo}^L = (-6900 - 0.23T) + (-9000 + 3.85T)(x_{Fe} - x_{Mo})$	IAD
$L_{Al,Mo,Fe}^L = (+10000)$	IAD
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Mo,Fe)</i>	
$L_{Al,Fe}^{bcc} = (-128300 + 35T) + (-13600 + 10T)(x_{Al} - x_{Fe})$	IAD
$L_{Al,Mo}^{bcc} = (-75000 + 25T)$	[25]
$L_{Fe,Mo}^{bcc} = (+36818 - 9.141T) + (-362 - 5.724T)(x_{Fe} - x_{Mo})$	[13]
$L_{Al,Mo,Fe}^{bcc} = (+10000 - 10T)x_{Al} + (+10000)x_{Fe} + (+10000)x_{Mo}$	IAD
$T_c^{bcc} = 1043x_{Fe} + x_{Al}x_{Fe}(-1100(x_{Al} - x_{Fe})) + x_{Fe}x_{Mo}(335 + 526(x_{Fe} - x_{Mo}))$	[13], IAD
$\beta^{bcc} = 2.22x_{Fe}$	[96]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Mo,Fe)</i>	
$L_{Al,Fe}^{fcc} = (-80000 + 16.4T) + (+22000)(x_{Al} - x_{Fe}) + (+6500)(x_{Al} - x_{Fe})^2$	IAD
$L_{Al,Mo}^{fcc} = (-120000 + 50T)$	IAD
$L_{Fe,Mo}^{fcc} = (+28347 - 17.691T)$	[13]
$T_c^{fcc} = -201x_{Fe}$	[96]
$\beta^{fcc} = -2.1x_{Fe}$	[96]
<i>Mu (μ) (3 sublattices, sites: 7:2:4, constituents: Al,Fe:Mo:Fe,Mo)</i>	
$G_{Al:Mo:Fe}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 2G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 4G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (+370000 + 70T)$	IAD
$G_{Al:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 6G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+10000 + 70T)$	IAD
$G_{Fe:Mo:Fe}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 2G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 4G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (+39475 - 6.032T)$	[13]
$G_{Fe:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 6G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (-46663 - 5.891T)$	[13]
$L_{Al:Mo:Fe,Mo}^{\mu} = (-1500000)$	IAD
$L_{Al,Fe:Mo:Mo}^{\mu} = (-500000)$	IAD
<i>R (3 sublattices, sites: 27:14:12, constituents: Fe:Mo:Fe,Mo)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Mo:Fe}^{\circ,R} = 27G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 14G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 12G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (-77487 - 50.486T)$	[13]
$G_{Fe:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,R} = 27G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 26G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+313474 - 289.472T)$	[13]
<i>Sigma (σ) (3 sublattices, sites: 8:4:18, constituents: Fe:Mo:Fe,Mo)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Mo:Fe}^{\circ,\sigma} = 8G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 4G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 18G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (-1813 - 27.272T)$	[13]
$G_{Fe:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,\sigma} = 8G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 22G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+83326 - 69.618T)$	[13]
$L_{Fe:Mo:Fe,Mo}^{\sigma} = (+222909)$	[13]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

Table 84 (continued)

Equation	Reference(s)
Fe_2Mo (λ) (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents: Al,Fe:Mo)	
$G_{Al:Mo}^{\circ,\lambda} = 2G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc}$	IAD
$G_{Fe:Mo}^{\circ,\lambda} = 2G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (-10798 - 0.132T)$	[161]
Al_5Fe_4 (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Mo,Fe)	
$G_{Al}^{\circ,Al_5Fe_4} = G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + (+12179 - 4.813T)$	[450]
$G_{Fe}^{\circ,Al_5Fe_4} = G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (+5009)$	[450]
$G_{Mo}^{\circ,Al_5Fe_4} = G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+5000)$	IAD
$L_{Al,Fe}^{Al_5Fe_4} = (-131500 + 29T) + (-16000)(x_{Al} - x_{Fe})$	IAD
$L_{Al,Mo}^{Al_5Fe_4} = (+5000)$	IAD
$L_{Fe,Mo}^{Al_5Fe_4} = (+20000)$	IAD
$L_{Al,Mo,Fe}^{Al_5Fe_4} = (-630000)x_{Al} + (+450000)x_{Fe} + (-120000)x_{Mo}$	IAD
Al_2Fe (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents: Al:Fe)	
$G_{Al:Fe}^{\circ,Al_2Fe} = 2G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (-98097 + 18.750T)$	[450]
Al_5Fe_2 (2 sublattices, sites: 5:2, constituents: Al:Fe,Mo)	
$G_{Al:Fe}^{\circ,Al_5Fe_2} = 5G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 2G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (-228576 + 48.995T)$	[450]
$G_{Al:Mo}^{\circ,Al_5Fe_2} = 5G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 2G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc}$	IAD
$L_{Al:Fe,Mo}^{Al_5Fe_2} = (-140000)$	IAD
$Al_{13}Fe_4$ (2 sublattices, sites: 7.52:2.48, constituents: Al:Fe)	
$G_{Al:Fe}^{\circ,Al_{13}Fe_4} = 7.52G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 2.48G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (-320004 + 74.7T)$	IAD
$Al_{12}Mo$ (2 sublattices, sites: 12:1, constituents: Al:Mo)	
$G_{Al:Mo}^{\circ,Al_{12}Mo} = 12G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (-139100 + 26.975T)$	[25]
Al_5Mo (2 sublattices, sites: 5:1, constituents: Al:Mo)	
$G_{Al:Mo}^{\circ,Al_5Mo} = 5G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (-139104 + 30.156T)$	[25]
Al_4Mo (2 sublattices, sites: 4:1, constituents: Al:Mo)	
$G_{Al:Mo}^{\circ,Al_4Mo} = 4G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (-137570 + 29.69T)$	[25]
$G_{Al:Fe}^{\circ,Al_4Mo} = 4G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc}$	IAD
$L_{Al:Fe,Mo}^{Al_4Mo} = (-100000)$	IAD
Al_8Mo_3 (2 sublattices, sites: 8:3, constituents: Al:Mo)	
$G_{Al:Mo}^{\circ,Al_8Mo_3} = 8G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 3G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (-412500 + 105.05T)$	[25]
$Al_{63}Mo_{37}$ (2 sublattices, sites: 63:37, constituents: Al:Mo)	
$G_{Al:Mo}^{\circ,Al_{63}Mo_{37}} = 63G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 37G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (-2268100 + 167.2T)$	[25]
$AlMo$ (2 sublattices, sites: 0.485:0.515, constituents: Al:Mo)	
$G_{Al:Mo}^{\circ,AlMo} = 0.485G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 0.515G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (-14180 - 2.35T)$	IAD
$AlMo_3$ (2 sublattices, sites: 1:3, constituents: Al,Fe:Mo)	
$G_{Fe:Mo}^{\circ,AlMo_3} = G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + 3G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+10000)$	IAD
$G_{Al:Mo}^{\circ,AlMo_3} = G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 3G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (-89000 + 20T - 0.003T^2)$	[25]
$L_{Al:Fe,Mo}^{AlMo_3} = (-10000)$	IAD

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

Table 84 (continued)

Equation	Reference(s)
$Al_9FeMo_3 (\pi)$ (3 sublattices, sites: 9:1:3, constituents: Al:Fe:Mo)	
$G_{Al:Fe:Mo}^{\circ,\pi} = 9G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + 3G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (-424000 + 70T)$	IAD
τ -AlFeMo ($\approx \tau$) (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Mo,Fe)	
$G_{Al}^{\circ,\tau} = G_{Al}^{\circ,bcc} + (+1500)$	IAD
$G_{Fe}^{\circ,\tau} = G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (+5000)$	IAD
$G_{Mo}^{\circ,\tau} = G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+5000)$	IAD
$L_{Al,Fe}^{\tau} = L_{Al,Fe}^{bcc}$	IAD
$L_{Al,Mo}^{\tau} = L_{Al,Mo}^{bcc}$	IAD
$L_{Fe,Mo}^{\tau} = L_{Fe,Mo}^{bcc}$	IAD
$L_{Al,Mo,Fe}^{\tau} = (-430000 - 60T)x_{Al} + (+160000 - 60T)x_{Fe} + (+200000 - 60T)x_{Mo}$	IAD

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

4.3.2 Results

The results of the calculations by IAD together with the experimental data (Table 83) are presented in Figures 152–155 and Table 85. The agreement is reasonably good. Note that the calculated liquidus projection in Figure 152 is tentative, as there are no experimental data for the liquid phase except for some molten Al-rich alloys of Eumann *et al.* [448, 449].

Table 85. The calculated (IAD) invariant points of the Fe–Al–Mo system.

Reaction	Code	Temp. [°C]	Al in Liq [at-%]	Mo in Liq [at-%]
$L + Al_{63}Mo_{37} = AlMo + Al_8Mo_3$	U ₁	1487	61.16	32.86
$L + AlMo = Al_8Mo_3 + AlMo_3$	U ₂	1472	60.42	32.40
$L + \sigma = bcc + R$	U ₃	1468	2.18	28.11
$L + AlMo_3 = bcc + \tau$	U ₄	1414	33.37	24.30
$L + Al_8Mo_3 = AlMo_3 + \pi$	U ₅	1377	57.20	26.44
$L + \tau = Al_5Fe_4 + AlMo_3$	U ₆	1347	52.78	23.29
$L = Al_5Fe_4 + AlMo_3 + \pi$	E	1333	55.10	23.76
$L + \tau = bcc + Al_5Fe_4$	U ₇	1269	52.47	6.09
$L + Al_5Fe_4 + \pi = Al_5Fe_2$	P	1169	71.35	2.72
$L + \pi = Al_5Fe_2 + Al_8Mo_3$	U ₈	1161	75.32	2.42
$L + Al_5Fe_4 = Al_2Fe + Al_5Fe_2$	U ₉	1157	68.95	0.04
$L + Al_5Fe_2 = Al_{13}Fe_4 + Al_8Mo_3$	U ₁₀	1122	80.81	1.65
$L + Al_8Mo_3 = Al_{13}Fe_4 + Al_4Mo$	U ₁₁	1091	84.64	1.33

Fig. 152. The calculated (IAD) liquidus projection in the Fe–Al–Mo system. Also shown by the dotted lines are the calculated liquidus isotherms between 2400 °C and 1100 °C.

Fig. 153. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1150 °C in the Fe–Al–Mo system, together with the experimental data points [449]. The experimental three-phase triangles are shown in grey. The letter "m" denotes the calculated phase region with liquid present.

Fig. 154. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1000 °C in the Fe–Al–Mo system, together with the experimental data points [449]. The experimental three-phase triangles are shown in grey. The letter "m" denotes calculated phase region with liquid present.

Fig. 155. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 800 °C in the Fe–Al–Mo system, together with the experimental data points [448]. The experimental three-phase triangles are shown in grey.

4.4 The Fe–Al–Ni system

Experimental studies on the Fe–Al–Ni system have been reviewed in [451–455] and a thermodynamic assessment has been given by Zhang and Du [71]. The system was later reassessed for the IAD ignoring the B2-ordering of the bcc phase but including its effect on the disordered bcc phase (compare the binary Fe–Al and Al–Ni descriptions according to the IAD). Due to this simplification, the new description is valid up to 50 at-% Al only. Consequently, it was not necessary to include the binary Fe–Al side or Al–Ni side compounds in that description. The only exceptions were the stoichiometric Al_3Ni_5 phase and the AlNi_3 phase, which was treated as a simple line-compound dissolving some iron.

The purpose of these treatments was to simplify the Fe–Al–Ni description for practical calculations for modeling the solidification of steels. The present work reviews the Fe–Al–Ni description according to the IAD and presents its experimental verification.

4.4.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 86 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 87 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 88.

Table 86. Phases and their modeling in the Fe–Al–Ni description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Al,Fe,Ni), substitutional, RKM
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Al,Fe,Ni), substitutional, RKM
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Al,Fe,Ni), substitutional, RKM
AlNi_3 (\approx γ' , dissolving Fe)	(Al)(Fe,Ni) ₃ , sublattice, RKM
Al_3Ni_5 (\approx γ_3)	(Al) ₃ (Ni) ₅ , stoichiometric

Note: RKM = Redlich–Kister–Muggianu excess model.

Table 87. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Fe–Al–Ni according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
10 isotherms at 1300–900 °C with 50 °C intervals	[418, 456–459]
2 vertical sections at 75 at-% Ni and 50 at-% Al	[245, 456, 459–461]
Activity coefficient f_{Al}^{Ni} in liquid alloys at 1600 °C	[462, 463]
Heat of solution of Al in liquid alloys at 1600 °C	[464]
Gibbs energy of formation for bcc alloys at 1127 °C	[465]
Enthalpy of formation for bcc alloys at 800 °C	[466]
Enthalpy of formation for solid alloys at 25 °C	[467]

Table 88. The thermodynamic description of the Fe–Al–Ni system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al, Fe, Ni)</i>	
$L_{Al,Fe}^L = (-80800 + 15T) + (-5000 + 3T)(x_{Al} - x_{Fe}) + (+4500 - 4T)(x_{Al} - x_{Fe})^2$	IAD
$L_{Al,Ni}^L = (-206257 + 40.826T) + (-6759 + 3.932T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})$ $+ (+69168 - 24.759T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})^2 + (-4181 + 2.314T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})^3$	IAD
$L_{Fe,Ni}^L = (-16911 + 5.162T) + (+10180 - 4.147T)(x_{Fe} - x_{Ni})$	[5]
$L_{Al,Fe,Ni}^L = (+150000 - 120T)$	IAD
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al, Fe, Ni)</i>	
$L_{Al,Fe}^{bcc} = (-128300 + 35T) + (-13600 + 10T)(x_{Al} - x_{Fe})$	IAD
$L_{Al,Ni}^{bcc} = (-264500 - 119T + 23T \ln T) + (-107000 + 559T - 67T \ln T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})$ $+ (414000 - 800T + 95T \ln T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})^2$ $+ (-118000 + 970T - 99T \ln T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})^3$	[65]
$L_{Fe,Ni}^{bcc} = (-957 - 1.287T) + (+1789 - 1.929T)(x_{Fe} - x_{Ni})$	[45]
$L_{Al,Fe,Ni}^{bcc} = (-400000 + 80T)x_{Al} + (0)x_{Fe} + (+40000)x_{Ni}$	IAD
$T_c^{bcc} = 1043x_{Fe} + 575x_{Ni} + x_{Al}x_{Fe}(-1100(x_{Al} - x_{Fe}))$	IAD
$\beta^{bcc} = 2.22x_{Fe} + 0.85x_{Ni}$	[45]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al, Fe, Ni)</i>	
$L_{Al,Fe}^{fcc} = (-80000 + 16.4T) + (+22000)(x_{Al} - x_{Fe}) + (+6500)(x_{Al} - x_{Fe})^2$	IAD
$L_{Al,Ni}^{fcc} = (-162408 + 16.213T) + (73418 - 34.914T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})$ $+ (33471 - 9.837T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})^2 + (-30758 + 10.253T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})^3$	[26]
$L_{Fe,Ni}^{fcc} = (-12054 + 3.274T) + (+11082 - 4.45T)(x_{Fe} - x_{Ni}) + (-726)(x_{Fe} - x_{Ni})^2$	[45]
$L_{Al,Fe,Ni}^{fcc} = (-80000)x_{Al} + (-120000 + 20T)x_{Fe} + (+10000 - 40T)x_{Ni}$	IAD
$T_c^{fcc} = -201x_{Fe} + 633x_{Ni} + x_{Fe}x_{Ni}(2133 - 682(x_{Fe} - x_{Ni}))$	[45]
$\beta^{fcc} = -2.1x_{Fe} + 0.52x_{Ni} + x_{Fe}x_{Ni}(9.55 + 7.23(x_{Fe} - x_{Ni}))$ $+ 5.93(x_{Fe} - x_{Ni})^2 + 6.18(x_{Fe} - x_{Ni})^3$	[45]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

Table 88 (continued)

Equation	Reference
<i>AlNi₃</i> (γ') (2 sublattices, sites: 6:19, constituents: Al:Fe,Ni)	
$G_{\text{Al:Fe}}^{\circ,\gamma'} = 6G_{\text{Al}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 19G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + (-500000 + 60T)$	IAD
$G_{\text{Al:Ni}}^{\circ,\gamma'} = 6G_{\text{Al}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 19G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + (-1073000 + 525T - 50T \ln T)$	[65]
$L_{\text{Al:Fe,Ni}}^{\gamma'} = (-500000 + 60T)$	IAD
<i>Al₃Ni₅</i> (γ_3) (2 sublattices, sites: 3:5, constituents: Al:Ni)	
$G_{\text{Al:Ni}}^{\circ,\gamma_3} = 3G_{\text{Al}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 5G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + (-444064 + 52.304T)$	[65]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

4.4.2 Results

The results of the calculations according to the IAD together with the experimental data (Table 87) are presented in Figures 156–173. The agreement is reasonable. In Figures 159–166, note the experimental splitting of the bcc phase into its disordered (bcc) and ordered (bcc') part. This was correctly modeled by Zhang and Du [71] (with reasonable agreement), but it could not be traced by the calculations according to the IAD as the bcc ordering was not included in that description. The bcc splitting according to the IAD, finally, takes place between 950 °C and 900 °C (see Figure 166) though the resulting miscibility gap only tentatively reflects the ordering tendency of bcc (and not in the way the ordering should be modeled).

In Figure 167 note the wide experimental composition region of the AlNi₃ phase in regard to that of the calculated line compound, AlNi₃. Better agreement was obtained by Zhang and Du [71] by describing the disordered fcc phase and the ordered γ' phase (\approx AlNi₃) as one phase. The simpler treatment according to the IAD, however, was favored due to practical reasons.

Fig. 156. The calculated (IAD) liquidus projection in the Fe–Al–Ni system. Also shown by the dotted lines are the calculated liquidus isotherms between 1400 °C and 1600 °C.

Fig. 157. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1350 °C in the Fe–Al–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [456].

Fig. 158. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1300 °C in the Fe–Al–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [418, 458].

Fig. 159. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1250 °C in the Fe–Al–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [456].

Fig. 160. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1200 °C in the Fe–Al–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [459]. The experimental three-phase triangles are shown in grey.

Fig. 161. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1150 °C in the Fe–Al–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [456, 457].

Fig. 162. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1100 °C in the Fe–Al–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [418, 458, 459]. The experimental three-phase triangles are shown in grey.

Fig. 163. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1050 °C in the Fe–Al–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [456, 457].

Fig. 164. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1000 °C in the Fe–Al–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [418, 457–459]. The experimental three-phase triangles are shown in grey.

Fig. 165. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 950 °C in the Fe–Al–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [456, 457].

Fig. 166. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 900 °C in the Fe–Al–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [418, 457–459]. The experimental three-phase triangles are shown in grey.

Fig. 167. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 75 at-% Ni in the Fe–Al–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [459, 461].

Fig. 168. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 50 at-% Al in the Fe–Al–Ni system, together with the experimental data points (37Ale [245], 49Bra [456], and 80Sch [460]).

Fig. 169. The calculated activity coefficient f_{Al}^{Ni} in liquid Fe–Al–Ni alloys at 1600 °C, together with the experimental data points (95Cho [462] and 96Li [62]).

Fig. 170. The calculated (IAD) heat of solution of Al in liquid Fe–Al–Ni alloys at 1600 °C, together with the experimental data points [464]. The reference state used is pure liquid Al.

Fig. 171. The calculated (IAD) Gibbs energy of formation for bcc Fe–Al–Ni alloys at 1127 °C and with 50 at-% Al, together with the experimental data points (06Ben [465]). The reference states used are pure liquid Al and pure fcc Fe and Ni.

Fig. 172. The calculated (IAD) enthalpy of formation for bcc Fe–Al–Ni alloys at 800 °C, together with the experimental data points [466]. The reference states used are pure liquid Al, pure bcc Fe and pure fcc Ni.

Fig. 173. The calculated (IAD) enthalpy of formation for solid Fe–Al–Ni alloys at 25 °C, together with the experimental data points [467]. The reference states used are pure bcc Fe and pure fcc Al and Ni.

4.5 The Fe–Cr–Cu system

Experimental studies on the Fe–Cr–Cu system have been reviewed by Chang *et al.* [436] and Raghavan [468–470], and a thermodynamic assessment has been given by Ohtani *et al.* [67], Wang *et al.* [72], and Dreval *et al.* [73]. The system was later reassessed for the IAD as part of its binary data differs from the data by [67, 72, 73]. The present work reviews this description and presents its experimental verification.

4.5.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 89 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 90 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 91.

Table 89. Phases and their modeling in the Fe–Cr–Cu description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Cr,Cu,Fe), substitutional, RKM
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Cr,Cu,Fe), substitutional, RKM
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Cr,Cu,Fe), substitutional, RKM
Sigma (\approx σ)	(Fe) ₈ (Cr) ₄ (Cr,Fe) ₁₈ , sublattice, RKM

Note: RKM = Redlich–Kister–Muggianu excess model.

Table 90. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Fe–Cr–Cu according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
6 isotherms at 1300 °C, 1200 °C, 1100 °C, 1000 °C, 900 °C, and 800 °C	[67, 72, 471, 472]
Bcc and fcc ₁ solubility in Cu-rich fcc ₂ phase at 1050 °C and 900 °C	[8, 72, 280, 282, 473]
6 vertical sections at 2, 4, and 20 wt-% Cu and at 5, 10, and 14 wt-% Cr	[474, 475]
Activity coefficient $f_{\text{Cu}}^{\text{Cr}}$ in liquid alloys at 1600 °C	[476, 477]
Enthalpy of mixing for liquid alloys at 1050 °C	[73, 136, 139]

Table 91. The thermodynamic description of the Fe–Cr–Cu system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Cu,Fe)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Cu}^L = (+35500 - 3T) + (-1000)(x_{Cr} - x_{Cu}) + (+5500)(x_{Cr} - x_{Cu})^2$	IAD
$L_{Cr,Fe}^L = (-17737 + 7.997T) + (-1331)(x_{Cr} - x_{Fe})$	[5]
$L_{Cu,Fe}^L = (+35626 - 2.19T) + (-1530 + 1.153T)(x_{Cu} - x_{Fe})$ $+ (+12714 - 5.186T)(x_{Cu} - x_{Fe})^2 + (+1177)(x_{Cu} - x_{Fe})^3$	[9]
$L_{Cr,Cu,Fe}^L = (+90000 - 40T)x_{Cr} + (+90000 - 40T)x_{Cu} + (+110000 - 40T)x_{Fe}$	IAD
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Cu,Fe)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Cu}^{bcc} = (+70700 + 5T)$	IAD
$L_{Cr,Fe}^{bcc} = (+20500 - 9.68T)$	[4]
$L_{Cu,Fe}^{bcc} = (+39676 - 4.732T)$	[9]
$L_{Cr,Cu,Fe}^{bcc} = (-10000 - 8T)$	IAD
$T_c^{bcc} = 1043x_{Fe} - 311x_{Cr} + x_{Fe}x_{Cr}(1650 - 550(x_{Fe} - x_{Cr})) - 41.4x_{Fe}x_{Cu}$	[9]
$\beta^{bcc} = 2.22x_{Fe} - 0.008x_{Cr} - 0.85x_{Fe}x_{Cr}$	[4]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Cu,Fe)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Cu}^{fcc} = (+74700 - 20T)$	IAD
$L_{Cr,Fe}^{fcc} = (+10833 - 7.477T) + (+1410)(x_{Cr} - x_{Fe})$	[4]
$L_{Cu,Fe}^{fcc} = (+43320 - 6.944T) + (+6069 - 2.837T)(x_{Cu} - x_{Fe}) + (+3629)(x_{Cu} - x_{Fe})^2$	[9]
$L_{Cr,Cu,Fe}^{fcc} = (+10000)$	IAD
$T_c^{fcc} = -201x_{Fe} - 1109x_{Cr}$	[96]
$\beta^{fcc} = -2.1x_{Fe} - 2.46x_{Cr}$	[96]
<i>Sigma (σ) (3 sublattices, sites: 8:4:18, constituents: Fe:Cr:Cr,Fe)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Cr:Cr}^{\sigma} = 8G_{Fe}^{\sigma,fcc} + 22G_{Cr}^{\sigma,bcc} + (+92300 - 95.96T)$	[4]
$G_{Fe:Cr:Fe}^{\sigma} = 8G_{Fe}^{\sigma,fcc} + 4G_{Cr}^{\sigma,bcc} + 18G_{Fe}^{\sigma,bcc} + (+117300 - 95.96T)$	[4]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

4.5.2 Results

The results of the calculations according to the IAD together with the experimental data (Table 90) are presented in Figures 174–189 and Table 92. The agreement is reasonably good. Due to the miscibility gaps of the liquid and fcc phases, the optimization of the system was quite difficult requiring a careful selection of the starting values (compositions) for the calculations. Due to these difficulties, no trials were made to recalculate the results of the earlier descriptions [67, 72, 73]. For the phase equilibria shown by these studies, however, the results are quite similar.

The liquidus projection in Figure 174 correlates reasonably well with that calculated by Dreval *et al.* [73], though the latter is a bit closer to the Cu–Cr side of the system and its critical point (1582 °C, 54 wt-% Cu, 28 wt-% Cr) is somewhat different from that

according to the IAD (1617 °C, 42 wt-% Cu, 20 wt-% Cr). Another point worth noting is that Dreval *et al.* [73] obtained better agreement for the measured mixing enthalpies of the liquid phase, shown in Figure 189. This is mainly due to their different binary Fe–Cu and Cr–Cu descriptions from those according to the IAD yielding quite different "starting enthalpies" for the calculation of the mixing enthalpy in ternary Fe–Cr–Cu alloys.

Concerning the vertical sections of Figures 182–187, one can notice the somewhat higher stability of the fcc phase in the measurements by Moriwaki [474] and Ahmed *et al.* [475]. On the other hand, the impurities in the alloys studied by Moriwaki [474] were quite high (up to 0.1 wt-%C, 0.2 wt-% Mn, 0.5 wt-% Si, 0.02 wt-% P and 0.03 wt-% S), which have certainly affected the results. Carbides detected by Moriwaki [474], for example, indicate that the fcc phase may have been stabilized by carbon before it bound to carbides at low temperatures.

Table 92. The calculated (IAD) invariant points of the Fe–Cr–Cu system.

Reaction	Code	Temp. [°C]	Cr in Liq [wt-%]	Cu in Liq [wt-%]
$L_1 + fcc_1 = L_2 + bcc$	U ₁	1439	18.73	10.25
$L_2 + fcc_1 = bcc + fcc_2$	U ₂	1090	0.485	97.25
$L_1 + L_2 + fcc_1 = bcc$	U ₃	1439	77.51	2.25

Fig. 174. The calculated (IAD) liquidus projection in the Fe–Cr–Cu system. Also shown by the dotted lines are the calculated liquidus isotherms between 1800 °C and 1100 °C.

Fig. 175. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1300 °C in the Fe–Cr–Cu system, together with the experimental data points [67].

Fig. 176. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1200 °C in the Fe–Cr–Cu system, together with the experimental data points [67].

Fig. 177. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1100 °C in the Fe–Cr–Cu system, together with the experimental data points [67,471].

Fig. 178. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1000 °C in the Fe–Cr–Cu system, together with the experimental data points by Jiang and Hao [472] for the bcc phase and Wang *et al.* [72] for the fcc₁+fcc₂ equilibria.

Fig. 179. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 900 °C in the Fe–Cr–Cu system, together with the experimental data points [72].

Fig. 180. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 800 °C in the Fe–Cr–Cu system, together with the experimental data points [72].

Fig. 181. The calculated (IAD) solubilities of fcc_1 and bcc phases in the Cu-rich fcc_2 phase at 1050 °C and 900 °C, together with the experimental data points (57Doi [280], 75Dri [282], 94Swa [8], 01Fer [473], and 02Wan [72]).

Fig. 182. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 2 wt-% Cu in the Fe–Cr–Cu system, together with the experimental data points [474, 475].

Fig. 183. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 4 wt-% Cu in the Fe–Cr–Cu system, together with the experimental data points [474, 475].

Fig. 184. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 20 wt-% Cu in the Fe–Cr–Cu system, together with the experimental data points [474].

Fig. 185. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 5 wt-% Cr in the Fe–Cr–Cu system, together with the experimental data points [474].

Fig. 186. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 10 wt-% Cr in the Fe–Cr–Cu system, together with the experimental data points [474].

Fig. 187. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 14 wt-% Cr in the Fe–Cr–Cu system, together with the experimental data points [474].

Fig. 188. The calculated (IAD) activity coefficient f_{Cu}^{Cr} in liquid Fe–Cr–Cu alloys at 1600 °C, together with smoothed experimental data points (59Sch [476] and 74Sig [477]).

Fig. 189. The calculated (IAD) enthalpy of mixing for liquid Fe–Cr–Cu alloys at 1600 °C, together with the experimental data points [73]. The reference states used are pure liquid components

4.6 The Fe–Cr–Mn system

Experimental studies on the Fe–Cr–Mn system have been reviewed by Raynor and Rivlin [478] and Raghavan [479, 480], while a thermodynamic assessment has been given by Lee [30]. The description by Lee [30] was later modified for use in the IAD to improve the agreement between the calculated and experimental phase equilibria at high Mn contents. That improvement, however, remained more or less cosmetic. The present work reviews the Fe–Cr–Mn description according to the IAD and presents its experimental verification.

4.6.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 93 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 94 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 95.

Table 93. Phases and their modeling in the Fe–Cr–Mn description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Cr,Fe,Mn), substitutional, RKM
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Cr,Fe,Mn), substitutional, RKM
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Cr,Fe,Mn), substitutional, RKM
cbcc_A12 (\approx cbcc)	(Cr,Fe,Mn), substitutional, RKM
cub_A13 (\approx cub)	(Cr,Fe,Mn), substitutional, RKM
Sigma (\approx σ)	(Fe,Mn) ₈ (Cr) ₄ (Fe,Cr,Mn) ₁₈ , sublattice, RKM
Sigma-H (\approx σ H, high-temp. sigma)	(Fe,Mn) ₈ (Cr) ₄ (Fe,Cr,Mn) ₁₈ , sublattice, RKM
Cr ₃ Mn ₅ (\approx α')	(Cr) ₃ (Mn) ₅ , stoichiometric

Note: RKM = Redlich–Kister–Muggianu excess model.

Table 94. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Fe–Cr–Mn according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Liquidus temperatures of Fe-rich alloys	[86]
9 isothermal sections at 1511 °C, 1503 °C, 1200 °C, 1100 °C, 1000 °C, 900 °C, 850 °C, 800 °C, and 650 °C	[481–489]
2 vertical sections at 6 and 16 wt-% Mn	[482]
Activity coefficient γ_{Mn}^{Cr} in liquid alloys at 1570 °C	[490]

Table 95. The thermodynamic description of the Fe–Cr–Mn system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Fe,Mn)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Fe}^L = (-17737 + 7.997T) + (-1331)(x_{Cr} - x_{Fe})$	[5]
$L_{Cr,Mn}^L = (-15009 + 13.659T) + (+504 + 0.948T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Mn})$	[30]
$L_{Fe,Mn}^L = (-3950 + 0.489T) + (1145)(x_{Fe} - x_{Mn})$	[491]
$L_{Cr,Fe,Mn}^L = (+2000)$	IAD
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Fe,Mn)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Fe}^{bcc} = (+20500 - 9.68T)$	[4]
$L_{Cr,Mn}^{bcc} = (-20328 + 18.734T) + (-9162 + 4.418T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Mn})$	[30]
$L_{Fe,Mn}^{bcc} = (-2759 + 1.237T)$	[491]
$L_{Cr,Fe,Mn}^{bcc} = (-6500)$	IAD
$T_c^{bcc} = 1043x_{Fe} - 311x_{Cr} - 580x_{Mn} + x_{Fe}x_{Mn}(123) + x_{Fe}x_{Cr}(1650 + 550(x_{Cr} - x_{Fe}))$	IAD
$+ x_{Cr}x_{Mn}(-1350 - 1350(x_{Cr} - x_{Mn})^2 - 2400(x_{Cr} - x_{Mn})^3)$	IAD
$\beta^{bcc} = 2.22x_{Fe} - 0.008x_{Cr} - 0.27x_{Mn} - 0.85x_{Fe}x_{Cr} + x_{Cr}x_{Mn}(0.5 - 1.9(x_{Cr} - x_{Mn})^2)$	IAD

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

Table 95 (continued).

Equation	Reference
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Fe,Mn)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Fe}^{fcc} = (+10833 - 7.477T) + (+1410)(x_{Cr} - x_{Fe})$	[4]
$L_{Cr,Mn}^{fcc} = (-19088 + 17.542T)$	[30]
$L_{Fe,Mn}^{fcc} = (-7762 + 3.865T) + (-259)(x_{Fe} - x_{Mn})$	[491]
$L_{Cr,Fe,Mn}^{fcc} = (5000 - 10T)x_{Fe} + (10000)x_{Cr} + (-15000 - 10T)x_{Mn}$	IAD
$T_c^{fcc} = -201x_{Fe} - 1109x_{Cr} - 1620x_{Mn} + x_{Fe}x_{Mn}(-2282 - 2068(x_{Fe} - x_{Mn}))$	[491]
$\beta^{fcc} = -2.1x_{Fe} - 2.46x_{Cr} - 1.86x_{Mn}$	[491]
<i>cbcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Fe,Mn)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Mn}^{cbcc} = (-38349 + 22.693T)$	[30]
$L_{Fe,Mn}^{cbcc} = (-10184)$	[491]
<i>cub (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Fe,Mn)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Mn}^{cub} = (-31260 + 16.492T)$	[30]
$L_{Fe,Mn}^{cub} = (-11518 + 2.819T)$	[491]
<i>Sigma-High (σ^H) (3 sublattices, sites: 8:4:18, constituents: Fe,Mn:Cr:Cr,Fe,Mn)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Cr:Cr}^{\sigma^H} = 8G_{Fe}^{\sigma, fcc} + 22G_{Cr}^{\sigma, bcc} + (+92300 - 95.96T)$	[30]
$G_{Fe:Cr:Fe}^{\sigma^H} = 8G_{Fe}^{\sigma, fcc} + 4G_{Cr}^{\sigma, bcc} + 18G_{Fe}^{\sigma, bcc} + (+117300 - 95.96T)$	[30]
$G_{Fe:Cr:Mn}^{\sigma^H} = 8G_{Fe}^{\sigma, fcc} + 4G_{Cr}^{\sigma, bcc} + 18G_{Mn}^{\sigma, bcc} + (-15321 - 36.94T)$	[30]
$G_{Mn:Cr:Cr}^{\sigma^H} = 8G_{Mn}^{\sigma, fcc} + 22G_{Cr}^{\sigma, bcc} + (-192369 + 152.4742T)$	[30]
$G_{Mn:Cr:Fe}^{\sigma^H} = 8G_{Mn}^{\sigma, fcc} + 4G_{Cr}^{\sigma, bcc} + 18G_{Fe}^{\sigma, bcc} + (-65212 - 69.729T)$	[30]
$G_{Mn:Cr:Mn}^{\sigma^H} = 8G_{Mn}^{\sigma, fcc} + 4G_{Cr}^{\sigma, bcc} + 18G_{Mn}^{\sigma, bcc} + (-74263 - 10.7082T)$	[30]
$L_{Fe:Cr:Cr,Mn}^{\sigma^H} = (+77000)$	IAD
$L_{Mn:Cr:Cr,Mn}^{\sigma^H} = (+90000)$	[30]
<i>Sigma (σ) (3 sublattices, sites: 8:4:18, constituents: Fe,Mn:Cr:Cr,Fe,Mn)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Cr:Cr}^{\sigma} = 8G_{Fe}^{\sigma, fcc} + 22G_{Cr}^{\sigma, bcc} + (+92300 - 95.96T)$	[4]
$G_{Fe:Cr:Fe}^{\sigma} = 8G_{Fe}^{\sigma, fcc} + 4G_{Cr}^{\sigma, bcc} + 18G_{Fe}^{\sigma, bcc} + (+117300 - 95.96T)$	[4]
$G_{Mn:Cr:Mn}^{\sigma} = 8G_{Mn}^{\sigma, fcc} + 4G_{Cr}^{\sigma, bcc} + 18G_{Mn}^{\sigma, bcc} + (-172946 + 69.0245T)$	[30]
$G_{Mn:Cr:Cr}^{\sigma} = 8G_{Mn}^{\sigma, fcc} + 22G_{Cr}^{\sigma, bcc} + (+65859.5)$	[30]
$G_{Fe:Cr:Mn}^{\sigma} = 8G_{Fe}^{\sigma, fcc} + 4G_{Cr}^{\sigma, bcc} + 18G_{Mn}^{\sigma, bcc} + (-83640 + 18.26T)$	[30]
$G_{Mn:Cr:Fe}^{\sigma} = 8G_{Mn}^{\sigma, fcc} + 4G_{Cr}^{\sigma, bcc} + 18G_{Fe}^{\sigma, bcc} + (-95576 - 45.2T)$	[30]
$L_{Fe:Cr:Cr,Mn}^{\sigma} = (-900000 + 683T)$	IAD
$L_{Mn:Cr:Cr,Mn}^{\sigma} = (-1095771 + 862.0312T)$	[30]
<i>Cr₃Mn₅ (α') (2 sublattices, sites: 3:5, constituents: Cr,Mn)</i>	
$G_{Cr:Mn}^{\sigma, \alpha} = 3G_{Cr}^{\sigma, bcc} + 5G_{Mn}^{\sigma, cbcc} + (-72550 + 21.173T)$	[30]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

4.6.2 Results

The results of the calculations according to the IAD and Lee [30] together with the experimental data (Table 94) are presented in Figures 190–203. The agreement is reason-

ably good in both calculations. In Figures 193–198, note the slightly better agreement according to the IAD for the phase equilibria at high Mn contents. In Figures 200 and 201, the overall agreement is not so good. One reason may be that the Mn contents of the alloys in these sections were not exactly 6 and 16 wt-% Mn. This variation (6.2–7 wt-% Mn and 14.6–18.5 wt-% Mn), however, is too small to explain the inconsistencies at low temperatures. Trials were made to improve this disagreement but with no success. A slight improvement was obtained only after introducing very strong and "dangerous" ternary interaction parameters.

Fig. 190. The calculated (IAD) liquidus projection in the Fe–Cr–Mn system. Also shown by the dotted lines are the calculated liquidus isotherms between 1900 °C and 1300 °C.

Fig. 191. The calculated liquidus temperatures in Fe-rich Fe–Cr–Mn alloys, together with the experimental data points (86Kun [86]). The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [30].

Fig. 192. The calculated Fe-rich isotherms 1511 °C and 1503 °C of the Fe–Cr–Mn system, together with the experimental data points (86Kun [86]). The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [30].

Fig. 193. The calculated isotherm of 1200 °C in the Fe–Cr–Mn system, together with the experimental data points [482, 486]. The experimental boundary points were read from the diagram by Okazaki *et al.* [486]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [30].

Fig. 194. The calculated isotherm of 1100 °C in the Fe–Cr–Mn system, together with the experimental data points [482, 489]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [30].

Fig. 195. The calculated isotherm of 1000 °C in the Fe–Cr–Mn system, together with the experimental data points [482,489]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [30].

Fig. 196. The calculated isotherm of 900 °C in the Fe–Cr–Mn system, together with the experimental data points [482, 483, 489]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [30].

Fig. 197. The calculated isotherm of 850 °C in the Fe–Cr–Mn system, together with the experimental data points [483, 484]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [30].

Fig. 198. The calculated isotherm of 800 °C in the Fe–Cr–Mn system, together with the experimental data points [483, 489]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [30].

Fig. 199. The calculated isotherm of 650 °C in the Fe–Cr–Mn system, together with the experimental data points (88Abe [485] and 89Oka2 [487]). The broken lines show the experimental fcc/fcc+sigma boundaries (38Bur [481] and 90Mur [488]). The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [30].

Fig. 200. The calculated vertical section of 6 wt-% Mn in the Fe–Cr–Mn system, together with the experimental data points [482]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [30].

Fig. 201. The calculated vertical section of 16 wt-% Mn in the Fe–Cr–Mn system, together with the experimental data points [482]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [30].

Fig. 202. The calculated activity coefficient γ_{Mn}^{Cr} in liquid Fe–Cr–Mn alloys at 1570 °C, together with smoothed experimental data points (75Muk [490]). The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [30].

Fig. 203. The calculated Cr and Mn contents in the Sigma phase of Fe-16 at-% Cr-xMn alloys at 700 °C, together with smoothed experimental data points [487]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [30].

4.7 The Fe-Cr-Mo system

Experimental studies on the Fe-Cr-Mo system have been reviewed by Raynor and Rivlin [492] and Raghavan [493], while a thermodynamic assessment has been given by Andersson [32] and Kroupa [74]. The system was later reassessed for use in the IAD to get better agreement between the experimental and calculated phase equilibria including the liquid and bcc phases. The present work reviews this description and presents its experimental verification.

4.7.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 96 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 97 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 98. Note that the Fe_2Mo phase is formulated as $(\text{Fe,Cr})_2\text{Mo}$ as it refers to the same Laves phase formulated as $(\text{Fe,Cr})_2\text{Ti}$ and $\text{Fe}_2(\text{Mo,Ti})$ in the Fe-Cr-Ti and Fe-Mo-Ti descriptions according to the IAD and Jin and Qiu [161], respectively. The treatment according to the IAD allows slight solubility of Cr in the Fe_2Mo phase, which was accepted as no experimental data denies such solubility.

Table 96. Phases and their modeling in the Fe–Cr–Mo description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Cr,Fe,M), substitutional, RKM
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Cr,Fe,Mo), substitutional, RKM
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Cr,Fe,Mo), substitutional, RKM
Chi (\approx χ)	(Cr,Fe) ₂₄ (Cr,Mo) ₁₀ (Cr,Fe,Mo) ₂₄ , sublattice, RKM
Mu (\approx μ)	(Cr,Fe) ₇ (Mo) ₂ (Cr,Fe,Mo) ₄ , sublattice, RKM
R	(Cr,Fe) ₂₇ (Mo) ₁₄ (Cr,Fe,Mo) ₁₂ , sublattice, RKM
Sigma (\approx σ)	(Fe) ₈ (Cr,Mo) ₄ (Cr,Fe,Mo) ₁₈ , sublattice, RKM
Fe ₂ Mo (\approx λ , dissolving Cr)	(Cr,Fe) ₂ (Mo), sublattice, RKM

Note: RKM = Redlich–Kister–Muggianu excess model.

Table 97. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Fe–Cr–Mo according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Liquidus projection	[494]
5 vertical sections at 10 wt-% Cr and Mo, and at $w_{\text{Mo}}:w_{\text{Cr}} = 3:2$, 1:2 and 1:5	[102, 494, 495]
7 isothermal sections at 1300 °C, 1200 °C, 1100 °C, 1050 °C, 1000 °C, 950 °C, and 800 °C	[32, 102, 496, 497]
Activity coefficient $\gamma_{\text{Mo}}^{\text{Cr}}$ in liquid alloys at 1600 °C	[477, 498] (theoretical)

Table 98. The thermodynamic description of the Fe–Cr–Mo system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Fe,Mo)</i>	
$L_{\text{Cr,Fe}}^{\text{L}} = (-17737 + 7.997T) + (-1331)(x_{\text{Cr}} - x_{\text{Fe}})$	[5]
$L_{\text{Cr,Mo}}^{\text{L}} = (+15810 - 6.714T) + (-9220)(x_{\text{Cr}} - x_{\text{Mo}})$	IAD
$L_{\text{Fe,Mo}}^{\text{L}} = (-6900 - 0.23T) + (-9000 + 3.85T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Mo}})$	IAD
$L_{\text{Cr,Fe,Mo}}^{\text{L}} = (-10000)x_{\text{Cr}} + (0)x_{\text{Fe}} + (-99000)x_{\text{Mo}}$	IAD
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Fe,Mo)</i>	
$L_{\text{Cr,Fe}}^{\text{bcc}} = (+20500 - 9.68T)$	[4]
$L_{\text{Cr,Mo}}^{\text{bcc}} = (+28890 - 7.962T) + (+5974 - 2.428T)(x_{\text{Cr}} - x_{\text{Mo}})$	[32]
$L_{\text{Fe,Mo}}^{\text{bcc}} = (+36818 - 9.141T) + (-362 - 5.724T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Mo}})$	[13]
$L_{\text{Cr,Fe,Mo}}^{\text{bcc}} = (+15000 - 12T)$	IAD
$T_{\text{c}}^{\text{bcc}} = 1043x_{\text{Fe}} - 311x_{\text{Cr}} + x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Cr}}(1650 - 550(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Cr}}))$ $+ x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Mo}}(335 + 526(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Mo}}))$	[32]
$\beta^{\text{bcc}} = 2.22x_{\text{Fe}} - 0.008x_{\text{Cr}} - 0.85x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Cr}}$	[32]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

Table 98 (continued)

Equation	Reference
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Fe,Mo)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Fe}^{fcc} = (+10833 - 7.477T) + (+1410)(x_{Cr} - x_{Fe})$	[4]
$L_{Cr,Mo}^{fcc} = L_{Cr,Mo}^{bcc}$	[301]
$L_{Fe,Mo}^{fcc} = (+28347 - 17.691T)$	[13]
$T_c^{fcc} = -201x_{Fe} - 1109x_{Cr}$	[32]
$\beta^{fcc} = -2.1x_{Fe} - 2.46x_{Cr}$	[32]
<i>Chi (χ) (3 sublattices, sites: 24:10:24, constituents: Cr,Fe:Cr,Mo:Cr,Fe,Mo)</i>	
$G_{Cr:Cr:Cr}^{\circ,\chi} = 48G_{Cr}^{\circ,fcc} + 10G_{Cr}^{\circ,bcc} + (+109000 + 123T)$	[32]
$G_{Cr:Cr:Fe}^{\circ,\chi} = 24G_{Cr}^{\circ,fcc} + 10G_{Cr}^{\circ,bcc} + 24oG_{fccFe} + (+500000)$	[32]
$G_{Cr:Cr:Mo}^{\circ,\chi} = 24G_{Cr}^{\circ,fcc} + 10G_{Cr}^{\circ,bcc} + 24G_{Mo}^{\circ,fcc} + (+500000)$	[32]
$G_{Cr:Mo:Cr}^{\circ,\chi} = 24G_{Cr}^{\circ,fcc} + 10G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 24G_{Cr}^{\circ,fcc} + (-26000)$	[32]
$G_{Cr:Mo:Fe}^{\circ,\chi} = 24G_{Cr}^{\circ,fcc} + 10G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 24G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + (+500000)$	[32]
$G_{Cr:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,\chi} = 24G_{Cr}^{\circ,fcc} + 10G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 24G_{Mo}^{\circ,fcc} + (+500000)$	[32]
$G_{Fe:Cr:Cr}^{\circ,\chi} = 24G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 10G_{Cr}^{\circ,bcc} + 24G_{Cr}^{\circ,fcc} + (+18300 - 100T)$	[32]
$G_{Fe:Cr:Fe}^{\circ,\chi} = 48G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 10G_{Cr}^{\circ,bcc} + (+57300 - 100T)$	[32]
$G_{Fe:Cr:Mo}^{\circ,\chi} = 24G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 10G_{Cr}^{\circ,bcc} + 24G_{Mo}^{\circ,fcc} + (+100000)$	[32]
$G_{Fe:Mo:Cr}^{\circ,\chi} = 24G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 10G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 24G_{Cr}^{\circ,fcc} + (+5000 - 365T)$	IAD
$G_{Fe:Mo:Fe}^{\circ,\chi} = 48G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 10G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+305210 - 270T)$	[32]
$G_{Fe:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,\chi} = 24G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 10G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 24G_{Mo}^{\circ,fcc} + (+97300 - 100T)$	[32]
<i>Mu (μ) (3 sublattices, sites: 7:2:4, constituents: Cr,Fe:Mo:Cr,Fe,Mo)</i>	
$G_{Cr:Mo:Cr}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{Cr}^{\circ,fcc} + 2G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 4G_{Cr}^{\circ,bcc} + (+130000 - 100T)$	[32]
$G_{Cr:Mo:Fe}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{Cr}^{\circ,fcc} + 2G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 4G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (+130000 - 100T)$	[32]
$G_{Cr:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{Cr}^{\circ,fcc} + 6G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+130000 - 100T)$	[32]
$G_{Fe:Mo:Cr}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 2G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 4G_{Cr}^{\circ,bcc} + (+130000 - 100T)$	[32]
$G_{Fe:Mo:Fe}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 2G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 4G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (+39475 - 6.032T)$	[13]
$G_{Fe:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 6G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (-46663 - 5.891T)$	[13]
$L_{Cr,Fe:Mo:Mo}^{\mu} = (-45000)$	[32]
<i>R (3 sublattices, sites: 27:14:12, constituents: Cr,Fe:Mo:Cr,Fe,Mo)</i>	
$G_{Cr:Mo:Cr}^{\circ,R} = 27G_{Cr}^{\circ,fcc} + 14G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 12G_{Cr}^{\circ,bcc} + (-20000)$	[32]
$G_{Cr:Mo:Fe}^{\circ,R} = 27G_{Cr}^{\circ,fcc} + 14G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 12G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (+618000 - 600T)$	IAD
$G_{Cr:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,R} = 27G_{Cr}^{\circ,fcc} + 26G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (-20000)$	[32]
$G_{Fe:Mo:Cr}^{\circ,R} = 27G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 14G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 12G_{Cr}^{\circ,bcc} + (+573000 - 600T)$	IAD
$G_{Fe:Mo:Fe}^{\circ,R} = 27G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 14G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 12G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (-77487 - 50.486T)$	[13]
$G_{Fe:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,R} = 27G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 26G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+313474 - 289.472T)$	[13]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

Table 98 (continued)

Equation	Reference
<i>Sigma</i> (σ) (3 sublattices, sites: 8:4:18, constituents: Fe:Cr,Mo:Cr,Fe,Mo)	
$G_{\text{Fe:Cr:Cr}}^{\sigma} = 8G_{\text{Fe}}^{\text{fcc}} + 22G_{\text{Cr}}^{\text{bcc}} + (+92300 - 95.96T)$	[4]
$G_{\text{Fe:Cr:Fe}}^{\sigma} = 8G_{\text{Fe}}^{\text{fcc}} + 4G_{\text{Cr}}^{\text{bcc}} + 18G_{\text{Fe}}^{\text{bcc}} + (+117300 - 95.96T)$	[4]
$G_{\text{Fe:Cr:Mo}}^{\sigma} = 8G_{\text{Fe}}^{\text{fcc}} + 4G_{\text{Cr}}^{\text{bcc}} + 18G_{\text{Mo}}^{\text{bcc}} + (+285000 - 240T)$	[32]
$G_{\text{Fe:Mo:Cr}}^{\sigma} = 8G_{\text{Fe}}^{\text{fcc}} + 4G_{\text{Mo}}^{\text{bcc}} + 18G_{\text{Cr}}^{\text{bcc}} + (+460000 - 340T)$	[32]
$G_{\text{Fe:Mo:Fe}}^{\sigma} = 8G_{\text{Fe}}^{\text{fcc}} + 4G_{\text{Mo}}^{\text{bcc}} + 18G_{\text{Fe}}^{\text{bcc}} + (-1813 - 27.272T)$	[13]
$G_{\text{Fe:Mo:Mo}}^{\sigma} = 8G_{\text{Fe}}^{\text{fcc}} + 22G_{\text{Mo}}^{\text{bcc}} + (+83326 - 69.618T)$	[13]
$L_{\text{Fe:Cr:Cr,Mo}}^{\sigma} = (-148000)$	[32]
$L_{\text{Fe:Cr:Fe,Mo}}^{\sigma} = (+570000)$	[32]
$L_{\text{Fe:Mo:Cr,Mo}}^{\sigma} = (+121000)$	[32]
$L_{\text{Fe:Mo:Fe,Mo}}^{\sigma} = (+222909)$	[13]
<i>Fe₂Mo</i> (λ) (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents: Cr,Fe:Mo)	
$G_{\text{Fe:Mo}}^{\lambda} = 2G_{\text{Fe}}^{\text{fcc}} + G_{\text{Mo}}^{\text{bcc}} + (-10798 - 0.132T)$	[161]
$G_{\text{Cr:Mo}}^{\lambda} = 2G_{\text{Cr}}^{\text{bcc}} + G_{\text{Mo}}^{\text{bcc}}$	IAD

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

4.7.2 Results

The results of the calculations according to the IAD as well as those by Andersson and Lange [32] together with the experimental data (Table 97) are presented in Figures 204–218. The agreement is reasonably good in both calculations.

In Figure 205, note the better agreement according to the IAD for the bcc region (bcc more stable) but the worse agreement for the R/Sigma boundary. For the eutectic reaction, $L = \text{bcc} + \text{Sigma} + \text{R}$, (point E1 in Figure 205) the IAD and [32] yield the following temperature and liquid composition values (the latter given in parenthesis): 1434 (1471) °C, 13.2 (10.8) wt-% Cr and 27.2 (24.8) wt-% Mo. According to Takeda and Yukawa [494], the Chi (χ) phase instead of Sigma is present in the reaction, and the corresponding temperature and liquid composition values are 1345 °C, 11 wt-% Cr and 30 wt-% Mo. Note the much lower eutectic temperature by Takeda and Yukawa [494] in regard to that in both calculations. Note also that according to Jansson and Lange [32], the Chi phase is not stable at temperatures above 1200 °C, though according to Jin [499], this could still be possible.

In Figures 206–210, note the better agreement according to the IAD for the bcc and liquid phase regions (Figures 206 and 207) and the slight mismatch with the experimental data suggesting stronger stability for the fcc phase at low temperatures (Fig-

ures 208–210). Additional data, for the isothermal sections of 1200 °C and 1100 °C, are available from Jin [499]. This data agrees reasonably well with both calculations, though it indicates a stronger stability for the Chi phase.

Some further data are also available from Cao and Zhao [497], at 1200 °C, 900 °C, and 700 °C, and not only at 800 °C in Figure 216. These data also agree reasonably well with the calculations, though there are also some differences concerning the stability of the intermediate phases (Chi, Mu, R, Sigma) and their solubility in the bcc phase. However, as the most part of the present Fe–Cr–Mo description was fixed before the appearance of Cao and Zhao [497] and already applied in higher-order assessments used in the IAD, no further optimizations are made here to improve the present Fe–Cr–Mo description, at least for a while.

Fig. 204. The calculated (IAD) liquidus projection of the Fe–Cr–Mo system. Also shown by the dotted lines are the calculated liquidus isotherms between 2400 °C and 1450 °C.

Fig. 205. The Fe-rich portion of the calculated liquidus projection of the Fe–Cr–Mo system, together with the experimental data points [494]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Andersson and Lange [32].

Fig. 206. The calculated vertical section of 10 wt-% Cr in the Fe–Cr–Mo system, together with the experimental data points [102,494]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Andersson and Lange [32].

Fig. 207. The calculated vertical section of 10 wt-% Mo in the Fe–Cr–Mo system, together with the experimental data points [102, 494]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Andersson and Lange [32].

Fig. 208. The calculated vertical section of $w_{Mo}:w_{Cr} = 3:2$ in the Fe-rich corner of the Fe–Cr–Mo system, together with the experimental data points [495]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Andersson and Lange [32].

Fig. 209. The calculated vertical section of $w_{Mo}:w_{Cr} = 1:2$ in the Fe-rich corner of the Fe-Cr-Mo system, together with the experimental data points [495]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Andersson and Lange [32].

Fig. 210. The calculated vertical section of $w_{Mo}:w_{Cr} = 1:5$ in the Fe-rich corner of the Fe-Cr-Mo system, together with the experimental data points [495]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Andersson and Lange [32].

Fig. 211. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1300 °C in the Fe–Cr–Mo system, together with the primary surfaces (51Put [102]) shown with dotted lines.

Fig. 212. The calculated isotherm of 1200 °C in the Fe–Cr–Mo system, together with the experimental data points indicating tie-line ends [32]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Andersson and Lange [32]

Fig. 213. The calculated isotherm of 1100 °C in the Fe–Cr–Mo system, together with the experimental data points indicating tie-line ends [32]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Andersson and Lange [32].

Fig. 214. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1000 °C in the Fe–Cr–Mo system, together with the experimental data points indicating tie-line ends [32]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Andersson and Lange [32].

Fig. 215. The calculated isotherm of 950 °C in the Fe–Cr–Mo system, together with the experimental data points indicating tie-line ends [32]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Andersson and Lange [32]

Fig. 216. The calculated isotherm of 800 °C in the Fe–Cr–Mo system, together with the experimental data points indicating tie-line ends [497]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Andersson and Lange [32]

Fig. 217. The calculated isotherm of 1050 °C in the Fe-rich corner of the Fe–Cr–Mo system, together with the experimental data points [496]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Andersson and Lange [32]

Fig. 218. The calculated activity coefficient γ_{Mo}^{Cr} in liquid Fe–Cr–Mo alloys at 1600 °C, together with smoothed experimental (74Sig [477]) and theoretical ([498]) data points. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Andersson and Lange [32].

4.8 The Fe–Cr–Ni system

Experimental studies on the Fe–Cr–Ni system have been reviewed by Raynor and Rivlin [500], Raghavan [501, 502], and Cao and Zhao [503] and thermodynamic assessments have been given by Hillert and Qiu [75], Lee [5], Miettinen [76], Tomiska [77], and by using the IAD. The IAD slightly modifies the description by Miettinen [76] to get a better description of the bcc and sigma phases. The present work reviews the Fe–Cr–Ni description according to the IAD and presents its experimental verification.

4.8.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 99 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 100 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 101.

Table 99. Phases and their modeling in the Fe–Cr–Ni description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Cr,Fe,Ni), substitutional, RKM
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Cr,Fe,Ni), substitutional, RKM
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Cr,Fe,Ni), substitutional, RKM
Sigma (\approx σ)	(Fe,Ni) ₈ (Cr) ₄ (Fe,Cr,Ni) ₁₈ , sublattice, RKM

Note: RKM = Redlich–Kister–Muggianu excess model.

Table 100. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Fe–Cr–Ni according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Liquidus projection	[109, 504, 505]
Fe content of liquid along the L / bcc+fcc line	[109, 311, 495, 504]
Liquidus isotherms between 1525 °C and 1450 °C	[109, 164, 504–506]
Bcc+Fcc+Liq triangles at 1480 °C, 1470 °C, and 1460 °C	[504]
9 vertical sections at 2–18 wt-% Ni	[109, 505, 506]
11 isothermal sections at 1400 °C, 1350 °C, 1300 °C, 1250 °C, 1200 °C, 1100 °C, 1000 °C, 900 °C, 850 °C, 800 °C, and 650 °C	[503, 507–517]
Fcc/L and Bcc/L partition of Cr and Ni	[109, 504, 505, 518]

Table 100 (continued)

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Activity of Fe, Cr, and Ni in liquid alloys at 1600 °C	[116, 519]
Activity of Fe, Cr, and Ni in solid alloys at 1227 °C	[520]
Activity of Cr in solid alloys at 1200–900 °C	[322, 521]
Enthalpy of formation for solid alloys at 1292 °C	[178]
Liquidus and solidus temperatures of Fe–Cr–Ni–C–Si alloys containing 0.04 wt-% C and 0.4 wt-% Si (max.)	[495]

Table 101. The thermodynamic description of the Fe–Cr–Ni system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr, Fe, Ni)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Fe}^L = (-17737 + 7.997T) + (-1331)(x_{Cr} - x_{Fe})$	[5]
$L_{Cr,Ni}^L = (+318 - 7.332T) + (+16941 - 6.37T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Ni})$	[34]
$L_{Fe,Ni}^L = (-16911 + 5.162T) + (+10180 - 4.147T)(x_{Fe} - x_{Ni})$	[5]
$L_{Cr,Fe,Ni}^L = (+140000 - 50T)x_{Cr} + (+100000 - 50T)x_{Fe} + (+80000 - 50T)x_{Ni}$	[76]
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr, Fe, Ni)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Fe}^{bcc} = (+20500 - 9.68T)$	[4]
$L_{Cr,Ni}^{bcc} = (+17170 - 11.82T) + (+34418 - 11.858T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Ni})$	[34]
$L_{Fe,Ni}^{bcc} = (-957 - 1.287T) + (+1789 - 1.929T)(x_{Fe} - x_{Ni})$	[45]
$L_{Cr,Fe,Ni}^{bcc} = (+6000 + 10T)x_{Cr} + (-19000 + 10T)x_{Fe} + (-27000 + 10T)x_{Ni}$	IAD
$T_c^{bcc} = 1043x_{Fe} - 311x_{Cr} + 575x_{Ni} + x_{Fe}x_{Cr}(1650 - 550(x_{Fe} - x_{Cr}))$	[76]
$+x_{Cr}x_{Ni}(2376 + 617(x_{Cr} - x_{Ni}))$	[76]
$\beta^{bcc} = 2.22x_{Fe} - 0.008x_{Cr} + 0.85x_{Ni} - 0.85x_{Fe}x_{Cr} + 4x_{Cr}x_{Ni}$	
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr, Fe, Ni)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Fe}^{fcc} = (+10833 - 7.477T) + (+1410)(x_{Cr} - x_{Fe})$	[4]
$L_{Cr,Ni}^{fcc} = (+8030 - 12.88T) + (+33080 - 16.036T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Ni})$	[34]
$L_{Fe,Ni}^{fcc} = (-12054 + 3.274T) + (+11082 - 4.45T)(x_{Fe} - x_{Ni}) + (-726)(x_{Fe} - x_{Ni})^2$	[45]
$L_{Cr,Fe,Ni}^{fcc} = (+10000 - 10T)x_{Cr} + (-6500)x_{Fe} + (+48000)x_{Ni}$	[76]
$T_c^{fcc} = -201x_{Fe} - 1109x_{Cr} + 633x_{Ni} + x_{Fe}x_{Ni}(2133 - 682(x_{Fe} - x_{Ni})) - 3605x_{Cr}x_{Ni}$	[76]
$\beta^{fcc} = -2.1x_{Fe} - 2.46x_{Cr} + 0.52x_{Ni}$	[76]
$+x_{Fe}x_{Ni}(9.55 + 7.23(x_{Fe} - x_{Ni}) + 5.93(x_{Fe} - x_{Ni})^2 + 6.18(x_{Fe} - x_{Ni})^3)$	
$-1.91x_{Cr}x_{Ni}$	
<i>Sigma (σ) (3 sublattices, sites: 8:4:18, constituents: Fe, Ni:Cr:Fe, Cr, Ni)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Cr:Fe}^{\sigma} = 8G_{fcc}^{\sigma,Fe} + 4G_{bcc}^{\sigma,Cr} + 18G_{bcc}^{\sigma,Fe} + (+117300 - 95.96T)$	[4]
$G_{Fe:Cr:Cr}^{\sigma} = 8G_{fcc}^{\sigma,Fe} + 22G_{bcc}^{\sigma,Cr} + (+92300 - 95.96T)$	[4]
$G_{Fe:Cr:Ni}^{\sigma} = 8G_{fcc}^{\sigma,Fe} + 4G_{bcc}^{\sigma,Cr} + 18G_{bcc}^{\sigma,Ni}$	[75]
$G_{Ni:Cr:Fe}^{\sigma} = 8G_{fcc}^{\sigma,Ni} + 4G_{bcc}^{\sigma,Cr} + 18G_{bcc}^{\sigma,Fe}$	[75]
$G_{Ni:Cr:Cr}^{\sigma} = 8G_{fcc}^{\sigma,Ni} + 22G_{bcc}^{\sigma,Cr} + (+205000 - 200T)$	IAD
$G_{Ni:Cr:Ni}^{\sigma} = 8G_{fcc}^{\sigma,Ni} + 4G_{bcc}^{\sigma,Cr} + 18G_{bcc}^{\sigma,Ni} + (+175400)$	[75]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

4.8.2 Results

The results of the calculations according to the IAD and Lee [5] together with the experimental data (Table 100) are presented in Figures 219–248 and Tables 102 and 103. The agreement is reasonably good in both calculations but slightly better according to the IAD. Note, however, that the IAD puts the most weight on the properties of iron alloys, whereas Lee [5] constructed his description for the whole system. The results according to the IAD are also slightly better than by Miettinen [76] but not much. Therefore, one can still use that paper [76] for a more detailed discussion of the present results.

The recent measurements by Cao and Zhao [503], however, deserve some additional discussion (see Figures 229, 232, 234, and 235). In Figures 232, 234, and 235, note the measurements of the bcc boundary composition located clearly in the calculated bcc+ σ or bcc+fcc+ σ regions (Figures 232, 234, and 235) and the measurements of the sigma boundary composition located clearly in the calculated fcc+ σ region (Figure 235). For the present, it seems impossible to improve this poor agreement, without making considerable changes to the present sigma phase description. Such steps, however, are not taken here, since the present description is already applied in the higher-order assessments according to the IAD.

Table 102. The calculated and experimental values of $K_{Ni}^{fcc/liq}$ for some Fe–Cr–Ni alloys.

Content [wt-%]		Calculated $K_{Ni}^{fcc/liq}$			Experimental $K_{Ni}^{fcc/liq}$	
Cr	Ni	[75]	[5]	IAD	Value	Reference
15.2	11.7	0.99	0.99	0.97	0.97	[109]
18.0	19.9	1.00	0.99	0.93	0.94	[518]
18.8	29.7	1.00	0.98	0.91	0.95	[518]
17.2	11.9	1.00	1.01	0.98	0.94	[504]
17.6	12.5	1.00	1.01	0.98	0.95	[504]
15.5	14.7	0.99	0.98	0.95	0.92	[504]
20.8	18.7	1.02	1.01	0.95	0.96	[504]
20.4	16.5	1.02	1.01	0.97	0.97	[504]
23.0	17.9	1.03	1.03	0.98	0.94	[504]

Table 103. Average error between calculated and experimental values of different properties in Fe–Cr–Ni alloys.

Property	Alloys		Maximum content [wt-%]		Calculated value			
	Number	Type	Cr	Ni	[75]	[5]	IAD	Unit
ΔT_L	178	A	25	23	3.00	1.92	1.45	°C
ΔT_L	87	B	30	30	5.09	5.06	4.80	°C
ΔT_S	85	B	30	30	7.80	7.38	6.71	°C
$\Delta K_{Cr}^{bcc/L}$	70	C	28	30	2.62	2.43	2.36	%
$\Delta K_{Cr}^{fcc/L}$	70	C	28	30	3.62	3.25	2.62	%
$\Delta K_{Ni}^{bcc/L}$	70	C	28	30	3.74	4.17	3.49	%
$\Delta K_{Ni}^{fcc/L}$	70	C	28	30	5.25	4.65	3.65	%

Notes: T_L = liquidus temperature; T_S = solidus temperature; $\Delta K_{Me}^{\phi/L} = \phi/L$ partition of component Me; A = Fe–Cr–Ni alloys [109, 164, 505, 506]; B = Fe–Cr–Ni–Si–C alloys containing up to 0.04 wt-% C and up to 0.4 wt-% Si [495]; C = Fe–Cr–Ni alloys [109, 504, 505, 518].

Fig. 219. The calculated liquidus projection in the Fe–Cr–Ni system, together with the experimental data points (77Sch [109], 87Yam [504], and 88Kun [505]). The solid line refers to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted line refers to those by Lee [5].

Fig. 220. The calculated Fe content of the liquid phase in the univariant L/bcc+fcc equilibrium vs. temperature in the Fe–Cr–Ni system, together with the experimental data points (31Wev [495], 37Jen [311], 77Sch [109], and 87Yam [504]). The solid line refers to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted line refers to those by Lee [5].

Fig. 221. The calculated liquidus isotherms in the Fe–Cr–Ni system, together with the experimental data points (76Cho [164], 77Sch [109], 87Yam [504], 88Kun [505], and 94Sch [506]). The experimental temperature points were selected from ± 2 °C intervals of the selected temperatures). The solid line refers to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted line refers to those by Lee [5].

Fig. 222. The calculated bcc+fcc+liq triangles in the Fe–Cr–Ni system at 1480 °C, 1470 °C, and 1460 °C, together with experimentally determined triangles (87Yam [504]). The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5].

Fig. 223. The calculated vertical sections at 2–18 wt-% Ni of the Fe–Cr–Ni system, together with experimental data points (77Sch [109], 88Kun [505], and 94Sch [506]). The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5].

Fig. 224. The calculated (IAD) bcc/L and fcc/L partition of Cr and Ni (solid lines) in the Fe–Cr–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [109,504,505,518] connected with broken lines.

Fig. 225. The calculated isothermal section of the Fe–Cr–Ni system at 1400 °C, together with experimental data points [513,514]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5]. The abbreviation "bnd" denotes the boundary composition.

Fig. 226. The calculated isothermal section of the Fe–Cr–Ni system at 1350 °C, together with the experimental data points [513,514]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5]. The abbreviation "bnd" denotes the boundary composition.

Fig. 227. The calculated isothermal section of the Fe–Cr–Ni system at 1300 °C, together with the experimental data points [509, 510, 513, 514]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5]. The abbreviation "bnd" denotes the boundary composition.

Fig. 228. The calculated isothermal section of the Fe–Cr–Ni system at 1250 °C, together with the experimental data points [514]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5]. Abbreviation "bnd" denotes the boundary composition.

Fig. 229. The calculated isothermal section of the Fe–Cr–Ni system at 1200 °C, together with the experimental data points [503, 510, 512–514]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5]. The abbreviation "bnd" denotes the boundary composition.

Fig. 230. The calculated isothermal section of the Fe–Cr–Ni system at 1100 °C, together with the experimental data points [510,512]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5]. The abbreviation "bnd" denotes the boundary composition.

Fig. 231. The calculated isothermal section of the Fe–Cr–Ni system at 1000 °C, together with the experimental data points [512,516]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5]. The abbreviation "bnd" denotes the boundary composition.

Fig. 232. The calculated isothermal section of the Fe–Cr–Ni system at 900 °C, together with the experimental data points [503]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5]. The abbreviation "bnd" denotes the boundary composition.

Fig. 233. The calculated isothermal section of the Fe–Cr–Ni system at 850 °C, together with the experimental data points [513,517]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5]. The abbreviation "bnd" denotes the boundary composition.

Fig. 234. The calculated isothermal section of the Fe–Cr–Ni system at 800 °C, together with the experimental data points [503, 507, 508, 516]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5]. The abbreviation "bnd" denotes boundary composition

Fig. 237. The calculated activity of Fe in liquid Fe–Cr–Ni alloys at 1600 °C, together with the experimental data points [116]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5]. The reference state used is pure liquid Fe.

Fig. 235. The calculated isothermal section of the Fe–Cr–Ni system at 700 °C, together with the experimental data points [503]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5]. The abbreviation "bnd" denotes boundary composition

Fig. 238. The calculated Henrian activity of Cr in liquid Fe–Cr–Ni alloys at 1600 °C, together with the experimental data points [116]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5]. The reference state used is an infinite dilute solution of liquid Cr.

Fig. 236. The calculated isothermal section of the Fe-Cr-Ni system at 650 °C, together with the experimental data points [507, 508, 511]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5].

Fig. 239. The calculated Henrian activity of Ni in liquid Fe–Cr–Ni alloys at 1600 °C, together with the experimental data points [116]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5]. The reference state used is an infinite dilute solution of liquid Ni.

Fig. 240. The calculated activity of Fe in liquid Fe–Cr–Ni alloys at 1600 °C, together with the experimental data points [519]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5]. The reference state used is pure liquid Fe.

Fig. 241. The calculated Henrian activity of Cr in liquid Fe–Cr–Ni alloys at 1600 °C, together with the experimental data points [519]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5]. The reference state used is infinite dilute solution of liquid Cr.

Fig. 242. The calculated Henrian activity of Ni in liquid Fe–Cr–Ni alloys at 1600 °C, together with the experimental data points [519]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5]. The reference state used is infinite dilute solution of liquid Ni.

Fig. 243. The calculated activity of Fe in solid Fe–Cr–Ni alloys at 1227 °C, together with the experimental data points [520]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5]. The reference state used is pure fcc Fe.

Fig. 244. The calculated activity of Cr in solid Fe–Cr–Ni alloys at 1227 °C, together with the experimental data points [520]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5]. The reference state used is pure bcc Cr.

Fig. 245. The calculated activity of Ni in solid Fe–Cr–Ni alloys at 1227 °C, together with the experimental data points [520]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5]. The reference state used is pure fcc Ni.

Fig. 246. The calculated activities of Cr in solid Fe–Cr–Ni alloys at 1000 °C, together with the experimental data points [521]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5]. The reference state used is pure bcc Cr.

Fig. 247. The calculated activities of Cr in solid Fe–Cr–Ni alloys at 1200–900 °C, together with the experimental data points [322]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5]. The reference state used is pure bcc Cr.

Fig. 248. The calculated enthalpy of formation for solid Fe–Cr–Ni alloys at 1292 °C, together with the experimental data points [178]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lee [5]. The reference states used are pure bcc Fe, pure bcc Cr and pure fcc Ni.

4.9 The Fe–Cr–Si system

Experimental studies on the Fe–Cr–Si system have been reviewed by Raghavan [522–524] and a thermodynamic assessment has been given by Lindholm [78]. The system was later reassessed for use in the IAD as its binary data differs from that of Lindholm [78]. The present work reviews this description and presents its experimental verification.

4.9.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 104 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 105 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 106.

Table 104. Phases and their modeling in the Fe–Cr–Si description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Cr,Fe,Si), substitutional, RKM
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Cr,Fe,Si), substitutional, RKM
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Cr,Fe,Si), substitutional, RKM
Sigma (\approx σ)	(Fe) ₈ (Cr) ₄ (Cr,Fe,Si) ₁₈ , sublattice, RKM
Cr ₃ Si (dissolving Fe)	(Cr,Fe) ₃ (Si), sublattice, RKM
Cr ₅ Si ₃ (dissolving Fe)	(Cr,Fe) ₅ (Si) ₃ , sublattice, RKM
Fe ₅ Si ₃ (dissolving Cr)	(Cr,Fe) ₅ (Si) ₃ , sublattice, RKM
FeSi (extending to CrSi)	(Cr,Fe)(Si), sublattice, RKM
CrSi ₂	(Cr)(Si) ₂ , stoichiometric
Fe ₂ Si	(Fe) ₂ (Si), stoichiometric
FeSi ₂ -H	(Fe) ₃ (Si) ₇ , stoichiometric
FeSi ₂ -L	(Fe)(Si) ₂ , stoichiometric
dia_A4 (\approx dia)	pure Si

Note: RKM = Redlich–Kister–Muggianu excess model.

Table 105. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Fe–Cr–Si according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
5 isothermal sections at 1047 °C, 1000 °C, 947 °C, 800 °C, and 600 °C	[525–527]
3 vertical sections at 8 wt-% Si, 79 wt-% Fe, and 67.8 wt-% Fe	[528, 529]
2 vertical sections at $w_{\text{Si}}:w_{\text{Cr}} = 2$ and $w_{\text{Cr}}:w_{\text{Fe}} = 1.5$	[528, 530]
Enthalpy of mixing for liquid alloys at 1600 °C	[531]
Activity coefficient $\gamma_{\text{Si}}^{\text{Cr}}$ in liquid alloys at 1560 °C	[380]
Activity coefficient $\gamma_{\text{Cr}}^{\text{Si}}$ in liquid alloys at 1630 °C	[532]
Silicon iso-activities in bcc alloys at 1400 °C	[533]

Table 106. The thermodynamic description of the Fe–Cr–Si system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr, Fe, Si)</i>	
$L_{\text{Cr,Fe}}^{\text{L}} = (-17737 + 7.997T) + (-1331)(x_{\text{Cr}} - x_{\text{Fe}})$	[5]
$L_{\text{Cr,Si}}^{\text{L}} = (-119811 + 16.602T) + (-49125 + 14.11T)(x_{\text{Cr}} - x_{\text{Si}})$	[37]
$L_{\text{Fe,Si}}^{\text{L}} = (-164435 + 41.977T) + (-21.523T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Si}}) + (5220 + 5.726T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Si}})^2$ $+ (-28955 + 26.275T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Si}})^3$	[534]
$L_{\text{Cr,Fe,Si}}^{\text{L}} = (+78000 - 60T)$	IAD

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

Table 106 (continued)

Equation	Reference
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Fe,Si)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Fe}^{bcc} = (+20500 - 9.68T)$	[4]
$L_{Cr,Si}^{bcc} = (-102085 + 9.543T) + (-49125 + 14.110T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Si})$	[37]
$L_{Fe,Si}^{bcc} = (-59098 + 11.57T) + (-1796 + 1T)(x_{Fe} - x_{Si}) + (+5602 + 3.57T)(x_{Fe} - x_{Si})^2$	[535]
$L_{Cr,Fe,Si}^{bcc} = (-106000 + 35T)$	IAD
$T_c^{bcc} = 1043x_{Fe} - 311x_{Cr} + x_{Fe}x_{Cr}(1650 - 550(x_{Fe} - x_{Cr})) + x_{Fe}x_{Si}(+504(x_{Fe} - x_{Si}))$	[536]
$\beta^{bcc} = 2.22x_{Fe} - 0.008x_{Cr} - 0.85x_{Fe}x_{Cr}$	[4]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Fe,Si)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Fe}^{fcc} = (+10833 - 7.477T) + (+1410)(x_{Cr} - x_{Fe})$	[4]
$L_{Cr,Si}^{fcc} = L_{Cr,Si}^{bcc}$	IAD
$L_{Fe,Si}^{fcc} = (-125248 + 41.166T) + (-142708)(x_{Fe} - x_{Si}) + (89907)(x_{Fe} - x_{Si})^2$	[536]
$L_{Cr,Fe,Si}^{fcc} = (-145000 + 50T)$	IAD
$T_c^{fcc} = -201x_{Fe} - 1109x_{Cr}$	[4]
$\beta^{fcc} = -2.1x_{Fe} - 2.46x_{Cr}$	[4]
<i>Sigma (σ) (3 sublattices, sites: 8:4:18, constituents: Fe:Cr:Cr,Fe,Si)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Cr:Cr}^{\circ,\sigma} = 8G_{fcc}^{\circ,Fe} + 22G_{bcc}^{\circ,Cr} + (+92300 - 95.96T)$	[4]
$G_{Fe:Cr:Fe}^{\circ,\sigma} = 8G_{fcc}^{\circ,Fe} + 4G_{bcc}^{\circ,Cr} + 18G_{bcc}^{\circ,Fe} + (+117300 - 95.96T)$	[4]
$G_{Fe:Cr:Si}^{\circ,\sigma} = 8G_{fcc}^{\circ,Fe} + 4G_{bcc}^{\circ,Cr} + 18G_{bcc}^{\circ,Si} + (-130000 + 380T)$	IAD
$L_{Fe:Cr:Cr,Si}^{\sigma} = (-2420000 + 380T)$	IAD
$L_{Fe:Cr:Fe,Si}^{\sigma} = (-2240000 + 380T)$	IAD
<i>Cr₃Si (2 sublattices, sites: 3:1, constituents: Cr,Fe:Si)</i>	
$G_{Cr:Si}^{\circ,Cr_3Si} = 3G_{Cr}^{\circ,bcc} + G_{Si}^{\circ,dia} + (-127685 + 5.106T)$	[37]
$G_{Fe:Si}^{\circ,Cr_3Si} = 3G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + G_{Si}^{\circ,dia} + (-62000)$	IAD
<i>Cr₅Si₃ (2 sublattices, sites: 5:3, constituents: Cr,Fe:Si)</i>	
$G_{Cr:Si}^{\circ,Cr_5Si_3} = 5G_{Cr}^{\circ,bcc} + 3G_{Si}^{\circ,dia} + (-268968 + 138.0708T - 20.4422T \ln T + 0.0078417T^2)$	IAD
$G_{Fe:Si}^{\circ,Cr_5Si_3} = 5G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + 3G_{Si}^{\circ,dia} + (-80000)$	IAD
<i>CrSi₂ (2 sublattices, sites: 1:2, constituents: Cr:Si)</i>	
$G_{Cr:Si}^{\circ,CrSi_2} = G_{Cr}^{\circ,bcc} + 2G_{Si}^{\circ,dia} + (-76539 - 30.0488T + 4.4806T \ln T - 0.003426T^2)$	IAD
<i>Fe₂Si (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents: Fe:Si)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Si}^{\circ,Fe_2Si} = 2G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + G_{Si}^{\circ,dia} + (-71256.6 - 10.62T)$	[536]
<i>Fe₅Si₃ (2 sublattices, sites: 5:3, constituents: Cr,Fe:Si)</i>	
$G_{Cr:Si}^{\circ,Fe_5Si_3} = 5G_{Cr}^{\circ,bcc} + 3G_{Si}^{\circ,dia} + (-260000 + 20T)$	IAD
$G_{Fe:Si}^{\circ,Fe_5Si_3} = 5G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + 3G_{Si}^{\circ,dia} + (-241144 + 2.16T)$	[536]
<i>FeSi (CrSi) (2 sublattices, sites: 1:1, constituents: Cr,Fe:Si)</i>	
$G_{Cr:Si}^{\circ,FeSi} = G_{Cr}^{\circ,bcc} + G_{Si}^{\circ,dia} + (-63665 + 59.411T - 8.7776T \ln T + 0.0039T^2)$	IAD
$G_{Fe:Si}^{\circ,FeSi} = G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + G_{Si}^{\circ,dia} + (-72761.2 + 4.44T)$	[536]
$L_{Cr,Fe:Si}^{FeSi} = (+12000)$	IAD
<i>FeSi₂-H (2 sublattices, sites: 3:7, constituents: Fe:Si)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Si}^{\circ,FeSi_2-H} = 3G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + 7G_{Si}^{\circ,dia} + (-196490 - 9.2T)$	[536]
<i>FeSi₂-L (2 sublattices, sites: 1:2, constituents: Fe:Si)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Si}^{\circ,FeSi_2-L} = G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + 2G_{Si}^{\circ,dia} + (-82149 + 10.44T)$	[536]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

4.9.2 Results

The results of the calculations according to the IAD and Lindholm [78] together with the experimental data (Table 105) are presented in Figures 249–264 and Table 107. The agreement is reasonable in both calculations but slightly better in those according to the IAD.

Table 107. The calculated (IAD) invariant points of the Fe–Cr–Si system.

Reaction	Code	Temp. [°C]	Content [at-%]	
			Cr in Liq	Si in Liq
$L + \text{bcc} + \text{Cr}_3\text{Si} = \sigma$	P	1353	37.34	16.98
$L + \text{Cr}_5\text{Si}_3 = \text{Fe}_5\text{Si}_3 + \text{FeSi}$	U ₁	1349	23.94	40.34
$L + \text{Cr}_5\text{Si}_3 = \text{Fe}_5\text{Si}_3 + \text{Cr}_3\text{Si}$	U ₂	1349	26.98	34.63
$L + \text{Cr}_3\text{Si} = \text{Fe}_5\text{Si}_3 + \sigma$	U ₃	1230	16.43	28.56
$L + \sigma = \text{bcc} + \text{Fe}_5\text{Si}_3$	U ₄	1221	15.20	28.46
$L + \text{FeSi} = \text{Fe}_2\text{Si} + \text{Fe}_5\text{Si}_3$	U ₅	1193	0.82	35.32
$L + \text{FeSi} = \text{FeSi}_2\text{-H} + \text{CrSi}_2$	U ₆	1187	2.86	68.68
$L = \text{FeSi}_2\text{-H} + \text{dia} + \text{CrSi}_2$	E ₁	1186	2.84	71.92
$L = \text{bcc} + \text{Fe}_2\text{Si} + \text{Fe}_5\text{Si}_3$	E ₂	1178	2.37	32.01

Fig. 249. The calculated (IAD) liquidus projection in the Fe–Cr–Si system. Also shown by the dotted lines are the calculated liquidus isotherms between 1200–1900 °C.

Fig. 250. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1300 °C in the Fe–Cr–Si system.

Fig. 251. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1047 °C in the Fe–Cr–Si system, together with the experimental data points [526]. The dotted lines show the bcc and Sigma phase regions calculated by Lindholm [78].

Fig. 252. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1000 °C in the Fe–Cr–Si system, together with the experimental data points [525].

Fig. 253. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 947 °C in the Fe–Cr–Si system, together with the experimental data points [526]. The dotted lines show the bcc and Sigma phase regions calculated by Lindholm [78].

Fig. 254. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 800 °C in the Fe–Cr–Si system, together with the experimental data points [525].

Fig. 255. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 600 °C in the Fe–Cr–Si system, together with the experimental data points [525, 527].

Fig. 256. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 8 wt-% Si in the Fe–Cr–Si system, together with the experimental data points [528].

Fig. 257. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 79 wt-% Fe in the Fe–Cr–Si system, together with the experimental data points [528, 529].

Fig. 258. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 67.8 wt-% Fe in the Fe–Cr–Si system, together with the experimental data points [528].

Fig. 259. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of $w_{Si}:w_{Cr} = 2$ in the Fe–Cr–Si system, together with the experimental data points [528].

Fig. 260. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of $w_{Cr}:w_{Fe} = 1.5$ in the Fe–Cr–Si system, together with the experimental data points [530].

Fig. 261. The calculated enthalpy of mixing for liquid Fe–Cr–Si alloys at 1600 °C, together with the experimental data points [531]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dashed lines refer to those by Lindholm [78]. The reference states used are pure liquid components.

Fig. 262. The calculated activity coefficient γ_{Si}^{Cr} in liquid Fe–Cr–Si alloys at 1600 °C and at 3.5 at-% Si, together with the experimental data points [380]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lindholm [78].

Fig. 263. The calculated activity coefficient γ_{Cr}^{Si} in liquid Fe–Cr–Si alloys at 1630 °C and at 1 at-% Cr, together with the experimental data points [532]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lindholm [78].

Fig. 264. The calculated iso-activity lines of Si in bcc Fe–Cr–Si alloys at 1400 °C, together with the experimental data points [533]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Lindholm [78]. The reference state used is pure diamond Si.

4.10 The Fe–Cu–Mn system

Experimental studies on the Fe–Cu–Mn system have been reviewed by Chang *et al.* [436], Raynor and Rivlin [537], Raghavan [538–541], Villars *et al.* [542]. A thermodynamic assessment has been given by Ohtani *et al.* [67], Miettinen [79], Wang *et al.* [42], and Zhang *et al.* [80]. The system was later reassessed for use in the IAD as part of its binary data differs from those published in [42, 67, 79, 80]. The present work reviews this description and presents its experimental verification.

4.10.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 108 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 109 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 110.

Table 108. Phases and their modeling in the Fe–Cu–Mn description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Cu,Fe,Mn), substitutional, RKM
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Cu,Fe,Mn), substitutional, RKM
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Cu,Fe,Mn), substitutional, RKM
cbcc_A12 (\approx cbcc)	(Cu,Fe,Mn), substitutional, RKM
cub_A13 (\approx cub)	(Cu,Fe,Mn), substitutional, RKM

Note: RKM = Redlich–Kister–Muggianu excess model.

Table 109. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Fe–Cu–Mn according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Liquidus temperatures	[537]
6 isotherms at 1300 °C, 1200 °C, 1100 °C, 1050 °C, 950 °C, and 850 °C	[8, 67, 537, 543]
6 vertical sections at 10 and 20 wt-% Cu, Mn and Fe	[544]
Activity coefficient MnCu in liquid alloys at 1600 °C	[498] (theoretical)

Table 110. The thermodynamic description of the Fe–Cu–Mn system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Fe,Mn)</i>	
$L_{Cu,Fe}^L = (+35626 - 2.19T) + (-1530 + 1.153T)(x_{Cu} - x_{Fe})$ $+ (+12714 - 5.186T)(x_{Cu} - x_{Fe})^2 + (+1177)(x_{Cu} - x_{Fe})^3$	[9]
$L_{Cu,Mn}^L = (+1119 - 5.623T) + (-10915)(x_{Cu} - x_{Mn})$	[43]
$L_{Fe,Mn}^L = (-3950 + 0.489T) + (1145)(x_{Fe} - x_{Mn})$	[491]
$L_{Cu,Fe,Mn}^L = (+90000 - 40T)x_{Cu} + (+90000 - 50T)x_{Fe} + (+0)x_{Mn}$	IAD
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Fe,Mn)</i>	
$L_{Cu,Fe}^{bcc} = (+39676 - 4.732T)$	[9]
$L_{Cu,Mn}^{bcc} = (+18366 - 16.221T) + (-12668)(x_{Cu} - x_{Mn})$	[43]
$L_{Fe,Mn}^{bcc} = (-2759 + 1.237T)$	[491]
$L_{Cu,Fe,Mn}^{bcc} = (+30000)$	[80]
$T_c^{bcc} = 1043x_{Fe} - 580x_{Mn} - 41.4x_{Fe}x_{Cu} + x_{Fe}x_{Mn}(123)$	[491]
$\beta^{bcc} = 2.22x_{Fe} - 0.27x_{Mn}$	[491]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

Table 110 (continued)

Equation	Reference
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Fe,Mn)</i>	
$L_{\text{Cu,Fe}}^{\text{fcc}} = (+43320 - 6.944T) + (+6069 - 2.837T)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Fe}}) + (+3629)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Fe}})^2$	[9]
$L_{\text{Cu,Mn}}^{\text{fcc}} = (+20236 - 13.244T) + (-12155 + 2.94T)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Mn}}) + (+1038)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Mn}})^2$	[43]
$L_{\text{Fe,Mn}}^{\text{fcc}} = (-7762 + 3.865T) + (-259)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Mn}})$	[491]
$L_{\text{Cu,Fe,Mn}}^{\text{fcc}} = (+13000)x_{\text{Cu}} + (-150000 + 120T)x_{\text{Fe}} + (+0)x_{\text{Mn}}$	IAD
$T_c^{\text{fcc}} = -201x_{\text{Fe}} - 1620x_{\text{Mn}} + x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Mn}}(-2282 - 2068(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Mn}}))$	[491]
$\beta^{\text{fcc}} = -2.1x_{\text{Fe}} - 1.86x_{\text{Mn}}$	[491]
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Fe,Mn)</i>	
$G_{\text{Cu}}^{\text{o,bcc}} = G_{\text{Cu}}^{\text{o,fcc}} + (+3556)$	[43]
$L_{\text{Cu,Fe}}^{\text{bcc}} = (+50000)$	[80]
$L_{\text{Cu,Mn}}^{\text{bcc}} = (+36627 - 12.209T)$	[43]
$L_{\text{Fe,Mn}}^{\text{bcc}} = (-10184)$	[491]
<i>cub (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Fe,Mn)</i>	
$G_{\text{Cu}}^{\text{o,cub}} = G_{\text{Cu}}^{\text{o,fcc}} + (+2092)$	[43]
$L_{\text{Cu,Fe}}^{\text{cub}} = (+50000)$	[80]
$L_{\text{Cu,Mn}}^{\text{cub}} = (+42493 - 14.164T)$	[43]
$L_{\text{Fe,Mn}}^{\text{cub}} = (-11518 + 2.819T)$	[491]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

4.10.2 Results

The results of the calculations according to the IAD and Zhang *et al.* [80] together with the experimental data (Table 109) are presented in Figures 265–278. The agreement is reasonably good in both calculations. In Figure 265, note point P indicating the invariant point (minimum) of the disappearance of the iron-rich bcc phase. According to Zhang *et al.* [80] and the IAD, the corresponding temperatures are 1429 °C and 1431 °C, respectively. Note also the saddle point PS where the liquid completely converts into iron-rich fcc₁ and copper-rich fcc₂ phases. The calculated temperatures and liquid compositions of this point by Zhang *et al.* [80] and IAD are 889 °C–0.9 wt-% Fe–33.6 wt-% Mn and 903 °C–1.0 wt-% Fe–35.1 wt-% Mn, respectively. The assessed values by Raynor and Rivlin [537] are 880 °C–10 wt-% Fe–35 wt-% Mn indicating a much higher Fe content than the values obtained by the calculations. Additional experimental phase equilibrium data are available from Salter [545] and Wang [546] agreeing to a reasonable degree with the calculations.

Fig. 265. The calculated (IAD) liquidus projection in the Fe–Cu–Mn system. Also shown are the calculated liquidus isotherms between 1450 °C and 1150 °C (broken lines) together with some experimental data points (88Ray [537]).

Fig. 266. The calculated isotherm of 1300 °C in the Fe–Cu–Mn system, together with the experimental data points (88Ray [537], 94Swa [8], and 97Oht [67]). The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zhang *et al.* [80].

Fig. 267. The calculated isotherm of 1200 °C in the Fe–Cu–Mn system, together with the experimental data points (88Ray [537], 94Swa [8], and 97Oht [67]). The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zhang *et al.* [80].

Fig. 268. The calculated isotherm of 1100 °C in the Fe–Cu–Mn system, together with the experimental data points (94Swa [8] and 97Oht [67]). The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zhang *et al.* [80].

Fig. 269. The calculated isotherm of 1050 °C in the Fe–Cu–Mn system, together with experimental data points (78Has [543] and 94Swa [8]). The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zhang *et al.* [80].

Fig. 270. The calculated isotherm of 950 °C in the Fe–Cu–Mn system, together with the experimental data points (78Has [543] and 94Swa [8]). The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zhang *et al.* [80].

Fig. 271. The calculated isotherm of 850 °C in the Fe–Cu–Mn system, together with the experimental data points (78Has [543] and 94Swa [8]). The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zhang *et al.* [80].

Fig. 272. The calculated vertical section of 10 wt-% Cu in the Fe–Cu–Mn system, together with the experimental data points [544]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zhang *et al.* [80].

Fig. 273. The calculated vertical section of 20 wt-% Cu in the Fe–Cu–Mn system, together with the experimental data points [544]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zhang *et al.* [80].

Fig. 274. The calculated vertical section of 10 wt-% Fe in the Fe–Cu–Mn system, together with the experimental data points [544]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zhang *et al.* [80].

Fig. 275. The calculated vertical section of 20 wt-% Fe in the Fe–Cu–Mn system, together with the experimental data points [544]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zhang *et al.* [80].

Fig. 276. The calculated vertical section of 10 wt-% Mn in the Fe–Cu–Mn system, together with the experimental data points [544]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zhang *et al.* [80].

Fig. 277. The calculated vertical section of 20 wt-% Mn in the Fe–Cu–Mn system, together with the experimental data points [544]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zhang *et al.* [80].

Fig. 278. The calculated activity coefficient γ_{Mn}^{Cu} in liquid Fe–Cu–Mn alloys at 1600 °C, together with theoretically determined data points (98Uen [498]). The solid line refers to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted line refers to those by Zhang *et al.* [80].

4.11 The Fe–Cu–Mo system

Experimental studies on the Fe–Cu–Mo system have been reviewed by Raghavan [547, 548] and a thermodynamic assessment has been given by Wang *et al.* [44]. The system was later reassessed for the IAD as part of its binary data differs from those of Wang *et al.* [44]. The present work reviews this description and presents its experimental verification.

4.11.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 111 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 112 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 113.

Table 111. Phases and their modeling in the Fe–Cu–Mo description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Cu,Fe,Mo), substitutional, RKM
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Cu,Fe,Mo), substitutional, RKM
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Cu,Fe,Mo), substitutional, RKM
Mu (\approx μ)	(Fe) ₇ (Mo) ₂ (Fe,Mo) ₄ , sublattice, RKM
R	(Fe) ₂₇ (Mo) ₁₄ (Fe,Mo) ₁₂ , sublattice, RKM
Sigma (\approx σ)	(Fe) ₈ (Mo) ₄ (Fe,Mo) ₁₈ , sublattice, RKM
Fe ₂ Mo (\approx λ)	(Fe) ₂ (Mo), stoichiometric

Note: RKM = Redlich–Kister–Muggianu excess model.

Table 112. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Fe–Cu–Mn according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
6 isotherm at 1300 °C, 1200 °C, 1100 °C, 1000 °C, 900 °C, and 800 °C	[8, 44]
5 vertical sections at 5, 10, 15, 20, and 25 wt-% Mo	[549]

Table 113. The thermodynamic description of the Fe–Cu–Mo system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference(s)
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Fe,Mo)</i>	
$L_{Cu,Fe}^L = (+35626 - 2.19T) + (-1530 + 1.153T)(x_{Cu} - x_{Fe})$	[9]
$+ (+12714 - 5.186T)(x_{Cu} - x_{Fe})^2 + (+1177)(x_{Cu} - x_{Fe})^3$	[44]
$L_{Cu,Mo}^L = (+57285 + 2T) + (-1200)(x_{Cu} - x_{Mo})$	
$L_{Fe,Mo}^L = (-6900 - 0.23T) + (-9000 + 3.85T)(x_{Fe} - x_{Mo})$	IAD
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Fe,Mo)</i>	
$L_{Cu,Fe}^{bcc} = (+39676 - 4.732T)$	[9]
$L_{Cu,Mo}^{bcc} = (+82313)$	[44]
$L_{Fe,Mo}^{bcc} = (+36818 - 9.141T) + (-362 - 5.724T)(x_{Fe} - x_{Mo})$	[13]
$L_{Cu,Fe,Mo}^{bcc} = (+48000 - 35T)$	IAD
$T_c^{bcc} = 1043x_{Fe} - 41.4x_{Fe}x_{Cu} + x_{Fe}x_{Mo}(335 + 526(x_{Fe} - x_{Mo}))$	[9, 13]
$\beta^{bcc} = 2.22x_{Fe}$	[96]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Fe,Mo)</i>	
$L_{Cu,Fe}^{fcc} = (+43320 - 6.944T) + (+6069 - 2.837T)(x_{Cu} - x_{Fe}) + (+3629)(x_{Cu} - x_{Fe})^2$	[9]
$L_{Cu,Mo}^{fcc} = (+83144)$	[44]
$L_{Fe,Mo}^{fcc} = (+28347 - 17.691T)$	[13]
$T_c^{fcc} = -201x_{Fe}$	[96]
$\beta^{fcc} = -2.1x_{Fe}$	[96]
<i>Mu (μ) (3 sublattices, sites: 7:2:4, constituents: Fe:Mo:Fe,Mo)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Mo:Fe}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 2G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 4G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (+39475 - 6.032T)$	[13]
$G_{Fe:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 6G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (-46663 - 5.891T)$	[13]
<i>R (3 sublattices, sites: 27:14:12, constituents: Fe:Mo:Fe,Mo)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Mo:Fe}^{\circ,R} = 27G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 14G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 12G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (-77487 - 50.486T)$	[13]
$G_{Fe:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,R} = 27G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 26G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+313474 - 289.472T)$	[13]
<i>Sigma (σ) (3 sublattices, sites: 8:4:18, constituents: Fe:Mo:Fe,Mo)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Mo:Fe}^{\circ,\sigma} = 8G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 4G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 18G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (-1813 - 27.272T)$	[13]
$G_{Fe:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,\sigma} = 8G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 22G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+83326 - 69.618T)$	[13]
$L_{Fe:Mo:Fe,Mo}^{\sigma} = (+222909)$	[13]
<i>Fe₂Mo (λ) (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents: Fe:Mo)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Mo}^{\circ,\lambda} = 2G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (-10798 - 0.132T)$	[161]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

4.11.2 Results

The results of the calculations according to the IAD together with the experimental data (Table 112) are presented in Figures 279–293 and Table 114. The agreement is reasonably good and quite similar with those by Wang *et al.* [44]. Note that the liquidus projections of Figures 279 and 280 are tentative, due to the lack of proper experimental data for the liquid phase.

Table 114. The calculated (IAD) invariant points of the Fe–Cu–Mo system.

Reaction	Code	Figure	Temp. [°C]	Content in Liq [wt-%]	
				Cu	Mo
$L_1 + \text{bcc} = \sigma + L_2$	U ₁	279	1534	46.89	6.56
$L_1 + L_2 + \text{bcc} = \sigma$	P ₁	280	1534	90.72	1.79
$L_1 + \text{fcc}_1 = \text{bcc} + L_2$	U ₂	279	1432	25.13	3.60
$L_1 + L_2 + \text{fcc}_1 = \text{bcc}$	P ₂	280	1432	72.04	0.40
$L_1 + \sigma = R + L_2$	U ₃	279	1426	35.99	7.01
$L_1 + L_2 + \sigma = R$	P ₃	280	1426	91.17	0.99
$L_1 + R = \text{bcc} + L_2$	U ₄	279	1423	35.65	7.04
$L_1 + L_2 + R = \text{bcc}$	P ₄	280	1423	91.16	0.97
$L_1 + R + \sigma = \mu$	P ₅	280	1368	93.45	0.69
$L_1 + R = \text{bcc} + \mu$	U ₅	280	1307	93.86	0.42
$L_1 + \sigma = \text{bcc} + \mu$	U ₆	280	1241	97.19	0.36
$L_1 + \text{fcc}_1 = \text{bcc} + \text{fcc}_2$	U ₇	280	1095	97.32	0.04
$L_1 + \text{bcc} = \text{fcc}_2 + \mu$	U ₈	280	1094	97.47	0.08
$L_1 + \mu = \text{bcc} + \text{fcc}_2$	U ₉	280	1089	98.70	0.14

Fig. 279. The calculated (IAD) liquidus projection in the Fe-rich region of the Fe–Cu–Mo system. Also shown by the dotted lines are the calculated liquidus isotherms between 2800 °C and 1430 °C.

Fig. 280. The calculated (IAD) liquidus projection in the Cu-corner of the Fe-Cu-Mo system.

Fig. 281. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1300 °C at the Cu-Fe side of the Fe-Cu-Mo system, together with the experimental data points by Wang *et al.* [44] for ternary alloys and by Swartzendruber [8] for the binary Cu-Fe side.

Fig. 282. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1200 °C at the Cu-Fe side of the Fe-Cu-Mo system, together with the experimental data points by Wang *et al.* [44] for ternary alloys and by Swartzendruber [8] for the binary Cu-Fe side.

Fig. 283. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1100 °C at the Cu-Fe side of the Fe-Cu-Mo system, together with the experimental data points by Wang *et al.* [44] for ternary alloys and by Swartzendruber [8] for the binary Cu-Fe side.

Fig. 284. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1000 °C at the Cu–Fe side of the Fe–Cu–Mo system, together with the experimental data points by Wang *et al.* [44] for ternary alloys and by Swartzendruber [8] for the binary Cu–Fe side.

Fig. 285. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 900 °C at the Cu–Fe side of the Fe–Cu–Mo system, together with the experimental data points by Wang *et al.* [44] for ternary alloys and by Swartzendruber [8] for the binary Cu–Fe side.

Fig. 286. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 800 °C at the Cu-Fe side of the Fe-Cu-Mo system, together with the experimental data points by Wang *et al.* [44] for ternary alloys and by Swartzendruber [8] for the binary Cu-Fe side.

Fig. 287. The calculated (IAD) vertical section at 5 wt-% Mo in the Fe-Cu-Mo system, together with the experimental data points [549].

Fig. 288. The calculated (IAD) vertical section at 10 wt-% Mo in the Fe–Cu–Mo system, together with the experimental data points [549].

Fig. 289. The calculated (IAD) vertical section at 15 wt-% Mo in the Fe–Cu–Mo system, together with the experimental data points [549].

Fig. 290. The calculated (IAD) vertical section at 20 wt-% Mo in the Fe-Cu-Mo system, together with the experimental data points [549].

Fig. 291. The calculated (IAD) vertical section at 25 wt-% Mo in the Fe-Cu-Mo system, together with the experimental data points [549].

Fig. 292. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1500 °C in the Fe–Cu–Mo system.

Fig. 293. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1350 °C in the Fe–Cu–Mo system.

4.12 The Fe–Cu–Ni system

Experimental studies on the Fe–Cu–Ni system have been reviewed by Köster and Dan-nöhl [550], Chang *et al.* [436] and Gupta [551], while a thermodynamic assessment has been presented by Jansson [45], Ohtani *et al.* [67], Servant *et al.* [81], and Turchanin *et al.* [82]. The system was later reassessed for the IAD as part of its binary data differs from those published in [45, 81, 82]. The present work reviews this description by and presents its experimental verification.

4.12.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 115 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 116 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 117.

Table 115. Phases and their modeling in the Fe–Cu–Ni description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Cu,Fe,Ni), substitutional, RKM
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Cu,Fe,Ni), substitutional, RKM
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Cu,Fe,Ni), substitutional, RKM

Note: RKM = Redlich–Kister–Muggianu excess model.

Table 116. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Fe–Cu–Ni according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Liquidus temperatures	[67, 543, 550]
9 isotherms at 1300 °C, 1250 °C, 1200 °C, 1150 °C, 1050 °C, 1000 °C, 900 °C, 850, and 600 °C	[67, 543, 551–555]
5 vertical sections at 15, 30, and 40 wt-% Ni, and at $w_{\text{Fe}} = w_{\text{Ni}}$ and $w_{\text{Fe}} = w_{\text{Cu}}$	[550, 555]
Activity of Fe and Cu in liquid alloys at 1350 °C	[556]
Activity of Fe in fcc alloys at 1000 °C and 800 °C and at $x_{\text{Ni}} = 0.40$	[365]
Activity of Fe and Ni in fcc alloys at 1247 °C and along $4x_{\text{Ni}} + 3x_{\text{Cu}} = 3$	[557]
Enthalpy of formation for fcc alloys at 1050 °C	[558]

Table 117. The thermodynamic description of the Fe–Cu–Ni system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Fe,Ni)</i>	
$L_{\text{Cu,Fe}}^{\text{L}} = (+35626 - 2.19T) + (-1530 + 1.153T)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Fe}})$ $+ (+12714 - 5.186T)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Fe}})^2 + (+1177)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Fe}})^3$	[9]
$L_{\text{Cu,Ni}}^{\text{L}} = (11760 + 1.084T) + (-1672)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Ni}})$	[45]
$L_{\text{Fe,Ni}}^{\text{L}} = (-16911 + 5.162T) + (+10180 - 4.147T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})$	[5]
$L_{\text{Cu,Fe,Ni}}^{\text{L}} = (-74000 + 40T)$	IAD
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Fe,Ni)</i>	
$L_{\text{Cu,Fe}}^{\text{bcc}} = (+39676 - 4.732T)$	[9]
$L_{\text{Cu,Ni}}^{\text{bcc}} = (+8366 + 2.802T)$	[45]
$L_{\text{Fe,Ni}}^{\text{bcc}} = (-957 - 1.287T) + (+1789 - 1.929T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})$	[45]
$L_{\text{Cu,Fe,Ni}}^{\text{bcc}} = 0$	IAD
$T_{\text{c}}^{\text{bcc}} = 1043x_{\text{Fe}} + 575x_{\text{Ni}} - 41.4x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Cu}}$	[9]
$\beta^{\text{bcc}} = 2.22x_{\text{Fe}} + 0.85x_{\text{Ni}}$	[45]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Fe,Ni)</i>	
$L_{\text{Cu,Fe}}^{\text{fcc}} = (+43320 - 6.944T) + (+6069 - 2.837T)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Fe}}) + (+3629)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Fe}})^2$	[9]
$L_{\text{Cu,Ni}}^{\text{fcc}} = (8366 + 2.802T) + (-4360 + 1.812T)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Ni}})$	[45]
$L_{\text{Fe,Ni}}^{\text{fcc}} = (-12054 + 3.274T) + (+11082 - 4.45T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}}) + (-726)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})^2$	[45]
$L_{\text{Cu,Fe,Ni}}^{\text{fcc}} = (-80000 + 40T)x_{\text{Cu}} + (-50000 + 30T)x_{\text{Fe}} + (-50000 + 30T)x_{\text{Ni}}$	IAD
$T_{\text{c}}^{\text{fcc}} = -201x_{\text{Fe}} + 633x_{\text{Ni}} + x_{\text{Cu}}x_{\text{Ni}}(-935.5 - 549.9(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Ni}}))$ $+ x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Ni}}(2133 - 682(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})) + x_{\text{Cu}}x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Ni}}(7000)$	[45]
$\beta^{\text{fcc}} = -2.1x_{\text{Fe}} + 0.52x_{\text{Ni}} + x_{\text{Cu}}x_{\text{Ni}}(-0.732 - 0.317(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Ni}}))$ $+ x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Ni}}(9.55 + 7.23(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}}) + 5.93(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})^2$ $+ 6.18(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})^3) + x_{\text{Cu}}x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Ni}}(20)$	[45]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

4.12.2 Results

The results of the calculations according to the IAD and [45] together with the experimental data (Table 116) are presented in Figures 294–313. The agreement is reasonably good in both calculations, but slightly better according to the IAD for the different phase equilibria.

Additional experimental phase equilibrium data are available from the old studies of [559] and [560] agreeing in a reasonable way with the calculations. In addition, Turchanin *et al.* [82] have quite recently measured mixing enthalpies of liquid Fe–Cu–Ni alloys at 1600 °C. These measurements agree well with their own calculations but only moderately with those according to the IAD and Jansson [45]. This is mainly due to their different binary Fe–Cu and Cu–Ni descriptions yielding quite different "starting

enthalpies" for the calculation of the mixing enthalpy in ternary Fe–Cu–Ni alloys. The overall agreement according to the IAD, however, can be considered quite satisfactory, especially as it was obtained using a very simple ternary interaction parameter of liquid, in regard to the more complex expression of Turchanin *et al.* [82].

Fig. 294. The calculated (IAD) liquidus projection in the Fe–Cu–Ni system (thick lines). Also shown are the calculated liquidus isotherms between 1100 °C and 1525 °C (thin lines) together with some experimental data points [67, 543, 550].

Fig. 295. The calculated isotherm of 1300 °C in the Fe–Cu–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [67]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [45].

Fig. 296. The calculated isotherm of 1250 °C in the Fe–Cu–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [543]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [45].

Fig. 297. The calculated isotherm of 1200 °C in the Fe–Cu–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [67]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [45].

Fig. 298. The calculated isotherm of 1150 °C in the Fe–Cu–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [543]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [45].

Fig. 299. The calculated isotherm of 1050 °C in the Fe–Cu–Ni system, together with the experimental data points (78Has [543] and 00Qin [554]). The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [45].

Fig. 300. The calculated isotherm of 1000 °C in the Fe–Cu–Ni system, together with the experimental data points (96Ron [553] and 00Qin [554]). The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [45].

Fig. 301. The calculated isotherm of 900 °C in the Fe–Cu–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [552]. Fcc_S denotes the solubility composition. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [45].

Fig. 302. The calculated isotherm of 850 °C in the Fe–Cu–Ni system, together with the experimental data points (78Has [543] and 08Gal [555]). The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [45].

Fig. 303. The calculated isotherm of 600 °C in the Fe–Cu–Ni system, together with smoothed experimental data points (90Gup [551] and 00Qin [554]). The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [45].

Fig. 304. The calculated vertical section of 15 wt-% Ni in the Fe–Cu–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [550]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [45].

Fig. 305. The calculated vertical section of 30 wt-% Ni in the Fe–Cu–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [550]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [45].

Fig. 306. The calculated vertical section of 40 wt-% Ni in the Fe–Cu–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [550]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [45].

Fig. 307. The calculated vertical section of $w_{Fe} = w_{Ni}$ in the Fe-Cu-Ni system, together with the experimental data points [555]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [45].

Fig. 308. The calculated vertical section of $w_{Fe} = w_{Cu}$ in the Fe-Cu-Ni system, together with the experimental data points [550]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [45].

Fig. 309. The calculated activity of Fe in liquid Fe–Cu–Ni alloys at 1350 °C, together with the experimental data points [556]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [45]. The reference state used is pure liquid Fe.

Fig. 310. The calculated activity of Cu in liquid Fe–Cu–Ni alloys at 1350 °C, together with the experimental data points [556]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [45]. The reference state used is pure liquid Cu.

Fig. 311. The calculated activity of Fe in fcc Fe–Cu–Ni alloys at 1000 °C and 800 °C and at $x_{Ni} = 0.40$, together with the experimental data points [365]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [45]. The reference state used is pure fcc Fe at 1000 °C and pure bcc Fe at 800 °C.

Fig. 312. The calculated activity of Fe and Ni in fcc Fe–Cu–Ni alloys at 1247 °C and along section $4x_{Ni} + 3x_{Cu} = 3$, together with the experimental data points [557]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [45]. The reference states used are pure fcc Fe and Ni.

Fig. 313. The calculated enthalpy of formation for fcc Fe–Cu–Ni alloys at 1050 °C, together with the experimental data points [558]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Jansson [45]. The reference states used are pure fcc components.

4.13 The Fe–Cu–Si system

Experimental studies on the Fe–Cu–Si system have been reviewed in [436, 440, 561, 562] and a thermodynamic assessment has been given in [67, 72, 83–85]. The system was later reassessed for the IAD as its binary data differs from those presented in [67, 72, 83–85]. The present work reviews this description and presents its experimental verification.

4.13.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 118 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 119 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 120.

Table 118. Phases and their modeling in the Fe–Cu–Si description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Cu,Fe,Si), substitutional, RKM
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Cu,Fe,Si), substitutional, RKM
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Cu,Fe,Si), substitutional, RKM
hcp_A3 (\approx hcp)	(Cu,Fe,Si), substitutional, RKM
Cu ₅₆ Si ₁₁ (\approx γ)	(Cu) ₅₆ (Si) ₁₁ , stoichiometric
Cu ₃₃ Si ₇ (\approx σ)	(Cu) ₃₃ (Si) ₇ , stoichiometric
Cu ₁₅ Si ₄ (\approx ϵ)	(Cu) ₁₅ (Si) ₄ , stoichiometric
Cu ₁₉ Si ₆ (\approx η)	(Cu) ₁₉ (Si) ₆ , stoichiometric
Fe ₂ Si	(Fe) ₂ (Si), stoichiometric
Fe ₅ Si ₃	(Fe) ₅ (Si) ₃ , stoichiometric
FeSi	(Fe)(Si), stoichiometric
FeSi ₂ -H	(Fe) ₃ (Si) ₇ , stoichiometric
FeSi ₂ -L	(Fe)(Si) ₂ , stoichiometric
dia_A4 (\approx dia)	pure Si

Note: RKM = Redlich–Kister–Muggianu excess model.

Table 119. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Fe–Cu–Si according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference
3 isotherms at 1450 °C, 1350 °C, and 1250 °C	[83]
3 isotherms at 1300 °C, 1200 °C, and 1100 °C	[67]
3 isotherms at 1000 °C, 900 °C, and 800 °C	[72]
2 vertical sections at 30 and 70 at-% Cu	[85]
Heat content of liquid alloys at 1800 °C	[72]
Isoactivity line of $a_{\text{Si}} = 5.2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ in liquid alloys at 1560 °C	[380]

Table 120. The thermodynamic description of the Fe–Cu–Si system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Fe,Si)</i>	
$L_{\text{Cu,Fe}}^{\text{L}} = (+35626 - 2.19T) + (-1530 + 1.153T)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Fe}})$	[9]
$+ (+12714 - 5.186T)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Fe}})^2 + (+1177)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Fe}})^3$	[50]
$L_{\text{Cu,Si}}^{\text{L}} = (-38764 + 12T) + (-52431 + 27.457T)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Si}})$	
$+ (-29427 + 14.775T)(x_{\text{Cu}} - x_{\text{Si}})^2$	
$L_{\text{Fe,Si}}^{\text{L}} = (-164435 + 41.977T) + (-21.523T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Si}})$	[534]
$+ (5220 + 5.726T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Si}})^2 + (-28955 + 26.275T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Si}})^3$	
$L_{\text{Cu,Fe,Si}}^{\text{L}} = 0$	[85]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

Table 120 (continued)

Equation	Reference
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Fe,Si)</i>	
$L_{Cu,Fe}^{bcc} = (+39676 - 4.732T)$	[9]
$L_{Cu,Si}^{bcc} = (-26447 + 10.216) + (-47275 - 8.517T)(x_{Cu} - x_{Si})$	[50]
$L_{Fe,Si}^{bcc} = (-211000 + 80.2T) + (37000 - 74.5T)(x_{Fe} - x_{Si})$ $+ (-10000 + 41.2T)(x_{Fe} - x_{Si})^2$	IAD
$L_{Cu,Fe,Si}^{bcc} = (-170000 + 64T)$	IAD
$T_c^{bcc} = 1043x_{Fe} + x_{Fe}x_{Si} (+504(x_{Fe} - x_{Si}))$	[536]
$\beta^{bcc} = 2.22x_{Fe}$	[96]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Fe,Si)</i>	
$L_{Cu,Fe}^{fcc} = (+43320 - 6.944T) + (+6069 - 2.837T)(x_{Cu} - x_{Fe}) + (+3629)(x_{Cu} - x_{Fe})^2$	[9]
$L_{Cu,Si}^{fcc} = (-42204 + 13.891T) + (-1102 - 18.178T)(x_{Cu} - x_{Si})$	[50]
$L_{Fe,Si}^{fcc} = (-125248 + 41.166T) + (-142708)(x_{Fe} - x_{Si}) + (89907)(x_{Fe} - x_{Si})^2$	[536]
$L_{Cu,Fe,Si}^{fcc} = (-175000 + 100T)$	IAD
$T_c^{fcc} = -201x_{Fe}$	[96]
$\beta^{fcc} = -2.1x_{Fe}$	[96]
<i>hcp (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cu,Fe,Si)</i>	
$L_{Cu,Fe}^{hcp} = (+40000 - 4T)$	[42]
$L_{Cu,Si}^{hcp} = (-26799 - 0.732T) + (-28065 - 0.029T)(x_{Cu} - x_{Si})$	[50]
$L_{Fe,Si}^{hcp} = (-123468 + 41.166T) + (-142708)(x_{Fe} - x_{Si}) + (89907)(x_{Fe} - x_{Si})^2$	[563]
<i>Fe₂Si (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents: Fe:Si)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Si}^{o,Fe_2Si} = 2G_{Fe}^{o,bcc} + G_{Si}^{o,dia} + (-71256.6 - 10.62T)$	[536]
<i>Fe₅Si₃ (2 sublattices, sites: 5:3, constituents: Fe:Si)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Si}^{o,Fe_5Si_3} = 5G_{Fe}^{o,bcc} + 3G_{Si}^{o,dia} + (-241144 + 2.16T)$	[536]
<i>FeSi (2 sublattices, sites: 1:1, constituents: Fe:Si)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Si}^{o,FeSi} = G_{Fe}^{o,bcc} + G_{Si}^{o,dia} + (-72761.2 + 4.44T)$	[536]
<i>FeSi₂-H (2 sublattices, sites: 3:7, constituents: Fe:Si)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Si}^{o,FeSi_2-H} = 3G_{Fe}^{o,bcc} + 7G_{Si}^{o,dia} + (-196490 - 9.2T)$	[536]
<i>FeSi₂-L (2 sublattices, sites: 1:2, constituents: Fe:Si)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Si}^{o,FeSi_2-L} = G_{Fe}^{o,bcc} + 2G_{Si}^{o,dia} + (-82149 + 10.44T)$	[536]
<i>Cu₅₆Si₁₁ (γ) (2 sublattices, sites: 56:11, constituents: Cu:Si)</i>	
$G_{Cu:Si}^{o,γ} = 56G_{Cu}^{o,fcc} + 11G_{Si}^{o,dia} + (+70116 - 393.605T)$	[50]
<i>Cu₃₃Si₇ (σ) (2 sublattices, sites: 33:7, constituents: Cu:Si)</i>	
$G_{Cu:Si}^{o,σ} = 33G_{Cu}^{o,fcc} + 7G_{Si}^{o,dia} + (+78896 - 278.656T)$	[50]
<i>Cu₁₅Si₄ (ε) (2 sublattices, sites: 15:4, constituents: Cu:Si)</i>	
$G_{Cu:Si}^{o,ε} = 15G_{Cu}^{o,fcc} + 4G_{Si}^{o,dia} + (+23579 - 127.663T)$	[50]
<i>Cu₁₉Si₆ (η) (2 sublattices, sites: 19:6, constituents: Cu:Si)</i>	
$G_{Cu:Si}^{o,η} = 19G_{Cu}^{o,fcc} + 6G_{Si}^{o,dia} + (+34193 - 179.94T)$	[50]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

4.13.2 Results

The results of the calculations according to the IAD and Zhao *et al.* [85] together with the experimental data (Table 119) are presented in Figures 314–327. The agreement is reasonably good in both calculations. Additional phase equilibrium data for the system are available from Vogel and Horstmann [564], but these data do not agree so well with the calculations.

Fig. 314. The calculated (IAD) liquidus projection in the Fe–Cu–Si system. Also shown by the dotted lines are the calculated liquidus isotherms between 1300 °C and 1980 °C.

Fig. 315. The calculated isotherm of 1450 °C in the Fe–Cu–Si system, together with the experimental data points [83]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zhao *et al.* [85].

Fig. 316. The calculated isotherm of 1350 °C in the Fe–Cu–Si system, together with the experimental data points [83]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zhao *et al.* [85].

Fig. 317. The calculated isotherm of 1300 °C in the Fe–Cu–Si system, together with the experimental data points [67]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zhao *et al.* [85].

Fig. 318. The calculated isotherm of 1250 °C in the Fe–Cu–Si system, together with the experimental data points [83]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zhao *et al.* [85].

Fig. 319. The calculated isotherm of 1200 °C in the Fe–Cu–Si system, together with the experimental data points [67]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zhao *et al.* [85].

Fig. 320. The calculated isotherm of 1100 °C in the Fe–Cu–Si system, together with the experimental data points [72]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zhao *et al.* [85].

Fig. 321. The calculated isotherm of 1000 °C in the Fe–Cu–Si system, together with the experimental data points [72]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zhao *et al.* [85].

Fig. 322. The calculated isotherm of 900 °C in the Fe–Cu–Si system, together with the experimental data points [72]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zhao *et al.* [85].

Fig. 323. The calculated isotherm of 800 °C in the Fe–Cu–Si system, together with the experimental data points [72]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Zhao *et al.* [85].

Fig. 324. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 30 at-% Cu in the Fe–Cu–Si system, together with the experimental data points [85]. The calculations are very close to those by Zhao *et al.* [85].

Fig. 325. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 70 at-% Cu in the Fe-Cu-Si system, together with the experimental data points [85]. The calculations are very close to those by Zhao *et al.* [85].

Fig. 326. The calculated heat content in Fe-Cu-12 wt-% Si melts at 1800 °C, together with the experimental data points [72]. The solid line refers to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted line refers to those by Zhao *et al.* [85].

Fig. 327. The calculated isoactivity line $a_{\text{Si}} = 5.2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ in Fe–Cu–Si melts at 1560 °C, together with the experimental data points (64Bow [380]). The solid line refers to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted line refers to those by Zhao *et al.* [85].

4.14 The Fe–Mn–Mo system

Experimental studies on the Fe–Mn–Mo system have been reviewed by Raynor and Rivlin [565] and a thermodynamic assessment has been given in the IAD. The present work reviews this description and presents its experimental verification.

4.14.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 121 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 122 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 123.

Table 121. Phases and their modeling in the Fe–Mn–Mo description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Fe,Mn,Mo), substitutional, RKM
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Fe,Mn,Mo), substitutional, RKM
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Fe,Mn,Mo), substitutional, RKM
cbcc_A12 (\approx cbcc)	(Fe,Mn,Mo), substitutional, RKM
cub_A13 (\approx cub)	(Fe,Mn,Mo), substitutional, RKM
Mu (\approx μ)	(Fe) ₇ (Mo) ₂ (Fe,Mo) ₄ , sublattice, RKM
R	(Fe) ₂₇ (Mo) ₁₄ (Fe,Mn,Mo) ₁₂ , sublattice, RKM
Sigma (\approx σ)	(Fe) ₈ (Mo) ₄ (Fe,Mo) ₁₈ , sublattice, RKM
Fe ₂ Mo (\approx λ)	(Fe) ₂ (Mo), stoichiometric
Mn ₅ Mo ₄	(Mn) ₅ (Mo) ₄ , stoichiometric
Mn ₁₆ Mo ₉	(Mn) ₁₆ (Mo) ₉ , stoichiometric

Note: RKM = Redlich–Kister–Muggianu excess model.

Table 122. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Fe–Mn–Mo according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference
4 isotherms at 1100 °C, 1000 °C, 950 °C, and 900 °C	[566]
1 vertical section at $w_{\text{Mo}}:w_{\text{Mn}} = 7:4$	[566]
Activity coefficient $\gamma_{\text{Mn}}^{\text{Mo}}$ in liquid alloys at 1560 °C	[490]

Table 123. The thermodynamic description of the Fe–Mn–Mo system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe,Mn,Mo)</i>	
$L_{\text{Fe,Mn}}^{\text{L}} = (-3950 + 0.489T) + (1145)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Mn}})$	[491]
$L_{\text{Fe,Mo}}^{\text{L}} = (-6900 - 0.23T) + (-9000 + 3.85T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Mo}})$	IAD
$L_{\text{Mn,Mo}}^{\text{L}} = (-22500 + 13.83T) + (+23600 - 10.82T)(x_{\text{Mn}} - x_{\text{Mo}})$	IAD
$L_{\text{Fe,Mn,Mo}}^{\text{L}} = (+3000)$	IAD
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe,Mn,Mo)</i>	
$L_{\text{Fe,Mn}}^{\text{bcc}} = (-2759 + 1.237T)$	[491]
$L_{\text{Fe,Mo}}^{\text{bcc}} = (+36818 - 9.141T) + (-362 - 5.724T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Mo}})$	[13]
$L_{\text{Mn,Mo}}^{\text{bcc}} = (+49900 - 14.30T) + (-7150)(x_{\text{Mn}} - x_{\text{Mo}})$	IAD
$L_{\text{Fe,Mn,Mo}}^{\text{bcc}} = (-38000 + 30T)$	IAD
$T_{\text{c}}^{\text{bcc}} = 1043x_{\text{Fe}} - 580x_{\text{Mn}} + x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Mn}}(123) + x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Mo}}(335 + 526(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Mo}}))$	[491]
$\beta^{\text{bcc}} = 2.22x_{\text{Fe}} - 0.27x_{\text{Mn}}$	[96]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

Table 123 (continued)

Equation	Reference
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe,Mn,Mo)</i>	
$L_{Fe,Mn}^{fcc} = (-7762 + 3.865T) + (-259)(x_{Fe} - x_{Mn})$	[491]
$L_{Fe,Mo}^{fcc} = (+28347 - 17.691T)$	[13]
$L_{Mn,Mo}^{fcc} = (+8500)$	IAD
$L_{Fe,Mn,Mo}^{fcc} = (+40000)$	IAD
$T_c^{fcc} = -201x_{Fe} - 1620x_{Mn} + x_{Fe}x_{Mn}(-2282 - 2068(x_{Fe} - x_{Mn}))$	[491]
$\beta^{fcc} = -2.1x_{Fe} - 1.86x_{Mn}$	[96]
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe,Mn,Mo)</i>	
$L_{Fe,Mn}^{bcc} = (-10184)$	[491]
$L_{Mn,Mo}^{bcc} = (+4700)$	IAD
$L_{Fe,Mn,Mo}^{bcc} = (+40000)$	IAD
<i>cub (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe,Mn,Mo)</i>	
$L_{Fe,Mn}^{cub} = (-11518 + 2.819T)$	[491]
$L_{Mn,Mo}^{cub} = (+11500)$	IAD
$L_{Fe,Mn,Mo}^{cub} = (+40000)$	IAD
<i>Mu (μ) (3 sublattices, sites: 7:2:4, constituents: Fe:Mo:Fe,Mo)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Mo:Fe}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 2G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 4G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (+39475 - 6.032T)$	[13]
$G_{Fe:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 6G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (-46663 - 5.891T)$	[13]
<i>R (3 sublattices, sites: 27:14:12, constituents: Fe:Mo:Fe,Mn,Mo)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Mo:Fe}^{\circ,R} = 27G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 14G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 12G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (-77487 - 50.486T)$	[13]
$G_{Fe:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,R} = 27G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 26G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+313474 - 289.472T)$	[13]
$G_{Fe:Mo:Mn}^{\circ,R} = 27G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 14G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 12G_{Mn}^{\circ,cbcc} + (-286000)$	IAD
<i>Sigma (σ) (3 sublattices, sites: 8:4:18, constituents: Fe:Mo:Fe,Mo)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Mo:Fe}^{\circ,\sigma} = 8G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 4G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 18G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (-1813 - 27.272T)$	[13]
$G_{Fe:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,\sigma} = 8G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 22G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+83326 - 69.618T)$	[13]
$L_{Fe:Mo:Fe,Mo}^{\sigma} = (+222909)$	[13]
<i>Fe₂Mo (λ) (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents: Fe:Mo)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Mo}^{\circ,\lambda} = 2G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (-10798 - 0.132T)$	[161]
<i>Mn₅Mo₄ (2 sublattices, sites: 0.5555:0.4445, constituents: Mn:Mo)</i>	
$G_{Mn:Mo}^{\circ,Mn_5Mo_4} = 0.5555G_{Mn}^{\circ,cbcc} + 0.4445G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+2000 - 4.4T)$	IAD
<i>Mn₁₆Mo₉ (2 sublattices, sites: 0.64:0.36, constituents: Mn:Mo)</i>	
$G_{Mn:Mo}^{\circ,Mn_{16}Mo_9} = 0.64G_{Mn}^{\circ,cbcc} + 0.36G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+4758 - 6.1T)$	IAD

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

4.14.2 Results

The results of the calculations according to the IAD together with the experimental data (Table 122) are presented in Figures 328–335 and Table 124. The agreement is reasonable. Note that the calculated liquidus projection of Figure 328 is tentative, as

there are no experimental data for the liquid phase. In Figure 334, note that the λ phase of the calculations is described by the symbol X since the R phase could not be distinguished from λ by Ishida *et al.* [566].

Table 124. The calculated (IAD) invariant points of the Fe–Mn–Mo system.

Reaction	Code	Temp. [°C]	Content in Liq [wt-%]	
			Mn	Mo
$L + \sigma = R + bcc_2$	U ₁	1364	13.45	41.72
$L + R = bcc_2 + bcc_1$	P	1280	20.67	37.33
$L + Mn_5Mo_4 = bcc_1 + bcc_2$	U ₂	1211	48.82	30.93

Fig. 328. The calculated (IAD) liquidus projection of the Fe–Mn–Mo system. Also shown by the dotted lines are the calculated liquidus isotherms between 1900 °C and 1210 °C.

Fig. 329. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1250 °C of the Fe-Mn-Mo system.

Fig. 330. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1100 °C in the Fe-rich corner of the Fe-Mn-Mo system, together with the experimental data points (73Ish [566]).

Fig. 331. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1000 °C in the Fe-rich corner of the Fe–Mn–Mo system, together with the experimental data points and suggested phase regions shown by the dotted lines (73lsh [566]).

Fig. 332. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 950 °C in the Fe-rich corner of the Fe–Mn–Mo system, together with the experimental data points and suggested phase regions shown by the dotted lines (73lsh [566]).

Fig. 333. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 900 °C in the Fe-rich corner of the Fe–Mn–Mo system, together with the experimental data points and suggested phase regions shown by the dotted lines (73Ish [566]).

Fig. 334. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of $w_{Mo}:w_{Mn} = 7:4$ in the Fe-rich corner of the Fe–Mn–Mo system, together with the experimental data points [566].

Fig. 335. The calculated (IAD) activity coefficient γ_{Mn}^{Mo} in liquid Fe–Mn–Mo alloys at 1560 °C, together with smoothed experimental data points (75Muk [490]).

4.15 The Fe–Mn–Ni system

Experimental studies on the Fe–Mn–Ni system have been reviewed by Raynor and Rivlin [567] and Raghavan [568], while a thermodynamic assessment has been given by Kundrat [86] and Zhang *et al.* [87]. The system was later reassessed for the IAD as its binary Fe–Ni and Mn–Ni data differs from those by Kundrat [86] and Zhang *et al.* [87]. The present work reviews this description and presents its experimental verification.

4.15.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 125 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 126 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 127.

Table 125. Phases and their modeling in the Fe–Mn–Ni description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Fe,Mn,Ni), substitutional, RKM
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Fe,Mn,Ni), substitutional, RKM
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Fe,Mn,Ni), substitutional, RKM
cbcc_A12 (\approx cbcc)	(Fe,Mn,Ni), substitutional, RKM
cub_A13 (\approx cub)	(Fe,Mn,Ni), substitutional, RKM
MnNi ($\approx \lambda_1$)	(Mn)(Ni), stoichiometric
Mn ₂ Ni ($\approx \lambda_2$)	(Mn) ₂ (Ni), stoichiometric
MnNi ₂ ($\approx \lambda_3$)	(Mn)(Ni) ₂ , stoichiometric

Note: RKM = Redlich–Kister–Muggianu excess model.

Table 126. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Fe–Mn–Ni according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference
Liquidus projection	[544]
Liquidus temperatures in the Fe-rich corner	[86]
3 isothermal sections at 1519 °C, 1505 °C and 1489 °C	[86]
8 vertical sections at 10, 20 and 30 wt-% Mn, at 10, 20 and 30 wt-% Ni, at 10 wt-% Fe and at $w_{Ni} = w_{Mn}$	[86, 87, 544]
Enthalpy of melting	[569]
Activity coefficient γ_{Mn}^{Ni} in liquid alloys at 1570 °C	[570]
Iso-activities of Mn in fcc alloys at 959 °C	[394]

Table 127. The thermodynamic description of the Fe–Mn–Ni system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe, Mn, Ni)</i>	
$L_{Fe,Mn}^L = (-3950 + 0.489T) + (1145)(x_{Fe} - x_{Mn})$	[491]
$L_{Fe,Ni}^L = (-16911 + 5.162T) + (+10180 - 4.147T)(x_{Fe} - x_{Ni})$	[30]
$L_{Mn,Ni}^L = (-85853 + 22.715T) + (-1620 + 4.902T)(x_{Mn} - x_{Ni})$	[52]
$L_{Fe,Mn,Ni}^L = (+15000)$	IAD
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe, Mn, Ni)</i>	
$L_{Fe,Mn}^{bcc} = (-2759 + 1.237T)$	[491]
$L_{Fe,Ni}^{bcc} = (-957 - 1.287T) + (+1789 - 1.929T)(x_{Fe} - x_{Ni})$	[45]
$L_{Mn,Ni}^{bcc} = (-51785 + 3.5T) + (6700)(x_{Mn} - x_{Ni})$	[52]
$L_{Fe,Mn,Ni}^{bcc} = (+15000)$	IAD
$T_c^{bcc} = 1043x_{Fe} - 580x_{Mn} + 575x_{Ni} + x_{Fe}x_{Mn}(123)$	[491]
$\beta^{bcc} = 2.22x_{Fe} - 0.27x_{Mn} + 0.85x_{Ni}$	[491]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

Table 127 (continued)

Equation	Reference
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe,Mn,Ni)</i>	
$L_{\text{Fe,Mn}}^{\text{fcc}} = (-7762 + 3.865T) + (-259)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Mn}})$	[491]
$L_{\text{Fe,Ni}}^{\text{fcc}} = (-12054 + 3.274T) + (+11082 - 4.45T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}}) + (-726)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})^2$	[45]
$L_{\text{Mn,Ni}}^{\text{fcc}} = (-58173 + 10.5T) + (6300)(x_{\text{Mn}} - x_{\text{Ni}})$	[52]
$L_{\text{Fe,Mn,Ni}}^{\text{fcc}} = (+15000)$	IAD
$T_{\text{c}}^{\text{fcc}} = -201x_{\text{Fe}} - 1620x_{\text{Mn}} + 633x_{\text{Ni}} + x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Mn}}(-2282 - 2068(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Mn}}))$ $+ x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Ni}}(2133 - 682(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}}))$	[30]
$\beta^{\text{fcc}} = -2.1x_{\text{Fe}} - 1.86x_{\text{Mn}} + 0.52x_{\text{Ni}} + x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Ni}}(9.55 + 7.23(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}}))$ $+ 5.93(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})^2 + 6.18(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})^3$	[30]
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe,Mn,Ni)</i>	
$L_{\text{Fe,Mn}}^{\text{bcc}} = (-10184)$	[491]
$L_{\text{Mn,Ni}}^{\text{bcc}} = (-53000 + 30T) + (-58000 + 30T)(x_{\text{Mn}} - x_{\text{Ni}})$	[52]
<i>cub (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe,Mn,Ni)</i>	
$L_{\text{Fe,Mn}}^{\text{cub}} = (-11518 + 2.819T)$	[491]
$L_{\text{Mn,Ni}}^{\text{cub}} = (-63000 + 29T) + (-15000)(x_{\text{Mn}} - x_{\text{Ni}})$	[52]
<i>MnNi (λ_1) (2 sublattices, sites: 1:1, constituents: Mn:Ni)</i>	
$G_{\text{Mn:Ni}}^{\circ,\lambda_1} = G_{\text{Mn}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + (-36300)$	[52]
<i>Mn₂Ni (λ_2) (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents: Mn:Ni)</i>	
$G_{\text{Mn:Ni}}^{\circ,\lambda_2} = 2G_{\text{Mn}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + (-43900)$	[52]
<i>MnNi₂ (λ_3) (2 sublattices, sites: 1:2, constituents: Mn:Ni)</i>	
$G_{\text{Mn:Ni}}^{\circ,\lambda_3} = G_{\text{Mn}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + 2G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + (-48100)$	[52]

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

4.15.2 Results

The results of the calculations by IAD together with the experimental data (Table 126) are presented in Figures 336–349. The agreement is reasonably good and similar to that achieved by Zhang *et al.* [87]. Additional experimental data for the fcc-liquid equilibrium along the section $x_{\text{Ni}} = x_{\text{Mn}}$ is available from Kocherzhinskii *et al.* [571], but these data do not agree so well with the other experimental studies [86, 87, 544] and the calculations.

Fig. 336. The calculated (IAD) liquidus projection in the Fe–Mn–Ni system (thick lines). Also shown by the thin lines are the calculated liquidus isotherms between 1500 °C and 1100 °C, and by the thin dotted lines those determined experimentally (13Par [544]).

Fig. 337. The calculated (IAD) liquidus temperatures in the Fe-rich corner of the Fe–Mn–Ni system, together with the experimental data points (86Kun [86]).

Fig. 338. The calculated (IAD) isotherms at 1519 °C, 1505 °C, and 1489 °C in the in the Fe-rich corner of the Fe–Mn–Ni system, together with the experimental data points (86Kun [86]).

Fig. 339. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 10 wt-% Mn in the Fe–Mn–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [544].

Fig. 340. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 20 wt-% Mn in the Fe-Mn-Ni system, together with the experimental data points [544].

Fig. 341. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 30 wt-% Mn in the Fe-Mn-Ni system, together with the experimental data points [544].

Fig. 342. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 10 wt-% Ni in the Fe–Mn–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [544].

Fig. 343. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 20 wt-% Ni in the Fe–Mn–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [544].

Fig. 344. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 30 wt-% Ni in the Fe–Mn–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [544].

Fig. 345. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 10 wt-% Fe in the Fe–Mn–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [544].

Fig. 346. The calculated (IAD) vertical section along the section $w_{Ni} = w_{Mn}$ in the Fe-Mn-Ni system, together with the experimental data points (13Par [544], 86Kun [86], and 09Zha [87]).

Fig. 347. The calculated (IAD) enthalpy of melting of Fe-Mn-Ni alloys, together with the experimental data points (87Dan [569]).

Fig. 348. The calculated (IAD) activity coefficient γ_{Mn}^{Ni} in liquid Fe–Mn–Ni alloys at 1570 °C, together with smoothed experimental data points (74Muk [570]).

Fig. 349. The calculated (IAD) iso-activity lines of Mn in fcc Fe–Mn–Ni alloys at 959 °C, together with the experimental data points (64Smi [394]). The reference state used is pure fcc Mn.

4.16 The Fe–Mo–Ni system

Experimental studies on the Fe–Mo–Ni system have been reviewed by Raynor and Rivlin [572] and Raghavan [573,574]. A thermodynamic assessment of the Fe–Mo–Ni system has been given by Frisk [88]. The description by Frisk [88] was later modified for the IAD to improve the agreement between the experimental and calculated phase equilibria including the liquid Mu and P phases. In addition, a simpler description was introduced for the Delta (MoNi) phase. The present work reviews the Fe–Mo–Ni description according to the IAD and presents its experimental verification.

4.16.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 128 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 129 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 130. Note that the Delta phase was formulated by IAD as Mo(Fe,Ni) whereas Frisk [88] treated it as a more complex phase, formulated as $(\text{Fe,Ni})_{24}(\text{Fe,Mo,Ni})_{20}\text{Mo}_{12}$.

Table 128. Phases and their modeling in the Fe–Mo–Ni description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Fe,Mo,Ni), substitutional, RKM
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Fe,Mo,Ni), substitutional, RKM
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Fe,Mo,Ni), substitutional, RKM
Mu (\approx μ)	(Fe,Ni) ₇ (Mo) ₂ (Fe,Mo,Ni) ₄ , sublattice, RKM
P	(Fe,Ni) ₂₄ (Fe,Mo,Ni) ₂₀ (Mo) ₁₂ , sublattice, RKM
R	(Fe,Ni) ₂₇ (Mo) ₁₄ (Fe,Mo,Ni) ₁₂ , sublattice, RKM
Sigma (\approx σ)	(Fe,Ni) ₈ (Mo) ₄ (Fe,Mo,Ni) ₁₈ , sublattice, RKM
Delta (\approx $\delta \approx$ MoNi, dissolving Fe)	(Mo)(Fe,Ni), sublattice, RKM
Fe ₂ Mo (\approx λ , dissolving Ni)	(Fe,Ni)(Mo), sublattice, RKM
MoNi ₃	(Mo) ₂ (Ni), stoichiometric
MoNi ₄	(Mo)(Ni) ₂ , stoichiometric

Note: RKM = Redlich–Kister–Muggianu excess model.

Table 129. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Fe–Mo–Ni according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
3 isotherms, at 1490 °C, 1425 °C, and 1375 °C	[575]
2 vertical sections at $w_{\text{Mo}}:w_{\text{Ni}} = 0.67$ and $w_{\text{Ni}}:w_{\text{Fe}} = 9$	[575–577]
5 isothermal sections at 1270 °C, 1200 °C, 1100 °C, 1000 °C, and 950 °C	[88, 577–580]
4 Fe-rich isothermal sections at 1250 °C, 1100 °C, 1000 °C, and 800 °C	[578–580]

Table 130. The thermodynamic description of the Fe–Mo–Ni system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe, Mo, Ni)</i>	
$L_{\text{Fe,Mo}}^{\text{L}} = (-6900 - 0.23T) + (-9000 + 3.85T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Mo}})$	IAD
$L_{\text{Fe,Ni}}^{\text{L}} = (-16911 + 5.162T) + (+10180 - 4.147T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})$	[5]
$L_{\text{Mo,Ni}}^{\text{L}} = (-46540 + 19.53T) + (+2915)(x_{\text{Mo}} - x_{\text{Ni}})$	[55]
$L_{\text{Fe,Mo,Ni}}^{\text{L}} = (+220000 - 100T)x_{\text{Fe}} + (+200000 - 100T)x_{\text{Mo}} + (+210000 - 100T)x_{\text{Ni}}$	IAD
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe, Mo, Ni)</i>	
$L_{\text{Fe,Mo}}^{\text{bcc}} = (+36818 - 9.141T) + (-362 - 5.724T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Mo}})$	[13]
$L_{\text{Fe,Ni}}^{\text{bcc}} = (-957 - 1.287T) + (+1789 - 1.929T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})$	[45]
$L_{\text{Mo,Ni}}^{\text{bcc}} = (+46422)$	[55]
$L_{\text{Fe,Mo,Ni}}^{\text{bcc}} = (-65000 + 20T)$	IAD
$T_{\text{c}}^{\text{bcc}} = 1043x_{\text{Fe}} + 575x_{\text{Ni}} + x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Mo}}(335 + 526(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Mo}}))$	[88]
$\beta^{\text{bcc}} = 2.22x_{\text{Fe}} + 0.85x_{\text{Ni}}$	[88]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe, Mo, Ni)</i>	
$L_{\text{Fe,Mo}}^{\text{fcc}} = (+28347 - 17.691T)$	[13]
$L_{\text{Fe,Ni}}^{\text{fcc}} = (-12054 + 3.274T) + (+11082 - 4.45T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}}) + (-726)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})^2$	[45]
$L_{\text{Mo,Ni}}^{\text{fcc}} = (+4804 - 5.96T) + (+10880)(x_{\text{Mo}} - x_{\text{Ni}})$	[55]
$L_{\text{Fe,Mo,Ni}}^{\text{fcc}} = (-200000 + 160T)x_{\text{Fe}} + (+12000 - 60T)x_{\text{Mo}} + (+80000)x_{\text{Ni}}$	IAD
$T_{\text{c}}^{\text{fcc}} = -201x_{\text{Fe}} + 633x_{\text{Ni}} + x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Ni}}(2133 - 682(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}}))$	[88]
$\beta^{\text{fcc}} = -2.1x_{\text{Fe}} + 0.52x_{\text{Ni}} + x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Ni}}(9.55 + 7.23(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}}) + 5.93(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})^2 + 6.18(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})^3)$	[88]
<i>Mu (μ) (3 sublattices, sites: 7:2:4, constituents: Fe, Ni:Mo:Fe, Mo, Ni)</i>	
$G_{\text{Fe:Mo:Fe}}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 2G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + 4G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + (+39475 - 6.032T)$	[13]
$G_{\text{Fe:Mo:Mo}}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 6G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + (-46663 - 5.891T)$	[13]
$G_{\text{Fe:Mo:Ni}}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 2G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + 4G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + (+300000 - 200T)$	IAD
$G_{\text{Ni:Mo:Fe}}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 2G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + 4G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + (+700000 - 200T)$	IAD
$G_{\text{Ni:Mo:Ni}}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 2G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + 4G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + (+400000 - 200T)$	IAD
$G_{\text{Ni:Mo:Mo}}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 6G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + (+9000 - 35T)$	IAD

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

Table 130 (continued)

Equation	Reference
<i>P</i> (3 sublattices, sites: 24:20:12, constituents: Fe,Ni:Fe,Mo,Ni:Mo)	
$G_{Fe:Fe:Mo}^{\circ,P} = 24G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 20G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + 12G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+111361)$	[88]
$G_{Fe:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,P} = 24G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 32G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+362525 - 332.7T)$	[88]
$G_{Fe:Ni:Mo}^{\circ,P} = 24G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 20G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + 12G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+111361)$	[88]
$G_{Ni:Fe:Mo}^{\circ,P} = 24G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + 20G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + 12G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+200000 - 90T)$	IAD
$G_{Ni:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,P} = 24G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + 32G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (-15000 - 80T)$	IAD
$G_{Ni:Ni:Mo}^{\circ,P} = 24G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + 20G_{Ni}^{\circ,bcc} + 12G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+190000 - 80T)$	IAD
<i>R</i> (3 sublattices, sites: 27:14:12, constituents: Fe,Ni:Mo:Fe,Mo,Ni)	
$G_{Fe:Mo:Fe}^{\circ,R} = 27G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 14G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 12G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (-77487 - 50.486T)$	[13]
$G_{Fe:Mo:Ni}^{\circ,R} = 27G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 14G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 12G_{Ni}^{\circ,bcc}$	[88]
$G_{Fe:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,R} = 27G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 26G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+313474 - 289.472T)$	[13]
$G_{Ni:Mo:Ni}^{\circ,R} = 27G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + 14G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 12G_{Ni}^{\circ,bcc} + (+100000)$	[88]
$G_{Ni:Mo:Fe}^{\circ,R} = 27G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + 14G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 12G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc}$	[88]
$G_{Ni:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,R} = 27G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + 26G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (-25000)$	IAD
<i>Sigma</i> (σ) (3 sublattices, sites: 8:4:18, constituents: Fe,Ni:Mo:Fe,Mo,Ni)	
$G_{Fe:Mo:Fe}^{\circ,\sigma} = 8oG_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 4oG_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 18oG_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (-1813 - 27.272T)$	[13]
$G_{Fe:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,\sigma} = 8G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 22G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+83326 - 69.618T)$	[13]
$G_{Fe:Mo:Ni}^{\circ,\sigma} = 8G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 4G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 18G_{Ni}^{\circ,bcc} + (+408600 - 200T)$	[88]
$G_{Ni:Mo:Fe}^{\circ,\sigma} = 8G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + 4G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 18G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (+658600 - 200T)$	[88]
$G_{Ni:Mo:Ni}^{\circ,\sigma} = 8G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + 4G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 18G_{Ni}^{\circ,bcc} + (-16385)$	[88]
$G_{Ni:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,\sigma} = 8G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + 22G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+85662)$	[88]
$L_{Fe:Mo:Fe,Mo}^{\circ,\sigma} = (+222909)$	[13]
$L_{Fe,Ni:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,\sigma} = (-164570 - 10T)$	[88]
<i>Delta</i> (δ) (2 sublattices, sites: 1:1, constituents: Mo:Fe,Ni)	
$G_{Mo:Fe}^{\circ,\delta} = G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc}$	IAD
$G_{Mo:Ni}^{\circ,\delta} = G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + (-6000 + 32.5T - 4.6T \ln T)$	IAD
$L_{Mo:Fe,Ni}^{\circ,\delta} = (-4300 - 2T)$	IAD
<i>Fe₂Mo</i> (λ) (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents: Fe,Ni:Mo)	
$G_{Fe:Mo}^{\circ,\lambda} = 2G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (-10798 - 0.132T)$	[161]
$G_{Ni:Mo}^{\circ,\lambda} = 2G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+15000)$	IAD
<i>MoNi₃</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 3:1, constituents: Mo:Ni)	
$G_{Mo:Ni}^{\circ,MoNi_3} = 3G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + (-4300 - 7T)$	IAD
<i>MoNi₄</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 4:1, constituents: Mo:Ni)	
$G_{Mo:Ni}^{\circ,MoNi_4} = 4G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + (-4600 - 9T)$	IAD

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

4.16.2 Results

The results of the calculations according to the IAD and Frisk [88] together with the experimental data (Table 129) are presented in Figures 350–362 and Table 131. The agreement is reasonably good in both calculations, though only some of the results by Frisk [88] are reviewed.

Table 131. The calculated (IAD) invariant points of the Fe–Mo–Ni system

Reaction	Code	Temp. [°C]	Content in Liq [wt-%]	
			Mo	Ni
$L + \sigma + P = \mu$	P	1451	9.46	37.06
$L + R = P + \mu$	U ₁	1448	8.50	37.76
$L + \sigma = \text{bcc} + P$	U ₂	1443	42.39	50.05
$L + R = \text{bcc} + \mu$	U ₃	1421	9.46	33.17
$L + \text{bcc} = P + \sigma$	U ₄	1379	47.77	49.76
$L + \text{bcc} = \text{fcc} + \mu$	U ₅	1373	19.39	26.57
$L + \mu = \text{fcc} + P$	U ₆	1361	43.60	31.40
$L + P = \text{fcc} + \sigma$	U ₇	1331	52.06	44.70

In Figures 351 and 352, note the somewhat moderate agreement with the liquidus temperatures of the Fe-rich alloys by Schürmann *et al.* [575] and the solidus temperatures by Bamberger *et al.* [576]. The agreement according to the IAD, however, is slightly better. The inconsistency with the former measurements cannot be avoided without losing the good agreement for the bcc-liquid equilibrium of the Fe–Mo system according to the IAD.

Fig. 350. The calculated (IAD) liquidus projection of the Fe–Mo–Ni system. Also shown by the dotted lines are the calculated liquidus isotherms between 2200 °C to 1365 °C.

Fig. 351. The calculated liquidus isotherms of 1490 °C, 1425 °C, and 1375 °C in the Fe-rich corner of the Fe–Mo–Ni system, together with the experimental data points (97Sch [575]). The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Frisk [88]. The thin solid line shows the calculated boundary between the primary bcc and fcc regions.

Fig. 352. The calculated vertical section of $w_{\text{Mo}}:w_{\text{Ni}} = 0.67$ in the Fe–Mo–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [575, 576]. The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by Frisk [88].

In the isothermal sections of Figures 354–362, the main difference between the IAD and Frisk [88] is the less stable P phase and the more stable Mu phase according to the IAD. These two features were supported by the measurements by Loo *et al.* [578] and Gozlan *et al.* [577], respectively. The Mu phase, however, was not allowed to extend to such high Ni contents as proposed by Gozlan *et al.* [577], as this does not agree with the measurements of other studies [88, 580]. In Figure 356 (at 1100 °C), the location of the Ni–Mo side three-phase triangles according to the IAD is better to those by Frisk [88] in regard to the experimental two-phase and three-phase data points.

In Figure 357 (at 1000 °C), the calculations by Frisk [88] show a tiny P region at about 49 at-% Mo and 39 at-% Ni, whereas according to the IAD and the experimental data, the phase is not stable at this temperature. In fact, Loo *et al.* [578] showed that P disappears soon below 1100 °C (agreeing well with the tiny P region according to the IAD in Figure 356), whereas according to Frisk [88], it remains stable down to 950 °C. Note that the calculated P phase region in Figure 353 shows no sign of disappearance regarding P at low temperatures, but this is just due to the suspension of the Delta phase from the calculations. In Figure 362, note the slight solubility of Ni in the Fe_2Mo phase which was allowed according to the experimental data by Odagiri [579].

Fig. 353. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of $w_{Ni}:w_{Fe} = 9$ in the Fe–Mo–Ni system, together with the phase regions determined by Gozlan *et al.* [577] (91Goz) shown by the dotted lines. As Gozlan *et al.* [577] did not detect the Delta phase, it was suspended from the calculations.

Fig. 354. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1270 °C in the Fe–Mo–Ni system, together with the experimental data points indicating tie-line ends [88]. The thin dotted lines show the three-phase triangles calculated by Frisk [88].

Fig. 355. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1200 °C in the Fe–Mo–Ni system, together with the experimental data points indicating tie-line ends [88,577].

Fig. 356. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1100 °C in the Fe–Mo–Ni system, together with the experimental data points indicating tie-line ends [578,579]. The thin dotted lines show the three-phase triangles calculated by Frisk [88].

Fig. 357. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1000 °C in the Fe–Mo–Ni system, together with the experimental data points indicating tie-line ends [88,577,579,580]. The thin dotted lines show the three-phase triangles calculated by Frisk [88] and the symbol (P) refers to the obtained P phase region which is not stable according to the IAD calculations.

Fig. 358. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 950 °C in the Fe–Mo–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [88].

Fig. 359. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1250 °C in the Fe-rich corner of the Fe–Mo–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [579]. The thin dotted lines show the three-phase triangles calculated by Frisk [88].

Fig. 360. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1100 °C in the Fe-rich corner of the Fe–Mo–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [578,579]. The thin dotted lines show the three-phase triangle calculated by Frisk [88].

Fig. 361. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1000 °C in the Fe-rich corner of the Fe–Mo–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [579,580]. The thin dotted lines show the three-phase triangle calculated by Frisk [88].

Fig. 362. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 800 °C in the Fe-rich corner of the Fe–Mo–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [579]. The dotted lines show the three-phase triangles suggested by Odagiri [579].

4.17 The Fe–Mo–Si system

Experimental studies on the Fe–Mo–Si system have been reviewed by Raynor and Rivlin [581] and Raghavan [582], while a thermodynamic assessment has been carried out for use in the IAD. The present work reviews this description and presents its experimental verification.

4.17.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 132 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 133 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 134 .

Table 132. Phases and their modeling in the Fe–Mo–Si description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Fe,Mo,Si), substitutional, RKM
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Fe,Mo,Si), substitutional, RKM
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Fe,Mo,Si), substitutional, RKM
Mu (\approx μ)	(Fe) ₇ (Mo) ₂ (Fe,Mo) ₄ , sublattice, RKM
R	(Fe) ₂₇ (Mo) ₁₄ (Fe,Mo,Si) ₁₂ , sublattice, RKM
Sigma (\approx σ)	(Fe) ₈ (Mo) ₄ (Fe,Mo) ₁₈ , sublattice, RKM
FeSi (dissolving Mo)	(Fe,Mo)(Si), sublattice, RKM
Mo ₅ Si ₃ (dissolving Fe)	(Fe,Mo) ₅ (Si) ₃ , sublattice, RKM
Fe ₂ Mo (\approx λ)	(Fe) ₂ (Mo), stoichiometric
Fe ₂ Si	(Fe) ₂ (Si), stoichiometric
Fe ₅ Si ₃	(Fe) ₅ (Si) ₃ , stoichiometric
FeSi ₂ -H	(Fe) ₃ (Si) ₇ , stoichiometric
FeSi ₂ -L	(Fe)(Si) ₂ , stoichiometric
Mo ₃ Si	(Mo) ₃ (Si), stoichiometric
MoSi ₂	(Mo)(Si) ₂ , stoichiometric
Fe ₂ MoSi ₂	(Fe) _{3.924} (Mo) _{1.854} (Si) _{4.222} , stoichiometric
dia_A4 (\approx dia)	pure Si

Note: RKM = Redlich–Kister–Muggianu excess model.

Table 133. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Fe–Mo–Si according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Liquidus projection	[581, 583]
5 vertical sections at 9 wt-% Si, wt-% Si = 14.5 + 0.2464 wt-% Mo, wt-%Si = 33.464 – 0.3033 wt-% Mo, wt-%Si = 33.464-0.2048 wt-% Mo, and wt-%Si = 58.778 - -1.037 wt-%Mo	[583]
Silicon iso-activities in bcc alloys at 1400 °C	[584]

Table 134. The thermodynamic description of the Fe–Mo–Si system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe,Mo,Si)</i>	
$L_{Fe,Mo}^L = (-6900 - 0.23T) + (-9000 + 3.85T)(x_{Fe} - x_{Mo})$	IAD
$L_{Fe,Si}^L = (-164435 + 41.977T) + (-21.523T)(x_{Fe} - x_{Si}) + (5220 + 5.726T)(x_{Fe} - x_{Si})^2 + (-28955 + 26.275T)(x_{Fe} - x_{Si})^3$	[534]
$L_{Mo,Si}^L = (-146000 + 16.5T) + (+7100 - 3T)(x_{Mo} - x_{Si}) + (+8000 + 12T)(x_{Mo} - x_{Si})^2$	[61]
$L_{Fe,Mo,Si}^L = (+100000 - 80T)x_{Fe} + (+300000 - 80T)x_{Mo} + (-200000 - 80T)x_{Si}$	IAD
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe,Mo,Si)</i>	
$L_{Fe,Mo}^{bcc} = (+36818 - 9.141T) + (-362 - 5.724T)(x_{Fe} - x_{Mo})$	[13]
$L_{Fe,Si}^{bcc} = (-211000 + 80.2T) + (37000 - 74.5T)(x_{Fe} - x_{Si}) + (-10000 + 41.2T)(x_{Fe} - x_{Si})^2$	IAD
$L_{Mo,Si}^{bcc} = (-60000 + 5T)$	[61]
$L_{Fe,Mo,Si}^{bcc} = (-160000 + 50T)$	IAD
$T_c^{bcc} = 1043x_{Fe} + x_{Fe}x_{Mo}(335 + 526(x_{Fe} - x_{Mo})) + x_{Fe}x_{Si}(504(x_{Fe} - x_{Si}))$	[536]
$\beta^{bcc} = 2.22x_{Fe}$	[96]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe,Mo,Si)</i>	
$L_{Fe,Mo}^{fcc} = (+28347 - 17.691T)$	[13]
$L_{Fe,Si}^{fcc} = (-125248 + 41.166T) + (-142708)(x_{Fe} - x_{Si}) + (89907)(x_{Fe} - x_{Si})^2$	[536]
$L_{Mo,Si}^{fcc} = L_{Mo,Si}^{bcc}$	IAD
$T_c^{fcc} = -201x_{Fe}$	[96]
$\beta^{fcc} = -2.1x_{Fe}$	[96]
<i>Mu (μ) (3 sublattices, sites: 7:2:4, constituents: Fe:Mo:Fe,Mo)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Mo:Fe}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 2G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 4G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (+39475 - 6.032T)$	[13]
$G_{Fe:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,\mu} = 7G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 6G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (-46663 - 5.891T)$	[13]
<i>R (3 sublattices, sites: 27:14:12, constituents: Fe:Mo:Fe,Mo,Si)</i>	
$G_{Fe:Mo:Fe}^{\circ,R} = 27G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 14G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 12G_{Fe}^{\circ,bcc} + (-77487 - 50.486T)$	IAD
$G_{Fe:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,R} = 27G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 26G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+313474 - 289.472T)$	IAD
$G_{Fe:Mo:Si}^{\circ,R} = 27G_{Fe}^{\circ,fcc} + 14G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 12G_{Si}^{\circ,dia} + (-1950000 + 99T)$	IAD
$L_{Fe:Mo:Mo,Si}^R = (-500000)$	IAD

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

Table 134 (continued)

Equation	Reference
<i>Sigma</i> (σ) (3 sublattices, sites: 8:4:18, constituents: Fe:Mo:Fe,Mo)	
$G_{\text{Fe:Mo:Fe}}^{\circ,\sigma} = 8G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 4G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + 18G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + (-1813 - 27.272T)$	[13]
$G_{\text{Fe:Mo:Mo}}^{\circ,\sigma} = 8G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 22G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + (+83326 - 69.618T)$	[13]
$L_{\text{Fe:Mo:Fe,Mo}}^{\sigma} = (+222909)$	[13]
<i>FeSi</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 1:1, constituents: Fe,Mo:Si)	
$G_{\text{Fe:Si}}^{\circ,\text{FeSi}} = G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ,\text{dia}} + (-72761.2 + 4.44T)$	[536]
$G_{\text{Mo:Si}}^{\circ,\text{FeSi}} = G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ,\text{dia}}$	IAD
$L_{\text{Fe,Mo:Si}}^{\text{FeSi}} = (-82000)$	IAD
<i>Mo₅Si₃</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 5:3, constituents: Fe,Mo:Si)	
$G_{\text{Fe:Si}}^{\circ,\text{Mo}_5\text{Si}_3} = 5oG_{\text{bccFe}} + 3oG_{\text{diaSi}}$	IAD
$G_{\text{Mo:Si}}^{\circ,\text{Mo}_5\text{Si}_3} = 5G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + 3G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ,\text{dia}} + (-311840 - 10.792T)$	[61]
$L_{\text{Fe,Mo:Si}}^{\text{Mo}_5\text{Si}_3} = (-600000 + 160T)$	IAD
<i>Fe₂Mo</i> (λ) (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents: Fe:Mo)	
$G_{\text{Fe:Mo}}^{\circ,\lambda} = 2G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + (-10798 - 0.132T)$	[161]
<i>Fe₂Si</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents: Fe:Si)	
$G_{\text{Fe:Si}}^{\circ,\text{Fe}_2\text{Si}} = 2G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ,\text{dia}} + (-71256.6 - 10.62T)$	[536]
<i>Fe₅Si₃</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 5:3, constituents: Fe:Si)	
$G_{\text{Fe:Si}}^{\circ,\text{Fe}_5\text{Si}_3} = 5G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + 3G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ,\text{dia}} + (-241144 + 2.16T)$	[536]
<i>FeSi₂-H</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 3:7, constituents: Fe:Si)	
$G_{\text{Fe:Si}}^{\circ,\text{FeSi}_2\text{-H}} = 3G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + 7G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ,\text{dia}} + (-196490 - 9.2T)$	[536]
<i>FeSi₂-L</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 1:2, constituents: Fe:Si)	
$G_{\text{Fe:Si}}^{\circ,\text{FeSi}_2\text{-L}} = G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + 2G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ,\text{dia}} + (-82149 + 10.44T)$	[536]
<i>Mo₃Si</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 3:1, constituents: Mo:Si)	
$G_{\text{Mo:Si}}^{\circ,\text{Mo}_3\text{Si}} = 3G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ,\text{dia}} + (-111600 - 1.12T)$	[61]
<i>MoSi₂</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 1:2, constituents: Mo:Si)	
$G_{\text{Mo:Si}}^{\circ,\text{MoSi}_2} = G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + 2G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ,\text{dia}} + (-135468 + 0.669T)$	[61]
<i>Fe₂MoSi₂</i> (T_1) (3 sublattices, sites: 3.924:1.854:4.222, constituents: Fe:Mo:Si)	
$G_{\text{Fe:Mo:Si}}^{\circ,T_1} = 3.924G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + 1.854G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + 4.222G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ,\text{dia}} + (-520000 + 70T)$	IAD

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

4.17.2 Results

The results of the calculations according to the IAD together with the experimental data (Table 133) are presented in Figures 363–370 and Table 135. The agreement is reasonable. In the liquidus projection of Figure 363, note the somewhat different location of the experimental and calculated T_1 and Mo_5Si_3 surfaces (experimental regions correspond to higher Si contents). Note also the differences in the reactions concerning P_1/U_1 , U_3/E_3 and E_5/U_5 in Table 135. Several trials were made to improve this reaction

type disagreement, but no success was obtained using reasonable parameter values. On the other hand, the experimental data in Table 135 do not represent direct measurements but were derived from them. In Figures 366–369, note the inconsistency in the liquidus surfaces of T_1 (Figure 366), $MoSi_2$ (Figures 367 and 368) and Mo_5Si_3 (Figure 369).

Table 135. The calculated (IAD) and experimental invariant points of the Fe–Mo–Si system.

Code	Reaction	Temp. [°C]	C_{Mo}^L [wt-%]	C_{Si}^L [wt-%]	Type	Ref.
P_1	$L + Mo_5Si_3 + MoSi_2 = T_1$	1414	29.1	24.0	Calc.	IAD
U_1	$L + Mo_5Si_3 = MoSi_2 + T_1$	1342	23.0	27.5	Exp.	[581]
U_2	$L + Mo_5Si_3 = R + T_1$	1354	23.0	17.9	Calc.	IAD
		1356	27.5	20.5	Exp.	[581]
U_3	$L + MoSi_2 = T_1 + FeSi$	1334	16.1	28.6	Calc.	IAD
E_3	$L = MoSi_2 + T_1 + FeSi$	1331	18.5	28.5	Exp.	[581]
U_4	$L + R = T_1 + bcc$	1190	7.3	15.8	Calc.	IAD
		1186	7.5	16.5	Exp.	[581]
E_5	$L = Fe_2Si + FeSi + T_1$	1183	3.1	21.4	Calc.	IAD
U_5	$L + Fe_2Si = FeSi + bcc$	–	4.0	19.0	Exp.	[581]
E_6	$L = bcc + T_1 + Fe_2Si$	1170	3.7	18.2	Calc.	IAD
	$L = bcc + T_1 + FeSi$	1172	6.5	18.5	Exp.	[581]

Fig. 363. The calculated (IAD) liquidus projection of the Fe–Mo–Si system, together with the experimental data points [581, 583]. Also shown by the dotted lines are the calculated liquidus isotherms between 1700 °C and 1200 °C. See Table 135 for the invariants.

Fig. 364. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1350 °C of the Fe–Mo–Si system.

Fig. 365. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 9 wt-% Si of the Fe–Mo–Si system, together with the experimental data points [583].

Fig. 366. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of wt-% Si = 14.5 + 0.2464 wt-% Mo of the Fe–Mo–Si system, together with the experimental data points [583].

Fig. 367. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of wt-% Si = 33.464–0.3033 wt-% Mo of the Fe–Mo–Si system, together with the experimental data points [583].

Fig. 368. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of wt-% Si = 33.464–0.2048 wt-% Mo of the Fe–Mo–Si system, together with the experimental data points [583].

Fig. 369. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of wt-% Si = 58.778–1.037 wt-% Mo of the Fe–Mo–Si system, together with the experimental data points [583].

Fig. 370. The calculated (IAD) iso-activity lines of Si in bcc Fe–Mo–Si alloys at 1400 °C, together with the experimental data points [584]. The reference state used is pure diamond Si.

4.18 The Fe–Ni–Si system

Experimental studies on the Fe–Ni–Si system have been reviewed by Raynor and Rivlin [585] and Raghavan [440, 586–588], and a thermodynamic assessment has been developed for the IAD. The present work reviews this description and presents its experimental verification.

4.18.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 136 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 137 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 138.

Table 136. Phases and their modeling in the Fe–Ni–Si description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Fe,Ni,Si), substitutional, RKM
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Fe,Ni,Si), substitutional, RKM
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Fe,Ni,Si), substitutional, RKM
Fe ₂ Si (dissolving Ni)	(Fe,Ni) ₂ (Si), sublattice, RKM
FeSi (dissolving Ni)	(Fe,Ni)(Si), sublattice, RKM
FeSi ₂ -H (dissolving Ni)	(Fe,Ni) ₃ (Si) ₇ , sublattice, RKM
Ni ₅ Si ₂ - γ (dissolving Fe)	(Fe,Ni) ₅ (Si) ₂ , sublattice, RKM
Ni ₂ Si- δ (dissolving Fe)	(Fe,Ni) ₂ (Si), sublattice, RKM
Ni ₃ Si ₂ (dissolving Fe)	(Fe,Ni) ₃ (Si) ₂ , sublattice, RKM
NiSi (dissolving Fe)	(Fe,Ni)(Si), sublattice, RKM
NiSi ₂ (dissolving Fe)	(Fe,Ni)(Si) ₂ , sublattice, RKM
τ -FeNiSi (\approx τ)	(Fe,Ni) ₄ (Si), sublattice, RKM
Fe ₅ Si ₃	(Fe) ₅ (Si) ₃ , stoichiometric
FeSi ₂ -L	(Fe)(Si) ₂ , stoichiometric
Ni ₃ Si- β_1	(Ni) ₁₉ (Si) ₆ , stoichiometric
Ni ₃ Si- β_2	(Ni) ₃ (Si), stoichiometric
Ni ₃ Si- β_3	(Ni) ₃ (Si), stoichiometric
Ni ₂ Si- θ	(Ni) ₂ (Si), stoichiometric
dia_A4 (\approx dia)	pure Si

Note: RKM = Redlich–Kister–Muggianu excess model.

Table 137. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Fe–Ni–Si according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Liquidus projection	[589]
8 isothermal sections at 1200 °C, 1100 °C, 1000 °C, 900 °C, 800 °C, 700 °C, 650 °C, and 600 °C	[418, 589–594]
3 vertical sections at 4 and 5 wt-% Si and at 33 at-% Si	[589, 595]
Activity coefficient $\gamma_{\text{Si}}^{\text{Ni}}$ in liquid alloys at 1560 °C	[380]

Table 138. The thermodynamic description of the Fe–Ni–Si system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe, Ni, Si)</i>	
$L_{\text{Fe, Ni}}^{\text{L}} = (-16911 + 5.162T) + (+10180 - 4.147T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})$	[5]
$L_{\text{Fe, Si}}^{\text{L}} = (-164435 + 41.977T) + (-21.523T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Si}}) + (5220 + 5.726T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Si}})^2 + (-28955 + 26.275T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Si}})^3$	[534]
$L_{\text{Ni, Si}}^{\text{L}} = (-205000 + 33T) + (-102700 + 27T)(x_{\text{Ni}} - x_{\text{Si}}) + (+25000)(x_{\text{Ni}} - x_{\text{Si}})^2 + (+117000 - 55T)(x_{\text{Ni}} - x_{\text{Si}})^3$	[65]
$L_{\text{Fe, Ni, Si}}^{\text{L}} = (+40000)x_{\text{Fe}} + (+120000)x_{\text{Ni}} + (-300000)x_{\text{Si}}$	IAD
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe, Ni, Si)</i>	
$L_{\text{Fe, Ni}}^{\text{bcc}} = (-957 - 1.287T) + (+1789 - 1.929T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})$	[45]
$L_{\text{Fe, Si}}^{\text{bcc}} = (-211000 + 80.2T) + (37000 - 74.5T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Si}}) + (-10000 + 41.2T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Si}})^2$	IAD
$L_{\text{Ni, Si}}^{\text{bcc}} = (-185000 + 30T)$	IAD
$L_{\text{Fe, Ni, Si}}^{\text{bcc}} = (-80000 - 15T)x_{\text{Fe}} + (-40000)x_{\text{Ni}} + (-40000)x_{\text{Si}}$	IAD
$T_{\text{c}}^{\text{bcc}} = 1043x_{\text{Fe}} + 575x_{\text{Ni}} + x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Si}}(+504(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Si}}))$	[536]
$\beta^{\text{bcc}} = 2.22x_{\text{Fe}} + 0.85x_{\text{Ni}}$	[45]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Fe, Ni, Si)</i>	
$L_{\text{Fe, Ni}}^{\text{fcc}} = (-12054 + 3.274T) + (+11082 - 4.45T)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}}) + (-726)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})^2$	[45]
$L_{\text{Fe, Si}}^{\text{fcc}} = (-125248 + 41.166T) + (-142708)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Si}}) + (89907)(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Si}})^2$	[536]
$L_{\text{Ni, Si}}^{\text{fcc}} = (-205000 + 30T) + (-52000 + 20T)(x_{\text{Ni}} - x_{\text{Si}})$	[65]
$L_{\text{Cr, Fe, Si}}^{\text{fcc}} = (-60000)$	IAD
$L_{\text{Fe, Ni, Si}}^{\text{fcc}} = (-55000 - 5T)x_{\text{Fe}} + (0)x_{\text{Ni}} + (-40000)x_{\text{Si}}$	IAD
$T_{\text{c}}^{\text{fcc}} = -201x_{\text{Fe}} + 633x_{\text{Ni}} + x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Ni}}(2133 - 682(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}}))$	[45]
$\beta^{\text{fcc}} = -2.1x_{\text{Fe}} + 0.52x_{\text{Ni}} + x_{\text{Fe}}x_{\text{Ni}}(9.55 + 7.23(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}}) + 5.93(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})^2 + 6.18(x_{\text{Fe}} - x_{\text{Ni}})^3)$	[45]
<i>Fe₂Si (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents: Fe, Ni, Si)</i>	
$G_{\text{Fe, Si}}^{\circ, \text{Fe}_2\text{Si}} = 2G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-71256.6 - 10.62T)$	[536]
$G_{\text{Ni, Si}}^{\circ, \text{Fe}_2\text{Si}} = 2G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-115333 - 10T)$	IAD
$L_{\text{Fe, Ni, Si}}^{\text{Fe}_2\text{Si}} = (+5000)$	IAD

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

Table 138 (continued)

Equation	Reference
<i>FeSi</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 1:1, constituents: Fe,Ni:Si)	
$G_{\text{Fe:Si}}^{\circ, \text{FeSi}} = G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-72761.2 + 4.44T)$	[536]
$G_{\text{Ni:Si}}^{\circ, \text{FeSi}} = G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-76000)$	IAD
<i>FeSi₂-H</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 3:7, constituents: Fe,Ni:Si)	
$G_{\text{Fe:Si}}^{\circ, \text{FeSi}_2\text{-H}} = 3G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + 7G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-196490 - 9.2T)$	[536]
$G_{\text{Ni:Si}}^{\circ, \text{FeSi}_2\text{-H}} = 3G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + 7G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-240000)$	IAD
<i>Ni₅Si₂-γ</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 5:2, constituents: Fe,Ni:Si)	
$G_{\text{Fe:Si}}^{\circ, \gamma} = 5G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + 2G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-120000 + 50T)$	IAD
$G_{\text{Ni:Si}}^{\circ, \gamma} = 5G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + 2G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-302190 + 14T)$	[65]
$L_{\text{Fe,Ni:Si}}^{\gamma} = (-150000 + 50T) + (+55000)(y_{\text{Fe}} - y_{\text{Ni}})$	IAD
<i>Ni₂Si-δ</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents: Fe,Ni:Si)	
$G_{\text{Fe:Si}}^{\circ, \delta} = 2G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-77000)$	IAD
$G_{\text{Ni:Si}}^{\circ, \delta} = 2G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-149000 + 166T - 21T \ln T)$	[65]
$L_{\text{Fe,Ni:Si}}^{\delta} = (-6000 + 3T)$	IAD
<i>Ni₃Si₂-ε</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 3:2, constituents: Fe,Ni:Si)	
$G_{\text{Fe:Si}}^{\circ, \epsilon} = 3G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + 2G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-110000)$	IAD
$G_{\text{Ni:Si}}^{\circ, \epsilon} = 3G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + 2G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-218700 + 10T)$	IAD
<i>NiSi</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 1:1, constituents: Fe,Ni:Si)	
$G_{\text{Fe:Si}}^{\circ} = G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-53000)$	IAD
$G_{\text{Ni:Si}}^{\circ} = G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-80600 + 1.2T)$	[65]
<i>NiSi₂-α</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 1:2, constituents: Fe,Ni:Si)	
$G_{\text{Fe:Si}}^{\circ, \alpha} = G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + 2G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-64000)$	IAD
$G_{\text{Ni:Si}}^{\circ, \alpha} = G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + 2G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-106800 + 18T)$	[65]
<i>Fe₅Si₃</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 5:3, constituents: Fe:Si)	
$G_{\text{Fe:Si}}^{\circ, \text{Fe}_5\text{Si}_3} = 5G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + 3G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-241144 + 2.16T)$	[536]
<i>FeSi₂-L</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 1:2, constituents: Fe:Si)	
$G_{\text{Fe:Si}}^{\circ, \text{FeSi}_2\text{-L}} = G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + 2G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-82149 + 10.44T)$	[536]
<i>Ni₃Si-β₁</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 19:6, constituents: Ni:Si)	
$G_{\text{Ni:Si}}^{\circ, \beta_1} = 19G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + 6G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-1040800 + 120T)$	[65]
<i>Ni₃Si-β₂</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 3:1, constituents: Ni:Si)	
$G_{\text{Ni:Si}}^{\circ, \beta_2} = 3G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-161860 + 12T)$	[65]
<i>Ni₃Si-β₃</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 3:1, constituents: Ni:Si)	
$G_{\text{Ni:Si}}^{\circ, \beta_3} = 3G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-132440 - 9.2T)$	[65]
<i>Ni₂Si-θ</i> (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents: Ni:Si)	
$G_{\text{Ni:Si}}^{\circ, \theta} = 2G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-115333 - 10T)$	IAD
<i>τ-FeNiSi</i> (τ) (2 sublattices, sites: 4:1, constituents: Fe,Ni:Si)	
$G_{\text{Fe:Si}}^{\circ, \tau} = 4G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ, \text{bcc}} + G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-118000 + 10T)$	IAD
$G_{\text{Ni:Si}}^{\circ, \tau} = 4G_{\text{Ni}}^{\circ, \text{fcc}} + G_{\text{Si}}^{\circ, \text{dia}} + (-171000 + 16T)$	IAD

Notes: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

4.18.2 Results

The results of calculations according to the IAD together with the experimental data (Table 137) are presented in Figures 371–384 and Table 139. The agreement is reasonable. Note that there are some contradictions between the phase equilibria measured in [418, 590, 594] at 900 °C and 800 °C and those by Zhang *et al.* [596] measured at 850 °C (not included in the present optimization). The bcc, Ni₂Si- δ and Ni₅Si₂- γ stabilities by Zhang *et al.* [596] are higher than in the former studies resulting in somewhat different three-phase equilibria. At Si contents below 20 at-% Si, excluding the extensive bcc region, however, the phase equilibria by Zhang *et al.* [596] are still reasonably well described by the calculations. Evidently, more measurements are necessary to fix the complex solid-state phase equilibria of the Fe–Ni–Si system before we can get a reliable thermodynamic description for this system.

Table 139. The calculated (IAD) invariant points of the Fe–Ni–Si system.

Reaction	Code	Temp. [°C]	Content in Liq [at-%]	
			Ni	Si
L + Ni ₂ Si- δ = Fe ₂ Si+Ni ₅ Si ₂	U ₁	1242	70.39	29.24
L + Ni ₃ Si- β_3 = fcc + Ni ₅ Si ₂	U ₂	1135	77.63	21.08
L + bcc = fcc + Fe ₂ Si	U ₃	1093	39.16	24.94
L + Fe ₂ Si = FeSi + Ni ₂ Si- δ	U ₄	1002	41.91	43.30
L + dia = FeSi ₂ -H + NiSi ₂	U ₅	964	21.48	64.81
L + FeSi ₂ -H = FeSi + NiSi ₂	U ₆	956	21.24	67.72
L = fcc + Ni ₅ Si ₂ +Fe ₂ Si	E ₁	1089	41.64	24.73
L = FeSi + Ni ₂ Si- δ +NiSi	E ₂	946	48.96	44.93
L = FeSi + NiSi + NiSi ₂	E ₃	932	35.67	57.01

Fig. 371. The calculated (IAD) liquidus projection in the Fe–Ni–Si system, together with the experimental data points [589]. Also shown by the dotted lines are the calculated liquidus isotherms between 1500 °C and 1000 °C.

Fig. 372. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1200 °C in the Fe–Ni–Si system, together with the experimental data points [594].

Fig. 373. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1100 °C in the Fe–Ni–Si system, together with the experimental data points [590, 594].

Fig. 374. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1000 °C in the Fe–Ni–Si system, together with the experimental data points [590, 591, 594].

Fig. 375. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 900 °C in the Fe–Ni–Si system, together with the experimental data points [418, 590, 591].

Fig. 376. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 800 °C in the Fe–Ni–Si system, together with the experimental data points [418, 590, 594].

Fig. 377. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 700 °C in the Fe–Ni–Si system, together with the experimental data points [418, 589].

Fig. 378. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 700 °C in the Si-rich part of the Fe–Ni–Si system, together with the experimental data points [589].

Fig. 379. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 650 °C in the Fe–Ni–Si system, together with the experimental data points [593].

Fig. 380. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 600 °C in the Fe–Ni–Si system, together with the experimental data points [418, 590–592].

Fig. 381. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 4 wt-% Si in the Fe-Ni-Si system, together with the experimental data points [595].

Fig. 382. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 5 wt-% Si in the Fe-Ni-Si system, together with the experimental data points [595].

Fig. 383. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 33 at-% Si in the Fe–Ni–Si system, together with the experimental data points [589].

Fig. 384. The calculated (IAD) activity coefficient γ_{Si}^{Ni} in liquid Fe–Ni–Si alloys at 1560 °C and at 10 at-% Si, together with the experimental data points [380].

4.19 The Al–Cr–Ni system

Experimental studies on the Al–Cr–Ni system have been reviewed by Merchant and Notis [597] and Rogl [598], while thermodynamic assessments have been given by Huang and Chang [89], Dupin *et al.* [90], and Wang and Cacciamani [91]. The system was later reassessed for use in the IAD to get simple Al–Cr–Ni and Fe–Al–Cr–Ni descriptions for practical calculations for modeling solidification of steels. In this description, only the Ni-rich part of the system was assessed. The present work reviews the Al–Cr–Ni description according to the IAD and presents its experimental verification.

4.19.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 140 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 141 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 142.

Table 140. Phases and their modeling in the Ni-rich part of the Al–Cr–Ni system according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Al,Cr,Ni), substitutional, RKM
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Al,Cr,Ni), substitutional, RKM
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Al,Cr,Ni), substitutional, RKM
Al ₃ Ni ₅	(Al) ₃ (Ni) ₅ , stoichiometric
AlNi ₃	(Al) ₆ (Cr,Ni) ₁₉ , stoichiometric

Note: RKM = Redlich–Kister–Muggianu excess model.

Table 141. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Al–Cr–Ni system according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Liquidus projection	[246, 599–603]
9 isothermal sections at 1300 °C, 1200 °C, 1150 °C, 1127 °C, 1100 °C, 1027 °C, 1000 °C, 850 °C, and 750 °C	[246, 458, 604–610]
4 vertical sections at 5, 10, and 15 at-% Cr and at 75 at-% Ni	[246, 599, 600, 602, 607, 611]
Mixing enthalpy for liquid alloys at 1445 °C	[612]
Enthalpy of formation for solid alloys at 600 °C and 25 °C	[613, 614]

Table 142. The thermodynamic description in the Ni-rich part of the Al–Cr–Ni system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Cr,Ni)</i>	
$L_{Al,Cr}^L = (-33500) + (-10000 + 4T)(x_{Al} - x_{Cr})$	IAD
$L_{Al,Ni}^L = (-206257 + 40.826T) + (-6759 + 3.932T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})$ $+ (+69168 - 24.759T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})^2 + (-4181 + 2.314T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})^3$	IAD
$L_{Cr,Ni}^L = (+318 - 7.332T) + (+16941 - 6.37T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Ni})$	[34]
$L_{Al,Cr,Ni}^L = (-49000 + 30T)$	IAD
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Cr,Ni)</i>	
$L_{Al,Cr}^{bcc} = (-58258 + 8.441T)$	[19]
$L_{Al,Ni}^{bcc} = (-264500 - 119T + 23T \ln T) + (-107000 + 559T - 67T \ln T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})$ $+ (414000 - 800T + 95T \ln T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})^2$ $+ (-118000 + 970T - 99T \ln T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})^3$	[615]
$L_{Cr,Ni}^{bcc} = (+17170 - 11.82T) + (+34418 - 11.858T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Ni})$	[34]
$L_{Al,Cr,Ni}^{bcc} = (+75000 + 25T)x_{Al} + (+75000 + 25T)x_{Cr} + (-20000)x_{Ni}$	IAD
$T_c^{bcc} = -311x_{Cr} + 575x_{Ni} + x_{Cr}x_{Ni}(2376 + 617(x_{Cr} - x_{Ni}))$	[34]
$\beta^{bcc} = -0.008x_{Cr} + 0.85x_{Ni} + 4x_{Cr}x_{Ni}$	[34]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Al,Cr,Ni)</i>	
$L_{Al,Cr}^{fcc} = (-47000 + 7T)$	IAD
$L_{Al,Ni}^{fcc} = (-162408 + 16.213T) + (73418 - 34.914T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})$ $+ (33471 - 9.837T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})^2 + (-30758 + 10.253T)(x_{Al} - x_{Ni})^3$	[26]
$L_{Cr,Ni}^{fcc} = (+8030 - 12.88T) + (+33080 - 16.036T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Ni})$	[34]
$T_c^{fcc} = -1109x_{Cr} + 633x_{Ni} - 3605x_{Cr}x_{Ni}$	[34]
$\beta^{fcc} = -2.46x_{Cr} + 0.52x_{Ni} - 1.91x_{Cr}x_{Ni}$	[34]
<i>Al₃Ni₅ (2 sublattices, sites: 0.375:0.625, constituents: Al:Ni)</i>	
$G_{Al:Ni}^{\circ,Al_3Ni_5} = 3G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 5G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + (-444064 + 52.304T)$	[615]
<i>AlNi₃ (2 sublattices, sites: 6:19, constituents: Al:Cr,Ni)</i>	
$G_{Al:Cr,Ni}^{\circ,AlNi_3} = 6G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 19G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + (-1073000 + 525T - 50T \ln T)$	[615]
$G_{Al:Cr}^{\circ,AlNi_3} = 6G_{Al}^{\circ,fcc} + 19G_{Cr}^{\circ,bcc} + (+500000)$	IAD
$L_{Al:Cr,Ni}^{AlNi_3} = (-2300000 + 900T)$	IAD

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

4.19.2 Results

The results of the calculations according to the IAD together with the experimental data (Table 141) are presented in Figures 385–400 and Table 143. The agreement is reasonable. Quite similar agreement was obtained by Huang and Chang [89], Dupin *et al.* [90], and Wang and Cacciamani [91], though notice discrepancies in the two invariant points (U and E) according to the different sources. Particularly, note the wide composition range of the AlNi₃ phase, extending not only towards the Cr–Al side but

also towards of the Cr–Ni side of the system, whereas the description according to the IAD treats it as a simple semistoichiometric compound with a constant Al content of 24 at-% Al. Also note, in the 1000 °C isotherm in Figure 392, the higher stability of AlNi₃ by calculations. This is indicated by the measured [246] three-phase data points locating in the calculated two-phase regions of fcc+AlNi₃ and bcc'+AlNi₃. These data points, however, also disagree with the measurements by DeLanerolle and Seigle [604] and Hong *et al.* [607] at 1027 °C (Figure 391).

Table 143. The calculated and experimental invariant points in the Ni-rich part of the Al–Cr–Ni system.

Reaction	Code	Temp. [°C]	Content in Liq [at-%]		Type	Ref.
			Cr	Al		
L + AlNi ₃ = fcc + bcc'	U	1353	1.9	25.0	Calc.	IAD
		1365			Calc.	[91]
		1349	5.5	23.6	Calc.	[90]
		1343	5.3	24.0	Calc.	[89]
		1341			Exp.	[603]
		1340			Exp.	[246]
L = fcc + bcc + bcc'	E	1289	40.2	13.4	Calc.	IAD
		1283	38.9	15.8	Calc.	[91]
		1283	32.5	17.4	Calc.	[90]
		1292	34.5	15.5	Calc.	[89]
		1289			Exp.	[603]
		1300	37.7	16.8	Exp.	[599]
	1320	42.3	14.6	Exp.	[246]	

Finally, enthalpies of formation for three solid alloys (23 at-% Al–5 at-% Cr, 22 at-% Al–8 at-% Cr, and 21 at-% Al–12 at-% Cr) were measured at 25 °C by Kek *et al.* [614]. The measured values were –36.7, –35.2 and –34.9 kJ/mol, whilst the values calculated using the IAD were slightly more negative, –40.7, –39.4 and –37.7 kJ/mol, respectively. This deviation comes mainly from the Gibbs energy expression of AlNi₃ optimized in the Al–Ni assessment according to the IAD.

Fig. 385. The calculated (IAD) liquidus projection in the Ni-rich part of the Al–Cr–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [246, 599–602]. Also shown by dotted lines are calculated liquidus isotherms between 1500 °C and 1310 °C.

Fig. 386. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1300 °C in the Ni-rich part of the Al–Cr–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [458].

Fig. 387. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1200 °C in the Ni-rich part of the Al–Cr–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [605,609,610].

Fig. 388. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1150 °C in the Ni-rich part of the Al–Cr–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [246,606].

Fig. 389. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1127 °C in the Ni-rich part of the Al-Cr-Ni system, together with the experimental data points [607].

Fig. 390. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1100 °C in the Ni-rich part of the Al-Cr-Ni system, together with the experimental data points [458].

Fig. 391. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1027 °C in the Ni-rich part of the Al–Cr–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [604,607].

Fig. 392. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1000 °C in the Ni-rich part of the Al–Cr–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [246].

Fig. 393. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 850 °C in the Ni-rich part of the Al-Cr-Ni system, together with the experimental data points [246, 608].

Fig. 394. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 750 °C in the Ni-rich part of the Al-Cr-Ni system, together with the experimental data points [246].

Fig. 395. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 5 at-% Cr in the Al–Cr–Ni system, together with experimental data points (53Kor [599] and 90Dav [600]).

Fig. 396. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 10 at-% Cr in the Al–Cr–Ni system, together with experimental data points [599, 600, 602].

Fig. 397. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 15 at-% Cr in the Al–Cr–Ni system, together with experimental data points (53Kor [599] and 90Dav [600]).

Fig. 398. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 75 at-% Ni in the Al–Cr–Ni system, together with experimental data points [246, 600, 607, 611].

Fig. 399. The calculated (IAD) enthalpy of mixing for liquid Al–Cr–Ni alloys at 1445 °C, together with experimental data points [612]. The reference states used are pure liquid Cr, Ni and Al.

Fig. 400. The calculated (IAD) enthalpy of formation for solid Al–Cr–Ni alloys at 600 °C, together with experimental data points [613]. The reference states used are pure bcc Cr, pure fcc Ni and pure fcc Al.

4.20 The Cr–Mo–Ni system

Experimental studies on the Cr–Mo–Ni system have been reviewed by Gupta [616,617] and a thermodynamic assessment has been given by Frisk [92]. The description by Frisk [92] was later modified by IAD to improve the agreement between the experimental and calculated phase equilibria including the liquid and P phases. In addition, a simpler description was introduced for the Delta (MoNi) phase. The present work reviews the Cr–Mo–Ni description according to the IAD and presents its experimental verification.

4.20.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 144 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 145 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 146.

Table 144. Phases and their modeling in the Cr–Mo–Ni description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Cr,Mo,Ni), substitutional, RKM
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Cr,Mo,Ni), substitutional, RKM
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Cr,Mo,Ni), substitutional, RKM
Delta (\approx $\delta \approx$ MoNi, dissolving Cr)	(Mo)(Cr,Ni), sublattice, RKM
Sigma (\approx σ)	(Ni) ₈ (Cr,Mo) ₄ (Cr,Mo,Ni) ₁₈ , sublattice, RKM
P	(Cr,Ni) ₂₄ (Cr,Mo,Ni) ₂₀ (Mo) ₁₂ , sublattice, RKM
MoNi ₃	(Mo)(Ni) ₃ , stoichiometric
MoNi ₄	(Mo)(Ni) ₄ , stoichiometric

Note: RKM = Redlich–Kister–Muggianu excess model.

Table 145. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Cr–Mo–Ni according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Three isopleths at 12 wt-% Mo, $w_{\text{Mo}}:w_{\text{Cr}} = 1.5$, and $w_{\text{Mo}}:w_{\text{Cr}} = 1$	[302]
Liquidus temperatures	[302]
6 isothermal sections at 1250 °C, 1200 °C, 1150 °C, 1100 °C, 1000 °C, and 850 °C	[92, 302, 577, 618–622]

Table 146. The thermodynamic description of the Cr–Mo–Ni system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Mo,Ni)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Mo}^L = (+15810 - 6.714T) + (-9220)(x_{Cr} - x_{Mo})$	IAD
$L_{Cr,Ni}^L = (+318 - 7.332T) + (+16941 - 6.37T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Ni})$	[34]
$L_{Mo,Ni}^L = (-46540 + 19.53T) + (+2915)(x_{Mo} - x_{Ni})$	[55]
$L_{Cr,Mo,Ni}^L = (-43000 + 25T)$	IAD
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Mo,Ni)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Mo}^{bcc} = (+28890 - 7.962T) + (+5974 - 2.428T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Mo})$	[32]
$L_{Cr,Ni}^{bcc} = (+17170 - 11.82T) + (+34418 - 11.858T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Ni})$	[34]
$L_{Mo,Ni}^{bcc} = (+46422)$	[55]
$L_{Cr,Mo,Ni}^{bcc} = (-52000 + 25T)$	IAD
$T_c^{bcc} = -311x_{Cr} + 575x_{Ni} + x_{Cr}x_{Ni}(2376 + 617(x_{Cr} - x_{Ni}))$	[34]
$\beta^{bcc} = -0.008x_{Cr} + 0.85x_{Ni} + 4x_{Cr}x_{Ni}$	[34]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Mo,Ni)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Mo}^{fcc} = L_{Cr,Mo}^{bcc}$	[301]
$L_{Cr,Ni}^{fcc} = (+8030 - 12.88T) + (+33080 - 16.036T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Ni})$	[34]
$L_{Mo,Ni}^{fcc} = (+4804 - 5.96T) + (+10880)(x_{Mo} - x_{Ni})$	[55]
$L_{Cr,Mo,Ni}^{fcc} = (-52000 + 25T)$	IAD
$T_c^{fcc} = -1109x_{Cr} + 633x_{Ni} - 3605x_{Cr}x_{Ni}$	[34]
$\beta^{fcc} = -2.46x_{Cr} + 0.52x_{Ni} - 1.91x_{Cr}x_{Ni}$	[34]
<i>Delta (δ) (2 sublattices, sites: 1:1, constituents: Mo:Cr,Ni)</i>	
$G_{Mo:Cr}^{\circ,\delta} = G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + G_{Cr}^{\circ,bcc}$	IAD
$G_{Mo:Ni}^{\circ,\delta} = G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + (-6000 + 32.5T - 4.6T \ln T)$	IAD
$L_{Mo:Cr,Ni}^{\delta} = (-1000 - 5T) + (+2000)(y_{Cr} - y_{Ni})$	IAD
<i>Sigma (σ) (3 sublattices, sites: 8:4:18, constituents: Ni:Cr,Mo:Cr,Mo,Ni)</i>	
$G_{Ni:Cr:Cr}^{\circ,\sigma} = 8G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + 22G_{Cr}^{\circ,bcc} + (+205000 - 200T)$	IAD
$G_{Ni:Cr:Mo}^{\circ,\sigma} = 8G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + 4G_{Cr}^{\circ,bcc} + 18G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (-123000)$	IAD
$G_{Ni:Cr:Ni}^{\circ,\sigma} = 8G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + 4G_{Cr}^{\circ,bcc} + 18G_{Ni}^{\circ,bcc} + (+175400)$	[34]
$G_{Ni:Mo:Cr}^{\circ,\sigma} = 8G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + 4G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 18G_{Cr}^{\circ,bcc} + (+300000)$	IAD
$G_{Ni:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,\sigma} = 8G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + 22G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+85662)$	[88]
$G_{Ni:Mo:Ni}^{\circ,\sigma} = 8G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + 4G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + 18G_{Ni}^{\circ,bcc} + (-16385)$	[88]
<i>P (3 sublattices, sites: 24:20:12, constituents: Cr,Ni:Cr,Mo,Ni:Mo)</i>	
$G_{Cr:Cr:Mo}^{\circ,P} = 24G_{Cr}^{\circ,fcc} + 20G_{Cr}^{\circ,bcc} + 12G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+252300 - 100T)$	[92]
$G_{Cr:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,P} = 24G_{Cr}^{\circ,fcc} + 32G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+95573 - 200T)$	[92]
$G_{Cr:Ni:Mo}^{\circ,P} = 24G_{Cr}^{\circ,fcc} + 20G_{Ni}^{\circ,bcc} + 12G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc}$	IAD
$G_{Ni:Cr:Mo}^{\circ,P} = 24G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + 20G_{Cr}^{\circ,bcc} + 12G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (-385000 + 50T)$	IAD
$G_{Ni:Mo:Mo}^{\circ,P} = 24G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + 32G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (-15000 - 80T)$	IAD
$G_{Ni:Ni:Mo}^{\circ,P} = 24G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + 20G_{Ni}^{\circ,bcc} + 12G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + (+190000 - 80T)$	IAD
<i>MoNi₃ (2 sublattices, sites: 3:1, constituents: Mo:Ni)</i>	
$G_{Mo:Ni}^{\circ,MoNi_3} = 3G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + (-4300 - 7T)$	IAD
<i>MoNi₄ (2 sublattices, sites: 4:1, constituents: Mo:Ni)</i>	
$G_{Mo:Ni}^{\circ,MoNi_4} = 4G_{Mo}^{\circ,bcc} + G_{Ni}^{\circ,fcc} + (-4600 - 9T)$	IAD

Note: the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96].

4.20.2 Results

The results of the calculations according to the IAD and Frisk [92] together with the experimental data (Table 145) are presented in Figures 401–412 and Table 147. The agreement is reasonably good in both calculations. The results for the liquidus projection in Figure 401 are not so far from the calculations by Frisk [92]. The main differences are the slightly smaller P and Sigma phase regions according to the IAD. No experimental data are available to verify these calculations. In Figure 406, note the disappearance of the liquid phase by Frisk [92] on the Ni–Mo side, whereas according to IAD and the experimental data, the liquid phase region extends close to the Ni–Cr side of the system. In Figures 407–412, the main difference is the slightly less stable P phase according to the IAD. Note also the slightly better agreement according to the IAD for the location of the three-phase triangles in Figures 407 and 408 and for the bcc region in Figures 407 and 410.

Table 147. The calculated (IAD) invariant points of the Cr–Mo–Ni system.

Reaction	Code	Temp. [°C]	Content in Liq [wt-%]	
			Cr	Mo
$L + \text{bcc} + \sigma = P$	P_1	1431	23.06	37.50
$L + \text{bcc} + P = \delta$	P_2	1396	7.63	45.55
$L + P = \text{fcc} + \delta$	U_1	1320	5.34	41.96
$L + P = \text{fcc} + \sigma$	U_2	1310	20.15	30.68
$L = \text{bcc} + \text{fcc} + \sigma$	E	1299	44.78	11.88

Fig. 401. The calculated (IAD) liquidus projection of the Cr–Mo–Ni system. Also shown by the dotted lines are the calculated liquidus isotherms between 2400 °C and 1350 °C.

Fig. 402. The calculated (IAD) isopleth of 12 wt-% Mo in the Cr–Mo–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [302]. The dotted line shows the liquidus calculated by Frisk [92].

Fig. 403. The calculated (IAD) isopleth of $w_{Mo}:w_{Cr} = 1.5$ in the Cr–Mo–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [302]. The dotted line shows the liquidus calculated by Frisk [92].

Fig. 404. The calculated (IAD) isopleth of $w_{Mo}:w_{Cr} = 1$ in the Cr–Mo–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [302]. The dotted line shows the liquidus calculated by Frisk [92].

Fig. 405. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1368 °C in the Cr–Mo–Ni system, together with the experimental data points for the liquidus [302]. The dotted lines show the two liquid phase regions (L) calculated by Frisk [92].

Fig. 406. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1330 °C in the Cr–Mo–Ni system, together with the experimental data points for the liquidus [302]. The dotted line shows the tiny liquid phase region (L) calculated by Frisk [92].

Fig. 407. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1250 °C in the Cr–Mo–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [302,621]. The dotted lines show the three-phase triangles and the bcc region calculated by Frisk [92].

Fig. 408. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1200 °C in the Cr–Mo–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [577,618,619]. The dotted lines show the three-phase triangles calculated by Frisk [92].

Fig. 409. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1150 °C in the Cr-Mo-Ni system, together with the experimental data points [620,622]. The dotted lines show the three-phase triangles calculated by Frisk [92].

Fig. 410. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1100 °C in the Cr-Mo-Ni system, together with the experimental data points [92]. The dotted lines show the three-phase triangles and the bcc region calculated by Frisk [92].

Fig. 411. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1000 °C in the Cr–Mo–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [92,577,619]. The dotted lines show the three-phase triangles calculated by Frisk [92].

Fig. 412. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 850 °C in the Cr–Mo–Ni system, together with the experimental data points [577, 621]. The dotted lines show the three-phase triangles calculated by Frisk [92].

4.21 The Cr–Ni–Si system

The Cr–Ni–Si system has been assessed by Schuster and Du [93]. This description was later modified for use in the IAD as its binary Cr–Si and Ni–Si data differs from that by Schuster and Du [93]. The present work reviews this description and presents its experimental verification.

4.21.1 Phases, modeling, and data

Table 148 shows the phases and their modeling. Table 149 shows the experimental information selected for the assessment verification. The thermodynamic description of the system is presented in Table 150.

Table 148. Phases and their modeling in the Cr–Ni–Si description according to the IAD.

Phase	Modeling
liquid (\approx L)	(Cr,Ni,Si), substitutional, RKM
bcc_A2 (\approx bcc)	(Cr,Ni,Si), substitutional, RKM
fcc_A1 (\approx fcc)	(Cr,Ni,Si), substitutional, RKM
Sigma (\approx σ)	(Ni) ₈ (Cr) ₄ (Cr,Ni,Si) ₁₈ , sublattice, RKM
Cr ₃ Si (dissolving Ni)	(Cr,Ni) ₃ (Si), sublattice, RKM
CrSi (dissolving Ni)	(Cr,Ni)(Si), sublattice, RKM
Ni ₅ Si ₂ - γ (dissolving Cr)	(Cr,Ni) ₅ (Si) ₂ , sublattice, RKM
Ni ₂ Si- δ (dissolving Cr)	(Cr,Ni) ₂ (Si), sublattice, RKM
T2-CrNiSi (\approx τ_2)	(Cr,Ni) ₄ (Si) ₃ , sublattice, RKM
Cr ₅ Si ₃	(Cr) ₅ (Si) ₃ , stoichiometric
CrSi ₂	(Cr)(Si) ₂ , stoichiometric
Ni ₃ Si- β_1	(Ni) ₁₉ (Si) ₆ , stoichiometric
Ni ₃ Si- β_2	(Ni) ₃ (Si), stoichiometric
Ni ₃ Si- β_3	(Ni) ₃ (Si), stoichiometric
Ni ₂ Si- θ	(Ni) ₂ (Si), stoichiometric
Ni ₃ Si ₂ - ϵ	(Ni) ₃ (Si) ₂ , stoichiometric
NiSi	(Ni)(Si), stoichiometric
NiSi ₂	(Ni)(Si) ₂ , stoichiometric
Cr ₃ Ni ₅ Si ₂ (\approx π)	(Cr) ₃ (Ni) ₅ (Si) ₂ , stoichiometric
Cr ₅ Ni ₅ Si ₃ (\approx τ_1)	(Cr) ₅ (Ni) ₅ (Si) ₃ , stoichiometric
dia_A4 (\approx dia)	pure Si

Note: RKM = Redlich–Kister–Muggianu excess model.

Table 149. The experimental data applied in the assessment verification for Cr–Ni–Si according to the IAD.

Experimental data	Reference(s)
Ni-rich liquidus isotherms at 1400 °C, 1300 °C, and 1200 °C	[623]
6 isothermal sections at 1175 °C, 1125 °C, 1050 °C, 900 °C, and 850 °C	[93, 624–628]
6 vertical sections at 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, and 40 at-% Cr	[93, 623, 628]
Activity coefficient γ_{Si} in liquid alloys at 1600 °C and 1.5 wt-% Si	[629]

Table 150. The thermodynamic description of the Cr–Ni–Si system according to the IAD.

Equation	Reference
<i>liquid (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Mo,Ni)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Ni}^L = (+318 - 7.332T) + (+16941 - 6.37T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Ni})$	[34]
$L_{Cr,Si}^L = (-119811 + 16.602T) + (-49125 + 14.11T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Si})$	[37]
$L_{Ni,Si}^L = (-205000 + 33T) + (-102700 + 27T)(x_{Ni} - x_{Si})$ $+ (+25000)(x_{Ni} - x_{Si})^2 + (+117000 - 55T)(x_{Ni} - x_{Si})^3$	[65]
$L_{Cr,Ni,Si}^L = (0)x_{Cr} + (+30000 + 30T)x_{Ni} + (-270000 + 30T)x_{Si}$	IAD
<i>bcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Ni,Si)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Ni}^{bcc} = (+17170 - 11.82T) + (+34418 - 11.858T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Ni})$	[34]
$L_{Cr,Si}^{bcc} = (-102085 + 9.543T) + (-49125 + 14.110T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Si})$	[37]
$L_{Ni,Si}^{bcc} = (-185000 + 30T)$	IAD
$L_{Cr,Ni,Si}^{bcc} = (0)$	IAD
$T_c^{bcc} = -311x_{Cr} + 575x_{Ni} + x_{Cr}x_{Ni}(2376 + 617(x_{Cr} - x_{Ni}))$	[34]
$\beta^{bcc} = -0.008x_{Cr} + 0.85x_{Ni} + 4x_{Cr}x_{Ni}$	[34]
<i>fcc (1 sublattice, sites: 1, constituents: Cr,Ni,Si)</i>	
$L_{Cr,Ni}^{fcc} = (+8030 - 12.88T) + (+33080 - 16.036T)(x_{Cr} - x_{Ni})$	[34]
$L_{Cr,Si}^{fcc} = L_{Cr,Si}^{bcc}$	IAD
$L_{Ni,Si}^{fcc} = (-205000 + 30T) + (-52000 + 20T)(x_{Ni} - x_{Si})$	[65]
$L_{Cr,Ni,Si}^{fcc} = (-60000 - 30T)x_{Cr} + (+75000 - 30T)x_{Ni} + (+75000 - 30T)x_{Si}$	IAD
$T_c^{fcc} = -1109x_{Cr} + 633x_{Ni} - 3605x_{Cr}x_{Ni}$	[34]
$\beta^{fcc} = -2.46x_{Cr} + 0.52x_{Ni} - 1.91x_{Cr}x_{Ni}$	[34]
<i>Sigma (σ) (3 sublattices, sites: 8:4:18, constituents: Ni:Cr:Cr,Ni,Si)</i>	
$G_{Ni:Cr:Cr}^{\sigma} = 8G_{fcc}^{\sigma,Ni} + 22G_{bcc}^{\sigma,Cr} + (+205000 - 200T)$	IAD
$G_{Ni:Cr:Ni}^{\sigma} = 80G_{fcc}^{\sigma,Ni} + 4G_{bcc}^{\sigma,Cr} + 18G_{bcc}^{\sigma,Ni} + (+175400)$	[75]
$G_{Ni:Cr:Si}^{\sigma} = 8G_{fcc}^{\sigma,Fe} + 4G_{bcc}^{\sigma,Cr} + 18G_{bcc}^{\sigma,Si} + (-1200000 + 300T)$	IAD
$L_{Ni:Cr:Cr,Si}^{\sigma} = (-2610000 + 300T)$	IAD
$L_{Ni:Cr:Ni,Si}^{\sigma} = (-2610000 + 300T)$	IAD

Notes: # = simplified function; the reference states of Cr and Si were changed from SER; the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96];

Table 150 (continued)

Equation	Reference
Cr_3Si (2 sublattices, sites: 3:1, constituents: Cr,Ni:Si)	
$G_{Cr:Si}^{\circ, Cr_3Si} = 3G_{Cr}^{\circ, bcc} + G_{Si}^{\circ, dia} + (-127685 + 5.106T)$	[37]
$G_{Ni:Si}^{\circ, Ni_3Si} = 3G_{Ni}^{\circ, fcc} + G_{Si}^{\circ, dia} + (-40000)$	IAD
Cr_5Si_3 (2 sublattices, sites: 5:3, constituents: Cr:Si)	
$G_{Cr:Si}^{\circ, Cr_5Si_3} = 5G_{Cr}^{\circ, bcc} + 3G_{Si}^{\circ, dia} + (-268968 + 138.0708T - 20.4422T \ln T + 0.007841T^2)$	[37] #
$CrSi$ (2 sublattices, sites: 1:1, constituents: Cr,Ni:Si)	
$G_{Cr:Si}^{\circ, CrSi} = G_{Cr}^{\circ, bcc} + G_{Si}^{\circ, dia} + (-63665 + 59.411T - 8.7776T \ln T + 0.0039T^2)$	IAD
$G_{Ni:Si}^{\circ, CrSi} = G_{Ni}^{\circ, fcc} + G_{Si}^{\circ, dia} + (-76000)$	IAD
$L_{Cr:Ni:Si}^{CrSi} = (+20000 - 10T)$	IAD
$CrSi_2$ (2 sublattices, sites: 1:2, constituents: Cr:Si)	
$G_{Cr:Si}^{\circ, CrSi_2} = G_{Cr}^{\circ, bcc} + 2G_{Si}^{\circ, dia} + (-76539 - 30.0488T + 4.4806T \ln T - 0.003426T^2)$	[37] #
$Ni_3Si-\beta_1$ (2 sublattices, sites: 19:6, constituents: Ni:Si)	
$G_{Ni:Si}^{\circ, \beta_1} = 19G_{Ni}^{\circ, fcc} + 6G_{Si}^{\circ, dia} + (-1040800 + 120T)$	[65]
$Ni_3Si-\beta_2$ (2 sublattices, sites: 3:1, constituents: Ni:Si)	
$G_{Ni:Si}^{\circ, \beta_2} = 3G_{Ni}^{\circ, fcc} + G_{Si}^{\circ, dia} + (-161860 + 12T)$	[65]
$Ni_3Si-\beta_3$ (2 sublattices, sites: 3:1, constituents: Ni:Si)	
$G_{Ni:Si}^{\circ, \beta_3} = 3G_{Ni}^{\circ, fcc} + G_{Si}^{\circ, dia} + (-132440 - 9.2T)$	[65]
$Ni_5Si_2-\gamma$ (2 sublattices, sites: 5:2, constituents: Cr,Ni:Si)	
$G_{Cr:Si}^{\circ, \gamma} = 5G_{Cr}^{\circ, bcc} + 2G_{Si}^{\circ, dia} + (-100000 - 15T)$	IAD
$G_{Ni:Si}^{\circ, \gamma} = 5G_{Ni}^{\circ, fcc} + 2G_{Si}^{\circ, dia} + (-302190 + 14T)$	[65]
$Ni_2Si-\delta$ (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents: Cr,Ni:Si)	
$G_{Cr:Si}^{\circ, \delta} = 2G_{Cr}^{\circ, bcc} + G_{Si}^{\circ, dia} + (-55000 - 10T)$	IAD
$G_{Ni:Si}^{\circ, \delta} = 2G_{Ni}^{\circ, fcc} + G_{Si}^{\circ, dia} + (-149000 + 166T - 21T \ln T)$	[65]
$Ni_2Si-\theta$ (2 sublattices, sites: 2:1, constituents: Ni:Si)	
$G_{Ni:Si}^{\circ, \theta} = 2G_{Ni}^{\circ, fcc} + G_{Si}^{\circ, dia} + (-115333 - 10T)$	IAD
$Ni_3Si_2-\epsilon$ (2 sublattices, sites: 3:2, constituents: Ni:Si)	
$G_{Ni:Si}^{\circ, \epsilon} = 3G_{Ni}^{\circ, fcc} + 2G_{Si}^{\circ, dia} + (-218700 + 10T)$	IAD
$NiSi$ (2 sublattices, sites: 1:1, constituents: Ni:Si)	
$G_{Ni:Si}^{\circ, NiSi} = G_{Ni}^{\circ, fcc} + G_{Si}^{\circ, dia} + (-80600 + 1.2T)$	[65]
$NiSi_2$ (2 sublattices, sites: 1:2, constituents: Ni:Si)	
$G_{Ni:Si}^{\circ, NiSi_2} = G_{Ni}^{\circ, fcc} + 2G_{Si}^{\circ, dia} + (-106800 + 18T)$	[65]
$Cr_3Ni_5Si_2$ (π) (3 sublattices, sites: 3:5:2, constituents: Cr:Ni:Si)	
$G_{Cr:Ni:Si}^{\circ, \pi} = 3G_{Cr}^{\circ, bcc} + 5G_{Ni}^{\circ, fcc} + 2G_{Si}^{\circ, dia} + (-311000)$	IAD
$Cr_5Ni_5Si_3$ (τ_1) (3 sublattices, sites: 5:5:3, constituents: Cr:Ni:Si)	
$G_{Cr:Ni:Si}^{\circ, \tau_1} = 5G_{Cr}^{\circ, bcc} + 5G_{Ni}^{\circ, bcc} + 3G_{Si}^{\circ, dia} + (-455000 + 15T)$	IAD
τ_2 -CrNiSi (τ_2) (2 sublattices, sites: 4:3, constituents: Cr,Ni:Si)	
$G_{Cr:Si}^{\circ, \tau_2} = 4G_{Cr}^{\circ, bcc} + 3G_{Si}^{\circ, dia} + (-205000 - 9T)$	IAD
$G_{Ni:Si}^{\circ, \tau_2} = 4G_{Ni}^{\circ, fcc} + 3G_{Si}^{\circ, dia} + (-265000)$	IAD

Notes: # = simplified function; the reference states of Cr and Si were changed from SER; the thermodynamic data of pure components is given by [96];

4.21.2 Results

The results of the calculations according to the IAD together with the experimental data (Table 149) are presented in Figures 413–426 and Table 151. The agreement is reasonably good. Quite similar agreement was obtained by Schuster and Du [93] but this is not shown in the figures due their heavy amounts of information. In some phase equilibria of Table 151, note the replacement of Ni₂Si- θ by Schuster and Du [93] with Ni₂Si- δ by IAD, which is due to the simplified Ni–Si description according to the IAD.

Table 151. The calculated and experimental invariant points of the Cr–Ni–Si system.

Reaction	Code	Temperature [°C]	Type	Ref.
L + bcc = fcc + σ	U ₁	1294	Exp.	[93]
		1291	Calc.	IAD
L + bcc = σ + Cr ₃ Si	U ₂	1294	Exp.	[93]
		1302	Calc.	IAD
L + σ = fcc + τ_1	U ₃	1122	Exp.	[93]
		1099	Calc.	IAD
L + Cr ₃ Si = σ + τ_1	U ₄	1140	Exp.	[93]
		1138	Calc.	IAD
L + Cr ₃ Si = Ni ₅ Si ₂ + τ_1	U ₅	1122	Exp.	[93]
		1136	Calc.	IAD
L + Cr ₃ Si = Ni ₂ Si- δ + Cr ₅ Si ₃	U ₆	1210	Exp.	[93]
		1176	Calc.	IAD
L + Cr ₅ Si ₃ = Ni ₂ Si- δ + τ_2	U ₇	1063	Exp.	[93]
		1093	Calc.	IAD
L + Ni ₃ Si- β_3 = fcc + Ni ₅ Si ₂	U ₈	1127	Calc.	[93]
		1132	Calc.	IAD
L + τ_2 = CrSi + Ni ₂ Si- θ	U ₉	944	Exp.	[93]
L + τ_2 = CrSi + Ni ₂ Si- δ		952	Calc.	IAD

Table 151 (continued)

Reaction	Code	Temperature [°C]	Type	Ref.
L + dia = CrSi ₂ + NiSi ₂	U ₁₀	962	Exp.	[93]
		984	Calc.	IAD
L = fcc + Ni ₅ Si ₂ + τ ₁	E ₁	1084	Exp.	[93]
L = fcc + Ni ₅ Si ₂ + π		1077	Calc.	IAD
L = CrSi ₂ + NiSi + NiSi ₂	E ₂	946	Exp.	[93]
		940	Calc.	IAD
L = CrSi + Ni ₂ Si-θ + NiSi	E ₃	927	Exp.	[93]
L = CrSi + Ni ₂ Si-δ + NiSi		945	Calc.	IAD
L = Ni ₂ Si-L + Cr ₃ Si + Ni ₅ Si ₂	E ₄	1141	Exp.	[93]
L + Ni ₂ Si-L = Cr ₃ Si + Ni ₅ Si ₂	U ₁₁	1145	Calc.	IAD
L + CrSi + Cr ₅ Si ₃ = τ ₂	P ₁	1174	Exp.	[93]
		1165	Calc.	IAD
L = CrSi + CrSi ₂ + NiSi	D	943	Exp.	[93]
L + CrSi + CrSi ₂ = NiSi	P ₂	955	Calc.	IAD
L + bcc = σ	p _{1m}	1314	Calc.	[93]
		1312	Calc.	IAD
L + Cr ₃ Si = τ ₁	p _{2m}	1142	Calc.	[93]
		1141	Calc.	IAD
L = Cr ₃ Si + Ni ₂ Si-δ	e _{1m}	1207	Calc.	[93]
		1221	Calc.	IAD

Fig. 413. The calculated (IAD) liquidus projection in the Cr–Ni–Si system. Also shown by the dotted lines are the calculated liquidus isotherms between 1800 °C and 1000 °C, together with the experimental data points (79Lug [623]).

Fig. 414. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1175 °C in the Cr–Ni–Si system, together with the experimentally determined regions shown by the dotted lines [624].

Fig. 415. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1125 °C in the Cr-Ni-Si system, together with the experimental data points and the experimentally determined regions shown by the dotted lines [628].

Fig. 416. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1050 °C in the Cr-Ni-Si system, together with the experimental data points [624, 628] and the experimentally determined regions shown by the dotted lines [628].

Fig. 417. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 900 °C in the Cr–Ni–Si system, together with the experimental data points [93,627] and the experimentally determined regions shown by the dotted lines [627].

Fig. 418. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 900 °C in the Si-rich part of the Cr–Ni–Si system, together with the experimental data points [93,627].

Fig. 419. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 850 °C in the Cr-Ni-Si system, together with the experimental data points and the experimentally determined regions shown by the dotted lines [626].

Fig. 420. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 5 at-% Cr in the Cr-Ni-Si system, together with the experimental data points [93,623].

Fig. 421. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 10 at-% Cr in the Cr–Ni–Si system, together with the experimental data points [93, 623, 628].

Fig. 422. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 15 at-% Cr in the Cr–Ni–Si system, together with the experimental data points [93, 623].

Fig. 423. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 20 at-% Cr in the Cr-Ni-Si system, together with the experimental data points [93, 623].

Fig. 424. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 30 at-% Cr in the Cr-Ni-Si system, together with the experimental data points [93, 623].

Fig. 425. The calculated (IAD) vertical section of 40 at-% Cr in the Cr–Ni–Si system, together with the experimental data points [93, 623].

Fig. 426. The calculated (IAD) activity coefficient $\log \gamma_{Si}$ in liquid Ni–Cr–Si alloys at 1600 °C and at 1.5 wt-% Si, together with smoothed experimental data points [629]. The dotted line refers to the calculations by Schuster and Du [93].

5 Quaternary systems

5.1 The Fe–Al–Cr–Ni system

The phase equilibria in the Fe–Al–Cr–Ni system have been modeled according to the IAD using the substitutional solution model for the solution phases (liq, bcc and fcc). The corresponding quaternary description consists of its sub-descriptions according to the IAD and the quaternary solid-state parameters of

$$\begin{aligned}L_{\text{Al,Cr,Fe,Ni}}^{\text{bcc}} &= -100000 && \text{[J/mol]} \\L_{\text{Al,Cr,Fe,Ni}}^{\text{fcc}} &= -300000 && \text{[J/mol]} \\L_{\text{Al:Cr,Fe,Ni}}^{\text{AlNi}_3} &= +13000000 && \text{[J/mol]}\end{aligned}$$

The given interaction parameter was optimized using the measured [630] isothermal section of the quaternary system at 900 °C, at constant contents of 70 at-% Fe and 60 at-% Ni. The results of the calculations are presented in Figures 427 and 428 showing reasonable agreement with the experimental data. Concerning Figure 427, one should note that in the experimental phase equilibria by Yin *et al.* [630], the ordered Fe-rich bcc phase (bcc_B2) was separated from the disordered bcc phase (bcc_A2). In the IAD, there is no such separation but the energetic effect of the former phase is included in the latter. Consequently, the original phase symbols by Yin *et al.* [630] were simplified showing regions for one bcc phase only. On the other hand, the calculations still show phase regions where two bcc phases are present. The resulting bcc miscibility gap is now due to the Al–Ni rich bcc phase. This phase, truly, is a strongly ordered bcc phase (bcc_B2), which should be modeled with a sublattice model, but for practical reasons, the IAD treats it as a simple disordered bcc phase. So, in Figure 427, one is advised to keep the calculated bcc+bcc' regions as single bcc regions only, when making a comparison with the simplified data points by Yin *et al.* [630]. The present simple description can be expected to give a reasonable estimation of the mutual bcc and fcc phase stabilities in the quaternary Fe–Al–Cr–Ni description. Concerning Figure 428, one should note that reasonable agreement with the measurements by Yin *et al.* [630] was obtained only at low Al contents, below 20 at-% Al.

Fig. 427. The calculated (IAD) isothermal section of the Fe–Al–Cr–Ni system at 900 °C and 70 at-% Fe, together with the experimental data points of Yin *et al.* [630].

Fig. 428. The calculated (IAD) isothermal section of the Fe–Al–Cr–Ni system at 900 °C and 60 at-% Ni, together with the experimental data points of Yin *et al.* [630].

5.2 The Fe–Cr–Mo–Ni system

The phase equilibria in the Fe–Cr–Mo–Ni system have been modeled in the IAD using the substitutional solution model for the solution phases (liq, bcc and fcc) and the sublattice model for the P and Mu phases, which are formulated as

The corresponding quaternary description consists of its sub-descriptions according to the IAD and the solid-state quaternary and ternary parameters of

$$\begin{aligned} L_{\text{Cr,Fe,Mo,Ni}}^{\text{bcc}} &= +20000 && [\text{J/mol}] \\ L_{\text{Cr,Fe,Mo,Ni}}^{\text{fcc}} &= -80000 && [\text{J/mol}] \\ G_{\text{Fe:Cr:Mo}}^{\circ,\text{P}} &= 24G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 20G_{\text{Cr}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + 12G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + (-70000) && [\text{J/mol}] \\ G_{\text{Cr:Fe:Mo}}^{\circ,\text{P}} &= 24G_{\text{Cr}}^{\circ,\text{fcc}} + 20G_{\text{Fe}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} + 12G_{\text{Mo}}^{\circ,\text{bcc}} && [\text{J/mol}] \end{aligned}$$

The given parameters were optimized using the measured [631] liquidus and eutectic temperatures of the Fe + 20.1 wt-%Cr + 23.9 wt-% Ni + 12.1 wt-% Mo alloy and the measured [577] phase equilibria concerning the fcc, P and Mu phases at 1200 °C and 1000 °C, with a constant Cr content of 10 wt-%. The results of the calculations are presented in Figures 429–431 and are in reasonable agreement with the experimental data. That agreement is better than obtained by the calculations using Thermo-Calc [632] though one should note that no fitting data was available in Thermo-Calc [632] to get reasonable results. Note also that after adapting the given P phase parameters of the Fe–Cr–Mo system, the phase still remains metastable in that system.

Fig. 429. The calculated equilibrium solidification of alloy Fe + 20.1 wt-% Cr + 23.9 wt-% Ni + 12.1 wt-% Mo, together with the experimental data points (06Per [631]). The solid lines refer to the calculations according to the IAD and the dotted lines refer to those by [632].

Fig. 430. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1200 °C in the Fe–Cr–Mo–Ni system at a constant Cr content of 10 wt-%, together with the experimental data points [577]. The dotted lines show the Mu, P and fcc regions obtained by the calculations by [632].

Fig. 431. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of 1000 °C in the Fe–Cr–Mo–Ni system at a constant Cr content of 10 wt-%, together with the experimental data points [577]. The dotted lines show the Mu, P and fcc regions obtained by the calculations by [632].

6 The Fe–Cr–Mn–Ni–Si system

The bcc+fcc region in the Fe–Cr–Mn–Ni–Si system has been modeled for the IAD using the substitutional solution model for the bcc and fcc phases. The corresponding quinary description for the IAD consists of its sub-descriptions in the IAD and a quaternary fcc state interaction parameter of $L_{Cr,Fe,Mn,Si}^{fcc} = -150000 + 50T$ [J/mol].

The given interaction parameter was optimized using the measured [633] bcc–fcc phase equilibria in the Fe–Cr–Mn–Ni–Si system with different manganese (5, 10, and 15 wt-%) and silicon (0 and 1.4 wt-%) contents. The results of the calculations are presented in Figures 432–434 showing reasonable agreement with the experimental data. The effect of the 1.4 wt-% Si addition is regarded as small.

Fig. 432. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of the Fe–Cr–Mn–Ni–Si system at 1000 °C, 5 wt-% Mn, and at 0 and 1.4 wt-% Si, together with the experimental data points [633].

Fig. 433. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of the Fe–Cr–Mn–Ni–Si system at 1000 °C, at 10 wt-% Mn, and at 0 and 1.4 wt-% Si, together with the experimental data points [633].

Fig. 434. The calculated (IAD) isotherm of the Fe–Cr–Mn–Ni–Si system at 1000 °C, at 15 wt-% Mn, and at 0 and 1.4 wt-% Si, together with the experimental data points [633].

7 Conclusions

This work presents simple and consistent thermodynamic descriptions for Cr-, Cu-, Mo-, and Ni-containing sub-systems of the Fe–Al–Cr–Cu–Mn–Mo–Ni–Si system. The descriptions comprise a total of 46 sub-systems, which consist of 22 binary, 21 ternary, and two quaternary systems as well as one quinary system (see Table 152).

Table 152. Studied sub-systems of the Fe–Al–Cr–Cu–Mn–Mo–Ni–Si system.

Binary	Ternary	Quaternary	Quinary
1) Fe–Cr	23) Fe–Al–Cr	44) Fe–Al–Cr–Ni	46) Fe–Cr–Mn–Ni–Si
2) Fe–Cu	24) Fe–Al–Cu	45) Fe–Cr–Mo–Ni	
3) Fe–Mo	25) Fe–Al–Mo		
4) Fe–Ni	26) Fe–Al–Ni		
5) Al–Cr	27) Fe–Cr–Cu		
6) Al–Cu	28) Fe–Cr–Mn		
7) Al–Mo	29) Fe–Cr–Mo		
8) Al–Ni	30) Fe–Cr–Ni		
9) Cr–Cu	31) Fe–Cr–Si		
10) Cr–Mn	32) Fe–Cu–Mn		
11) Cr–Mo	33) Fe–Cu–Mo		
12) Cr–Ni	34) Fe–Cu–Ni		
13) Cr–Si	35) Fe–Cu–Si		
14) Cu–Mn	36) Fe–Mn–Mo		
15) Cu–Mo	37) Fe–Mn–Ni		
16) Cu–Ni	38) Fe–Mo–Ni		
17) Cu–Si	39) Fe–Mo–Si		
18) Mn–Mo	40) Fe–Ni–Si		
19) Mn–Ni	41) Al–Cr–Ni		
20) Mo–Ni	42) Cr–Mo–Ni		
21) Mo–Si	43) Cr–Ni–Si		
22) Ni–Si			

The new descriptions extend the earlier-published Fe–Al–Mn–Si–C description of the IAD database [1]. In the new descriptions, two essential simplifications were made to keep any compound description as simple as possible and to ignore the B2-ordering of the bcc phase in Al and Si bearing iron alloys. With these simplifications, the optimized thermodynamic data can be applied in the IDS solidification model, to simulate the non-equilibrium solidification of steels.

The new descriptions allow a simultaneous solution of the thermodynamic and the diffusion equations of the model, making the IDS independent of other model packages or sub-routines. It also reduces the calculation times of the IDS making it suitable for on-line applications, such as continuous casting. The current thermodynamic data has been validated with a huge amount of experimental literature measurements. The agreement is good, not only for typical steel compositions, but also for higher solute compositions, indicating that the stabilities of most phases of the system are in an acceptable relation with each other.

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